

PKanalix

Product Documentation

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PKanalix is a user-friendly and performant application for compartmental and non-compartmental analysis (NCA). This page contains the documentation for PKanalix versions between 2018 and 2024.

1 Introduction to PKanalix

PKanalix is a user-friendly and fast application for compartmental analysis (CA), non-compartmental analysis (NCA) and bioequivalence studies (BE).

The screenshot displays the PKanalix software interface for a Non-compartmental analysis (NCA). The main window is titled "Non compartmental analysis" and features a "RUN" button. Below this, the "Settings" panel is visible, divided into several sections:

- Calculations NCA:**
 - Administration type: Intravenous, Extravascular
 - Integral method: Linear up log down
 - BLQ method before Tmax: zero
 - BLQ method after Tmax: Missing
 - Partial AUC time:
 - Interdose interval for single dose profiles: 84
- Acceptance criteria NCA:**
 - Adjusted R2: 0.98
 - % extrapolated AUC: 20
 - Span: 3
- Bioequivalence design BE:** (Currently collapsed)

On the right side, the "Parameters NCA - BE" panel shows a table of parameters with checkboxes for selection. The table includes columns for "NCA", "BE", and "log".

Parameter	NCA	BE	log
AUC			
AUC_PerCentExtrap_obs % extrapolated AUC	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
AUC_PerCentExtrap_pred % extrapolated AUC _{pred}	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
AUCall AUC _{all}	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
AUCINF_D_obs AUC _{0-∞,obs} /Dose	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
AUCINF_D_pred AUC _{0-∞,pred} /Dose	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
AUCINF_obs AUC _{0-∞,obs}	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
AUCINF_pred AUC _{0-∞,pred}	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
AUClast AUC _{0-last}	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
AUClast_D AUC _{0-last} /Dose	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Concentration			
C0 C ₀	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Clast C _{last}	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Clast_pred C _{last}	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

1.1 Why should I use PKanalix?

1.1.1 Very intuitive interface & automatization via scripting

Designed with a user-friendly graphical interface. Intuitive settings panels, clear definitions of methods, visual tools to check the calculations and personalized display of results – all contribute to a better productivity. Accessible also via R for powerful scripting.

1.1.2 Straightforward NCA and Bioequivalence Studies

Complete workflow – integrated calculation of NCA parameters with industry-standard methods and bioequivalence study as recommended by regulatory agencies – is done in a few clicks. NCA analysis has never been so simple.

1.1.3 Reliable and clear results

Intuitive tables, sortable summaries and interactive plots provide a powerful environment for analysis of results. Reproducibility, correct installation and calculations are guaranteed by settings saved in the project and the integrated validation suite.

1.1.4 Compartmental analysis & integration towards population modeling

Built-in library of PK models and automatic features help to describe PK dynamics within the Compartmental Analysis framework. Together with a direct link towards population modeling using Monolix assure the most informative workflow.

1.2 The PKAnalix Workflows

1.2.1 A typical NCA and CA Workflow with PKAnalix

1.2.2 The NCA workflow

1. Set the data
2. Explore the data
 - Interactive plots
 - Table of concentrations
3. Select NCA parameters & calculation settings
 - Add data info (administration type, sparse, observation to use)
 - Add partial AUCs, custom parameters
 - Set BLQ and integral methods
 - Select flags
4. Check slopes for lambda_z calculation
5. Run NCA task
6. Check the individual parameters obtained

7. Get insights with interactive summary statistics table
8. Get insights with interactive diagnostic plots
9. Generate a report

1.2.3 The Bioequivalence (BE) workflow

1. First run the NCA workflow
2. Select BE parameters & calculation settings
3. Set the BE design
4. Run BE task
5. Check the ratios and confidence intervals obtained
6. Get insights with ANOVA (importance of the factors) and coefficients of variation
7. Get insights with diagnostic plots (Sequence by period, Subject by formulation, Confidence intervals)
8. Generate a report

1.2.4 The Compartmental Analysis (CA) workflow

Compartmental Analysis is using a model to fit the individuals one by one. It can be used to compare parameters of a PK model to NCA parameters, or to fit other types of data than PK (PD, joint PKPD...)

1. Set the data
2. Select a model and map observations to model outputs
3. Select settings for the optimization algorithm
4. Set initial values
5. Run CA task
6. Check the diagnostic plots (eg individual fits)
7. Check the estimated parameters
8. Generate a report

and potentially

- Export to Simulx to perform simulations with this model
- Export to Monolix to develop a population model

1.3 Validation with respect to WinNonlin

The results of the NCA calculations and bioequivalence calculations have been compared on an extensive number of datasets to the results of Phoenix WinNonlin and to published results obtained with SAS. All results were identical. See the poster below for more details.

Validation of non-compartmental analysis (NCA) and bioequivalence results of PKanalix with respect to Phoenix WinNonlin

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To watch "What's new in 2021" webinar:

INTRODUCTION

Need

Non-compartmental analysis (NCA) is used as a stage of drug development and is a key method to understand the pharmacokinetic properties of a compound. Bioequivalence analysis of the NCA parameters is a critical step to investigate generic formulations, food effects or drug-drug interactions.

Solution

PKanalix belongs to the Monodis Pharma applications, and performs NCA and CA (compartmental analysis) and includes a bioequivalence module going from the 2021 version.

Validated

As NCA and bioequivalence are commonly part of filings to the regulatory agencies, both implementing these methods must be appropriately validated. For historical reasons, Phoenix WinNonlin is considered as the standard. In this work, we rigorously compare the results of PKanalix with those of WinNonlin.

ALGORITHMS

λ_z CALCULATION

Selection of admissible points for the choice of the estimation

- $\text{Min}(\text{adjR}^2) = \text{Min}(\text{noncompartmental}(\lambda)) > 0$ and $\lambda_1 \geq 2 \cdot \text{Time}_{\text{max}}$
- $\text{Min}(\text{adjR}^2_{\text{max}}) = \text{Min}(\text{noncompartmental}(\lambda)) > 0$ and $\lambda_1 > \text{Time}_{\text{max}} \text{ and } \lambda_2 \geq 2 \cdot \text{Time}_{\text{max}}$
- $\text{Min}(\text{adjR}^2_{\text{max}}) = \text{Min}(\text{noncompartmental}(\lambda)) > 0$ and $\lambda_1 > \text{Time}_{\text{max}}$

Selection of points to calculate λ_z

(There are at least 3 admissible points. $\text{Min}(\text{adjR}^2_{\text{max}}) \geq 1$) then:

- 2 on all consecutive admissible points $\lambda = 1, 4, 6, 8, \dots$ $\text{Min}(\text{adjR}^2_{\text{max}})$
- Calculate adjusted R² coefficient $\text{adjR}^2(\lambda)$ and lambda value $\lambda_z(\lambda)$
- Find R_{max} = number of last consecutive admissible points corresponding to the maximal value of the adjR^2 and $\lambda_z < 0$
- Add all more admissible points $\lambda = \text{Time}_{\text{max}}, \dots, \text{R}_{\text{max}}, \dots, \text{Min}(\text{adjR}^2_{\text{max}})$
- $\lambda_z(\lambda) < 0$ and $(-\text{adjR}^2(\text{R}_{\text{max}})) = \text{adjR}^2(\lambda) \leq 0.0001$

BIOEQUIVALENCE (BE)

The bioequivalence analysis relies on the comparison of the geometric least squares mean ratio and its confidence interval (CI) to predefined BE limits. To construct the CI, the individual NCA parameter values are fitted to a general linear model with fixed effects (typically sequence, subject nested in sequence, period and treatment for 2, 2, 2 crossover). PKanalix uses QR factorization to solve the linear model ANOVA tables and coefficients of variations (a intra-subject variability) are also calculated.

Reference ranges for bioequivalence

- Factors included in the linear model (fixed effects only). (Default factors are proposed based on the detected design (parallel or repeated) crossover)
- Log-transformation or not of the NCA parameters
- Level for the confidence interval
- Bioequivalence limits
- Degrees of freedom: residual or Welch Satterthwaite (unequal variance)

METHODS AND RESULTS 1: NCA

The NCA validation with respect to Phoenix WinNonlin is based on comparing the results of real datasets to test realistic scenarios, specific datasets to detect possible differences in the algorithms, and simulated datasets to identify possible unexpected cases. All NCA parameters were calculated with PKanalix and compared with the results of Phoenix WinNonlin.

Real datasets

Datasets:

- Two drugs: "Naloxone" and "Mirtazapine" (from "Typical analysis in the pharmaceutical industry" by WinNonlin, version 8.1)
- Carbamazepine and Theophylline (from "Theophylline analysis in the pharmaceutical industry" by WinNonlin, version 8.1)
- Enrofloxacin (from "The comparability of pharmacokinetic parameters between different software tools" by WinNonlin, version 8.1)

The above datasets were used in the original and modified forms with multiple combinations of NCA settings.

Drug name	Design	Sampling	Analysis method	Matrix
Naloxone	Single dose	Uniform	Ln-Transform	None
Theophylline	Repeatability	1/1	Ln-Transform	None
		1/1	Ln-Transform	None
Enrofloxacin	Repeatability	1/1	Ln-Transform	None
		1/1	Ln-Transform	None

Results

This test considered 63 scenarios with a total of 734 individual PK profiles. In all cases, the relative difference between the values of NCA parameters obtained from PKanalix and WinNonlin were less than 10⁻⁴.

Specific datasets

Datasets: Manually generated to check rules for inclusion of points in λ_z calculation.

Results

This test considered a total of 19 individual PK profiles. In all cases, the points selected for the λ_z calculation were identical in PKanalix and WinNonlin.

Simulated datasets

Datasets are combinations of:

- 1, 2 or 3 compartments
- Administration oral or iv bolus
- Linear or non-linear elimination
- Proportional residual error: 4%, 10% or 20%

Datasets were simulated in R, where a population of individuals was generated for each combination of the above parameters.

Results

This test considered 36 scenarios with a total of 3600 individual PK profiles. In all cases, the relative difference between the values of NCA parameters obtained from PKanalix and WinNonlin were less than 10⁻⁴.

METHODS AND RESULTS 2: BIOEQUIVALENCE

The validation of the BE results is based on the comparison of the PKanalix results with published benchmarks which were designed to validate bioequivalence software. Reference values for the ratio and its confidence interval for parallel, crossover and repeated crossover designs are available. In addition, the other PKanalix outputs (coefficient of variance (CV), within subject) were compared to WinNonlin.

Parallel design

Publication: Pngwang, A., Ichihara, S. and Pngwang, A. (2015) Reference Datasets for Bioequivalence Trials in a Two-Group Parallel Design. The AAPS Journal, 17(2), pp. 400-406.

Datasets are combinations of:

- Small (N=12), medium (N=24) and large (N=3000) number of individuals
- Balanced and imbalanced between sequences
- With and without outliers (i.e. extreme values)
- Normal and heteroscedasticity (i.e. equal or unequal variance)
- Standard or extreme numeric range and geometric means ratio

Main bioequivalence settings:

- Linear model with treatment as fixed effect
- Log-transformation of the NCA parameter
- Degree of freedom: Both residual and Satterthwaite tested

Results

This test considered 8 datasets. In all cases, the ratio and confidence interval were identical to the reference values (given as a percentage with 2 digits). For CV and ANOVA tables, the relative difference with WinNonlin results were less than 10⁻⁴.

Crossover design

Publication: Ichihara, S., Ichihara, S. and Pngwang, A. (2014) Reference Datasets for 2-Treatment, 2-Sequence, 2-Period Bioequivalence Studies. AAPS, pp. 1292-1297

Datasets are combinations of:

- Small (N=12), medium (N=24) and large (N=3000) number of individuals
- Balanced and imbalanced between sequences
- With and without outliers (i.e. extreme values)
- Standard or extreme numeric range and geometric means ratio
- Normal or heteroscedasticity (i.e. equal or unequal variance)
- Standard or extreme numeric range and geometric means ratio

Main bioequivalence settings:

- Linear model with sequence, subject nested in sequence, period and treatment as fixed effects
- Log-transformation of the NCA parameter

Results

This test considered 8 datasets. In all cases, the ratio and confidence interval were identical to the reference values (given as a percentage with 2 digits). For CV and ANOVA tables, the relative difference with WinNonlin results were less than 10⁻⁴.

Repeated crossover design

Publication: Ichihara, S., Ichihara, S. and Pngwang, A. (2014) Reference Datasets for Average Bioequivalence with Repetitive Study. AAPS Journal, 16(2), pp. 1-7

Publication: Pngwang, A. (2015) Questions & Answers: positions on specific questions addressed by the Pharmaceutical Working Party (PWP)

Datasets are combinations of:

- Design: four-period full-replicate, three-period full-replicate, three-period partial-replicate, two-period full-replicate
- Small (N=12) or medium (N=24) number of individuals
- Balanced and imbalanced between sequences
- With and without outliers (i.e. extreme values)
- Standard or extreme numeric range and geometric means ratio
- Normal and heteroscedasticity (i.e. equal or unequal variance)
- Complete or incomplete (periods missing)

Main bioequivalence settings:

- Linear model with sequence, subject nested in sequence, period and treatment as fixed effects (i.e. this method A)
- Log-transformation of the NCA parameter

Results

This test considered 31 datasets. In all cases, the ratio and confidence interval were identical to the reference values (given as a percentage with 2 digits). For CV and ANOVA tables, the relative difference with WinNonlin results were less than 10⁻⁴.

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2 Data

On the following pages you can find information about loading and manipulating a data set in PKanalix:

2.1 Data overview

To load a dataset in PKanalix, follow these steps:

1. Create a new project and [load the dataset file](#)
 - a. **Dataset that needs formatting:** If needed, format your data first by selecting 'Browse' under '**Format data**' to use the data formatting module which allows you to:
 - to handle several header lines
 - merge several observation columns into one
 - add censoring information based on tags in the observation column
 - add treatment information manually or from external files
 - add more columns such as covariates from an external file
 - b. **Already formatted dataset:** If the data is already [in the right format](#), load it directly by selecting 'Browse' under '**Data file**'

 If the dataset does not follow a formatting rule, the dataset will not be accepted, but errors will guide you to find what is missing and could be added by data formatting.

2. [Column tagging](#): tag the columns not recognized automatically to indicate their type and click on ACCEPT.
3. [Defining units](#): If you want to work with units, indicate the units in the data and the appropriate conversion to the ones you prefer to use inside the Data tab (if relevant)
4. [Filters](#): If needed, filter your dataset to use only part of it in the Filters tab
5. [Explore](#): The interpreted dataset is displayed in Data, and Plots and covariate statistics are generated.

To use a dataset from a Monolix project, or to use simulations from a Simulx project, you can directly import or export the Monolix/Simulx project which will automatically define the dataset in the Data tab.

2.2 Loading a data set

2.2.1 Providing a data set

To start a new project, after clicking on the “New project” option, you need to provide a data set by loading a file in the Data tab.

 Supported file types include .txt, .csv, and .tsv files. Starting with version 2024, Excel and SAS files (.xls, .xlsx, .sas2bdat, and .xpt files) are supported as well.

There are two options available:

The option “Data file” (in purple) can be used if the data set follows the standard MonolixSuite format. This format is the same across all of the MonolixSuite applications. Briefly:

- Each line corresponds to one individual and one time point.
- Each line can include a single measurement (also called observation), or a dose amount, or both a measurement and a dose amount. Multiple types of observations are all specified in the same column and identified by a separate occasion or observation id column.
- Dosing information should be indicated for each individual, even if it is identical for all individuals.

If your data set is not already in this format, you can use the “Format data” (in green) option to transform it. The data formatting module allows adding information on dose amounts, limits of quantification, or removing excess header lines, for example.

More information about the two options can be found on these pages:

2.2.2 Data set load times

Starting with the 2024 version, project load times can be improved, especially for projects with large data sets, by saving the data as a binary file. This option is available in Settings>Preferences and will save a copy of the data file in binary format in the results folder. When reloading a project, the data set will be read from the binary file, which is faster. If the original dataset file has been modified (compared to the binary), a warning message appears, the binary dataset is not used and the original dataset file will be loaded instead.

2.2.3 Standard data format

In PKanalix, a dataset is loaded in the Data tab to create a project. After the dataset accepted, it is possible to specify units and filter the dataset, so units and filtering information do not need to be included in the dataset.

The dataset format used in PKanalix is the same across the entire MonolixSuite, so that it is easy to transition between applications. In this format:

- Each row corresponds to one individual and one time point.
- Each row can include a single measurement (also called observation), or a dose amount, or both a measurement and a dose amount.

- **Dosing information should be indicated for each individual in a specific column, even if it is the same for all individuals.**
- There are no restrictions on headers(column names), but there can be only one header row.
- Different types of information (dose, observation, covariate, etc.) are recorded in different columns, which must be tagged with a column type (see below).
- Multiple types of observations are all specified in the same column and identified by a separate observation id or occasion column (see below) .

If your dataset is not already in this format, in most cases it is possible to format it in a few steps with the data formatting module, to incorporate missing information (e.g., dose amounts or covariates) or combine columns (e.g., observations in separate columns).

2.2.3.1 Overview of common column-types

A dataset typically contains at least the following columns: ID (mandatory), TIME (mandatory), OBSERVATION (mandatory), AMOUNT (optional). The main rules for interpreting the dataset are:

- Missing values should be represented by a period (dot) (e.g., the dose AMOUNT column in a row for a measurement).
- There are no restrictions on headers(column names), but there can be only one header row. Each column must be assigned to one of the available column-types (columns can be ignored).

The full list of column-types is available at the end of this page and a detailed description is given on the data set documentation website.

The most common column types in addition to ID, TIME, OBSERVATION and AMOUNT are:

- For **IV infusion** data, either INFUSION RATE or INFUSION DURATION is required.
- For **steady-state** data, either an INTERDOSE INTERVAL column is present, or the interdose interval *tau* must be specified in the NCA settings.
- If a dose and a measurement occur at the same time, they can be specified on the same row or on two separate rows.
- **Sort and carry variables** can be defined using the OCCASION, CATEGORICAL COVARIATE, and CONTINUOUS COVARIATE column-types.
- **BLQ data** are defined using the CENSORING and LIMIT column-types.

In addition to the typical cases presented above, a few additional column-types may also be useful:

- **ignoring a row:** This is possible with the IGNORED OBSERVATION (ignores the measurement only) or IGNORED LINE (ignores the entire row, including regressor and dose information) column-types. However, it is more convenient to filter rows of your dataset without modifying it by using filters (available once your dataset is accepted).
- **working with several types of observations:** If several observation types are present in the dataset (for example parent and metabolite), all measurements should still appear in the same OBSERVATION column, and another column should be used to distinguish the observation types.

If this is not the case in your dataset, data formatting can merge several observation columns. To run **NCA for several observations** at the same time for the same id, tag the column with the observation types as OCCASION. To run **CA for several observations** with a model including several outputs (for example PK and PD), tag the column listing the observation types as OBSERVATION ID. In this case, only one observation type will be available for NCA. It can be selected in the “NCA” section to perform the calculations.

- **working with several types of administrations:** a single data set can contain different types of administrations, for instance, IV bolus and extravascular, distinguished using the ADMINISTRATION ID column-type. The setting “administration type” in “Tasks>Run” can be chosen separately for each administration id, and the appropriate parameter calculations will be performed.

2.2.3.2 Example datasets

Below we show how to specify the dataset for several common situations.

2.2.3.2.1 Plasma concentration data

2.2.3.2.1.1 Extravascular

For extravascular administration, the mandatory column-types are ID (individual identifiers as integers or strings), OBSERVATION (measured concentrations), AMOUNT (dose amount administered, mandatory for 2023 and previous versions) and TIME (time of dose or measurement). Starting with version 2024, datasets that do not contain an AMOUNT column or no information in the AMOUNT column are accepted for single dose or multiple dose administrations (bottom row in figure below). If there are concentration measurements and doses at the same time, they can be specified on the same row or separately (top row in figure below).

ID	TIME	AMOUNT	CONC	ID	TIME	AMOUNT	CONC
1	0	100	.	1	0	100	0
1	0	.	0	1	1	.	8.1
1	1	.	8.1	1	2	.	7.5
1	2	.	7.5	1	3	.	6.9
1	3	.	6.9	1	4	.	6.5
1	4	.	6.5	1	5	.	5.8
1	5	.	5.8				

ID	TIME	AMOUNT	CONC	ID	TIME	CONC
1	0	.	.	1	0	0
1	0	.	0	1	1	8.1
1	1	.	8.1	1	2	7.5
1	2	.	7.5	1	3	6.9
1	3	.	6.9	1	4	6.5
1	4	.	6.5	1	5	5.8
1	5	.	5.8			

To distinguish an extravascular administration from an IV bolus administration, in “Tasks>Run” the administration type must be set to “extravascular.”

If no measurement is recorded at the time of the dose, a concentration of zero is added for single dose data, the minimum concentration observed during the dose interval for steady-state data.

Example:

- demo **project_extravascular.pkx**

This data set records the drug concentration measured after single oral administration of 150 mg of the drug in 20 patients. For each individual, the first row records the dose (in the “Amount” column tagged as AMOUNT column-type) while the following rows record the measured concentrations (in the “Conc” column tagged as OBSERVATION). Cells in the “Amount” column for measurement rows contain a period, and similarly for the concentration column. The column containing the times of measurements or doses is tagged with the TIME column-type and the subject identifiers, which we will use as a sort variable, are tagged as ID. Use the OCCASION column-type if more sort variables are needed. After accepting the dataset, the data is automatically assigned as “Plasma.”

Data information

Urine
 Plasma

Units: TIME column × 1 = hour

CONC column × 1 = milligram / milliliter

AMT column × 1 = milligram

LINE NUMBER	Subject	Time	Conc	Amount
1	101	0		150
2	101	1	19.9938	
3	101	1	18.0248	
4	101	1.5	20.4776	
5	101	2	17.4913	
6	101	2.5	20.3812	
7	101	3	16.6674	
8	101	4	16.246	
9	101	5	19.7451	
10	101	6	8.29779	
11	101	8	11.6176	
12	101	10	7.98511	
13	101	12		

Records per page: 10 25 50 100 280

<< Page 1 of 6 >>

Showing 1 to 50 of 280 entries · 20 individuals

In the “Tasks/Run” tab, the user must indicate that this is extravascular data. In the “Check lambda_z” tab, data points as well as added points, such as a zero concentration at the dose time (only displayed with a linear scale for the y-axis), are shown. Points included in the λ_z calculation are highlighted in blue.

Non compartmental analysis

Administration type: Intravenous Extravascular

Integral method: Linear trapezoidal linear

Acceptance criteria: Adjusted R2, % extrapolated AUC

After running the NCA analysis, PK parameters relevant to extravascular administration are displayed in the “Results” tab.

Individual estimates

Non compartmental analysis results per individual Paginate

id	AUC _{0-inf}	AUC _{0-last}	CL/F	C _{last}	C _{max}	Flag_λ _z _Rule	k _{el}	Intercept	Number of points	R squared	adj
101	249.91	229.14	0.6	2.29	20.48	1	0.11	3.5	4	0.99	
102	160.81	144.31	0.93	1.6	14.14	1	0.097	2.79	3	0.99	
103	251.54	217.76	0.6	3.12	19.87	1	0.092	3.29	5	0.97	
104	213.71	189.58	0.7	2.28	22.38	1	0.095	3.11	3	0.99	
105	135.83	113.41	1.1	1.52	13.14	1	0.068	2.02	3	0.99	
106	115.87	108.79	1.29	0.81	12.28	1	0.11	2.71	8	0.98	
107	239.48	195.93	0.63	3.37	17.51	1	0.077	3.12	5	0.99	
108	175.63	159.74	0.85	1.8	14.39	1	0.11	3.34	3	0.99	
109	136.09	118.07	1.1	1.53	12.13	1	0.085	2.5	8	0.91	
1010	229.15	210.02	0.65	2.22	18.67	1	0.12	3.54	4	0.99	

Records per page: 10 20
 << < Page 1 of 2 >>
 Showing 1 to 10 of 20 entries

2.2.3.2.1.2 IV infusion

Intravenous infusions are indicated in the data set via the presence of an INFUSION RATE or INFUSION DURATION column-type, in addition to the ID (individual identifiers as integers or strings), OBSERVATION (measured concentrations), AMOUNT (dose amount administered, mandatory for 2023 and previous versions) and TIME (time of dose or measurement). The infusion duration (or rate) can be identical or different among individuals. Starting with version 2024, datasets that do not contain an AMOUNT column or no information in the AMOUT column are accepted for single dose or multiple dose administrations. If there are concentration measurements and doses at the same time, they can be specified on the same row or separately (see figure below).

ID	TIME	AMOUNT	CONC	TINF		ID	TIME	AMOUNT	CONC	TINF
1	0	100	.	0.5		1	0	100	0	0.5
1	0	.	0	.	or	1	1	.	8.1	.
1	1	.	8.1	.		1	2	.	7.5	.
1	2	.	7.5	.		1	3	.	6.9	.
1	3	.	6.9	.		1	4	.	6.5	.
1	4	.	6.5	.		1	5	.	5.8	.
1	5	.	5.8	.						

In “Tasks>Run” the administration type must be set to “intravenous”.

If no measurement is recorded at the time of the dose, a concentration of zero is added for single dose data and the minimum concentration observed during the dose interval is added for steady-state data.

Example:

- demo **project_ivinfusion.pkx**:

In this example, the patients receive an IV infusion taking 3 hours. The infusion duration is recorded in the column named “TINF” in this example, and tagged as INFUSION DURATION.

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	OBSERVATION	AMOUNT	INFUSION DURATION
			CONC	DOSE	TINF
1	1	0	0.01		
2	1	0		50	3
3	1	3	3.54211		
4	1	4	3.15839		
5	1	6	2.27295		
6	1	8	2.02452		
7	1	12	1.73403		
8	1	18	0.90528		
9	1	24	0.65119		
10	2	0	0.01		
11	2	0		50	3
12	2	3	4.08297		
13	2	4	3.95885		

Records per page: 10 25 50 100 225
 << < Page 1 of 5 >>
 Showing 1 to 50 of 225 entries - 25 Individuals

In the “Tasks/Run” tab, the user must indicate that this is intravenous data.

The screenshot displays the 'Non compartmental analysis' settings in PKanalix. The interface includes a top navigation bar with 'Data', 'Tasks', and 'Plots'. Below this, there are tabs for 'CHECK', 'z', and 'RUN'. The main area is titled 'Non compartmental analysis' and features a green 'NON-COMPARTMENTAL ANALYSIS' button, a 'BIOEQUIVALENCE' section, and a 'RUN' button. A 'Sparse NCA' toggle is also present.

The 'Settings' section is divided into two main panels:

- Calculations:**
 - Administration type:** Radio buttons for 'Intravenous' (selected) and 'Extravascular'.
 - Integral method:** A dropdown menu set to 'Linear trapezoidal linear'.
 - Partial AUC time:** An unchecked checkbox.
 - Interdose interval for single dose profiles:** A numeric input field set to '24'.
- Acceptance criteria:**
 - Adjusted R2:** A numeric input field set to '0.98'.
 - % extrapolated AUC:** A numeric input field set to '20'.
 - Span:** A numeric input field set to '3'.

The 'Parameters' panel on the right shows a search bar and a list of parameters with checkboxes:

- AUC Parameters:** AUC_PerCentExtrap_obs, AUC_PerCentExtrap_pred, AUCall, AUCINF_D_obs, AUCINF_D_pred, AUCINF_obs (checked), AUCINF_pred.
- AUClast:** AUCIlast (checked).

2.2.3.2.1.3 IV bolus

For IV bolus administration, the mandatory column-types are ID (individual identifiers as integers or strings), OBSERVATION (measured concentrations), AMOUNT (dose amount administered, mandatory for 2023 and previous versions) and TIME (time of dose or measurement). Starting with version 2024, datasets that do not contain an AMOUNT column or no information in the AMOUNT column are accepted for single dose or multiple dose administrations (bottom row in figure below). If there are concentration measurements and doses at the same time, they can be specified on the same row or separately (top row in figure below).

ID	TIME	AMOUNT	CONC
1	0	100	.
1	0	.	10.4
1	1	.	8.1
1	2	.	7.5
1	3	.	6.9
1	4	.	6.5
1	5	.	5.8

ID	TIME	AMOUNT	CONC
1	0	100	10.4
1	1	.	8.1
1	2	.	7.5
1	3	.	6.9
1	4	.	6.5
1	5	.	5.8

ID	TIME	AMOUNT	CONC
1	0	.	.
1	0	.	10.4
1	1	.	8.1
1	2	.	7.5
1	3	.	6.9
1	4	.	6.5
1	5	.	5.8

ID	TIME	CONC
1	0	10.4
1	1	8.1
1	2	7.5
1	3	6.9
1	4	6.5
1	5	5.8

To distinguish the IV bolus from the extravascular case, in "Tasks>Run" the administration type must be set to "intravenous".

If no measurement is recorded at the time of the dose, the concentration of at time zero is extrapolated using a log-linear regression of the first two data points, or is taken to be the first observed measurement if the regression yields a slope ≥ 0 . See the calculation details for more information.

Example:

- demo **project_ivbolus.pkx**:

In this data set, 25 individuals have received an IV bolus and their plasma concentration have been recorded over 12 hours. For each individual (indicated in the column "Subj" tagged as ID column-type), we specify the dose amount in a column "Dose," tagged as the AMOUNT column-type. The measured concentrations are tagged as OBSERVATION and the times as TIME. Use the OCCASION column-type if more sort variables are needed in addition to ID. After accepting the dataset, the data is automatically assigned as "plasma."

Data file: C:/Users/FranoMihaljevic/soft/pkanalix/pkanalix2024R1/demos/1.ba...

Data information: Urine Plasma

Units: TIME column × 1 = hour, CONC column × 1 = milligram / milliliter, AMT column × 1 = milligram

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	OBSERVATION	AMOUNT
	Subj	Time	Concentration	Dose
1	1			
2	1	0		15
3	1	0.2	1.56085	
4	1	1	1.80918	
5	1	2	2.02176	
6	1	4	1.57865	
7	1	6	1.32922	
8	1	8	1.2019	
9	1	12	0.94984	
10	2	0		15
11	2	0.2	1.6181	
12	2	1	1.79318	
13	2	2	1.47408	
14	2	4	1.33071	

Records per page: 10 25 50 100 200
 Page 1 of 4
 Showing 1 to 50 of 200 entries - 25 Individuals

In the "Tasks/Run" tab, the user must indicate that this is intravenous data. In the "Check lambda_z" tab, both measurements originally present in the data and added data points, such as the C₀ at the dose time, are shown. Data points included in the λ_z calculation are highlighted in blue.

After running the NCA analysis, PK parameters relevant to IV bolus administration are displayed in the "Results" tab.

Individual estimates

Non compartmental analysis results per individual

Records per page: 10 25

<< < Page 1 of 3 >>

Showing 1 to 10 of 25 entries

id	AUC _{0-inf}	AUC _{0-last}	CL	C _{last}	C _{max}	Flag_λ _z _Rule	K _{el}	Intercept	Number of points	R squared	adjusted R squ
1	33.76	16.92	0.44	0.95	2.02	1	0.056	0.63	3	0.99	
2	37.51	15.62	0.4	1.02	1.79	1	0.046	0.54	6	0.87	
3	12.69	9.22	1.18	0.39	1.21	1	0.11	0.41	4	0.99	
4	23.11	12.51	0.65	0.66	1.96	1	0.062	0.32	3	0.99	
5	11.62	10.27	1.29	0.26	1.45	1	0.19	0.93	3	0.99	
6	24.82	12.53	0.6	0.68	1.39	1	0.056	0.34	7	0.9	
7	27.53	14.04	0.54	0.85	1.77	1	0.063	0.52	7	0.87	
8	17.37	12.37	0.86	0.57	1.77	1	0.11	0.67	5	0.92	
9	22.81	17.1	0.66	0.67	2.34	1	0.12	1.01	5	0.99	
10	15.01	11.65	0.99	0.43	1.63	1	0.13	0.66	3	0.99	

2.2.3.2.2 Steady-state

Starting with version 2024, the interdose interval τ used to calculate NCA parameters specific to steady-state can be specified either in the dataset column tagged as INTERDOSE INTERVAL, or directly as part of the NCA settings.

In version 2023 and previous, it was necessary to specify steady-state using the STEADY STATE column-type: SS=1 indicates that the individual is already at steady-state when receiving the dose. This implicitly assumes that the individual has received many doses before this one. SS=0 or '.' indicates a single dose. Starting with version 2024, the SS column is still accepted but no longer mandatory.

The dosing interval (also called τ) is specified in the INTERDOSE INTERVAL column on the rows defining the doses, or as part of the NCA settings.

ID	TIME	CONC	AMT	TAU
1	0	.	150	12
1	0	6.89413	.	.
1	2	11.76211	.	.
1	4	13.16011	.	.
1	6	12.61962	.	.
1	8	10.16449	.	.
1	10	9.31669	.	.
1	12	7.36382	.	.
2	0	.	150	0
2	0	9.09039	.	.
2	2	14.47518	.	.
2	4	14.09411	.	.
2	6	13.74296	.	.
2	8	11.42575	.	.
2	10	10.33251	.	.
2	12	9.22173	.	.

OR

Settings

Calculations NCA

Administration type

Intravenous
 Extravascular

Integral method Linear trapezoidal linear

Partial AUC time

Interdose interval for single dose profiles 12

Steady state calculation formulas are applied for individuals with a dose with INTERDOSE INTERVAL = <double>. A data set can contain individuals which are at steady-state and some which are not. If the NCA setting "Interdose interval for single dose profiles" is selected, steady-state parameters are calculated for all individuals.

If no measurement is recorded at the time of the dose, the minimum concentration observed during the dose interval is added at the time of the dose for extravascular and infusion data. For IV bolus data, a regression using the two first data points is performed. Only measurements between the dose time and dose time + interdose interval will be used.

Examples:

- demo **project_steadystate.pkx**:

In this example, the individuals are already at steady-state when they receive the dose. This is indicated in the dataset via the column "SteadyState" tagged as the STEADY STATE column-type, which contains a "1" on rows recording doses. The interdose interval is specified on those same rows in the column "tau" tagged as INTERDOSE INTERVAL. When accepting the dataset, a "Settings" section appears, where one can define the number of steady-state doses. This information is relevant when exporting to Monolix, but not directly used in PKAnalix.

Data
Tasks
Plots

Data file

C:/Users/FranoMihaljevic/fix...

BROWSE... **FORMAT**

Data information

Urine Plasma

Number of steady state doses

5

Units

TIME column × 1 = hour

CONC column × 1 = milligram / milliliter

AMT column × 1 = milligram

Display

Additional rows

Add. covariates

NONE

LINE NUMBER	Id	Time	Y	Amount	STEADY STATE	INTERDOSE INTERVAL
					SteadyState	Tau
1	1					
2	1	-60		150		
2	1	-48		150		
2	1	-36		150		
2	1	-24		150		
2	1	-12		150		
2	1	0		150	1	12
3	1	0	6.89413			
4	1	2	11.7621			
5	1	4	13.1601			
6	1	6	12.6196			
7	1	8	10.1645			
8	1	10	9.31669			
9	1	12	7.36382			

Records per page: 10 25 50 100 500 2600
 << < Page 1 of 52 >>
 Showing 1 to 50 of 2,600 entries - 200 Individuals

After running the NCA estimation task, steady-state specific parameters are displayed in the “Results” tab.

Individual estimates

Non compartmental analysis results per individual

id	AUC _{0-inf}	AUC _{1au}	AUC _{0-last}	CL _{ss/F}	C _{last}	C _{max}	C _{max,SS}	C _{1au}	Flag_λ ₂ _Rule	k _{el}	Intercept	Number of poi
1	214.78	128.3	128.3	1.17	7.36	13.16	13.16	7.36	1	0.085	3.04	
2	318.58	146.45	146.45	1.02	9.22	14.48	14.48	9.22	1	0.054	2.87	
3	117.28	88	88	1.7	4.12	9.96	9.96	4.12	1	0.14	3.08	
4	106.59	75.88	75.88	1.98	3.62	7.81	7.81	3.62	1	0.12	2.75	
5	383.58	201.13	201.13	0.75	12.87	20.84	20.84	12.87	1	0.071	3.35	
6	122.4	95.27	95.27	1.57	4.27	10.39	10.39	4.27	1	0.16	3.37	
7	293.06	145.52	145.52	1.03	9.07	13.62	13.62	9.07	1	0.061	2.97	
8	126.75	94.85	94.85	1.58	4.17	10.74	10.74	4.17	1	0.13	3.02	
9	181.02	117.55	117.55	1.28	6.77	11.85	11.85	6.77	1	0.11	3.18	
10	543.79	193.13	193.13	0.78	13.13	18.86	18.86	13.13	1	0.037	3.02	

Records per page: 10 25 50 100 200
 << Page 1 of 20 >>
 Showing 1 to 10 of 200 entries

2.2.3.2.3 BLQ data

Below the limit of quantification (BLQ) data can be recorded in the data set using the CENSORING column:

- "0" indicates that the value in the OBSERVATION column is the measurement.
- "1" indicates that the observation is BLQ.

The lower limit of quantification (LOQ) must be indicated in the OBSERVATION column when CENSORING = "1". Note that strings are not allowed in the OBSERVATION column (except periods). A different LOQ value can be used for each BLQ measurement.

ID	TIME	AMT	CONC	BLQ
27	6	.	4.76	0
27	8	.	3.07	0
27	12	.	1.98	0
27	18	.	2.57	0
27	24	.	1.8	1
27	30	.	1.8	1
28	0	50	LOQ value	mark BLQ data
28	0.5	.	2	0
28	2	.	4.13	0
28	4	.	2.97	0
28	6	.	5.17	0

When performing an NCA analysis, the BLQ data before and after the T_{max} are can be handled differently. They can be replaced by:

- zero
- the LOQ value
- the LOQ value divided by 2
- or considered as missing

For a CA analysis, the same options are available, but no distinction is made before and after T_{max}. Once replaced, the BLQ data are treated as any other observation.

A LIMIT column can be added to record the other limit of the interval (generally zero). This value will not be used by PKanalix but can facilitate the transition from an NCA/CA analysis in PKanalix to a population model in Monolix.

 To easily transform BLQ data in a dataset that has BLQ tags in the observation column, you can use Data formatting.

Examples:

- demo **project_censoring.pkx**: two studies with BLQ data with two different LOQ values

In this dataset, the measurements of two different studies (indicated in the STUDY column, tagged as CATEGORICAL COVARIATE in order to be used to stratify results tables and plots) are observed. For the study 101, the LOQ value is 1.8 ug/mL, while it is 1 ug/mL for study 102. The BLQ measurements are marked with a "1" in the BLQ column, which is tagged as CENSORING. The LOQ values are specified for each BLQ measurement in the CONC column of measurements, tagged as OBSERVATION.

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	AMT	CONC	BLQ	STUDY
2	1	0	50	.	.	101
3	1	0.5	.	3.05	0	101
4	1	2	.	5.92	0	101
5	1	4	.	4.7	0	101
6	1	6	.	4.14	0	101
7	1	8	.	4.65	0	101
8	1	12	.	2.64	0	101
9	1	18	.	2	0	101
10	1	24	.	1.8	1	101
11	1	30	.	1.8	1	101
12	2	0	50	.	.	101
13	2	0.5	.	6.24	0	101
14	2	2	.	7.08	0	101
15	2	4	.	5.82	0	101
16	2	6	.	4.48	0	101

For the NCA analysis, in the “Task>NCA>Run” tab, the user can choose how to handle the BLQ measurements. For the BLQ measurements before and after the Tmax, the BLQ measurements can be considered as missing (as if this row in the dataset did not exist), or replaced by zero (the default before Tmax), the LOQ value, or half the LOQ value (the default after Tmax). In the “Check lambda_z” tab, the BLQ measurements are shown in red and displayed according to their replacement value.

For the CA analysis, the replacement value for all BLQ measurements can be chosen in the settings of the “Run” tab (the default is missing). In the “Check init.” tab, the BLQ are again displayed in red, **at the LOQ value (irrespective of the chosen method for the calculations).**

2.2.3.2.4 Urine data

To work with urine data, it is necessary to record the time and amount administered, the volume of urine collected for each time interval, the start and end time of the intervals and the drug concentration in a urine sample of each interval. The time intervals must be continuous (no gaps allowed).

In PKanalix, the start and end times of the intervals are recorded in a single column, tagged as TIME column-type. In this way, the end time of an interval automatically acts as start time for the next interval. The concentrations are recorded in the OBSERVATION column. The volume column must be tagged as the REGRESSOR column-type. This general column-type allows easy transitions to the other applications of MonolixSuite. As several REGRESSOR columns are allowed, the user can select which REGRESSOR column should be used as volume in the 'Data information' section once urine data is selected. The concentration and volume measured for the interval $[t_1, t_2]$ are noted on the t_2 row. The volume value on the dose row is meaningless, but it cannot be missing ('.'). We thus recommend setting it to zero.

A typical urine dataset has the following structure. A dose of 150 ng has been administered at time 0. The first sampling interval spans from the dose at time 0 to 4h post-dose. During this time, 410 mL of urine have been collected. In this sample, the drug concentration is 112 ng/mL. The second interval spans from 4h to 8h, the collected urine volume is 280 mL and its concentration is 92 ng/mL. The third interval is marked on the figure below: 390 mL of urine have been collected for the interval from 8h to 12h.

ID	TIME	VOL	CONC	AMOUNT
1	0	0	.	150
1	4	410	112	.
1	8	280	92	.
1	12	390	41	.
1	18	450	29	.
1	24	415	12	.
1	48	1730	2.6	.
1	72	2030	0.1	.

The given data is used to calculate the interval midpoints and the excretion rates for each interval. This information is then used to calculate λ_z and calculate urine-specific parameters. In “Tasks/Check lambda_z” tab, we display the midpoints and excretion rates. However, in the “Plots>Data viewer”, we display the measured concentrations at the end time of the interval.

Example:

- demo **project_urine.pkx**: urine PK dataset

In this urine PK data set, we record the consecutive time intervals in the “TIME” column tagged as TIME. The collected volumes and measured concentration are in the columns “VOL” and “CONC”, respectively tagged as REGRESSOR and OBSERVATION. Note that the volume and concentration are indicated on the row for the interval end time. The volume in the first row (start time of the first interval, as well as dose) is set to zero as it must be a numeric value. This value will not be used in the calculations. Once the dataset is accepted, the observation type must be set to “urine” and the regressor column corresponding to the volume specified.

The screenshot shows the PKanalix Data viewer interface. The top panel includes configuration options for Data file, Data information (Urine/Plasma, Regressor for urine volume, Regressors settings), Units, and Add. covariates. The main panel displays a table of data with columns: LINE NUMBER, ID, TIME, REGRESSOR (VOL), OBSERVATION (CONC), and AMOUNT. The table is grouped by individual (ID 1 and ID 2). The first row of each group shows a zero volume and amount. Subsequent rows show increasing time intervals with corresponding volume and concentration values.

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	REGRESSOR (VOL)	OBSERVATION (CONC)	AMOUNT
1	1				
2	1	0	0		150000
3	1	4	410	112	
4	1	8	280	92	
5	1	12	390	41	
6	1	18	450	29	
7	1	24	415	12	
8	1	48	1730	2.6	
9	1	72	2030	0.1	
10	2	0	0		150000
11	2	4	415	101	
12	2	8	300	87	

In the “Tasks>Check lambda_z” tab, the excretion rate are plotted at midpoint times for each individual. The data points selected for the lambda_z calculation works as usual.

Once the NCA task has run, urine-specific PK parameters are displayed in the “Results” tab.

Individual estimates

Non compartmental analysis results per individual

id	AURC _{0-inf} (ng)	AURC _{0-tlast} (ng)	Flag_λ _z -Rule	k _{el} (h ⁻¹)	Intercept	Rate _{max} (ng·h ⁻¹)	Number of points	Rate _{last} (ng·h ⁻¹)	R squared	adju:
1	102691.77	102622.38	1	0.12	9.48	11480	6	8.46	0.99	
2	101291.8	101178.02	1	0.11	9.39	10478.75	6	12.94	0.99	
3	104748.42	104679.5	1	0.12	9.63	8700	6	8.29	0.98	
4	103346.09	103175.44	1	0.11	9.16	11200	5	18.33	0.99	

2.2.3.2.5 Occasions (“Sort” variables)

The main sort level is by individual indicated by the ID column. **Additional sort levels can be specified using one or several OCCASION column(s).** OCCASION columns contain integer values that distinguish different time periods for a given individual. The time values can restart at zero or continue when switching from one occasion to the next. The variables that differ among periods, such as the

treatment for a crossover study, are tagged as CATEGORICAL or CONTINUOUS COVARIATES (see below). The NCA and CA calculations are performed on each ID-OCCASION combination. Each occasion is considered independent of other occasions (i.e., a washout is applied between each occasion).

Note: occasions columns encoding the sort variables as integers can easily be added to an existing data set using the data formatting module, Excel or R.

With R, the "OCC" column can be added to an existing data frame named "data" with a column "TREAT" with values "ref" and "test" using `data$OCC <- ifelse(data$TREAT=="ref", 1, 2)`.

With Excel, assuming the sort variable is specified in the column E with values "ref" and "test", use the formula `=IF(E2="ref",1,2)` to generate the first value of the "OCC" column and then propagate it to the entire column.

Examples:

- demo **project_occasions1.pkx**: a crossover study with two treatments

The subject column is tagged as ID, the treatment column as a CATEGORICAL COVARIATE and an additional column encoding the two periods with integers "1" and "2" as an OCCASION column.

The screenshot shows the PKanalix software interface. The main data table is displayed with the following columns: LINE NUMBER, ID, TIME, OCCASION, OBSERVATION, AMOUNT, and CATEGORICAL COVARIATE. The OCCASION and CATEGORICAL COVARIATE columns are highlighted with green boxes. The data rows show a crossover study with two treatments (ref and test) and two occasions (1 and 2).

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	OCCASION	OBSERVATION	AMOUNT	CATEGORICAL COVARIATE
1	1#1					ref
2	1	0	1		100	ref
3	1	1	1	3.17902		ref
4	1	1.5	1	3.85033		ref
5	1	2	1	4.46786		ref
6	1	2.5	1	5.22826		ref
7	1	3	1	4.86716		ref
8	1	4	1	5.0127		ref
9	1	5	1	5.55581		ref
10	1	6	1	3.94428		ref
11	1	8	1	3.1716		ref
12	1	10	1	3.19092		ref
13	1	12	1	1.82381		ref
14	1	18	1	0.8774		ref
15	1	24	1	0.39638		ref

Records per page: 10 25 50 100 500 700
 << < Page 1 of 14 >>
 Showing 1 to 50 of 700 entries - 25 Individuals

In the “Check lambda_z” tab (for the NCA) and the “Check init.” tab (for CA), each occasion for each individual is displayed. The syntax “1#2” indicates individual 1, occasion 2, according to the values defined in the ID and OCCASION columns.

In the “Individual estimates” output tables, the first columns indicate the ID and OCCASION (using the dataset headers). The covariates are included at the end of the table. Note that it is possible to sort the table by any column, including ID, OCCASION and COVARIATES.

Individual estimates

Non compartmental analysis results per individual Paginate

id	OCC	AUC _{0-inf}	AUC _{0-last}	CL/F	C _{last}	C _{max}	Flag_λ _z _Rule	k _{el}	Intercept	Number of points	Rsquared	ad
1	1	58.88	55.77	1.7	0.4	5.56	1	0.13	2.14	3	0.99	
1	2	59.8	58.29	1.67	0.23	7.66	1	0.16	2.28	3	0.99	
2	1	101.27	90.35	0.99	1.11	6.92	1	0.1	2.52	7	0.98	
2	2	105.01	92.31	0.95	1.19	8.79	1	0.094	2.36	7	0.98	
3	1	129.03	100.5	0.78	2.12	7.29	1	0.074	2.41	5	0.93	
3	2	123.67	105.7	0.81	1.53	9.94	1	0.085	2.41	8	0.98	
4	1	162.56	136.35	0.62	2.22	8.74	1	0.085	2.89	4	0.97	
4	2	163.97	131.91	0.61	2.26	10.01	1	0.07	2.48	10	0.97	
5	1	168.89	135.98	0.59	2.49	9.89	1	0.076	2.67	6	0.97	
5	2	148.51	127.17	0.67	1.74	10.9	1	0.081	2.51	3	0.99	

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The OCCASION values (here "OCC") are available to use in the plots for stratification, in addition to possible CATEGORICAL or CONTINUOUS COVARIATES (here "TREAT").

- demo **project_occasions2.ppkx**: a study with two treatments that are given with/without food

In this example, we have three sorting variables: ID, TREAT and FOOD. The TREAT and FOOD columns are duplicated: once with strings to be used as CATEGORICAL COVARIATE (TREAT and FOOD) and once with integers to be used as OCCASION (occT and occF).

The screenshot shows the 'Data file' section of the PKanalix software. It displays a table with the following columns: LINE NUMBER, ID, TIME, CONC, AMOUNT, CATEGORICAL COVARIATE (TREAT), CATEGORICAL COVARIATE (FOOD), OCCASION (occT), and OCCASION (occF). The data is sorted by ID, showing 15 records for ID 1. The TREAT column is 'ref' and the FOOD column is 'yes' for all records. The occT and occF columns are both '1' for all records.

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	CONC	AMOUNT	TREAT	FOOD	occT	occF
1	1	0		100	ref	yes	1	1
2	1	1	3.01805		ref	yes	1	1
3	1	1.5	4.154		ref	yes	1	1
4	1	2	5.15457		ref	yes	1	1
5	1	2.5	5.43767		ref	yes	1	1
6	1	3	6.03383		ref	yes	1	1
7	1	4	6.29869		ref	yes	1	1
8	1	5	6.47627		ref	yes	1	1
9	1	6	5.36803		ref	yes	1	1
10	1	8	5.06467		ref	yes	1	1
11	1	10	3.21281		ref	yes	1	1
12	1	12	3.23562		ref	yes	1	1
13	1	18	1.41012		ref	yes	1	1
14	1	24	0.77167		ref	yes	1	1

In the individual parameters tables and plots, three levels are visible (ID and the two occasions). In the "Individual parameters vs covariates" plot, we can plot Cmax versus FOOD, and split by TREAT for instance (Cmax versus TREAT and split by FOOD is also possible).

The screenshot shows the 'Individual estimates' table in the PKanalix software. It displays non-compartmental analysis results per individual. The table has columns for ID, occT, occF, AUC_{0-t}, AUC_{0-∞}, CLF, C_{max}, C_{min}, Flag_A_Risk, K_{el}, Intercept, Number of points, and R-square.

ID	occT	occF	AUC _{0-t}	AUC _{0-∞}	CLF	C _{max}	C _{min}	Flag_A_Risk	K _{el}	Intercept	Number of points	R-square
1	1	1	81.72	75.26	1.22	0.77	6.48	1	0.12	2.37	3	
1	1	2	88.7	81.93	1.23	0.79	7.12	1	0.12	2.37	3	
1	2	1	81.9	76.24	1.22	0.65	9.12	1	0.12	2.35	3	
1	2	2	87.64	82.95	1.14	0.59	9.13	1	0.12	2.49	9	
2	1	1	150.92	107.93	0.66	2.69	6.57	1	0.043	2.42	5	
2	1	2	140.47	115.9	0.7	2.01	8.65	1	0.076	2.3	3	
2	2	1	146.86	109.61	0.69	1.94	9.54	1	0.055	2.01	3	
2	2	2	136.85	114.96	0.72	1.69	9.91	1	0.077	2.42	5	
3	1	1	77.79	71.32	1.29	0.73	5.49	1	0.12	2.44	4	
3	1	2	81.31	76.96	1.23	0.41	7.09	1	0.18	3.33	3	

2.2.3.2.6 Covariates (“Carry” variables)

Individual information that should be carried over to output tables and plots must be tagged as CATEGORICAL or CONTINUOUS COVARIATES. Categorical covariates define variables with a few categories, such as treatment or sex, and are encoded as strings. Continuous covariates define variables on a continuous scale, such as weight or age, and are encoded as numbers. Covariates will not automatically be used as “Sort” variables. A dedicated OCCASION column is necessary (see above).

Covariates automatically appear in output tables. Plots of estimated NCA and/or CA parameters versus covariate values are also generated. In addition, covariates can be used to stratify (split, color or filter) plots. Statistics about the covariate distributions are available in table format in “Results > Cov. stat.” and in graphical format in “Plots > Covariate viewer”.

 Avoid spaces and special characters (stars, etc.) in the strings for the categories of the categorical covariates. Underscores are allowed.

Example:

- demo **project_covariates.pkx**

In this dataset, “SEX” is tagged as CATEGORICAL COVARIATE and “WEIGHT” as CONTINUOUS COVARIATE.

The screenshot shows the 'Data file' section of the PKanalix software. It includes a 'Data information' panel with 'Urine' and 'Plasma' radio buttons, and a 'Units' panel with dropdowns for 'TIME', 'CONC', and 'AMT'. The main data table is as follows:

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	OBSERVATION	AMOUNT	SEX	WEIGHT
1	1				F	70.6466
2	1	0		100	F	70.6466
3	1	1	16.6314		F	70.6466
4	1	1.5	21.5208		F	70.6466
5	1	2	11.746		F	70.6466
6	1	2.5	20.0199		F	70.6466
7	1	3	11.9624		F	70.6466
8	1	4	10.7658		F	70.6466
9	1	5	13.9579		F	70.6466
10	1	6	8.71148		F	70.6466
11	1	8	17.574		F	70.6466
12	1	10	8.24835		F	70.6466
13	1	12	5.81872		F	70.6466
14	1	18	4.55314		F	70.6466
15	1	24	2.54834		F	70.6466

The “cov stat” table displays some statistics for the covariate values in the dataset. In the plot “Covariate viewer,” we see that the distribution of weight is similar for male and female subjects.

The 'Continuous covariates' section shows the following statistics for the 'Weight' variable:

Statistic	Value
MIN	62.54
Q1	66.47
MEDIAN	69.91
Q3	73.44
MAX	83.27
SD	4.65

After running the NCA task, both covariates appear in the table of individual parameter estimates .

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NCA DISPLAY

Individual estimates

Non compartmental analysis results per individual Paginate

Flag_λ _z Rule	k _{el}	Intercept	Number of points	R squared	adjusted R squared	T _{last}	T _{max}	V _d /F	WEIGHT	SEX
1	0.077	2.81	4	0.96	0.94	24	1.5	5.7	70.65	F
1	0.21	4.63	3	0.99	0.99	24	2	2.28	67.52	F
1	0.057	1.83	4	0.94	0.9	24	3	17.37	65.31	M
1	0.12	2.8	3	0.99	0.99	24	1.5	7.82	66.67	M
1	0.1	2.74	3	0.99	0.98	24	2	5.76	68.13	F
1	0.067	3.01	3	0.99	0.99	24	5	5.47	71.19	F
1	0.1	3.16	5	0.96	0.95	24	3	5.08	71.81	F
1	0.13	2.1	9	0.97	0.97	24	2.5	13.79	76.76	M
1	0.091	3.39	6	0.92	0.9	24	5	3.8	64.49	F
1	0.095	3.66	3	0.99	0.98	24	5	3.53	64.74	F

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In the plot “parameters versus covariates,” the parameter values are plotted as scatter plots for continuous covariates with the parameter value (here C_{max} and AUCIN_F_pred) on the y-axis and the covariate on the x-axis, and as boxplots for categorical covariates.

All plots can be stratified using the covariates. For instance, the “Observed data” plot can be colored by weight with three custom weight groups. Or the “Distribution of the parameters” plot can be split by sex, shown with the AUCINF_pred parameter.

2.2.3.3 Description of all possible column types

Column-types used for all types of lines:

- ID (**mandatory**): identifier of the individual
- OCCASION (formerly OCC): identifier (index) of the occasion
- TIME (**mandatory**): time of the dose or observation record
- NOMINAL TIME (from 2024 version): time at which doses and observations were expected to occur
- DATE/DAT1/DAT2/DAT3: date of the dose or observation record, to be used in combination with the TIME column
- EVENT ID (formerly EVID): identifier to indicate if the line is a dose-line or a response-line
- IGNORED OBSERVATION (formerly MDV): identifier to ignore the OBSERVATION information of that line
- IGNORED LINE (from 2019 version): identifier to ignore all the informations of that line
- CONTINUOUS COVARIATE (formerly COV): continuous covariates (which can take values on a continuous scale)
- CATEGORICAL COVARIATE (formerly CAT): categorical covariate (which can only take a finite number of values)
- REGRESSOR (formerly X): defines a regression variable, i.e a variable that can be used in the structural model (used e.g for time-varying covariates)
- IGNORE: ignores the information of that column for all lines

Column-types used for response-lines:

- OBSERVATION (**mandatory, formerly Y**): records the measurement/observation for continuous, count, categorical or time-to-event data
- OBSERVATION ID (formerly YTYPE): identifier for the observation type (to distinguish different types of observations, e.g PK and PD)
- CENSORING (formerly CENS): marks censored data, below the lower limit or above the upper limit of quantification
- LIMIT: upper or lower boundary for the censoring interval in case of CENSORING column

Column-types used for dose-lines:

- AMOUNT (**mandatory, formerly AMT**): dose amount (with version 2024 only mandatory if dataset contains STEADY STATE, ADDITIONAL DOSES, INFUSIONRATE or INFUSION DURATION columns)
- ADMINISTRATION ID (formerly ADM): identifier for the type of dose (given via different routes for instance)
- INFUSION RATE (formerly RATE): rate of the dose administration (used in particular for infusions)
- INFUSION DURATION (formerly TINF): duration of the dose administration (used in particular for infusions)
- ADDITIONAL DOSES (formerly ADDL): number of doses to add in addition to the defined dose, at intervals INTERDOSE INTERVAL
- INTERDOSE INTERVAL (formerly II): interdose interval for doses added using ADDITIONAL DOSES or STEADY-STATE column types

- **STEADY STATE (formerly SS)**: marks that steady-state has been achieved, and will add a predefined number of doses before the actual dose, at interval INTERDOSE INTERVAL, in order to achieve steady-state

2.2.3.4 Columns used to identify subjects-occasions

2.2.3.4.1 ID: subject identifier

The column is used to identify the different subjects and is mandatory. Its content is totally free (integers, double, strings...), but we recommend to use integers for better readability. The IDs will be sorted by order of appearance in the data set.

2.2.3.4.1.1 Examples

- **Example with strings**: the string '.' will not be interpreted as a repetition of the previous line. As a consequence a data set of the form

```
ID * *  
John * *  
John * *  
Mike * *  
. * *
```

contains 3 different subjects : 'John', 'Mike' and '.'.

- **Example with mixed IDs**: the lines corresponding to the same subject do not need to be next to each other. Thus, the following file contains 2 subjects with IDs "1" and "2".

```
ID * *  
1 * *  
1 * *  
2 * *  
2 * *  
1 * *
```

2.2.3.4.1.2 Format restrictions

- A data set shall contain one and only one column ID.
- The ID must be defined for all lines.
- The string '.' will not be interpreted as a repetition of the previous line

2.2.3.4.2 OCCASION (formerly OCC): occasion identifiers

<https://youtu.be/ejBb9yxzwwY>

Occasions define different periods of time within individuals. **Each combination of subject ID and occasion will be analyzed as a separate profile in both NCA and CA.** The MonolixSuite allows the definition of several columns with the column-type OCCASION, which can be used to define several levels of inter-occasion variability. The OCCASION columns can contain only integers (neither necessarily starting at one, nor necessarily consecutive), which represent occasion identifiers. All times points belonging to one occasion must be in one block (i.e., not interrupted by time points of another occasion). When switching from one occasion to the next one, time can restart at the initial value or continue. If different occasions contain time points that overlap, a washout will automatically be added when performing compartmental analysis (CA).

2.2.3.4.2.1 Examples and typical situations

- **Cross over study:** In that case, data are collected for each patient during two independent treatment periods of time, there is an overlap on the time definition of the periods (e.g both periods start at 0). A column-type OCCASION can be used used to identify the periods.
- **Occasions without washout:** In that case, there are no overlap between the periods. The time is increasing and we want to differentiate periods in terms of occasions without any reset of the dynamical system.
- **Occasions with washout (due to overlapping times):** In that case, the time is increasing across the occasions. When performing compartmental analysis (CA), the overlap between two time points of two different occasions creates a washout. If the washout is not desired, one of the two times can be offset by a small value to avoid the overlap. When performing non-compartmental analysis (NCA), it is not important if the overlap exists or not.

Crossover with overlapping time periods					Occasions with increasing time and no washout					Occasions with increasing time and washout due to time overlap				
ID	TIME	OCC	AMT	Y	ID	TIME	OCC	AMT	Y	ID	TIME	OCC	AMT	Y
1	0	1	10	.	1	0	1	10	.	1	0	1	10	.
1	1	1	.	10.5	1	1	1	.	10.5	1	1	1	.	10.5
1	2	1	.	8.9	1	2	1	.	8.9	1	2	1	.	8.9
1	3	1	.	6.5	1	3	1	.	6.5	1	3	1	.	6.5
1	0	2	10	.	1	4	2	10	.	1	3	1	10	.
1	1	2	.	15.2	1	5	2	.	15.2	1	4	2	.	15.2
1	2	2	.	10.6	1	6	2	.	10.6	1	5	2	.	10.6
1	3	2	.	5.5	1	7	2	.	5.5	1	6	2	.	5.5

However, the following situation, which would aim at defining the same occasion index to all morning doses, is not allowed:

Not allowed

ID	TIME	OCC	AMT	Y	
1	0	1	10	.	<i>morning dose</i>
1	1	1	.	10.5	
1	2	1	.	8.9	
1	12	2	20	.	<i>evening dose</i>
1	13	2	.	15.2	
1	14	2	.	10.6	
1	24	1	10	.	<i>morning dose</i>
1	23	1	.	9.5	
1	25	1	.	7.8	

2.2.3.4.2.2 FAQ on occasions in the data set

- **Do all the individual need to share the same sequence of occasion?**
No, the number of occasions and the times defining the occasions can differ from one individual to another.
- **Do the occasion indices need to start at one for each individual?** No.
- **Do the occasion indices need to be consecutive for each individual?** No.
- **Is there any limit in terms of number of occasions?** No.
- **Is it possible to have several levels of occasions?**
Yes, it is possible to have several level of occasions (multiple occasion columns).

2.2.3.4.2.3 Format restrictions

- The OCCASION columns should contain only integers.
- If the OCCASION column-type is used, the OCCASION must be defined for all lines.

2.2.3.5 Columns used to define time

2.2.3.5.1 TIME: data time stamp

The TIME columns define the time at which dose and observation events occurred. When no DATE/DAT1/DAT2/DAT3 column is present, the time represents the time elapsed. When a DATE/DAT1/DAT2/DAT3 column is present, it represents the time of the day. **The time can be defined using a double, or a clock format hh:mm or hh:mm:ss. Negative time values are allowed.** When the double format is used, and no DATE/DAT1/DAT2/DAT3 column is present, the time has no predefined units. In all other cases, the time units are hours.

When a subject has time under the clock format, all times are converted into relative hours, as on the following example:

TIME	Reconstructed time
10:00	10
10:30	10.5
14:00	14
08:59	8.983333

When there is no column-type TIME, the column-type NOMINAL TIME is used as time, and if neither TIME nor NOMINAL TIME column-types are present, the column-type DATE is ignored, and the first column-type REGRESSOR is used as time. If no columns are tagged as REGRESSOR, time will be equal to the index of row number containing observations / amounts for each subject-occasion.

2.2.3.5.1.1 Format restrictions

- A data set shall not contain more than one column with the column-type TIME.
- If the TIME column-type is used, the TIME must be defined for all lines.
- String “.” will not be interpreted as a repetition of the previous line and is non-compliant with formats listed here-above.

2.2.3.5.2 **NOMINAL TIME: data nominal time stamp**

The NOMINAL TIME column defines the time at which doses and observations were expected to occur. The column format is the same as the format of the TIME column and the same restrictions apply, with the exception that lines with missing values are not automatically ignored, but taken from TIME column, if it exists in the data set.

If defined, the NOMINAL TIME column:

- can be used instead of TIME column on x-axis of Observed data (Monolix/PKanalix) and Visual predictive check (Monolix) plots,
- can be used instead of TIME column in the NCA Concentrations table (PKanalix),
- is used in NCA sparse data calculations (PKanalix),
- is used in all other calculations, if TIME column is not defined (Monolix/PKanalix).

2.2.3.5.3 **DATE/DAT1/DAT2/DAT3: date information**

The DATE column-type can be used to indicate the date of the dose or observation event. It is usually used in combination with the TIME column-type, which in that case indicates the time of the day. To accommodate the different date formats, several column types are possible:

	Format and associated date column name

	DATE	DAT1	DAT2	DAT3
Day, month and year	mm/dd/yy or mm/dd/yyyy mm-dd-yy or mm-dd-yyyy	dd/mm/yy or dd/mm/yyyy dd-mm-yy or dd-mm-yyyy	yy/mm/dd or yyyy/mm/dd yy-mm-dd or yyyy-mm-dd	yy/dd/mm or yyyy/dd/mm yy-dd-mm or yyyy-dd-mm

By default, when the year is coded with two digits, it is interpreted as 20xx.

2.2.3.5.3.1 Format restrictions

- A data set shall not contain more than one column-type DATE / DAT1 / DAT2 / DAT3.
- Year, day, and month shall be integers.
- The separator must be "/" or "-"
- Character "." will not be interpreted as a repetition of the previous line and is not compliant with the DATE formats.
- All the lines should be filled correctly within the same delimiter, according to the specified date format: i.e., no empty year, no empty month, no empty day, no mix of delimiters.

2.2.3.5.4 Timestamp summary

There are several ways to define the timestamp of the data set depending if there is a TIME column or not and if there is a DATE column or not.

	(NOMINAL) TIME column present	(NOMINAL) TIME column not present
DATE column present	DATE column is considered to represent the day and the TIME column the hour within this day	Date column ignored (regressor or index used)
DATE column not present	TIME column is considered to represent the time (no specific units)	First regression-column will be used to timestamp data

2.2.3.5.5 FAQ

- **My data is not "over time", what should I do?** You can arbitrarily set the time of each observation to 0.
- **What happens if neither TIME nor DATE is defined?** We strongly encourage the user to explicitly define the TIME column-type. However, if there is neither TIME nor DATE column-types, the first regression-column (i.e. first column with column-type REGRESSION) will be used to timestamp data. Moreover, if there is no TIME, no DATE and no REGRESSION column-type, time is equal to row indexes of each subject-occasion.

2.2.3.6 Columns used to define observations

2.2.3.6.1 OBSERVATION: response

The OBSERVATION column-type can be used to record continuous (PKAnalix and Monolix), categorical (Monolix), count (Monolix) or time-to-event (Monolix) data. For dose lines, the content is free and will not be used. For response lines, the requirements depend on the type of data and are summarized below.

2.2.3.6.1.1 Continuous data

The value represents what has been measured (e.g concentrations) and can be any double value.

Examples

- **Basic example:**

ID	TIME	AMT	Y
1	0	50	.
1	0.5	.	1.1
1	1	.	9.2
1	1.5	.	8.5
1	2	.	6.3
1	2.5	.	5.5

2.2.3.6.1.2 Warnings

- If a subject or a subject-occasion has no observations, a warning message arises telling which subjects or subjects-occasions have no measurements and will be ignored.

2.2.3.6.1.3 Format restrictions

- A data set shall not contain more than one column with column-type OBSERVATION. Multiple observation types need to be distinguished with the OBSERVATION ID column.

2.2.3.6.2 OBSERVATION ID: response identifier

The OBSERVATION ID column permits to distinguish several types of observations (several concentrations, effects, etc). The OBSERVATION ID column assigns an identifier to each observation of the OBSERVATION column. Those identifiers are used to map the observations of the data set to the

outputs of the model (in the OUTPUT block of the model file). The dot "." is not considered as a repetition of the previous line but as a different identifier.

There can be more OBSERVATION ID values than there are outputs in the model file. In that case only the observations corresponding to the first identifiers(s) in alphabetical order will be used (example below).

Typical use cases for the OBSERVATION ID column are to distinguish between urine and plasma concentration data, between parent and metabolite concentrations, or concentrations of different drugs in the combination therapy.

Note that remarks regarding model files are connected to the compartmental analysis (CA) feature of PKanalix. When performing non-compartmental analysis (NCA), user can select to perform the analysis only on one OBSERVATION ID per project. To analyze multiple OBSERVATION IDs, a user has to save multiple project files.

2.2.3.6.2.1 Format restrictions

- A data set shall not contain more than one column with column-type OBSERVATION ID.
- The content of the OBSERVATION ID column can be strings or integers.
- The dot "." is not considered as a repetition of the previous line but as a different identifier.

2.2.3.6.3 CENSORING: censored observation

The CENSORING column permits to mark censored data. When an observation is marked as censored, the (upper or lower) limit of quantification is given in the OBSERVATION column (not in a separate column).

- CENSORING = 1 means that the value in OBSERVATION column is a lower limit of quantification (LLOQ). The true observation y verifies $y < \text{LLOQ}$.
- CENSORING = 0 means the value in response-column corresponds to a valid observation (no interval associated).
- CENSORING = -1 means that the value in OBSERVATION column is an upper limit of quantification (ULOQ). The true observation y verifies $y > \text{ULOQ}$.

The observations that have CENSORING = 1 can be treated as zero, missing, equal to LLOQ or LLOQ/2 in both NCA and CA.

2.2.3.6.3.1 Format restrictions

- A data set shall not contain more than one column with column-type CENSORING.
- For dose lines, the content is free and will be ignored.
- For response lines, there are only four possible values : -1, 0, 1 and '.' (interpreted as 0).

2.2.3.6.4 LIMIT: limit for censored values

The LIMIT column does not impact calculations in PKanalix.

2.2.3.7 Columns used to define doses

2.2.3.7.1 AMOUNT: dose amount

The AMOUNT column records the amount of the administered doses. For dose-lines, the value must be a double. For response-lines, the content is free.

2.2.3.7.1.1 Examples

- **Basic example:** the individual 1 receives a dose of 10 at time 0

ID	TIME	AMT	Y
1	0	10	.
1	1	.	6
1	2	.	4

- **Example with a single dose split into two routes of absorption:** a single dose may be absorbed at different sites, leading to several absorption route. This can be taken into account by splitting the dose into several fractions, directed to several absorption macros. With the following data set:

ID	TIME	AMT	Y
1	0	10	.
1	1	.	6
1	2	.	4

and the following PK block in the model file:

```
PK:
oral(ka=ka1, p=F)
oral(ka=ka2, Tlag, p=1-F)
```

a fraction F of the dose is absorbed via a first-order process with rate constant ka1, and a fraction 1-F is absorbed with a absorption constant ka2 after a lag time Tlag.

2.2.3.7.1.2 Format restrictions

- A data set shall not contain more than one column-type AMOUNT.
- For dose-lines with EVENT ID = 1, 3 or 4, the value must be a double.
- For lines without EVENT ID, the value must be a double or a dot ''

2.2.3.7.2 ADMINISTRATION ID: administration identifier

The ADMINISTRATION ID column permits to distinguish different types of administrations, for instance oral administrations and intravenous administrations. The content of the ADMINISTRATION ID column is used for dose-line only and must be a positive integer. This integer works like a flag, which can be used in the model file to link the dose information of the data set to a specific administration route in the model.

2.2.3.7.2.1 Examples

- **Example with oral and iv administrations:** For instance, with the following data set:

```
ID  TIME  AMT  ADM  Y
John 0    10   1    .
Eric 0    20   2    .
Jean 0    10   3    .
```

and the following PK block in the Mlxtran model file:

```
PK:
iv(adm=1)
oral(adm=2, ka)
```

the subject John will receive a dose of 10 via a bolus iv, while subject Eric will receive a dose of 20 orally with first-order rate constant ka. The identifier in the ADMINISTRATION ID column should match the “adm=” field of the administration macros. A same subject can receive some doses via one route and other doses via another route. The administration type with id ‘3’ is not used in the model, thus all doses with this id will not be applied.

The default value for administration types is 1. This means that if there is no column ADMINISTRATION ID in the dataset, all doses will be associated to the administration id 1. If the dataset contains a column ADMINISTRATION ID but the structural model does not include arguments *adm* to indicate how to apply the different types of doses, only the doses with administration id ‘1’ in the data set will be used.

2.2.3.7.2.2 Format restrictions

- For dose-lines, the column shall contain only positive integers. For response-lines, dots ‘.’ or integers are allowed.
- A data set shall not contain more than one ADMINISTRATION ID column-type.

2.2.3.7.3 INFUSION RATE and INFUSION DURATION: rate and duration of infusion

These columns enable to define the rate (INFUSION RATE column-type) or duration (INFUSION DURATION column-type) of doses administered as infusions. The column content is meaningful only for dose-lines. The rate and duration information is transferred to the model via the use of the iv macro, depot macro or pkmodel macro. If a RATE is defined, the duration of the infusion will be AMOUNT/RATE. If a DURATION is defined, the rate will be AMOUNT/DURATION. The units must be coherent with the units of the AMOUNT and TIME columns. A dose-lines, if a negative value, or dot '.' or 0 is used, the infusion will be replaced by a bolus.

We strongly recommend to have small duration values (less than 10). Indeed, if the duration is too long, the calculation of the analytical solution of the model may produce NaN. Two workarounds are possible:

- Either rescale the time units to have smaller duration values.
- Use ODEs instead of analytical solutions. ODEs can be enforced with `useAnalyticalSolution = no` in the model file.

2.2.3.7.3.1 Examples

- **Basic example:** with the following data set, assuming the TIME units are minutes and AMOUNT units mg, an amount of 10 mg will be applied via an infusion over 5 minutes starting at time 0. This is equivalent to a RATE of 2 mg/minute. The 20 mg doses at time 2, 3, and 4 minutes are applied via a bolus.

ID	TIME	AMT	TINF	Y
1	0	10	5	.
1	1	.	.	6
1	2	20	0	.
1	3	20	-2	.
1	4	20	.	.

2.2.3.7.3.2 Format restrictions

- A data set shall not contain more than one column with column-type INFUSION RATE or INFUSION DURATION.
- A negative value, "." or 0 means a bolus dose, without any infusion rate or time.
- For dose-lines, the value must be a double, or a dot '.'.
- For response lines, the content is free.

2.2.3.7.4 STEADY STATE and INTERDOSE INTERVAL: steady-state and inter-dose interval

Steady-state is used to specify that any transitory effect is over and that the system response is now a periodic function of doses. In practice, a fixed number of doses (by default 5) is added before the dose entered with the STEADY STATE flag (so 6 doses in total, by default). The period between doses is set to the INTERDOSE INTERVAL. The number of doses to add can be changed when loading the data and will be saved in the project file. The number of added doses may be reduced compared to the specified value if the doses to add would interfere with another dose or observation: any steady-state dose that would be added before (i.e earlier in time) a dose or response line is not added, even if the line information is ignored (for instance with EVENT ID = 2 or IGNORED OBSERVATION = 1).

The allowed values are the following:

- STEADY-STATE = 0 or '': no steady-state, the dose is a normal dose.
- STEADY-STATE = 1 : the system has achieved steady-state. A washout (i.e reset to the initial values of the model) is applied before the first added dose.
- STEADY-STATE = 2 or 3 : the system has achieved steady-state. Unlike STEADY-STATE = 1, no washout is added.

STEADY-STATE and EVENT ID: when STEADY-STATE = 1 is used on the same line as EVENT ID = 3 or 4, a washout is applied just before the first dose added for steady-state (because of STEADY-STATE = 1) and also just before the dose defined on that line (because of EVENT ID = 3 or 4). When STEADY-STATE = 2 or 3 is used on the same line as EVENT ID = 3 or 4, a washout is added just before the dose defined on that line.

2.2.3.7.4.1 Examples

- **Basic example:** On the following example:

```
ID TIME AMT SS II Y
1 0 10 1 2 .
```

5 doses are applied, at times -10, -8, -6, -4, -2 in addition to the dose at time = 0. The above data set is thus equivalent to:

```
ID TIME AMT SS II Y
1 -10 10 0 0 .
1 -8 10 0 0 .
1 -6 10 0 0 .
1 -4 10 0 0 .
1 -2 10 0 0 .
1 0 10 0 0 .
```

The first added dose will have a wash-out.

- **Example with informations colliding with doses to add:** The following data set, with a normal dose at $t=0$ and a steady-state dose at $t=10$ with an interdose-interval of 3.5 will lead to the following situation:

Even if 5 additional doses are specified in the GUI when loading the data, there will be only 2 additional doses as otherwise the previous measurements would be interfered with. In addition, there is a washout (highlighted in purple) just before the first added dose. If we would replace $SS=1$ by $SS=2$ on line 5, we would again have only 2 doses added but no wash out as can be seen in the following figure:

- **Typical example with pre-dose PK measurement, dose at site and post-dose PK measurements:** the subject takes regularly doses at home. During a hospital visit, he gets a pre-dose PK measurement, a dose at site, and one or several post-dose PK measurements. The STEADY-STATE statement cannot be applied on the dose administered at site, as the doses to add would interfere with the pre-dose PK measurement. We thus need to write:

1	0	10	1	24	.	; steady-state statement
1	23.9	.	.	.	5.5	; pre-dose measurement

```

1  24    10  .  .  .  ; dose at site
1  25    .  .  .  9.9 ; post-dose measurement
  
```

2.2.3.7.4.2 FAQ

- **Can I define two different STEADY-STATE lines for morning and evening doses?** No, as the doses to add would collide with each other. You will have to use an ADDITIONAL DOSES column instead.

2.2.3.7.4.3 Format restrictions (STEADY STATE)

- A data set shall not contain more than one column with column-type STEADY STATE.
- If there is a column-type STEADY STATE, there should be a column-type INTERDOSE INTERVAL.
- Accepted values (for all lines, including response-lines): 0, 1, 2, 3 or dot '.'

2.2.3.7.4.4 Format restrictions (INTERDOSE-INTERVAL)

- A data set shall not contain more than one column with column-type INTERDOSE INTERVAL.
- If there is a column-type STEADY STATE, there should be a column-type INTERDOSE INTERVAL.
- Accepted values:
 - on response-line: 0 or '.' (non-zero double value will generate a warning)
 - on normal dose-line (no STEADY-STATE or ADDITIONAL DOSE): 0 or '.' (non-zero double value will generate a warning)
 - on STEADY-STATE or ADDITIONAL DOSE line: non-zero double value
- Clock format is not accepted

2.2.3.7.5 ADDITIONAL DOSES: additional dose line

The ADDITIONAL DOSES column is a useful shortcut to specify dose regimens with repetitive treatments. The value in ADDITIONAL DOSES is the number of times the dose shall be repeated (in addition to the dose defined on that line) and column INTERDOSE INTERVAL contains the dose repetition interval. Doses that would be added after the last measurement are useless and will thus not be added.

2.2.3.7.5.1 Examples

- **Basic example:** For instance to specify a dose of 10 every 12 hours during 3 days it is possible to write:

```

ID TIME AMT
Tom  0  10
Tom 12  10
  
```

```
Tom 24 10
Tom 36 10
Tom 48 10
Tom 60 10
Tom 72 10
```

but ADDITIONAL DOSES (ADDL) and INTERDOSE INTERVAL (II) can also be used to specify the same information in a single line

```
ID TIME AMT ADDL II
Tom 0 10 6 12
```

2.2.3.7.5.2 Format restrictions

- When there is an ADDL column there must be an INTERDOSE INTERVAL (interdose interval) column to indicate the inter dose timing.
- For dose-lines with ADDL strictly positive, the INTERDOSE INTERVAL value must be strictly positive.
- Accepted values:
 - on normal dose lines: 0 or ''
 - on response lines: 0 or ''
 - on lines where ADDITIONAL DOSES is needed: positive integer

2.2.3.8 Columns used to define covariates

2.2.3.8.1 CONTINUOUS COVARIATE: continuous covariate

The column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE is used to tag continuous covariates, i.e covariates which can take values on a continuous scale (such as weight or age). Covariates tagged in the data set can (but don't have to) be used as covariates in the model. The covariate value must be constant within subjects (or within occasions if occasions are present). If the value is not constant, the first value of each subject in time ordering will be used for all times (and a warning is generated). To define time varying covariate, use REGRESSORS.

The allowed values are doubles or dot '.'. There must be at least one non-dot value per subject (or per occasion if occasions are defined).

2.2.3.8.1.1 Examples

- **Basic example:** in the following data set, individual 1 has weight WT = 78, individual 2 has WT = 80 for all times points (first value in time ordering) and individual 3 has WT = 90.

ID	TIME	Y	WT
1	0	5.7	78
1	1	5.6	78
2	0	6.7	80
2	1	6.5	82
3	0	7.8	.
3	1	8.9	90

2.2.3.8.1.2 Format restrictions

- Continuous covariate columns shall contain either a double or “.”.
- The covariate must be defined at least once per subject-occasion.
- The covariate must remain the same for all the lines within the same subject-occasion.

2.2.3.8.2 CATEGORICAL COVARIATE: categorical covariate

The column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE is used to tag categorical covariates, i.e covariates which can only take a finite number of values (such as sex or a genotype). Covariates tagged in the data set can (but don't have to) be used as covariates in the model. The covariate value must be constant within subjects (or within occasions if occasions are present). If the value is not constant, the first value of each subject in time ordering will be used for all times (and a warning is generated). To define time varying covariate, use REGRESSORS.

The allowed values are strings, doubles or dot ‘.’. There must be at least one non-dot value per subject (or per occasion if occasions are defined), otherwise the category is considered to be ‘NA’.

2.2.3.8.2.1 Examples

- **Basic example:** in the following data set, the covariate SEX has two categories ‘F’ and ‘M’ and the individual 3 has value ‘F’. The covariate GENO has three categories ‘1’, ‘2’ and ‘NA’ (coming from the individual 3 which has no valid value). The covariate RACE has only one category ‘1’. Individual 1 has RACE = 1, as this is the value defined first in time. RACE will not appear in the graphical user interface because it is not possible to use a covariate with only one category in a model.

ID	TIME	Y	SEX	GENO	RACE
1	0	5.7	F	1	1
1	1	5.6	F	1	2
2	0	6.7	M	2	1
2	1	6.5	M	2	1
3	0	7.8	.	.	1
3	1	8.9	F	.	1

2.2.3.8.2.2 Format restrictions

- The covariate must be defined at least once per subject-occasion.
- The categorical covariate must be the same for all the lines with the same subject-occasion.

2.2.3.9 Columns used to define regressors (urine volume)

2.2.3.9.1 REGRESSOR: regression value

REGRESSOR columns define variables (possibly time-varying) that will be available:

- for display on x-axis in the Observed data plot,
- for NCA calculations as urine volume,
- for CA calculations in the structural model.

2.2.3.9.1.1 Tagging urine volume for NCA

If urine data is present in the data set, the column with urine volume needs to be tagged as a REGRESSOR. After accepting the data set, the radio buttons are displayed in the Data tab to select if the data is plasma concentration or urine concentration (purple). If the urine option is selected, a dropdown is displayed in which a user can choose which regressor column represents urine volume (orange).

Data information

Urine Plasma

Regressor for urine volume

VOL ▾

Regressors settings

Last carried forward Linear interpolation

2.2.3.9.1.2 Usage of regressors in CA

Allowed values in the REGRESSOR column are doubles and dot '.' (to indicate missing values). For the first record (observation or dose line) of each subject (or subject-occasion if occasions are present), the

regressor value cannot be missing (no dot '.' allowed). For the following missing values, the interpolation will be done using the setting chosen in the GUI, which can be **"Last Carried Forward"** or **"linear interpolation"**. Regressor values on observation or dose lines are used the same way, as well as regressor values on lines with no observation and no dose.

- **last carried forward:** if we have defined in the dataset two times for each individual with (reg_A) at time (t_A) and (reg_B) at time (t_B)
 - for (t ≤ t_A), (reg(t)=reg_A) [first defined value is used]
 - for (t_A < t < t_B), (reg(t)=reg_A) [previous value is used]
 - for (t > t_B), (reg(t)=reg_B) [previous value is used]
- **linear interpolation:** the interpolation is:
 - for (t ≤ t_A), (reg(t)=reg_A) [first defined value is used]
 - for (t_A < t < t_B), (reg(t)=reg_A+(t-t_A)frac{(reg_B-reg_A)}{(t_B-t_A)}) [linear interpolation is used]
 - for (t > t_B), (reg(t)=reg_B) [previous value is used]

LINE NUMBER	SUBJ	TIME	DV	WT	SEX	AGE	REGRESSOR
2	1	0	98	66.7	1	50	
3	1	24	49	66.7	1	50	9
4	1	36	32	66.7	1	50	7
5	1	48	26	66.7	1	50	6
6	1	72	22	66.7	1	50	4

Several columns can be tagged as REGRESSOR. In that case, **the mapping with the regressors defined in the model is done by name if possible, otherwise by order:** the first column tagged as REGRESSOR in the data set is mapped to the first element in the model input list defined as regressor.

If within a subject (or subject-occasion if occasions are present) two events are defined at the same time on two different lines, the regressor value must be the same on both lines. The regressor value is used even if the dose or observation is ignored (for instance using the EVENT ID and IGNORED OBSERVATION columns).

Lines added due to a STEADY-STATE column get the same regressor value as the line with the STEADY-STATE statement. Lines added due to an ADDITIONAL DOSES column get a dot '.' and are then interpolated based on the previous values.

2.2.3.9.1.3 Examples

- **Example with one regressor:** the regressor corresponds to the drug concentration, which will be used in a direct effect PD model. With the following data set:

ID	TIME	Y	REG
1	0	3.3	6.2
1	1	5.6	4.1
1	2	6.8	.
1	3	7.0	2.9

and the following model:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {E0, IC50 , Cc}
Cc = { use = regressor }

EQUATION:
E = E0 * (1 - Cc/(Cc+IC50))

OUTPUT:
output = {E}
```

The regressor variable Cc in the model will take the values defined in the REG column and be used to calculate the effect E. For time points not defined in the data set, interpolation will be done depending on the chosen Regressor Setting. **If "Last Observation Carried Forward" is selected:** during the time interval [0, 1[, the regressor value is that defined on time 0. Note that the column header and the model regressor variable name can differ.

Regressor Cc

Output E

- **Example with two regressors:** the regressors correspond to the individual PK parameters used to calculate the drug concentration, itself impacting the effect E. With the following data set:

ID	TIME	AMT	Y	V_mode	k_mode
1	0	10	.	6.2	1.2
1	0	.	3.3	6.2	1.2
1	1	.	5.6	6.2	1.2
1	2	.	6.8	6.2	1.2
1	3	.	7.0	6.2	1.2

and the following model:

```
[LONGITUDINAL]
input = {E0, EC50 , V, k}
V = { use = regressor }
k = { use = regressor }

EQUATION:
Cc = pkmodel(V,k)
E = E0 * (1 - Cc/(Cc+EC50))

OUTPUT:
output = {E}
```

The first column tagged as REGRESSOR (V_mode) is mapped to the first regressor in the input list (V), and the REGRESSOR column of the data set (k_mode) is mapped to the second regressor of the model (k).

Regressors V and k

Variable Cc

Output E

- **Example with STEADY-STATE and ADDITIONAL DOSES:**

ID	TIME	AMT	SS	ADDL	II	Y	REG
1	0	5.5	1
1	3	10	2
1	4	10	2
1	5	10	2
1	6	10	.	.	.	4.2	3
1	7	10	.	.	.	3.3	4
1	8	10	2
1	9	4.2	3
1	10	3.3	4
1	12	5	.	2	2	.	5
1	13	6.7	6
1	15	5.4	7
1	17	4.5	8

ID	TIME	AMT	Y	REG
1	0	.	5.5	1
1	3	10	.	2
1	4	10	.	2
1	5	10	.	2
1	6	10	.	2
1	7	10	.	2
1	8	10	.	2
1	9	.	4.2	3
1	10	.	3.3	4
1	12	5	.	5
1	13	.	6.7	6
1	14	5	.	6
1	15	.	5.4	7
1	16	5	.	7
1	17	.	4.5	8

lines added by SS=1 have the same regressor value as on the SS=1 line

lines added by ADDL are interpolated based on the previous time

2.2.3.9.1.4 Format restrictions

- The regression-columns (i.e. columns with column-type REGRESSOR) shall contain either doubles or "." (which will be interpolated).
- The first record for each subject (or subject-occasion) cannot be dot '.'.
- When there are several lines with the same time, same id and same occasion, the value of the regressor column must be the same.

2.2.3.10 Columns used to define controls and events

2.2.3.10.1 EVENT ID: event identification data item.

The EVENT ID column permits to assign lines to be dose or response-lines, and to define washouts/resets. The column is not mandatory, as dose and response lines can be recognized based on the content. The EVENT ID column can take 5 different values:

- **EVENT ID = 0:** observation event, the line is a response-line. The dose-related informations (AMOUNT column, etc) are ignored.
- **EVENT ID = 1:** dose event, the line is a dose-line. The response-related informations (OBSERVATION column, etc) are ignored.

- **EVENT ID = 2:** other event. Both the dose information and the observation are ignored. Note that no prediction will be outputted for that time in the output files.
- **EVENT ID = 3:** reset + dose event. The system is reset to the initial values and the dose is applied immediately after. To do a reset without applying a new dose, the dose amount can be set to zero. Unlike EVENT ID = 4, no occasions are created. The line is a dose-line (i.e the response-related informations are ignored).
- **EVENT ID = 4:** reset + dose event. The system is reset to the initial values and the dose is applied immediately after. If at least one EVENT ID = 4 appear at a position which is not the first record of an individual, a OCCASION column-type called OCCevid will be created. It may (but doesn't have to) be used to define inter-occasion variability. To do a reset without applying a new dose, the dose amount can be set to zero. The line is a dose-line (i.e the response-related informations are ignored).

All combinations of EVENT ID and IGNORED OBSERVATION values are possible and EVENT ID has priority over IGNORED OBSERVATION (for instance if EVENT ID = 1 and IGNORED OBSERVATION = 0, the line is a dose-line). For all EVENT ID values, the REGRESSOR values are taken into account.

2.2.3.10.1.1 Examples

- **Example with EVENT ID = 0, 1, 2 and 3:**

ID	TIME	AMT	Y	EVID	
1	0	10	.	1	dose-line
1	1	.	9.8	0	
1	2	.	6.7	0	
1	3	10	.	2	dose ignored
1	4	.	4.3	0	
1	5	.	2.3	0	
1	6	0	.	3	reset + dose=0
1	7	.	0	0	
1	8	.	0	0	
1	9	10	.	1	dose-line
1	10	10	.	3	reset + dose
1	11	.	7.6	0	

- **Example with EVENT ID = 4:**

2.2.3.10.1.2 Format restrictions

- A data set shall not contain more than one column with column-type EVENT ID.
- EVENT ID shall contain an integer in {0, 1, 2, 3, 4}.
- When a line is tagged EVENT ID = 0, and IGNORED OBSERVATION = 0, the value contained in column OBSERVATION shall be a double.
- When a line is tagged EVENT ID = 1, 3 or 4, the value in the AMOUNT column shall be a double.

2.2.3.10.2 IGNORED OBSERVATION: ignores the observations (missing dependent variable)

The IGNORED OBSERVATION column-type enables to tag lines for which the information in the OBSERVATION column-type should be ignored (because they are outliers, or because one wants to ignore all PK measurements for instance). The column is not mandatory. Several IGNORED OBSERVATION columns are possible (see below) and 3 values are possible:

- **IGNORED OBSERVATION = 0:** the value in the OBSERVATION column is not ignored. If in addition EVENT ID = 0, the value in the OBSERVATION column has to be a double.
- **IGNORED OBSERVATION = 1:** the value in the OBSERVATION column is ignored.
- **IGNORED OBSERVATION = 2:** identical to IGNORED OBSERVATION = 1. Note that no prediction will be made at that time point in the output files.

If there are both an IGNORED OBSERVATION and an EVENT ID column, the EVENT ID column has priority to define dose and response-lines. It is not necessary to set IGNORED OBSERVATION = 1 when EVENT ID = 1.

For all IGNORED OBSERVATION values, the REGRESSOR values are taken into account.

It is possible to have multiple IGNORED OBSERVATION columns in order to ignore observations for different reasons (for instance an "outliers" column to ignore outliers and a "placebo" column to ignore individuals which received only placebo, both tagged as IGNORED OBSERVATION column-type). When there are multiple IGNORED OBSERVATION columns, a synthetic value is computed as:

- if IGNORED OBSERVATION = 0 in all columns, then resulting synthetic IGNORED OBSERVATION equals 0.

- if IGNORED OBSERVATION = 1 or 2 in at least one column, then the resulting synthetic IGNORED OBSERVATION equals 1.

2.2.3.10.2.1 Examples

- **Example with IGNORED OBSERVATION = 0, 1 or 2:**

ID	TIME	AMT	Y	MDV
1	0	10	.	1
1	1	.	10.1	0
1	2	.	8.3	2
1	3	.	6.9	0
1	4	.	5.7	0
1	5	.	4.8	1
1	6	.	3.6	0

observation ignored

observation ignored

2.2.3.10.2.2 Format restrictions

- IGNORED OBSERVATION shall contain only integers in {0, 1, 2}.
- If IGNORED OBSERVATION = 0 and EVENT ID = 0, the value in the OBSERVATION column has to be a double.

2.2.3.10.3 IGNORED LINE: ignores all the element of the line

Starting from the 2019 version, the IGNORED LINE column-type enables to tag lines for which all the information should be ignored (because they are outliers, or because one wants to ignore all PK measurements for instance). Contrary to the IGNORED OBSERVATION column-type that only ignores the observation value, the IGNORED LINE column-type allows to ignore doses and regressor values in addition to the observation values.

The column is not mandatory.

Starting from the 2021 version, there can be several columns IGNORED LINE, while in previous versions there can be only one such column.

Starting from the 2024 version, IGNORED LINE column can contain integers larger than 1, while previously the values were restricted to 0 and 1.

2.2.3.10.3.1 Format restrictions

- IGNORED LINE shall contain only non-negative integers.

2.2.3.11 Allowed characters

We recommend to use only alphanumeric characters and the underscore “_” character in the strings of your data set.

Unfortunately, special characters such as spaces “ ”, stars “*”, parentheses “()”, brackets “[”], dashes “-”, dots “.” and slashes “/” are not supported in:

- the headers,
- the strings in categorical covariate columns.

Please be careful that if your data set includes unsupported characters, the error will only be detected and displayed when loading a saved project (and not when creating and saving the project).

2.2.3.11.1 On the use of “.”

The “.” can be used in almost all the lines of the data set but has several meaning depending on the context. The following table summarizes the use of it.

Type of column	Not allowed	Considered as a regular string	Considered as	Not considered
ID		X		
OCCASION (OCC)	X			
TIME	X			
DATE/DAT1/DAT2/ DAT3	X			
OBSERVATION (Y)	On a response line			On a dose line
OBSERVATION ID (YTYPE)		On a response line		On a dose line (not read)
CENSORED (CENS)			0	
LIMIT			-Inf if CENS =1 , +Inf if CENS = -1	
AMOUNT (AMT)	On a dose line			On a response line (not read)
ADMINISTRATION ID (ADM)	On a dose line			On a response line (not read)

Type of column	Not allowed	Considered as a regular string	Considered as	Not considered
STEADY STATE (SS)			0	
ADDITIONAL DOSE (ADDL)			0	
INTERDOSE INTERVAL (II)			0	
CONTINUOUS COVARIATE (COV)			Previously defined value of the COV (in the ID/OCC)	
CATEGORICAL COVARIATE (CAT)		X		
REGRESSOR			Interpolation	
EVENT ID (EVID)	X			
IGNORED OBSERVATION (MDV)	X			

2.2.4 Data formatting

The same dataset format is used in all applications of MonolixSuite, to allow for smooth transitions between applications. In this format, some rules have to be fulfilled, for example:

- Each line corresponds to one individual and one time point.
- Each line can include a single measurement (also called observation), or a dose amount (or both a measurement and a dose amount).
- Dose amount should be indicated for each individual dose in a column AMOUNT, even if it is identical for all.
- Headers are free but there can be only one header line.

If your dataset is not in this format, in most cases, it is possible to format it in a few steps in the **data formatting** tab, to incorporate the missing information.

In this case, the original dataset should be loaded in the “Format data” box, or directly in the “Data Formatting” tab, instead of the “Data” tab. In the data formatting module, you will be guided to build a dataset in the MonolixSuite format, starting from the loaded csv file. The resulting formatted dataset is then loaded in the Data tab as if you loaded an already-formatted dataset in “Data” directly. Then as for defining any dataset, you can tag columns, accept the dataset, and once accepted, units can be specified in the Data tab (only in PKanalix) and the Filters tab can be used to select only parts of this

dataset for analysis. Note that units and filters are neither information to be included in the data file, nor part of the data formatting process.

From the version 2024R1, it is possible to save and reapply data formatting steps on multiple projects, using data formatting presets (in both Monolix and PKanalix).

i The original datafile is NOT modified by PKanalix and Monolix. Formatting operations are saved in the projects and applied to the data when the project is loaded. The formatted dataset is not saved by default, but it can be exported by the user as a CSV file.

2.2.4.1 Data formatting workflow

When opening a new project, two Browse buttons appear. The first one, under “Data file”, can be used to load a dataset already in a MonolixSuite-standard format, while the second one, under “Format data”, allows to load a dataset to format in the Data formatting module.

After loading a dataset to format, data formatting operations can be specified in several subtabs: Initialization, Observations, Treatments and Additional columns.

- Initialization is mandatory and must be filled before using the other subtabs.
- Observations is required to enable the Treatments tab.

After Initialization has been validated by clicking on “Next”, a button “Preview” is available from any subtab to view in the Data tab the formatted dataset based on the formatting operations currently specified.

2.2.4.2 Dataset initialization

The first tab in Data formatting is named Initialization. This is where the user can select header lines or lines to exclude (in the blue area on the screenshot below) or tag columns (in the yellow area).

2.2.4.2.1 Selecting header lines or lines to exclude

These settings should contain line numbers for lines that should be either handled as column headers or that should be excluded.

- **Header lines:** one or several lines containing column header information. By default, the first line of the dataset is selected as header. If several lines are selected, they are merged by data formatting into a single line, concatenating the cells in each column.
- **Lines to exclude (optional):** lines that should be excluded from the formatted dataset by data formatting.

2.2.4.2.2 Tagging mandatory columns

Only the columns corresponding to the following tabs must be tagged in Initialization, while all the other columns should keep the default UNDEFINED tag:

- ID (mandatory): subject identifiers
- TIME (mandatory): the single time column

- SORT (optional): one or several columns containing SORT variables can be tagged as SORT. Occasions based on these columns will be created in the formatted dataset as described in Section "Creating occasions from a SORT column".
- START, END and VOLUME (mandatory in case of urine data): these column tags replace the TIME tag in case of urine data, if the urine collection time intervals are encoded in the dataset with two time columns for the start and end times of the intervals. In that case there should also be a column with the urine volume in each interval. See Section "Handling urine data" for more details.

2.2.4.2.3 Initialization example

- demo **CreateOcc_AdmlIdbyCategory.pkx** (can be imported to Monolix, the screenshot below focuses on the formatting initialization and excludes other elements present in the demo):

In this demo the first line of the dataset is excluded because it contains a description of the study. The second line contains column headers while the third line contains column units. Since the MonolixSuite-standard format allows only a single header line, lines 2 and 3 are merged together in the formatted dataset.

The screenshot illustrates the 'Data Formatting' process in PKanalix. The top panel shows the 'Data file' section with a file path and 'Lines settings' (Header lines: 2, Lines to exclude: 1). Below this is a table with columns: LINE NUMBER, ID, TIME_h, CONC_mg_L, FORM, AGE, WT, SEQ. An arrow points to the first row, labeled 'EXCLUDED LINE'. A bracket groups the first three rows, labeled 'CONCATENATED HEADERS'. A 'PREVIEW' button is shown below the table.

The bottom panel shows the 'Data information' section with 'Urine' selected and 'Plasma' unselected. The 'Units' section shows: TIME column x 1 = hour, CONC column x 1 = milligram / liter, AMT column x 1 = milligram / liter. Below this is a table with columns: TIME_h, CONC_mg_L, FORM, AGE, WT, SEQ, FORM_OCC, AMT, ADMINISTRATION ID, CENSURING. An arrow points to the 'FORM_OCC' column, which contains values 1 through 6.

2.2.4.3 Creating occasions from a SORT column

A SORT variable can be used to distinguish different sets of measurements (usually concentrations) within each subject, that should be analyzed separately by PKanalix or Monolix (for example: different formulations given to each individual at different periods of time, or multiple doses where concentration profiles are available to be analyzed following several doses).

These different sets of measurements must be distinguished as OCCASIONS (or periods of time), via the OCCASION column-type. However, a column tagged as OCCASION can only contain integers with occasion indexes. Thus, if a column with a SORT variable contains strings, its format must be adapted by Data formatting, in the following way:

- the user must tag the column as SORT in the Initialization subtab of Data formatting,
- the user validates the Initialization with “Next”, then clicks on “Preview” (after optionally defining other data formatting operations),
- the formatted data is shown in Data: the column tagged as SORT is automatically duplicated. The original column is automatically tagged as CATEGORICAL COVARIATE in Data, while the duplicated column, which has the same name appended with “_OCC”, is tagged as OCCASION. This column contains occasion indexes instead of strings.

Example:

- demo **CreateOcc_AdmlIdbyCategory.pkx** (can be imported to Monolix, the screenshot below focuses on the formatting of occasions and excludes other elements present in the demo):

The image below shows lines 25 to 29 from the dataset from the CreateOcc_AdmlIdbyCategory.pkx demo, where covariate columns have been removed to simplify the example. This dataset contains two sets of concentration measurements for each individual, corresponding to two different drug formulations administered on different periods. The sets of concentrations are distinguished with the FORM column, which contains “ref” and “test” categories (reference/test formulations). The column is tagged as SORT in Data formatting Initialization. After clicking on “Preview”, we can see in the Data tab that a new column named FORM_OCC has been created with occasion indexes for each individual: for subject 1, FORM_OCC=1 corresponds to the reference formulation because it appears first in the dataset, and FORM_OCC=2 corresponds to the test formulation because it appears in second in the dataset.

The left screenshot shows the 'Initialization' tab in the Data Formatting interface. It features a 'Data file' section with a 'BROWSE...' button, 'Lines settings' for header and exclusion, and a data table with columns: LINE NUMBER, ID, TIME, UNDEFINED, SORT, UNDEFINED, UNDEFINED, UNDEFINED. The 'PREVIEW' button is highlighted with a blue arrow pointing to the right screenshot.

The right screenshot shows the 'Observations' tab. It includes 'Data information' (Units, TIME, CONC, AMT columns), a 'Data file' section, and a detailed data table with columns: TIME, OBSERVATION, CATEGORICAL COVARIATE, CONTINUOUS COVARIATE, OCCASION, and AMOUNT. The 'PREVIEW' button is also visible.

2.2.4.4 Selecting an observation type

The second subtab in Data formatting allows to select one or several observation types. An observation type corresponds to a column of the dataset, that contains a type of measurements (usually drug concentrations, but it can also be PD measurements for example). Only columns that have not been tagged as ID, TIME or SORT are available as observation type.

This screenshot shows the 'Observations' subtab in the Data Formatting interface. A dropdown menu is open under the '+ ADD AN OBSERVATION TYPE' button, listing available columns: CONC_mg_L, AGE, WT, and SEQ.

This screenshot shows the 'Observations' subtab after selection. The 'CONC_mg_L' column is selected as the observation type. The interface includes a 'Censoring tags' section with a checkbox for 'Use all automatically detected tags' and a list of tags: BLQ and NA.

This action is optional and can have several purposes:

- If doses must be added by Data formatting (see Section "Adding doses in the data set"), specifying the column containing observations is mandatory, to avoid duplicating observations on new dose lines.
- If several observation types exist in different columns (for example: concentrations for different analytes, or measurements for PK and PD), they must be specified in Data formatting to be merged into a single observation column (see Section "Merging observations from several columns").
- In the MonolixSuite-standard format, the column containing observations can only contain numbers, and no string except "." for a missing observation. Thus if this column contains strings in the original dataset, it must be adapted by Data formatting, with two different cases:
 - if the strings are tags for censored observations (usually BLQ: below the limit of quantification), they can be specified in Data formatting to adapt the encoding of the censored observations (see Section "Specifying censoring from censoring tags"),
 - any other string in the column is automatically replaced by "." by Data formatting.

2.2.4.5 Merging observations from several columns

The MonolixSuite-standard format allows a single column containing all observations (such as concentrations or PD measurements). Thus if a dataset contains several observation types in different columns (for example: concentrations for different analytes, or measurements for PK and PD), they must be specified in Data formatting to be merged into a single observation column.

In that case, different settings can be chosen in the area marked in orange in the screenshot below:

- The user must choose between distinguishing observation types with observation ids or occasions.
- The user can unselect the option “Duplicate information from undefined columns”.

2.2.4.5.1 As observation ids

After selecting the “Distinguish observation types with: observation ids” option and clicking “Preview,” the columns for different observation types are combined into a single column called “OBS.” Each row of the dataset is duplicated for each observation type, with one value per observation type. Additionally, an “OBSID” column is created, with the name of the observation type corresponding to the measurement on each row.

This option is recommended for joint modeling of observation types, such as CA in PKanalix or population modeling in Monolix. It is important to note that NCA cannot be performed on two different observation ids simultaneously, so it is necessary to choose one observation id for the analysis.

Example:

- demo **merge_obsID_ParentMetabolite.pkx** (can be imported to Monolix, the screenshot below focuses on the formatting of observations and excludes other elements present in the demo):

This demo involves two columns that contain drug parent and metabolite concentrations. When merging both observation types with observation ids, a new column called OBSID is generated with categories labeled as “PARENT” and “METABOLITE.”

The image shows two screenshots of the PKanalix software interface during data formatting. The top screenshot shows the 'Data file' and 'Lines settings' sections. The 'Data file' section contains a file path and a 'BROWSE...' button. The 'Lines settings' section has 'Header lines' set to 1 and 'Lines to exclude' set to an empty field. Below this is a table with columns: LINE NUMBER, ID, TIME, PARENT, METABOLITE, DOSE, and SEX. The bottom screenshot shows the 'Data information' and 'Units' sections. The 'Data information' section has radio buttons for METABOLITE and PARENT, with 'Plasma' selected for both. The 'Units' section has dropdowns for TIME, CONC, and AMT. Below this is a table with columns: LINE NUMBER, ID, TIME, DOSE, SEX, AMT, OBS, and OBSID. A 'Settings' dialog box is shown on the right, with the 'Duplicate information from undefined columns' option checked. A blue arrow points from the 'PREVIEW' button in the settings dialog to the 'PREVIEW' button in the software interface.

2.2.4.5.2 As occasions

After selecting the “Distinguish observation types with: occasions” option and clicking “Preview,” the columns for different observation types are combined into a single column called “OBS.” Each row of the dataset is duplicated for each observation type, with one value per observation type. Additionally, two columns are created: an “OBSID_OCC” column with the index of the observation type corresponding to the measurement on each row, and an “OBSID_COV” with the name of the observation type.

This option is recommended for NCA, which can be run on different occasions for each individual. However, joint modeling of the observation types with CA or population modeling with Monolix cannot be performed with this option.

Example:

- demo **merge_occ_ParentMetabolite.pkx** (can be imported to Monolix):

This demo involves two columns that contain drug parent and metabolite concentrations. When merging both observation types with occasions, two new columns called OBSID_OCC and OBSID_COV are generated with OBSID_OCC=1 corresponding to OBSID_COV="PARENT" catand OBSID_OCC=2 corresponding to OBSID_COV="METABOLITE."

The screenshot displays the PKanalix software interface during data formatting. The top panel shows a table with columns for PARENT and METABOLITE concentrations. The bottom panel shows a table with columns for OBSID_OCC and OBSID_COV. A settings dialog is open on the right, showing options for distinguishing observation types and duplicating information from undefined columns.

Table 1: Data from the top panel (Initial state)

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	PARENT	METABOLITE	DOSE	SEX
1	1	1	13.4806	1.00136	1000	M
2	1	2	24.7161	2.66854	1000	M
3	1	4	34.6926	9.95048	1000	M
4	1	6	38.251	17.8245	1000	M
5	1	8	32.0533	20.99	1000	M

Table 2: Data from the bottom panel (After formatting)

ID	TIME	DOSE	SEX	AMT	OBSID_OCC	OBSID_COV
1	0	1000	M	1000	1	PARENT
1	0	1000	M	1000	2	METABOLITE
1	1	1000	M	-	1	PARENT
1	1	1000	M	-	2	METABOLITE
1	2	1000	M	-	1	PARENT
1	2	1000	M	-	2	METABOLITE

Settings Dialog:

- Distinguish observation types with:
 - observation IDs (recommended for joint CA and population modeling)
 - occasions (recommended for NCA)
- Duplicate information from undefined columns

2.2.4.5.3 Duplicate information from undefined columns

When merging two observation columns into a single column, all other columns will see their lines duplicated. The data formatting will know how to treat columns which have been tagged in the Initialization tab, but not the other columns (header "UNDEFINED") which are not used for data formatting. A checkbox enables to decide if the information from these columns should be duplicated on the new lines, or if "." should be used instead. The default option is to duplicate information, because in general, the undefined columns correspond to covariates with one value per individual, so this value is the same for the two lines that correspond to the same id.

The screenshot shows the PKanalix interface with the 'Data formatting' tab selected. The 'Lines settings' section is visible, showing 'Header lines: 1' and 'Lines to exclude:'. Below this is a table with columns: LINE NUMBER, ID, TIME, UNDEFINED, UNDEFINED, UNDEFINED, UNDEFINED. The data rows show values for ID, TIME, PARENT, METABOLITE, DOSE, and SEX. A red box highlights the DOSE and SEX columns, with the text 'DOSE AND SEX UNDEFINED' below it.

Below the table is a 'Settings' dialog box with the following options:

- Distinguish observation types with observation ids (recommended for joint CA and population modeling)
- occasions (recommended for IVC)
- Duplicate information from undefined columns

A 'PREVIEW' button is visible below the settings dialog.

The second screenshot shows the 'Data information' tab selected. The 'Units' section is visible, showing 'TIME column x 1' (hour), 'CONC column x 1' (milligram / milliliter), and 'AMT column x 1' (milligram). Below this is a table with columns: LINE NUMBER, ID, TIME, DOSE, SEX, AMT, OBS, OBSID. The data rows show values for ID, TIME, DOSE, SEX, AMT, OBS, and OBSID. A red box highlights the DOSE and SEX columns, with the text 'DOSE AND SEX VALUES DUPLICATED' below it.

It is rare that you need to uncheck this box. An example where you should not duplicate the information is if you already have a column Amount in the MonolixSuite format, so with a dose amount only at the dosing time, and "." everywhere else. If you do not want to specify amount again in data formatting, and simply want to merge observation columns as observation ids, you should not duplicate the lines of the Amount column which is undefined. Indeed, the dose amounts have been administered only once.

The screenshot shows the 'Data formatting' interface in MonolixSuite. The 'Data file' is 'C:/Users/FrancoMhaJevic/Documents/Documentation/Screenshots/formattedData.csv'. The 'Lines settings' show 'Header lines: 1' and 'Lines to exclude:'. The table below has columns: LINE NUMBER, ID, TIME, PARENT, METABOLITE, and AMT. The 'AMT' column is highlighted with an orange box and labeled 'AMT UNDEFINED'. A settings dialog box is open on the right, showing options for 'Distinguish observation types with:' (radio buttons for 'observation ids' and 'OCCASIONS'), and a checkbox for 'Duplicate information from undefined columns' which is checked. A blue arrow points from the 'AMT UNDEFINED' label to the 'Duplicate information from undefined columns' checkbox. Another blue arrow points from the 'PREVIEW' button in the dialog to the 'AMT' column in the table below.

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	PARENT	METABOLITE	AMT
1	ID	TIME	PARENT	METABOLITE	AMT
2	1	0	13.4806	.	1000
3	1	1	13.4806	1.00136	.
4	1	2	24.7161	2.66854	.
5	1	4	34.6926	9.95048	.
6	1	6	38.251	17.8245	.

AMT UNDEFINED

Settings

- Distinguish observation types with:
 - observation ids (recommended for joint CA and population modeling)
 - OCCASIONS (recommended for NCA)
- Duplicate information from undefined columns

PREVIEW

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	AMOUNT	OBSERVATION	OBSERVATION ID
2	1	0	1000	13.4806	PARENT
3	1	0	.	13.4806	METABOLITE
4	1	1	13.4806	1.00136	PARENT
5	1	1	1.00136	2.66854	METABOLITE
6	1	2	.	24.7161	PARENT
7	1	2	.	2.66854	METABOLITE
8	1	4	.	34.6926	PARENT
9	1	4	.	9.95048	MFTARCH ITF

DOSE LINE NOT DUPLICATED

2.2.4.6 Specifying censoring from censoring tags

In the MonolixSuite-standard format, censored observations are encoded with a 1 or -1 flag in a column tagged as CENSORING in the Data tab, while exact observations have a 0 flag in that column. In

addition, on rows for censored observations, the LOQ is indicated in the observation column: it is the LLOQ (lower limit of quantification) if CENSORING=1 or the ULOQ (upper limit of quantification) if CENSORING=-1. Finally, to specify a censoring interval, an additional column tagged as LIMIT in the Data tab must exist in the dataset, with the other censoring bound.

The Data Formatting module can take as input a dataset with censoring tags directly in the observation column, and adapt the dataset format as described above. After selecting one or several observation types in the Observations subtab (see Section "Selecting an observation type"), all strings found in the corresponding columns are displayed in the "Censoring tags" on the right of the observation types. If at least one string is found, the user can then define some censoring associated with an observation type and with one or several censoring tags with the button "Add censoring". Additionally, option "Use all automatically detected tags" exist and can be used when all censoring tags correspond to the same censoring type (this option is recommended for the usage with data formatting presets, if censoring tags vary between data sets in which the preset will be used). 3 types of censoring can be defined:

- **LLOQ**: this corresponds to left-censoring, where the censored observation is below a lower limit of quantification (LLOQ), that must be specified by the user. In that case Data Formatting replaces the censoring tags in the observation column by the LLOQ, and creates a new CENS column tagged as CENSORING in the Data tab, with 1 on rows that had censoring tags before formatting, and 0 on other rows.
- **ULOQ**: this corresponds to right-censoring, where the censored observation is above an upper limit of quantification (ULOQ), that must be specified by the user. Here Data Formatting replaces the censoring tags in the observation column by the ULOQ, and creates a new CENS column tagged as CENSORING in the Data tab, with -1 on rows that had censoring tags before formatting, and 0 on other rows.
- **Interval**: this is for interval-censoring, where the user must specify two bounds of a censoring interval, to which the censored observation belongs. Data Formatting replaces the censoring tags in the observation column by the upper bound of the interval, and creates two new columns: a CENS column tagged as CENSORING in the Data tab, with 1 on rows that had censoring tags before formatting, and 0 on other rows, and a LIMIT column with the lower bound of the censoring interval on rows that had censoring tags before formatting, and "." on other rows.

For each type of censoring, available options to define the limits are:

- **“Manual”**: limits are defined manually, by entering the limit values for all censored observations.
- **“By category”**: limits are defined manually for different categories read from the dataset.
- **“From data”**: limits are directly read from the dataset.

The options “by category” and “from data” are described in detail in Section “Reading censoring limits or dosing information from the data set”.

Example:

- demo **DoseAndLOQ_manual.ppx/DoseAndLOQ_manual.mlxtran** (the screenshot below focuses on the formatting of censored observations and excludes other elements present in the demo):

In this demo there are two censoring tags in the CONC column: BLQ1 (from Study 1) and BLQ2 (from Study 2), that correspond to different LLOQs. An interval censoring is defined for each censoring tag, with manual limits, where LLOQ=0.06 for BLQ1 and LLOQ=0.1 for BLQ2, and the lower limit of the censoring interval being 0 in both cases.

The screenshot illustrates the 'Data Formatting' module in PKanalix. It is divided into two main sections: 'Data file' and 'Data information'.

Data file section: Shows a table with columns: LINE NUMBER, ID, TIME_h, CONC_mg_L, AGE, WT, and STUDY. The table contains 8 rows of data. Two rows (218 and 219) have their 'CONC_mg_L' values highlighted with orange and purple boxes, respectively.

Data information section: Shows a table with columns: ID, TIME_h, OBSERVATION, CONTINUOUS COVARIATE, CATEGORICAL COVARIATE, AMOUNT, CENSORING, and LIMIT. The table contains 18 rows of data. Two rows (9 and 10) have their 'CONC_mg_L' and 'LIMIT' values highlighted with orange and purple boxes, respectively.

Interval censoring dialog boxes: Two dialog boxes are shown on the right, each with 'Upper limit' and 'Lower limit' fields. The top dialog box has 'Upper limit' set to 0.05 and 'Lower limit' set to 0. The bottom dialog box has 'Upper limit' set to 0.1 and 'Lower limit' set to 0. Both dialog boxes have 'By category' set to 'No category'. A 'PREVIEW' button is located below the dialog boxes.

2.2.4.7 Adding doses in the dataset

Datasets in MonolixSuite-standard format should contain all information on doses, as dose lines. An AMOUNT column records the amount of the administered doses on dose-lines, with "." on response-lines. In case of infusion, an INFUSION DURATION or INFUSION RATE column records the infusion duration or rate. If there are several types of administration, an ADMINISTRATION ID column can distinguish the different types of doses with integers.

If doses are missing from a dataset, the Data Formatting module can be used to add dose lines and dose-related columns: after initializing the dataset, the user can specify one or several treatments in the Treatments subtab. The following operations are then performed by Data Formatting:

- a new dose line is inserted in the dataset for each defined dose, with the dataset sorted by subject and times. On such a dose line, the values from the next line are duplicated for all columns, except for the observation column in which "." is used for the dose line.
- A new column AMT is created with "." on all lines except on dose lines, on which dose amounts are used. The AMT column is automatically tagged as AMOUNT in the Data tab.
- If administration ids have been defined in the treatment, an ADMID column is created, with "." on all lines except on dose lines, on which administration ids are used. The ADMID column is automatically tagged as ADMINISTRATION ID in the Data tab.
- If an infusion duration or rate has been defined, a new INFDUR (for infusion duration) or INFRATE (for infusion rate) is created, with "." on all lines except on dose lines. The INFDUR column is automatically tagged as INFUSION DURATION in the Data tab, and the INFRATE column is automatically tagged as INFUSION RATE.

Initialization
Observations
Treatments
Additional columns
RESTORE DATA
PREVIEW

+ ADD TREATMENT

Treatment 1 🗑️

REGULAR

MANUAL

EXTERNAL

Apply to all ids

Start time	Interdose interval	Number of doses
0	24	4

Repeat cycle

Amount MANUAL FROM DATA 100

By category No category

Infusion MANUAL FROM DATA 2

By category No category

Administration id MANUAL FROM DATA 1

By category No category

Common settings

Dose intervals as occasions

Duplicate observations at dose time into each occasion

Infusion type

duration rate

79

For each treatment, the dosing schedule can be defined as:

- **regular**: for regularly spaced dosing times, defined with the start time, inter-dose interval, and number of doses. A “repeat cycle” option allows to repeat the regular dosing schedule to generate a more complex regimen.
- **manual**: a vector of one or several dosing times, each defined manually. A “repeat cycle” option allows to repeat the manual dosing schedule to generate a more complex regimen.
- **external**: an external text file with columns id (optional), occasions (optional), time (mandatory), amount (mandatory), admid (administration id, optional), tinf or rate (optional), that allows to define individual doses.

Starting from the 2024R1 version, different dosing schedules can be defined for different individuals, based on information from other columns, which can be useful in cases when different cohorts received different dosing regimens, or when working with data pooled from multiple studies. To define a treatment just for a specific cohort or study, the dropdown on the top of the treatment section can be used:

Start time	Interdose interval	Number of doses
0	24	4

While dose amounts, administration ids and infusion durations or rates are defined in the external file for external treatments, available options to define them for treatments of type “manual” or “regular” are:

- **“Manual”**: this applies the same amount (or administration id or infusion duration or rate) to all doses.
- **“By category”**: dose amounts (or administration id or infusion duration or rate) are defined manually for different categories read from the dataset.
- **“From data”**: dose amounts (or administration id or infusion duration or rate) are directly read from the dataset.

The options “by category” and “from data” are described in detail in Section “Reading censoring limits or dosing information from the dataset”.

There is a “common settings” panel on the right:

- **dose intervals as occasions:** this creates a column to distinguish the dose intervals as different occasions (see Section "Creating occasions from dosing intervals").
- **infusion type:** If several treatments correspond to infusion administration, they need to share the same type of encoding for infusion information: as infusion duration or as infusion rate.

Example:

- demo **DoseAndLOQ_manual.ppx/DoseAndLOQ_manual.mlxtran** (the screenshot below focuses on the formatting of doses and excludes other elements present in the demo):

In this demo, doses are initially not included in the dataset to format. A single dose at time 0 with an amount of 600 is added for each individual by Data Formatting. This creates a new AMT column in the formatted dataset, tagged as AMOUNT.

The screenshot shows the PKanalix Data Formatting interface. The top panel displays the 'Data file' and 'Lines settings' sections. The 'Data file' section shows the path to the data file. The 'Lines settings' section shows the 'Header lines' and 'Lines to exclude' options. The main table shows the data for individual 1, with columns for LINE NUMBER, ID, TIME, CONC, AGE, WT, and STUDY. The 'AMT' column is highlighted in orange, and a '600' value is entered in the first row (line 2) under the 'AMT' column. The bottom panel shows the 'Data information' and 'Units' sections. The 'Data information' section shows the 'Line' and 'Plasma' options. The 'Units' section shows the 'TIME' column set to 'hour', 'CONC' column set to 'mg/L', and 'AMT' column set to 'mg/L'. The 'AMT' column is highlighted in orange, and a '600' value is entered in the first row (line 2) under the 'AMT' column. A 'PREVIEW' button is visible at the bottom right of the interface.

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME_h	CONC_mg_L	AGE	WT	STUDY	AMT
1	1	0	-	25	66	1	-
2	1	0	-	25	66	1	600
3	1	1	-	25	66	1	-
4	1	2	0.34	25	66	1	-
5	1	3	0.95	25	66	1	-
6	1	4	1.44	25	66	1	-
7	1	4	1.44	25	66	1	-

2.2.4.8 Reading censoring limits or dosing information from the dataset

When defining censoring limits for observations (see Section "Specifying censoring from censoring tags") or dose amounts, administration ids, infusion duration or rate for treatments (see Section "Adding doses in the dataset"), two options allow to define different values for different rows, based on information already present in the dataset: "by category" and "from data".

2.2.4.8.1 By category

It is possible to define manually different censoring limits, dose amounts, administration ids, infusion durations, or rates for different categories within a dataset's column. After selecting this column in the "By category" drop-down menu, the different modalities in the column are displayed and a value must be manually assigned each modality.

The left screenshot shows the configuration for "Observation type based on CONC_mg_L". The "Upper limit" is set to "MANUAL" and "FROM DATA". A table is displayed with the following data:

By category	Modalities	Upper limit
STUDY	SD_400mg	0.01
	SD_500mg	0.1
	SD_600mg	0.1

The right screenshot shows the configuration for "Treatment 1". The "Amount" is set to "MANUAL" and "FROM DATA". A table is displayed with the following data:

By category	Modalities	AMOUNT
STUDY	SD_400mg	400
	SD_500mg	500
	SD_600mg	600

- For censoring limits, the censoring limit used to replace each censoring tag depends on the modality on the same row.
- For doses, the value chosen for the newly created column (AMT for amount, ADMID for administration id, INFDUR for infusion duration, INFRATE for infusion rate) on each new dose line depends on the modality on the first row found in the dataset for the same individual and the same time as the dose, or the next time if there is no line in the initial dataset at that time, or the previous time if no time is found after the dose.

Example:

- demo **DoseAndLOQ_byCategory.pkx/DoseAndLOQ_byCategory.mlxtran** (the screenshot below focuses on the formatting of doses and excludes other elements present in the demo):

In this demo there are three studies distinguished in the STUDY column with the categories "SD_400mg", "SD_500mg" and "SD_600mg". In Data Formatting, a single dose is manually defined at time 0 for all individuals, with different amounts depending the STUDY category. In addition, censoring interval is defined for the censoring tags BLQ, with an upper limit of the censoring interval (lower limit of quantification) that also depends on the STUDY category. Three new columns – AMT for dose amounts, CENS for censoring tags (0 or 1), and LIMIT for the lower limit of the censoring intervals – are created by Data Formatting. A new dose line is then inserted at time 0 for each individual.

The image illustrates the process of importing data from a dataset into PKanalix. It shows three main stages:

- Data Import:** The top screenshot shows the 'Data file' section where a dataset is loaded. The 'Lines settings' are configured, and a table of data lines is displayed. The 'STUDY' column contains values like 'SD_400mg' and 'SD_500mg', which are highlighted with orange and purple boxes respectively.
- Data Information and Units:** The middle screenshot shows the 'Data information' section where units are defined for columns like 'CONC', 'AMT', and 'CENS'. The 'Display' section shows that 'ignored columns' are selected.
- Configuration and Preview:** The right side shows the 'Interval censoring' and 'Treatment 1' settings. The 'Interval censoring' panel shows 'Upper limit' and 'Lower limit' settings for different studies. The 'Treatment 1' panel shows 'Amount' settings for different studies. A 'PREVIEW' button is visible, which is linked by a blue arrow to the 'AMT' column in the bottom screenshot.

The bottom screenshot shows the resulting data table after import. The 'AMT' column now contains numerical values (e.g., 0.01, 400, 500) extracted from the original data, corresponding to the highlighted rows in the top screenshot.

2.2.4.8.2 From data

The option "From data" is used to directly read censoring limits, dose amounts, administration ids, infusion durations, or rates from a dataset's column. The column must contain either numbers or numbers inside strings. In that case, the first number found in the string is extracted (including decimals with .).

- For censoring limits, the censoring limit used to replace each censoring tag is read from the selected column on the same row.
- For doses, the value chosen for the newly created column (AMT for amount, ADMID for administration id, INF DUR for infusion duration, INFRATE for infusion rate) on each new dose line is read from the selected column on the first row found in the dataset for the same individual and the same time as the dose, or the next time if there is no line in the initial dataset at that time, or the previous time if no time is found after the dose.

Example:

- demo **DoseAndLOQ_fromData.ppx/DoseAndLOQ_fromData.mlxtran** (the screenshot below focuses on the formatting of doses and censoring and excludes other elements present in the demo):

In this demo there are three studies distinguished in the STUDY column with the categories "SD_400mg", "SD_500mg" and "SD_600mg". In Data Formatting, a single dose is manually defined at time 0 for all individuals, with the amount read the STUDY column. In addition, censoring interval is defined for the censoring tags BLQ, with an upper limit of the censoring interval (lower limit of quantification) read from the LLOQ_mg_L column. Three new columns – AMT for dose amounts, CENS for censoring tags (0 or 1), and LIMIT for the lower limit of the censoring intervals – are created by Data Formatting. A new dose line is then inserted at time 0 for each individual, with amount 400, 500 or 600 for studies SD_400mg, SD_500mg and SD_600mg respectively.

The screenshot displays the PKanalix Data Formatting interface. The top section shows the 'Data file' and 'Lines settings' tabs. The main area contains a table of raw data with columns: LINE NUMBER, ID, TIME_h, CONC_mg_L, AGE, WT, STUDY, and LLOQ_mg_L. The 'STUDY' column contains values like 'SD_400mg' and 'SD_500mg'. A 'PREVIEW' button is visible on the right side of the interface.

Below the raw data table, the 'Interval censoring' settings are shown. The 'Upper limit' is set to 'LLOQ_mg_L' and 'BLQ'. The 'Lower limit' is set to '0'. The 'By category' is set to 'No category'.

The bottom section shows the 'Display' settings, including 'Amount' (MANUAL, FROM DATA, STUDY) and 'Censoring' (MANUAL, FROM DATA, STUDY). The 'PREVIEW' button is highlighted, indicating the next step in the process.

The bottom screenshot shows the formatted data table with columns: LINE NUMBER, ID, TIME_h, CONC_mg_L, AGE, WT, STUDY, LLOQ_mg_L, AMT, and CENS. The 'AMT' column contains values like '400' and '500'. The 'CENS' column contains values like '1' and '0'. The 'PREVIEW' button is highlighted, indicating the next step in the process.

2.2.4.9 Creating occasions from dosing intervals

The option “Dose intervals as occasions” in the Treatments subtab of Data Formatting allows to create an occasion column to distinguish dose intervals. This is useful if the sets of measurements following different doses should be analyzed independently for a same individual. From the 2024 version on, an additional option “Duplicate observations at dose times into each occasion” is available. This option allows to duplicate the observations which are at exactly the same time as dose, such that they appear both as last point of the previous occasion and first point of the next occasion.

Example:

- demo **doseIntervals_as_Occ.mlxtran** (Monolix demo, can be imported into PKanalix):

This demo has an initial dataset in Monolix-standard format, with multiple doses encoded as dose lines with dose amounts in the AMT column. When using this dataset directly into Monolix or PKanalix, a single analysis is done on each individual concentration profile considering all doses, which means that NCA would be done on the concentrations after the last dose only, and modeling (CA in PKanalix or population modeling in Monolix) would be estimated with a single set of parameter values for each individual. If instead we want to run separate analyses on the sets of concentrations following each dose, we need to distinguish them as occasions with a new column added with the Data Formatting module. To this end, we define the same treatment as in the initial dataset with Data Formatting (here as regular multiple doses) with the option “Dose intervals as occasions” selected. After clicking Preview, Data Formatting adds two new columns: an AMT1 column with the new doses, to be tagged as AMOUNT instead of the AMT column that will now be ignored, and a DOSE_OCC column to be tagged as OCCASION.

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	CONC	AMT
10	1	12	-	40
11	1	23	3.54146	-
12	1	24	-	40
13	1	35	4.33902	-
14	1	36	-	40
15	1	47	4.9619	-
16	1	48	-	40

**INITIAL DATA SET
(NO OCCASIONS)**

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	OBSERVATION	IGNORE	OCCASION	AMOUNT
11	1	12			2	40
12	1	12			2	40
13	1	23	3.54146		2	
14	1	24			3	40
15	1	24			3	40

**FORMATTED DATA SET
(WITH OCCASIONS)**

Example:

- demo **CreateOcc_duplicateObs.pkx** (can be imported into Monolix):

Data Tasks Plots

Data formatting
 Data
 Filters
 Covariates statistics

Data file

From data formatting

Data information

Urine Plasma

Units

TIME column × 1 = hour
 CONC column × 1 = milligram / milliliter
 AMT column × 1 = milligram

LINE NUMBER	Animal	Dose_mg_kg	Time_h	Concentration_ng_mL	DOSE_OCC	AMT
7	1001	2	4	29	1	
	1001#2	2				
8	1001	2	8		2	2
9	1001	2	8	5.35	2	
10	1001	2	8.5	94.1	2	
11	1001	2	9	75.1	2	
12	1001	2	10	43.7	2	

Records per page: 10 25 50 100 364
 << Page 1 of 8 >>
 Showing 1 to 50 of 364 entries - 28 Individuals

Duplicate observations at dose time into each occasion

Data Tasks Plots

Data formatting
 Data
 Filters
 Covariates statistics

Data file

From data formatting

Data information

Urine Plasma

Units

TIME column × 1 = hour
 CONC column × 1 = milligram / milliliter
 AMT column × 1 = milligram

LINE NUMBER	Animal	Dose_mg_kg	Time_h	Concentration_ng_mL	DOSE_OCC	AMT
7	1001	2	4	29	1	
8	1001	2	8	5.35	1	
	1001#2	2				
9	1001	2	8		2	2
10	1001	2	8	5.35	2	
11	1001	2	8.5	94.1	2	
12	1001	2	9	75.1	2	

Records per page: 10 25 50 100 392
 << Page 1 of 8 >>
 Showing 1 to 50 of 392 entries - 28 Individuals

2.2.4.10 Handling urine data

In PKanalix-standard format, the start and end times of urine collection intervals must be recorded in a single column, tagged as TIME column-type, where the end time of an interval automatically acts as start time for the next interval. If a dataset contains start and end times in two different columns, they can be merged into a single column by Data Formatting. This is done automatically by tagging these two columns as START and END in the Initialization subtab of Data Formatting (see Section "Data set initialization"). In addition the column containing urine collection volume must be tagged as VOLUME.

Example:

- demo **Urine_LOQinObs.pkx** (can be imported into Monolix):

Home Data Tasks Plots

Data formatting Initialization Observations Treatments Additional columns RESTORE DATA

Data file

C:/Users/FrancoMihaljevic/ixor/pkanalix/pkanalix2024R1/demos/0_data_format...

BROWSE...

Lines settings

Header lines:

Lines to exclude:

LINE NUMBER	ID	START	END	VOLUME	UNDEFINED
LINE NUMBER	ID	START_TIME	END_TIME	VOLUME	CONC
1	ID	START TIME	END TIME	VOLUME	CONC
2	1	0	4	410	112
3	1	4	8	280	92
4	1	8	12	390	41
5	1	12	18	450	29
6	1	18	24	415	12
7	1	24	48	1730	2.6

Records per page: 10 25 29
Showing 1 to 29 of 29 entries

PREVIEW

Home Data Tasks Plots

Data formatting Data information Units

Data file

BROWSE...

From data formatting

Data information

Urine Plasma

Regressor for urine volume

VOLUME

Units

TIME column × 1 = hour

CONC column × 1 = milligram

AMT column × 1 = milligram

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	REGRESSOR	OBSERVATION	AMOUNT	INFUSION DURATION	CENSORING
LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	VOLUME	CONC	AMT	INFDUR	CENS
1	1						
2	1	0	0		146	2	
3	1	0	0				
4	1	4	410	112			notCensored
5	1	8	280	92			notCensored
6	1	12	390	41			notCensored
7	1	18	450	29			notCensored

Records per page: 10 25 36
Showing 1 to 36 of 36 entries - 4 individuals

2.2.4.11 Adding new columns from an external file

The last subtab is used to insert additional columns in the dataset from a separate file. The external file must contain a table with a column named ID or id with the same subject identifiers as in the dataset to format, and other columns with a header name and individual values (numbers or strings). There can be only one value per individual, which means that the additional columns inserted in the formatted dataset can contain only a constant value within each individual, and not time-varying values.

Examples of additional columns that can be added with this option are:

- individual parameters estimated in a previous analysis, to be read as regressors to avoid estimating them. **Time-varying regressors are not handled.**
- new covariates.

If occasions are defined in the formatted dataset, it is possible to have an occasion column in the external file and values defined per subject-occasion.

Example:

- demo **warfarin_PKPDseq_project.mlxtran** (can be imported into PKanalix):

This demo has an initial PKPD dataset in Monolix-standard format. The option “Additional columns” is used to add the PK parameters estimated on the PK part of the data in another Monolix project.

The screenshot illustrates the process of exporting a formatted dataset from PKanalix. It is divided into two main sections:

Top Section: Data Formatting

- File: `warfarinPK_regressors.txt`
- Buttons: `Tag_mode`, `ka_mode`, `V_mode`, `Cl_mode`, `BROWSE`
- Preview Table:

id	Tag_mode	ka_mode	V_mode	Cl_mode
1	0.881068	1.27612	7.68831	0.111825
2	0.739306	0.906915	8.35584	0.128526
3	0.909005	0.955194	8.46397	0.112645
4	0.893931	1.42947	5.08504	0.072557
5	0.851363	1.36498	11.5598	0.176061

Bottom Section: Main Data Table

The main data table includes columns for `LINE NUMBER`, `id`, `time`, `amt`, `dv`, `dvid`, `wt`, `sex`, `age`, and four `REGRESSOR` columns: `Tag_mode`, `ka_mode`, `V_mode`, and `Cl_mode`. The regressor values are highlighted with a red box in the original image.

LINE NUMBER	id	time	amt	dv	dvid	wt	sex	age	Tag_mode	ka_mode	V_mode	Cl_mode
1	1	0	100			66.7	1	50	0.881068	1.27612	7.68831	0.111825
2	1	0		98	2	66.7	1	50	0.881068	1.27612	7.68831	0.111825
3	1	24		9.2	1	66.7	1	50	0.881068	1.27612	7.68831	0.111825
4	1	24		49	2	66.7	1	50	0.881068	1.27612	7.68831	0.111825
5	1	36		8.5	1	66.7	1	50	0.881068	1.27612	7.68831	0.111825
6	1	36		32	2	66.7	1	50	0.881068	1.27612	7.68831	0.111825
7	1	48		6.4	1	66.7	1	50	0.881068	1.27612	7.68831	0.111825

2.2.4.12 Exporting the formatted dataset

Once data formatting is done and the new dataset is accepted, the project can be saved and it is possible to export the formatted dataset as a csv file from the main menu `Export > Export formatted data`.

Note that if you did some data formatting directly in Monolix (instead of PKanalix), the possibility to save the project and export the formatted data is enabled only after loading a model in the structural model tab.

2.2.4.13 Data formatting presets

Starting from the 2024R1 version, if users need to perform the same or similar data formatting steps with each new project, a data formatting preset can be created and applied for new projects.

A typical workflow for using data formatting presets is as follows:

1. Data formatting steps are performed on a specific project.
2. Steps are saved in a data formatting preset.
3. Preset is reapplied on multiple new projects (manually or automatically).

2.2.4.13.1 Creating a data formatting preset

After data formatting steps are done on a project, a preset can be created by clicking on the New button in the bottom left corner of the interface, while in the Data formatting tab:

The screenshot shows the PKanalix software interface. At the top, there are navigation tabs: 'Data', 'Tasks', and 'Plots'. Below these, there are sub-tabs: 'Data formatting', 'Initialization', 'Observations', 'Treatments', and 'Additional columns'. The 'Data' sub-tab is active, showing a 'Data file' section with a file path and a 'BROWSE...' button. To the right, there are 'Lines settings' with 'Header lines' (1 x 2 x) and 'Lines to exclude' (empty) fields. Below this is a data table with columns: LINE NUMBER, ID, TIME_h, CONC_mg_L, AGE, WT, STUDY, and LLOQ_mg_L. The table contains 8 rows of data. At the bottom left, there is a 'Presets' section with a 'NEW +' button highlighted by a red box and an 'APPLY' button. At the bottom right, there is a pagination control showing 'Page 1 of 18' and 'Showing 1 to 50 of 866 entries'.

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME_h	CONC_mg_L	AGE	WT	STUDY	LLOQ_mg_L
1	ID	TIME	CONC	AGE	WT	STUDY	LLOQ
2		h	mg/L				mg/L
3	1	0	BLQ	26	78	SD_400mg	0.01
4	1	1	BLQ	26	78	SD_400mg	0.01
5	1	2	0.0638908	26	78	SD_400mg	0.01
6	1	3	0.213188	26	78	SD_400mg	0.01
7	1	4	0.35487	26	78	SD_400mg	0.01
8	1	5	0.46173	26	78	SD_400mg	0.01

Clicking on this button will open a pop-up window with a form that contains four parts:

New custom preset from current data formatting

Name:

INITIALIZATION
 OBSERVATIONS
 TREATMENTS

Description:
Add description

Use this preset as default to format data in all MonolixSuite apps

CANCEL

CREATE

1. **Name:** contains a name of the preset, this information will be used to distinguish between presets when applying them.
2. **Configuration:** contains three checkboxes (initialization, observations, treatments). Users can choose which steps of data formatting will be saved in the preset. If option “External” was used in creating treatments, the external file paths will not be saved in the preset.
3. **Description:** a custom description can be added.
4. **Use this preset as default to format data in all MonolixSuite apps:** if ticked, the preset will be automatically applied every time a data set is loaded for data formatting in PKanalix and Monolix.

After saving the preset by clicking on Create, the description will be updated with the summary of all the steps performed in data formatting.

Important to note is that if a user wants to save censoring information in the data formatting preset, and the censored tags change between projects (e.g., censoring tag <LOQ=0.1> with varying numbers is used in different projects), the option “Use all automatically detected tags” should be used in the Observations tab. This way, no specific censoring tags will be saved in the preset, but they will be automatically detected and applied each time a preset is applied.

Censoring tags
↻

Use all automatically detected tags
(recommended for creating presets in case of dataset dependent censoring tags)

BLQ ×
×

2.2.4.13.2 Applying a preset

A preset can be applied manually using the Apply button in the bottom left corner of the data formatting tab. Clicking on the Apply button will open a dropdown selection of all saved presets and the desired preset can be chosen.

The Apply button is enabled only after the initialization step is performed (ID and TIME columns are selected and the button Next was clicked). This allows PKanalix/Monolix to fall back to the initialized state, if the initialization step from a preset fails (e.g., if ID and TIME column header saved in the presets do not exist in the new data set).

After applying a preset, all data formatting steps saved in the preset will try to be applied. If it is not possible to apply certain steps (e.g., some censoring tags or column headers saved in a preset do not exist), the error message will appear.

Manage data formatting presets
×

Presets list

Custom presets

- DF_preset
- Plasma
- Plasma_infusion
- Urine

+ NEW
DELETE
IMPORT
EXPORT

Preset information

DF_preset ✎

Data formatting: OBSERVATIONS TREATMENTS

Description:

Here is a sample user-defined description.

OBSERVATIONS:

tags = BLQ

CONC_mg_L

interval = (tags = BLQ, loq = (fromData = LLOQ_mg_L, limit = (value = 0)))

TREATMENT:

Use this preset as default to format data in all MonolixSuite apps

CLOSE

2.2.4.13.3 Managing presets

Presets can be created, deleted, edited, imported and exported by clicking on Settings > Manage Presets > Data Formatting.

The pop-window allows users to:

1. **Create presets:** clicking on the button New has the same behavior as clicking on the button New in the Data formatting tab (described in the section "Creating a data formatting preset").
2. **Delete presets:** clicking on the button Delete will permanently delete a preset. Clicking on this button will not ask for confirmation.
3. **Edit presets:** by clicking on a preset in the left panel, the preset information will appear in the right panel. Name and preset description of the presets can then be updated, and a preset can be selected to automatically format data in PKanalix and Monolix.
4. **Export presets:** a selected preset can be exported as a lixpst file which can be shared between users and imported using the Import button.
5. **Import presets:** a user can import a preset from a lixpst file exported from another computer.

Additionally, an option to pin presets (always show them on top) can be used by clicking on the icon to facilitate the usage of presets when a user has a lot of them.

2.3 Tagging a data set

2.3.1 Column tagging

After loading a formatted data set directly, or previewing a data set that has gone through data formatting, users need to assign meaning to different columns of the formatted data set.

This is done in the Data tab by clicking on the dropdown menus above each of the column headers:

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	AMOUNT	OBSERVATION	IGNORE	CATEGORICAL COVARIATE
	ID	TIME	AMT	CONC	BLQ	STUDY
2	1	0	50	.	.	101
3	1	0.5	.	3.05	0	101
4	1	2	.	5.92	0	101
5	1	4	.	4.7	0	101
6	1	6	.	4.14	0	101
7	1	8	.	4.65	0	101
8	1	12	.	2.64	0	101
9	1	18	.	2	0	101
10	1	24	.	1.8	1	101
11	1	30	.	1.8	1	101
12	2	0	50	.	.	101
13	2	0.5	.	6.24	0	101
14	2	2	.	7.08	0	101

Records per page: 10 25 50 100 500 1000
 << < Page 1 of 20 > >>
 Showing 1 to 50 of 1,000 entries - 100 individuals

CANCEL **ACCEPT**

After tagging the columns and accepting the data set, the interpreted data set is shown. The interpreted data set may be different from original data set, as it shows a data set after data formatting and filtering steps were applied. It also includes doses added through the ADDL column and steady state settings, additional covariates, interpolated values of regressors, censoring information as strings, ...

The information about the meaning of each of the dropdown option can be found on these pages:

- [Columns used to identify subjects-occasions](#)
- [Columns used to define covariates](#)
- [Columns used to define observations](#)
- [Columns used to define controls and events](#)
- [Columns used to define regressors \(urine volume\)](#)
- [Columns used to define doses](#)
- [Columns used to define time](#)

2.3.2 Automatic column tagging

MonolixSuite applications automatically suggest column types based on the headers in the data, which can be customized in the preferences. Clicking on Settings>Preferences, displays the following window where mapped headers can be added or removed.

In the Data section, you can add or remove preferences for each column.

- To remove a mapping, double-click on the preference you would like to remove. A confirmation window will appear.

- To add a mapping, click on the header type you want to use, add a column name in the 'header name' field and click on "ADD HEADER" as shown here.

Note that the header mapping preferences are shared between Monolix and PKanalix.

Starting with version 2024, the preferences can be updated with the columns tagged in the current project by clicking on the icon in the top left corner of the data table:

LINE NUMBER ↕	ID ↕
2	1
3	1

This will open a window with the option to choose which of the tagged headers to add to preferences:

Send header types to preferences

 Hide up to date aliases

- id** : Already defined in *ID*
- time** : Already defined in *TIME*
- y** : Already defined in *OBSERVATION*
- z** : Add to *REGRESSOR*

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6CTyrut93v8>

2.4 Handling urine data

If urine data is present in the data set, the column with urine volume needs to be tagged as a REGRESSOR. After accepting the data set, the radio buttons are displayed in the Data tab to select if the data is plasma concentration or urine concentration (purple). If the urine option is selected, a dropdown is displayed in which a user can choose which regressor column represents urine volume (orange).

Data information

Urine Plasma

Regressor for urine volume
 VOL ▼

Regressors settings
 Last carried forward Linear interpolation

i Specifying if the data is urine or plasma will have an impact on NCA calculations - different parameters are calculated in two cases. This information will however not impact CA.

2.5 Defining units

PKanalix **displays units of the NCA and CA parameters** calculated automatically from information provided by a user about units of measurements in a dataset. Units are shown in the results tables, on plots and are added to the saved files.

It allows for **scaling** values of a dataset **to represent outputs in preferred units**, which facilitates the interpretation of the results. Scaling is done in the PKanalix data manager, and does not change the original data file.

The screenshot shows the PKanalix software interface. The 'Units' configuration panel is highlighted with a purple box. It contains the following settings:

- TIME column × 1: hour
- CONC column × 1: milligram / liter
- AMT column × 1: milligram

Below the configuration panel, a data table is displayed with the following columns: LINE NUMBER, ID, TIME_h, PERIOD, AMT_mg, ADM, Conc_mg_L, CENS, LIMIT, FORM, AGE, and WT. The table contains 8 rows of data.

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME_h	PERIOD	AMT_mg	ADM	Conc_mg_L	CENS	LIMIT	FORM	AGE	WT
1	1	0	1	600	1				ref	25	66
2	1	0	1			0.06	intervalCensored	0	ref	25	66
3	1	1	1			0.06	intervalCensored	0	ref	25	66
4	1	2	1			0.34	notCensored		ref	25	66
5	1	3	1			0.98	notCensored		ref	25	66
6	1	4	1			1.44	notCensored		ref	25	66
7	1	5	1			1.81	notCensored		ref	25	66

2.5.1 Units definition

Units of the NCA and CA parameters are considered as combinations of units of: time, amount and volume. For instance, unit of AUC is [concentration unit * time unit] = [amount unit / volume unit * time unit]. These quantities correspond to columns in a typical PK dataset: time of measurements, observed concentration, dose amount (and volume of collected urine when relevant).

The “Units” block allows to define the preferred units for the output NCA parameters (purple frame below), which are related to the units of the data set columns (green frame below) via scaling factors (in the middle). The output units are displayed in results and plots after running the NCA and CA tasks.

In PKanalix version 2023R1, the amount can now also be specified in mass of the administered dose per body mass or body surface area. This eliminates the need to edit NCA or CA parameters by post-processing unit conversion.

Concentration is a quantity defined as “amount per volume”. It has two separate units, which are linked (and equal) to AMT and VOLUME respectively. Changing the amount unit of CONC will automatically update the amount unit of AMT. This constraint allows to apply simplifications to the output parameters units, for instance have Cmax_D as [mL] and not [mg/mL/mg].

Units without data conversion: Output units correspond to units of the input data.

In other words, desired units of the NCA and CA parameters correspond to units of measurements in the dataset. In this case, select from the drop-down menus units of the input data and keep the default scaling factor (equal to one). All calculations are performed using values in the original dataset and selected units are displayed in the results tables and on plots.

Units conversion: output units are different from the units of the input data.

NCA and CA parameters can be calculated and displayed in any units, not necessarily the same as used in the dataset. The scaling factors (by default equal to 1) multiply the corresponding columns in a dataset and transform them to a dataset in new units. PKanalix shows data with new, scaled values after having clicked on the “accept” button. **This conversion occurs only internally and the original dataset file remains unchanged.** So, in this case, select desired output units from the list and, knowing units of the input data, scale the original values to the new units.

Example 1: input time units in [hours] and desired output units in [days]

For instance, let measurement times in a dataset be in hours. To obtain the outputs in days, set the output time unit as “days” and the scaling factor to 1/24, as shown below. It reads as follows:

(values of time in **hours** from the dataset) * (1/24) = time in **days**.

After accepting the scaling, a dataset shown in the Data tab is converted internally to a new data set. It contains original values multiplied by scaling factors. Then, all computations in the NCA and CA tasks are performed using new values, so that the results correspond to selected units.

Example 2: input data set concentration units in [ng/mL] and amount in [mg]

	ID	TIME	AMOUNT	OBSERVATION
			mg	ng/mL = ug/L
LINE NUMBER	ID	time	Amount	DV
2	271	0	100	.
3	271	0	.	2950
4	271	0.17	.	2164
5	271	0.25	.	1884
6	271	0.5	.	1366
7	271	1	.	844
8	271	1.5	.	625
9	271	2	.	478
10	271	4	.	256
11	271	6	.	147

Let's assume that we have a data set where the concentration units are [ng/mL]=[ug/L] and the dose amount units are [mg], as presented above. It is not possible to indicate these units directly, as the amount unit of CONC and AMT must be the same. One option would be to indicate the CONC as [mg/kL] and the AMT as [mg] but having the volume unit as [kL] is not very convenient. We will thus use the scaling factors to harmonize the units of the concentration and the amount.

If we would like to have the output NCA parameters using [ug] and [L], we can define the CONC units as [µg/L] (as the data set input units) and scale the AMT to convert the amount column from [mg] to [ug] unit with a scaling factor of 1000. After clicking “accept” on the bottom right, the values in the amount column of the (internal) data set have been multiplied by 1000 by PKanalix such that they are now in [µg].

Data file

C:/Users/skolmann/Work/pkanalix/pkanalix2023R1/demos/2.case_studies/data/M2000_ivbolus_single_dose.csv

BROWSE...

Data information

Urine Plasma

Units ●

TIME column × 1 = hour

CONC column × 1 = microgram / liter

AMT column × 1000 = microgram

Add. covariates

NONE

LINE NUMBER	ID	time	Amount	DV	GENDER	AGE	HT	WT
1	271				F	69	157	63.7
2	271	0	100000		F	69	157	63.7
3	271	0	2950	2950	F	69	157	63.7
4	271	0.17	2164	2164	F	69	157	63.7
5	271	0.25	1884	1884	F	69	157	63.7
6	271	0.5	1366	1366	F	69	157	63.7
7	271	1	844	844	F	69	157	63.7

Amount in data set has been multiplied by 1000 by PKanalix to obtain µg

If we would like to have the output NCA parameters using [ng] and [mL], we can define the CONC units as [ng/mL] (as the data set input units) and scale the AMT to convert the amount column from [mg] to [ng] unit with a scaling factor of 1000000.

Data file

C:/Users/skolmann/Work/pkanalix/pkanalix2023R1/demos/2.case_studies/data/M2000_ivbolus_single_dose.csv

BROWSE...

Data information

Urine Plasma

Units ●

TIME column × 1 = hour

CONC column × 1 = nanogram / milliliter

AMT column × 1000000 = nanogram

Add. covariates

NONE

LINE NUMBER	ID	time	Amount	DV	GENDER	AGE	HT	WT
1	271				F	69	157	63.7
2	271	0	1e+08		F	69	157	63.7
3	271	0	2950	2950	F	69	157	63.7
4	271	0.17	2164	2164	F	69	157	63.7
5	271	0.25	1884	1884	F	69	157	63.7
6	271	0.5	1366	1366	F	69	157	63.7
7	271	1	844	844	F	69	157	63.7

2.5.2 Units for the NCA parameters

Rsq	no unit
Rsq_adjusted	no unit

Corr_XY	no unit
No_points_lambda_z	no unit
Lambda_z	time-1
Lambda_z_lower	time
Lambda_z_upper	time
HL_lambda_z	time
Span	no unit
Lambda_z_intercept	no unit
T0	time
Tlag	time
Tmax_Rate	time
Max_Rate	amount.time-1
Mid_Pt_last	time
Rate_last	amount.time-1
Rate_last_pred	amount.time-1
AURC_last	amount
AURC_last_D	grading
Vol_UR	volume
Amount_recovered	amount
Percent_recovered	% [not calculable when grading -> set as NaN]
AURC_all	amount
AURC_INF_obs	amount
AURC_PerCentExtrap_obs	%

AURC_INF_pred	amount
AURC_PerCentExtrap_pred	%
C0	amount.volume-1
Tmin	time
Cmin	amount.volume-1
Tmax	time
Cmax	amount.volume-1
Cmax_D	grading.volume-1
Tlast	time
Clast	amount.volume-1
AUClast	time.amount.volume-1
AUClast_D	grading.time.volume-1
AUMClast	time2.amount.volume-1
AUCall	time.amount.volume-1
AUCINF_obs	time.amount.volume-1
AUCINF_D_obs	grading.time.volume-1
AUCINF_pred	time.amount.volume-1
AUCINF_D_pred	grading.time.volume-1
AUC_PerCentExtrap_obs	%
AUC_PerCentBack_Ext_obs	%
AUMCINF_obs	time2.amount.volume-1
AUMC_PerCentExtrap_obs	%
Vz_F_obs	volume.grading-1

Cl_F_obs	volume.time-1.grading-1
Cl_obs	volume.time-1.grading-1
Cl_pred	volume.time-1.grading-1
Vss_obs	volume.grading-1
Clast_pred	amount.volume-1
AUC_PerCentExtrap_pred	%
AUC_PerCentBack_Ext_pred	%
AUMCINF_pred	time2.amount.volume-1
AUMC_PerCentExtrap_pred	%
Vz_F_pred	volume.grading-1
Cl_F_pred	volume.time-1.grading-1
Vss_pred	volume.grading-1
Tau	time
Ctau	amount.volume-1
Ctrough	amount.volume-1
AUC_TAU	time.amount.volume-1
AUC_TAU_D	grading.time.volume-1
AUC_TAU_PerCentExtrap	%
AUMC_TAU	time2.amount.volume-1
Vz	volume.grading-1
Vz_obs	volume.grading-1
Vz_pred	volume.grading-1
Vz_F	volume.grading-1

CLss_F	volume.time-1.grading-1
CLss	volume.time-1.grading-1
CAvg	amount.volume-1
FluctuationPerCent	%
FluctuationPerCent_Tau	%
Accumulation_index	no unit
Swing	no unit
Swing_Tau	no unit
Dose	amount.grading-1
N_Samples	no unit
MRTlast	time
MRTINF_obs	time
MRTINF_pred	time
AUC_lower_upper	time.amount/volume
AUC_lower_upper_D	grading.time.volume-1
CAVG_lower_upper	amount/volume
AURC_lower_upper	amount
AURC_lower_upper_D	grading

2.5.3 Units for the PK parameters

Units are available only in PKanalix. When exporting a project to Monolix, values of PK parameters are re-converted to the original dataset unit. Below, volumeFactor is defined implicitly as: $\text{volumeFactor} = \text{amtFactor} / \text{concFacto}$, where “factor” is the scaling factor used in the “Units” block in the Data tab.

PARAMETER	UNIT	INVERSE of UNITS
V (V1, V2, V3)	volume.grading-1	value/volumeFactor
k (ka, k12, k21, k31, k13, Ktr)	1/time	value*timeFactor
Cl, Q (Q2, Q3)	volume/time.grading-1	value*timeFactor/volumeFactor
Vm	amount/time.grading-1	value*timeFactor/amountFactor
Km	concentration	value/concFactor
T (Tk0, Tlag, Mtt)	time	value/timeFactor
alpha, beta, gamma	1/time	value*timeFactor
A, B, C	grading/volume	value*volumeFactor

2.5.4 Units display

To visualise units, switch on the “units toggle” and accept a dataset. Then, after running the NCA and CA tasks, units are displayed:

- In the results table next to the parameter name (violet frame), in the table copied with “copy” button (blue frame) and in the saved .txt files in the result folder (green frame).

The screenshot displays the PKanalix software interface for a project named 'project_extravascular.plx [demo]'. The 'Results' tab is active, showing 'Individual estimates' for a 'Non compartmental analysis'. A table of individual estimates is visible, with columns for 'id', 'AUCINF_obs', 'AUC_PerCentExtrap_obs', 'AUClast', 'CL_F_obs', 'Clast', 'Cmax', 'Lambda_z', 'Tlast', 'Tmax', and 'Vz_F_obs'. A Notepad window titled 'ncalIndividualParameters - Notepad' is open, showing the raw data for the first 10 records, with units specified for each parameter.

id	AUCINF_obs (h·g·mL ⁻¹)	AUC_PerCentExtrap_obs (%)	AUClast (h·g·mL ⁻¹)	CL_F_obs (mL·h ⁻¹)	Clast (g·mL ⁻¹)	Cmax (g·mL ⁻¹)	Lambda_z (h ⁻¹)	Tlast (h)	Tmax (h)	Vz_F_obs (mL)
101	249.91	8.31	229.14	0.6	2.29	20.48	0.11	24	2	5.45
102	160.81	10.26	144.31	0.93	1.6	14.14	0.097	24	2.5	9.65
103	251.54	13.43	217.76	0.6	3.12	19.87	0.092	24	2.5	6.46
104	213.71	11.29	189.58	0.7	2.28	22.38	0.095	24	3	7.42
105	135.83	16.51	113.41	1.1	1.52	13.14	0.068	24	2.5	16.33
106	115.87	6.11	108.79	1.29	0.81	12.28	0.11	24	3	11.27
107	239.48	18.19	195.93	0.63	3.37	17.51	0.077	24	2.5	8.09
108	175.63	9.05	159.74	0.85	1.8	14.39	0.11	24	2	7.56
109	136.09	13.24	118.07	1.1	1.53	12.13	0.085	24	3	13
1010	229.15	8.35	210.02	0.65	2.22	18.67	0.12	24	1	5.65

```

ncalIndividualParameters - Notepad
File Edit Format View Help
id,AUCINF_obs,AUC_PerCentExtrap_obs,AUClast,CL_F_obs,Clast,Cmax,Lambda_z,Tlast,Tmax,Vz_F_obs
id,AUCIFO,AUCPEO,AUCLST,CLFO,CLST,CMAX,LAMZ,TLST,TMAX,VZFO
,h,g mL-1,%,h,g mL-1,mL·h-1,g mL-1,g mL-1,h-1,h,h,mL
101,249.907,8.30835,229.143,0.600224,2.286,20.4776,0.110099,24,2,5.45167
102,160.811,10.2615,144.309,0.932775,1.59526,14.136,0.096673,24,2.5,9.64876
103,251.542,13.4281,217.764,0.596323,3.11717,19.8727,0.0922858,24,2.5,6.4617
104,213.707,11.2908,189.578,0.701897,2.28098,22.383,0.0945321,24,3,7.42496
105,135.834,16.5097,113.408,1.10429,1.51674,13.1413,0.067634,24,2.5,16.3275
106,115.87,6.10671,108.795,1.29455,0.81243,12.2776,0.114817,24,3,11.2749
107,239.481,18.1871,195.926,0.626355,3.3704,17.5126,0.0773832,24,2.5,8.09427
    
```

- On plots if the “units” display is switched on in the General plots settings

2.5.5 Units preferences

The units selected by default when starting a new PKanalix project can be chosen in the menu Settings > Preferences.

2.6 Filtering a data set

Starting on the 2020 version, filtering a data set to only take a subpart into account in your modelization is possible. It allows to make filters on some specific IDs, times, measurement values,... It is also possible to define complementary filters and also filters of filters. It is accessible through the filters item on the data tab.

The screenshot shows the PKanalix software interface. The 'Filters' menu item in the left sidebar is highlighted with a red rectangle. The main window displays data formatting options, including 'Data file', 'Data information' (Urine/Plasma), 'Units' (TIME, CONC, AMT), and 'Add. covariates'. Below these options is a data table with columns: LINE NUMBER, ID, TIME, DV, AMT, SEX, and WEIGHT. The table contains 14 rows of data. At the bottom, there is a pagination control showing 'Page 1 of 14' and 'Showing 1 to 50 of 700 entries - 50 Individuals'.

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	DV	AMT	SEX	WEIGHT
1	1				F	70.6466
2	1	0		100	F	70.6466
3	1	1	16.6314		F	70.6466
4	1	1.5	21.5208		F	70.6466
5	1	2	11.746		F	70.6466
6	1	2.5	20.0199		F	70.6466
7	1	3	11.9624		F	70.6466
8	1	4	10.7658		F	70.6466
9	1	5	13.9579		F	70.6466
10	1	6	8.71148		F	70.6466
11	1	8	17.574		F	70.6466
12	1	10	8.24835		F	70.6466
13	1	12	5.81872		F	70.6466
14	1	18	4.55314		F	70.6466

2.6.1 Creation of a filter

To create a filter, you need to click on the data set name. You can then create a “child”. It corresponds to a subpart of the data set where you will define your filtering actions.

You can see on the top (in the green rectangle) the action that you will complete and you can CANCEL, ACCEPT, or ACCEPT & APPLY with the bottoms on the bottom.

The screenshot shows the PKanalix software interface. The main window displays a data table with columns: action, header, operator, and value. The 'action' column has a dropdown menu with 'select ids' selected. The 'header' column has a dropdown menu with 'ID' selected. The 'operator' column has a dropdown menu with '=' selected. The 'value' column has a text input field with '1' entered. At the bottom of the dialog are three buttons: 'CANCEL', 'ACCEPT', and 'ACCEPT & APPLY'.

2.6.2 Filtering a data set: actions

In all the filtering actions, you need to define

- An **action**: it corresponds to one of the following possibilities: select ids, remove ids, select lines, remove lines.
- A **header**: it corresponds to the column of the data set you wish to have an action on. Notice that it corresponds to a column of the data set that was tagged with a header.
- An **operator**: it corresponds to the operator of choice ($=$, \neq , $<$, \leq , $>$, or \geq).
- A **value**. When the header contains numerical values, the user can define it. When the header contains strings, a list is proposed.

For example, you can

- Remove the ID 1 from your study:

action	header	operator	value
remove ids ▾	ID ▾	= ▾	1

In that case, all the IDs except ID = 1 will be used for the study.

- Select all the lines where the time is less or equal 24:

action	header	operator	value
select lines ▾	TIME ▾	≤ ▾	24

In that case, all lines with time strictly greater than 24 will be removed. If a subject has no measurement anymore, it will be removed from the study.

- Select all the ids where SEX equals F:

action	header	operator	value
select lines ▾	SEX ▾	= ▾	F ▾

In that case, all the male subjects will be removed from the study.

- Remove all Ids where WEIGHT less or equal 65:

action	header	operator	value
remove ids ▾	WEIGHT ▾	≤ ▾	65

In that case, only the subjects with a weight over 65 will be kept for the study.

In any case, the interpreted filter data set will be displayed in the data tab.

2.6.3 Filters with several actions

In the previous examples, we only did one action. It is also possible to do several actions to define a filter. We have the possibility to define UNION and/or INTERSECTION of actions.

2.6.3.1 Intersection

By clicking by the + and - button on the right, you can define an intersection of actions. For example, by clicking on the +, you can define a filter corresponding to intersection of

- The IDs that are different to 1.
- The lines with the time values less than 24.

	action	header	operator	value	
	select ids ▾	ID ▾	≠ ▾	1	-
INTERSECTION	select lines ▾	TIME ▾	≤ ▾	24	- +

Thus in that case, all the lines with a time less than 24 and corresponding to an ID different than 1 will be used in the study. If we look at the following data set as an example

2.6.3.2 Union

By clicking by the + and - button on the bottom, you can define an union of actions. For example, in a data set with a multi dose, I can focus on the first and the last dose. Thus, by clicking on the +, you can define a filter corresponding to union of

- The lines where the time is strictly less than 12.
- The lines where the time is greater than 72.

select lines ▾
TIME ▾
← ▾
12
↕

UNION

select lines ▾
ID ▾
≡ ▾
12
↕

UNION

select lines ▾
AMT ▾
= ▾
100

id	time	amt	y
1	0	40	
1	0.5		3.365
1	1		2.4718
1	3		2.5617
1	5		1.8819
1	7		2.1349
1	9		1.6741
1	11		2.0317
1	12	40	
1	12.5		4.219
1	13		3.3258
1	15		3.4157
1	17		2.7359
1	19		2.9889
1	21		2.5281
1	23		2.8857
1	24	40	
...
1	72	40	
1	72.5		6.0911
1	73		5.874
1	75		6.0025
1	77		4.7898
1	79		4.1839
1	81		4.2116
1	83		3.2958

select lines with
time < 12

➔

select lines with
time > 72

➔

select lines
with amt = 40

➔

id	time	amt	y
1	0	40	
1	0.5		3.365
1	1		2.4718
1	3		2.5617
1	5		1.8819
1	7		2.1349
1	9		1.6741
1	11		2.0317
1	12	40	
1	12.5		4.219
1	13		3.3258
1	15		3.4157
1	17		2.7359
1	19		2.9889
1	21		2.5281
1	23		2.8857
1	24	40	
...
1	72	40	
1	72.5		6.0911
1	73		5.874
1	75		6.0025
1	77		4.7898
1	79		4.1839
1	81		4.2116
1	83		3.2958

id	time	amt	y
1	0	40	
1	0.5		3.365
1	1		2.4718
1	3		2.5617
1	5		1.8819
1	7		2.1349
1	9		1.6741
1	11		2.0317
1	12	40	
1	12.5		4.219
1	13		3.3258
1	15		3.4157
1	17		2.7359
1	19		2.9889
1	21		2.5281
1	23		2.8857
1	24	40	
...
1	72	40	
1	72.5		6.0911
1	73		5.874
1	75		6.0025
1	77		4.7898
1	79		4.1839
1	81		4.2116
1	83		3.2958

Union of all three

Notice that, if just define the first two actions, all the dose lines at a time in]12, 72[will also be removed. Thus, to keep having all the doses, we need to add the condition of selecting the lines where the dose is defined.

In addition, it is possible to do any combination of INTERSECTION and UNION.

2.6.3.3 Other filters: filter of filter and complementary filters

Filtering a data set can be nested. Based on the definition of a filter, by clicking on the filter, it is possible to create:

- A **child**: it corresponds to a new filter with the initial filter as the source data set.
- A **complement**: corresponds to the complement of the filter. For example, if you defined a filter with only the IDs where the SEX is F, then the complement corresponds to the IDs where the SEX is not F.

2.7 Data exploration

2.7.1 Data exploration

Once the dataset has been tagged and accepted:

- **Plots** are automatically generated based on the interpreted dataset to help you explore the data before running any of the tasks.

- The **interpreted dataset** appears in Data tab, which shows the final dataset after formatting, setting units, and filtering.

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	OBSERVATION	AMOUNT	ADMINISTRATION ID	CATEGORICAL COVARIATE
1	1	0	3826.27	100	1	IV
2	1	0.083	3101.72			IV
3	1	0.25	3955.83			IV
4	1	0.5	3024.63			IV
5	1	1	3441.82			IV
6	1	2	3869.37			IV
7	1	8	3127.52			IV
8	1	12	2259.83			IV
9	1	24				IV
10	1					IV

- **Covariate Statistics** appear in a section of the data tab.

2.8 Import a Monolix project

MonolixSuite applications are interconnected and projects can be exported/imported between different applications. This interconnection is guaranteed by using the same model syntax (mlxtran language) and the same dataset format.

i Import and export to PKanalix is available starting from the 2023 version. In the previous versions, you can only export a PKanalix project to Monolix.

2.8.1 Import a Monolix project to PKanalix

To import a Monolix project, open PKanalix application and in the home page select IMPORT FROM:

In PKanalix, it is possible to import only a Monolix project with its original dataset. When you select in the home screen **IMPORT FROM > Monolix**, then PKanalix will create a new, untitled, project with:

- Dataset tagging and formatting steps if present as in the Monolix project.
- Dataset filters if applied as in the Monolix project.
- NCA settings: “administration type” set to intravenous or extravascular depending on the administration in a model selected in the Monolix project.
- NCA settings: “observation ID to use” set to the first one alphabetically (if obsid are strings) or numerically (if obsid are integers).
- NCA settings: default PKanalix settings for the integral method, treatment of BLQ values, parameters.
- Acceptance criteria: not selected.
- Bioequivalence: default PKanalix settings
- CA model: set to the same structural model and the same mapping between observation ids and model outputs as in the Monolix project
- CA initial parameter values: equal to the initial estimates of the Monolix project
- CA parameters constraints: none for normally distributed parameters, positive for log-normally distributed parameters; bounded with limits imported from the Monolix project for logit-normally and probit-normally distributed parameters.
- CA calculations settings: default PKanalix settings

After the import, you can save the PKanalix project as usual, edit it and run the analysis.

Remark: Importing a Monolix project to PKanalix is only with the original dataset used to create a Monolix project. Export from Monolix to PKanalix has more options. You can choose to import a Monolix project with its original dataset, vpc dataset or with individual fits dataset, see the next section. Import from Simulx is currently unavailable.

2.8.2 Export from Monolix to PKanalix

To export a Monolix project to PKanalix click **EXPORT PROJECT TO** in the top menu “Export”:

The screenshot displays the PKanalix software interface. The 'Export' menu is open, showing options for exporting project data, plots, charts, VPC simulations, datasets, settings, and reports. The main interface includes a 'Tasks' section with buttons for 'POPULATION PAR...', 'CONDITIONAL DI...', 'STANDARD ER...', 'LIKELIHOOD', 'PLOTS', and a 'RUN' button. Below this are sections for 'Observation model' and 'Individual model', each with a table of parameters and covariates.

TYPE	OBSERVATION ID	NAME	PREDICTION	ERROR MODEL	DISTRIBUTION
continuous	1	y1	Cc	COMBINED1	NORMAL

PARAMETERS	DISTRIBUTIONS	RANDOM EFFECTS	CORRELATION	age	sex	wt
Tag	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	#1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
ka	LOGNORMAL	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

When you export a Monolix project, in the export pop-up window you can choose:

- to which application you want to export your current project: PKanalix or Simulx: select "PKanalix"
- which dataset you want to use in the export: original dataset, vpc dataset, individual fits dataset

By default, Monolix will copy all files, e.g. dataset and model, next to the new PKanalix project. To keep current location of these files, switch the toggle “Generated files next to project” off. Click the “EXPORT” button at the bottom to confirm. PKanalix application will open automatically with a predefined project called “untitled”. It will contain the same pre-defined elements as during the import, see the description above. If you selected export with vpc dataset or individual fits dataset, then Monolix creates a .csv files with vpc simulations or individual model predictions in the MonolixSuite data format. These dataset will be automatically loaded in the new PKanalix project.

2.8.2.1 Export with individual fits dataset

The .csv generated file contains model predictions on a fine time grid (specified in the Plots tasks settings in Monolix) obtained with different individual parameters:

LINE NUMBER	ID	TIME	popPred_medianCOV	popPred	indivPred_mean	indivPred_mode	amt	age	wt	sex
1	100							50	66.7	1
2	100	0					100	50	66.7	1
3	100	0	0	0	0	0		50	66.7	1
4	100	1.5e-15	0	0	0	0		50	66.7	1

- **popPred**: model predictions with individual parameters corresponding to the population parameters estimated by Monolix and the impact of the individual covariates, but random effects set to zero. For instance, $V_i = V_{pop} \times \exp^{\beta_{V,WT} \times WT_i}$
- **popPred_medianCOV**: model predictions with individual parameters corresponding to the population parameters and the impact of the covariates using the population median for continuous covariates and reference category for categorical covariates, and random effects set to zero. For instance, $V_i = V_{pop} \times \exp^{\beta_{V,WT} \times WT_{med}}$
- **indivPred_mode**: [when EBEs task has run] model predictions with individual parameters corresponding to the EBEs (conditional mode) estimated by Monolix (as displayed in Monolix Results > Indiv. param > Cond. mode.). Tagged as OBSERVATION by default.
- **indivPred_mean**: [when COND. DISTRIB. task has run] model predictions with individual parameters corresponding to the conditional mean estimated by Monolix (as displayed in in Monolix Results > Indiv. param > Cond. mean.)

The dataset contains also the individual design: doses, occasions, regressors, covariates.

2.8.2.2 Export with vpc dataset

The .csv generated dataset in the Monolix format constructed from the VPC simulations and individual design (doses, occasions, regressors, covariates)

LINE NUMBER	rep	ID	uid	TIME	timeAfterLastDose	doseid	OBSERVATION	obsid	amt	age	wt	sex
1	1		100_rep1							50	66.7	1
2	1	100	100_rep1	0	0	1			100	50	66.7	1
3	1	100	100_rep1	0.5	0.5	1	0.0582826	y1		50	66.7	1
4	1	100	100_rep1	1	1	1	-0.296608	y1		50	66.7	1

- **rep**: simulation replicate. Tagged as stratification categorical covariate
- **uid**: unique id obtained by concatenation of "rep" and "id". Tagged as ID by default.
- **time/timeAfterLastDose**: observation times or times after last dose
- **doseid**: administration id

- **y1/observation:** simulated observation values. Default header is “y1” if a model has only one output, and “observation” in case of several outputs (obsid column is created automatically). Tagged automatically as OBSERVATION

2.9 Data set examples

Here you can download examples of MonolixSuite formatted data sets and see their references, descriptions and explanations of columns:

2.9.1 Warfarin data set

Download data set: warfarin_data.txt

This data set has been originally published in:

O'Reilly (1968). Studies on coumarin anticoagulant drugs. Initiation of warfarin therapy without a loading dose. Circulation 1968, 38:169-177.

Warfarin is an anticoagulant normally used in the prevention of thrombosis and thromboembolism, the formation of blood clots in the blood vessels and their migration elsewhere in the body, respectively. The data set provides set of plasma warfarin concentrations and Prothrombin Complex Response in thirty normal subjects after a single loading dose. A single large loading dose of warfarin sodium, 1.5 mg/kg of body weight, was administered orally to all subjects. Measurements were made each 12 or 24h.

On the two following figure, one could see the concentration and the effect with respect to time for all subjects.

The data set for subject one can be defined as follows

```

id time    amt dv  dvid   wt  age sex
1   0    100 .   1   66.7  50  1
1   0     .  100 2   66.7  50  1
1  24     .   9.2 1   66.7  50  1
1  24     .   49  2   66.7  50  1
1  36     .   8.5 1   66.7  50  1
1  36     .   32  2   66.7  50  1
1  48     .   6.4 1   66.7  50  1
1  48     .   26  2   66.7  50  1
1  72     .   4.8 1   66.7  50  1
1  72     .   22  2   66.7  50  1
1  96     .   3.1 1   66.7  50  1
1  96     .   28  2   66.7  50  1
1 120     .   2.5 1   66.7  50  1
1 120     .   33  2   66.7  50  1
  
```

2.9.1.1 Interpretation

One can see the following columns

- id: the subject ID, column-type ID
- time: the time of the measurement or of the dose, column-type TIME.
- amt: the amount of drug provided to this subject, column-type AMOUNT.
- dv: the measurement, column-type OBSERVATION.

- `dvid`: the type of measurement. In this study, one has two measurement, the concentration measurement (corresponding to the PK dynamics), and the Prothrombin Complex Response (corresponding to the PD-part), column-type OBSERVATION ID.
- `wt`: Weight of the subject, column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE.
- `age`: Age of the subject, column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE.
- `sex`: Sex of the subject, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE.

Several points can be noticed.

1. The first line corresponds to a dose, while the other ones are measurements. This explains the dot in the CONC column for the first line and the dots in the AMT column for the other ones.
2. The covariates columns (the continuous `wt` and the categorical covariates `age` and `sex`) are filled with the same values. Even though it is not necessary, we encourage the user to fill the columns for readability and usage reasons.
3. In the presented case, both PK and PD measurements are at the same time, this is not required for data exploration using Datxplora, nor parameter estimation using Monolix.
4. Finally, notice that no initial washout is needed at the beginning as by default, the null initial condition is used for parameter estimation.

Interestingly, one can display the Effect with respect to the Concentration in order to have an idea on how to model the interaction between the PD and the PK part.

Then, the response does not seem to be direct. **Notice that, as the observation times are no the same between the PK and the PD, interpolation is made to propose this kind of plot.** One can also focus on one individual in particular as on the following figure

Notice that we also propose a red arrow to describe the evolution of time.

2.9.2 Theophylline data set

Download data set: `theophylline_data.txt`

The data considered here are courtesy of Dr. Robert A. Upton of the University of California, San Francisco. Theophylline is a methylxanthine drug used in therapy for respiratory diseases such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and asthma under a variety of brand names. Theophylline was administered orally to 12 subjects whose serum concentrations were measured at 11 times over the next 25 hours. This is an example of a laboratory pharmacokinetic study characterized by many observations on a moderate number of individuals. A representation of the concentration over time for each subject is presented on the following figure.

The purpose of this page is to see the construction, the definition and the use of such a data set in Datxlore and Monolix. For sake of simplicity, we look only on one subject (corresponding to ID 1).

2.9.2.1 Simplified data set

The data set for subject one writes as follows

ID	AMT	TIME	CONC	WEIGHT	SEX
1	4.02	0	.	79.6	M
1	.	0.25	2.84	79.6	M
1	.	0.57	6.57	79.6	M
1	.	1.12	10.5	79.6	M
1	.	2.02	9.66	79.6	M
1	.	3.82	8.58	79.6	M
1	.	5.1	8.36	79.6	M
1	.	7.03	7.47	79.6	M
1	.	9.05	6.89	79.6	M
1	.	12.12	5.94	79.6	M
1	.	24.37	3.28	79.6	M

2.9.2.1.1 Interpretation

One can see the following columns

- ID: the subject ID, column-type ID.
- AMT: the amount of drug provided to this subject, column-type AMOUNT.
- TIME: the time of the event, column-type TIME.
- CONC: the measured concentration, column-type OBSERVATION.

- WEIGHT: Weight of the subject, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE.
- SEX: Sex of the subject, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE.

Several points can be noticed.

1. The first line corresponds to a dose, while the other ones are measurements. This explains the dot in the CONC column for the first line and the dots in the AMT column for the other ones.
2. The covariates columns (the continuous WEIGHT and the categorical SEX) are constant over the individual. Even though it is not necessary, we encourage the user to fill the columns for readability and usage reasons.
3. Finally, notice that no initial washout is needed at the beginning as by default, the null initial condition is used for parameter estimation.

2.9.3 Tobramycin data set

Download data set: tobramycin.txt

This data set has been originally published in:

Aarons, L., Vozeh, S., Wenk, M., Weiss, P. H., & Follath, F. (1989). Population pharmacokinetics of tobramycin. British journal of clinical pharmacology, 28(3), 305-314.

Tobramycin is an antimicrobial agent of the aminoglycosides family, which is among others used against severe gram-negative infections. Because tobramycin does not pass the gastro-intestinal tract, it is usually administrated intravenously as intermittent bolus doses or short infusions. Tobramycin is a drug with a narrow therapeutic index.

Tobramycin bolus doses ranging from 20 to 140mg were administrated every 8 hours in 97 patients (45 females, 52 male) during 1 to 21 days (for most patients, during ~6 days). Age, weight (kg), sex and creatinine clearance (mL/min) were available as covariates. The tobramycin concentration (mg/L) was measured 1 to 9 times per patients (322 measures in total), most of the time between 2 and 6h post-dose. This sparse data set is presented on the figure below

Below is an extract of the data set:

ID	TIME	CP	EVID	DOSE	WT	AGE	SEX	CLCR
2	0	0	1	100	69.5	72	0	39
2	8	0	1	80	69.5	72	0	39
2	16	0	1	80	69.5	72	0	39
2	24	0	1	80	69.5	72	0	39
2	26	7.12	0	0	69.5	72	0	39
2	30	2.98	0	0	69.5	72	0	39

The columns have the following meaning:

- ID: the subject's ID, column-type ID.
- TIME: the time of the record (administration or measurement) in hours, column-type TIME.
- CP: the measured drug's concentration in mg/L, column-type OBSERVATION.
- EVID: event identifier, 1 for doses and 0 for response lines (measurements), column-type EVENT ID.
- DOSE: the amount of drug administrated to this subject in mg, column-type AMOUNT.
- WT: weight of the subject in kg, column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE.
- SEX: sex of the subject, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE.
- CLCR: creatinine clearance of the subject in mL/min, column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE.

Several points can be noticed:

1. The four first lines correspond to doses, while the other ones are measurements, as indicated by the EVID column. The MDV column is not necessary. The zeros of the DOSE and CP columns could have been replaced by dots '.'.
2. The covariates columns (WT, SEX and CLCR) are filled with the same value for each individual. Covariates must be constant within subjects (or subject-occasions when occasions are defined).

2.9.4 HIV data set

Download data set: hiv_data.txt

In the COPHAR II-ANRS 134 trial, an open prospective non-randomized interventional study, 115 HIV-infected patients adults started an antiviral therapy. 48 patients were treated with indinavir (and ritonavir as a booster) (treatment A), 38 with lopinavir (and ritonavir as a booster) (treatment B), and 35 with nelfinavir (Treatment C). patients were followed one year after treatment initialization.

Viral load and CD4 cell count were measured at screenin, at inclusion and at weeks 2 (or 4), 8, 16, 24, 36, and 48. Plasma HIV-1-RNA were measured by Roche monitored with a limit of quantification of 50 copies/ml. The results of this trial are reported in Duval and al. (2009).

On the two following figures, one could see the two outputs with respect to time for all subjects split by treatments. The red circle corresponds to censored data.

2.9.4.1 Simplified HIV data set

The data set for subject 2 can be defined as follows

ID	TIME	Y_NCENS	Y	CENS	YTYPE	TREATMENT
2	-2.43	4.9443	4.9443	0	1	A
2	-2.43	249	249	0	2	A
2	0	4.5245	4.5245	0	1	A
2	2	2.3546	2.3546	0	1	A
2	2	266	266	0	2	A
2	4.29	268	268	0	2	A
2	8	2.5585	2.5585	0	1	A
2	8	34	34	0	2	A
2	16	352	352	0	2	A
2	24	1.7981	2	1	1	A
2	24	385	385	0	2	A
2	32	348	348	0	2	A
2	43	415	415	0	2	A

2.9.4.1.1 Interpretation

One can see the following columns

- ID: the subject ID, column-type ID.
- TIME: the time of the measurement, column-type TIME.
- Y_NCENS: Non censored measurement. Ignored in the representation.

- Y: Considered measurement taking the censoring constraints into account, column-type OBSERVATION.
- CENS: Explicit if the data is censored or not, and the associated type of censoring, column-type CENSORING.
- YTYPE: the type of measurement. In this study, one has two measurements, column-type OBSERVATION ID.
- TREATMENT: Type of treatment, considered as a categorical covariate in our case, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE.

Several points can be noticed.

1. There are no dose in the data set.
2. There is only a categorical covariate defining the treatment.
3. In the presented case, one does not necessary have both measurements at the same time. Indeed, this is not required for data export using Datxplore, nor parameter estimation using Monolix. Moreover, measurements for negative time is possible.

2.9.5 Remifentanil data set

Download data set: pkpdRemifentanil.csv

This data set has been originally published in:

Influence of age and gender on the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of remifentanil. I. Model development. Anesthesiology, Minto, et al. (1997)

Remifentanil is an opioid analgesic drug with a rapid onset and rapid recovery time. It is used for sedation as well as combined with other medications for use in general anesthesia. It is given in adults via continuous IV infusion.

65 healthy adults have received remifentanil IV infusion at a constant diffusion rate between 1 and 8 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ for 4 to 20 minutes. The data set contains remifentanil admission characteristics (time and rate of infusion), dense measurements of remifentanil blood concentration during infusion and after (PK data), as well as dense electroencephalogram measurements (PD data) recording the depth of anesthesia. In addition, a list of covariates is available: age, gender, and lean body mass (LBM). Moreover, a variable TINFCAT classifies the patients in several categories with similar infusion time.

One can see on the following figure the remifentanil concentrations over time split in two groups (female and male). On each figure, the subjects with age lower than 50 are in blue while the ones with an age over 50 are in green.

On the following figure, one can see the electroencephalogram measurements with respect to time for all subjects.

Below is an extract of the data set file:

ID	TIME	AMOUNT	RATE	OBSERVATION YTYPE: 1 CONTINUOUS	YTYPE	MDV	CONTINUOUS COVARIATE	CATEGORICAL COVARIATE	CONTINUOUS COVARIATE	CATEGORICAL COVARIATE
ID	TIME	AMT	RATE	DV	YTYPE	MDV	AGE	SEX	LBM	TINFCAT
1	0	.	.	18.85	2	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	0	1439.8	71.99	.	.	1	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	0.5	.	.	19.91	2	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	1	.	.	19.51	2	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	1.5	.	.	18.67	2	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	1.5	.	.	9.51	1	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	2	.	.	11.5	1	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	2	.	.	19.03	2	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	2.5	.	.	16.04	2	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20
1	2.52	.	.	14.1	1	0	30.58	M	56.5075	20

The columns have the following meaning:

- ID: the subject's ID, column-type ID.
- TIME: the time of the record (administration or measurement) in minutes, column-type TIME.
- AMT: the amount of drug, column-type AMOUNT.
- RATE: the rate of drug delivery, column-type INFUSION RATE.
- DV: remifentanil concentration measurement or electroencephalogram measurement, column-type OBSERVATION.
- YTYPE: the type of measurement. There are two measurement types in this data set: the remifentanil concentration measurement (corresponding to the PK dynamics), and the electroencephalogram measurement (corresponding to the PD-part), column-type OBSERVATION ID.
- MDV: Missing Data Variable, column-type MDV.
- AGE: Age of the subject in year, column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE.
- SEX: sex of the subject (F for female and M for male), column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE.
- LBM: lean body mass, column-type CONTINUOUS COVARIATE.
- TINFCAT: Categories of infusion time, column-type CATEGORICAL COVARIATE.

2.9.6 Veralipride data set

Download data set: PK_veralipride.csv

This data set has been originally published in:

Plusquellec, Y, Campistron, G, Staveris, S, Barre, J, Jung, L, Tillement, JP, Houin, G (1987). A double-peak phenomenon in the pharmacokinetics of veralipride after oral administration: a double-site model for drug absorption. J Pharmacokinet Biopharm, 15, 3:225-39.

Veralipride is a benzamide neuroleptic medicine indicated in the treatment of vasomotor symptoms associated with the menopause.

In this dataset, 100 mg doses of veralipride were given to 12 healthy volunteers by oral solution. Individual plasma concentrations of veralipride (ng/ml) were observed at 16 time points during 24h (time is measured in h) after the administration. Doses were given in the morning after an overnight fast, and subjects fasted up to 4 hr after drug administration in each case.

This data set is displayed on the figure below. For some individuals, as the one highlighted on the figure, a double peak in plasma concentrations was observed after oral administration of the solution.

This double peak phenomenon is not systematically noticeable, as can be seen on the next figure.

Below is an extract of the data set file:

ID	TIME	AMOUNT	OBSERVATION	CONTINUOUS
1	0	100	.	.
1	0.17	.	571.7	.
1	0.33	.	780	.
1	0.5	.	629.3	.
1	0.75	.	551.7	.

The columns are:

- ID: the subject ID, column-type ID.
- TIME: the time of the measurement or of the dose, column-type TIME.
- AMT: the amount of drug provided to this subject, column-type AMOUNT
- Y: the measurement, column-type OBSERVATION.

3 Non Compartmental Analysis

3.1 Overview

One of the main features of PKanalix is the calculation of the parameters in the Non Compartmental Analysis framework.

3.1.1 NCA task

The main function of PKanalix is to calculate PK metrics (non-compartmental parameters). In the Tasks tab, there is a dedicated section called "NCA" (left panel). There are two subtabs: RUN and CHECK λz.

The screenshot displays the PKanalix software interface for Non Compartmental Analysis (NCA). The main window shows the 'Tasks' tab with 'CHECK λz' and 'RUN' subtabs. The 'Settings' section is divided into 'Calculations NCA' and 'Acceptance criteria NCA'. The 'Parameters NCA-BE' table lists various metrics and their status for NCA and BE.

		NCA	BE	log
Custom Parameters				
AUC				
AUC_PerCentExtrap_obs	% extrapolated AUC	✓		
AUC_PerCentExtrap_pred	% extrapolated AUC _{pred}			
AUCall	AUC _{all}			
AUCINF_D_obs	AUC _{0-∞,Dose}	✓	✓	✓
AUCINF_D_pred	AUC _{0-∞,pred,Dose}			
AUCINF_obs	AUC _{0-∞}	✓		
AUCINF_pred	AUC _{0-∞,pred}			
AUClast	AUC _{0-last}	✓		
AUClast_D	AUC _{0-last,Dose}	✓	✓	✓
Concentration				
C0	C ₀			
Clast	C _{last}	✓		
Clast_pred	C _{last,pred}			

- The **RUN** tab contains a section with calculation task buttons (for non-compartmental analysis and bioequivalence) and the corresponding settings: calculation, acceptance criteria, parameters and bioequivalence design. The meaning of all the settings and their defaults is documented in a separate page here.
- The **CHECK λ_z** tab allows defining the calculation of λ_z . It is a graphical preview of the data for each individual and the regression line, more details are here.

To calculate NCA parameters, click on the button NON-COMPARTMENTAL ANALYSIS. When you click on RUN button, PKanalix runs all selected tasks (those tasks which are enabled and shown in green). Results and plots are automatically generated in separate tabs.

3.1.2 NCA results

When you run the NCA task, results are automatically generated and displayed in the RESULTS tab. There are three tables: individual estimates, summary and points for λ_z .

3.1.2.1 Non compartmental analysis results per individual

Individual estimates of the NCA parameters are displayed in a table in the tab "INDIV. ESTIM."

All the computed parameters depend on the type of observation and administration. Description of all the parameters is here. You can copy this table to a word or an excel file using the icon at the top right (indicated with the purple box).

project_aPCSK9_SAD.plx [demo] * - PKanalix - 2024R1

Project Settings Export Help

Data Tasks Results Plots

POINTS FOR λ_z CONCENTRATIONS SUMMARY INDIV. ESTIM.

NCA DISPLAY

Individual estimates

Non compartmental analysis results per individual

id	AUC _{0-inf} (d·mg·L ⁻¹)	AUC _{0-last} (d·mg·L ⁻¹)	CL/F (L·d ⁻¹)	C _{last} (mg·L ⁻¹)	C _{max} (mg·L ⁻¹)	Flag_λ _z _Rule	Flag_Rsq_adjusted	k _{el} (d ⁻¹)	Intercept	V _d /F (L)	DOSE_mg
1	338.7602	332.6599	0.4428	0.42	19.72	1	1	0.06885	3.2295	6.4313	150mg
2	270.5851	269.762	0.5544	0.12	12.52	1	0	0.1458	6.1349	3.8025	150mg
3	197.7757	194.5233	0.7584	0.39	11.03	1	1	0.1199	4.0937	6.3249	150mg
4	136.3369	133.844	1.1002	0.27	8.04	1	1	0.1083	3.2476	10.158	150mg
5	144.3502	141.8276	1.0391	0.29	8.35	1	1	0.115	3.6013	9.0392	150mg
6	174.4401	170.5119	0.8599	0.46	8.68	1	1	0.1171	4.153	7.3432	150mg
7	285.3552	283.5441	1.0513	0.1901	15.31	1	1	0.105	4.2514	10.0151	300mg
8	630.3973	621.8114	0.4759	0.77	26.6801	1	1	0.08968	4.8097	5.3065	300mg
9	810.8555	809.7794	0.37	0.105	31.0001	1	1	0.09757	5.9764	3.7919	300mg
10	717.2634	715.7889	0.4183	0.12	33.4701	1	1	0.08138	4.6793	5.1393	300mg

Records per page: 10 18

<< Page 1 of 2 >>

Showing 1 to 10 of 18 entries

3.1.2.2 Summary statistics on NCA results

Statistics on non-compartmental parameters are displayed in a summary table in the sub-tab "SUMMARY". A description of all the summary calculations is here.

Summary

Statistics on non compartmental analysis results

	MIN	Q1	MEDIAN	Q3	MAX	MEAN	SD	SE	CV	NTOT	NOBS	NMISS	GEOMEAN	GEOSD	GEOCV	HARMMEAN
AUC _{inf} (h*ng/ml ⁻¹)	25850.42	42220.7	49748.67	61934.08	356602.34	62049.43	56524.69	7011.02	91.1	65	65	0	52825.99	1.6	49.75	48660.07
AUC _{0-last} (h*ng/ml ⁻¹)	25668.95	42129.49	49307.9	61349.58	356193.24	61821.74	56427.45	6998.96	91.27	65	65	0	52607.04	1.6	49.81	48452.14
CL/F (ml/h ⁻¹)	0.02	0.033	0.038	0.045	0.065	0.039	0.009	0.0011	22.9	65	65	0	0.038	1.26	23.37	0.037
C _{last} (ng/ml ⁻¹)	0.1	0.12	0.13	0.18	1.32	0.18	0.17	0.021	93.82	65	65	0	0.15	1.57	47.76	0.14
C _{max} (ng/ml ⁻¹)	21.3	87.27	86.62	83.04	245.4	73.41	36.64	4.84	49.91	65	65	0	66.98	1.53	44.4	61.18
K _{sel} (h ⁻¹)	0.000083	0.00091	0.0011	0.0013	0.0018	0.0011	0.00034	0.000043	31.99	65	65	0	0.00099	1.67	54.65	0.00079
Intercept	-0.81	2.67	3.35	3.72	4.71	3.1	1.05	0.13	33.81	65	65	0	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
Number of points	3	4	9	14	36	10.74	7.9	0.98	73.59	65	65	0	8.26	2.11	86.07	6.38
R squared	0.89	0.98	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.98	0.023	0.0028	2.31	65	65	0	0.98	1.02	2.38	0.98
adjusted R squared	0.89	0.98	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.98	0.024	0.003	2.43	65	65	0	0.98	1.03	2.5	0.98

Records per page: 10 13

« < Page 1 of 2 > »

Showing 1 to 10 of 13 entries

Elapsed time (seconds): 0.041

The summary table can be

- split and filtered according to the categorical and continuous covariates tagged in the data set
- filtered according to the acceptance criteria defined in the NCA settings

Summary

Statistics on non compartmental analysis results

	AGE	SEX	MIN	Q1	MEDIAN	Q3	MAX	MEAN	SD	SE	CV	NTOT	NOBS	NMISS
AUCINF_obs	20-38.5	0	391.472997	577.139521	645.444303	731.874034	805.511991	639.521525	143.40919	58.428206	22.455724	6	6	0
AUCINF_obs	20-38.5	1	428.032774	740.902488	802.402501	1285.049323	3403.045484	1441.47845	1563.229423	521.076474	108.446257	9	9	0
AUCINF_obs	38.5-66.5	0	402.777208	539.923232	694.244894	813.285525	937.595739	683.562383	194.126605	80.048384	28.49184	6	6	0
AUCINF_obs	38.5-66.5	1	484.349804	664.899491	835.844474	949.095261	1140.070335	827.144894	200.352483	60.408547	24.222116	11	11	0
AUCINF_obs	66.5-85	0	447.767093	600.877438	674.414744	779.494331	1039.794136	707.128546	171.412442	54.205374	24.240433	10	10	0
AUCINF_obs	66.5-85	1	607.144244	607.443544	688.138459	1028.417599	1163.195774	797.082017	238.759314	97.473082	28.954172	6	6	0
C _{max}	20-38.5	0	32.56	45.82	55.12	59.07	93.6	56.981447	20.409878	8.332298	35.881295	6	6	0
C _{max}	20-38.5	1	21.7	34.77	44.28	89.955	237.7	83.443333	62.740358	20.920119	75.213148	9	9	0
C _{max}	38.5-66.5	0	58.64	58.78	72.43	85.72	87.4	72.566447	14.748578	6.021082	20.324177	6	6	0
C _{max}	38.5-66.5	1	44.22	47.935	80.15	88.4275	100.72	76.430909	18.408218	5.410589	24.344457	11	11	0
C _{max}	66.5-85	0	59.64	45.48	76.36	79.39	96.93	74.964	10.707247	3.385929	14.283185	10	10	0
C _{max}	66.5-85	1	59.05	42.39	70.995	94.45	94.65	75.421647	15.793252	6.447568	20.93941	6	6	0
Flag_AUC_%Extrap_pred	20-38.5	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	6	6	0
Flag_AUC_%Extrap_pred	20-38.5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	9	9	0
Flag_AUC_%Extrap_pred	38.5-66.5	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	6	6	0

Elapsed time (seconds): 0.004

- **Split by covariates:** When you apply “split” to a table, the values of the splitting covariates are displayed in the first columns of the summary table (blue highlight). The order of these columns corresponds to the order of the clicks to setup the splitting covariates (orange highlight). You can discretize continuous covariates into groups by defining the group limits (yellow highlight), and create new categories for categorical covariates (drag and drop to merge existing categories). It is currently not possible to split the table in several subtables (instead of splitting the rows), nor to choose the orientation of the table (NCA parameters as columns for instance). See the reporting documentation for details how these options can be applied in a report.
- **Filter by acceptance criteria:** you can remove parameter values from subjects that do not meet the acceptance criteria from the calculations in the summary table.

Filtering rules - details

- When filtering by the “% extrapolated AUC” criterion, values from subjects that do not meet the criterion are excluded for the following parameters: [AUCINF_obs, AUCINF_pred, AUCINF_D_obs, AUCINF_D_pred, AUC_PerCentExtrap_obs, AUC_PerCentExtrap_pred, Vz_obs, Vz_pred, Vz_F_obs, Vz_F_pred, Cl_obs, Cl_pred, Cl_F_obs, Cl_F_pred, AUMCINF_obs, AUMCINF_pred, AUMC_PerCentExtrap_obs, AUMC_PerCentExtrap_pred, MRTINF_obs, MRTINF_pred, Vss_obs, Vss_pred, AURC_INF_obs, AURC_INF_pred, AURC_PerCentExtrap_obs, AURC_PerCentExtrap_pred].
- When filtering by the “Adjusted R2” or “Span” criteria, all parameters in the previous list are similarly impacted, as well as the additional following parameters: [Rsqr, Rsqr_adjusted, Corr_XY, Lambda_z, Lambda_z_intercept, Lambda_z_lower, Lambda_z_upper, HL_Lambda_z, Span, Clast_pred, No_points_lambda_z, AUC_PerCentBack_Ext_obs, AUC_PerCentBack_Ext_pred, Rate_last_pred].
- The following parameters are not impacted by the filtering: [AUC_T1_T2, AUC_T1_T2_D, AUC_TAU, AUC_TAU_D, AUC_TAU_PerCentExtrap, AUCall, AUClast, AUClast_D, AUMC_TAU, Accumulation_Index, C0, CLss, Cavg, Cavg_0_20, Clast, Cmax, Cmax_D, Cmin, Ctau, Ctrough, Dose, FluctuationPerCent, FluctuationPerCent_Tau, N_Samples, Swing, Swing_Tau, T0, Tau, Tlast, Tmax, Tmin, Vz]. In particular, parameters that relate to steady-state or partial AUC are not filtered, even though they rely on the lambda_z value for extrapolation when no valid observation is available at the upper end of the interval.

When you save a PKanalix project, the stratification settings of the results are saved in the result folder and are reloaded when reloading a PKanalix project. **The table in the <result folder>/PKanalix/IndividualParameters/nca/ncaIndividualParametersSummary.txt takes into account the split definition.** This table is generated when clicking “run” in the task tab (usually without splits, as the result tab is not yet available to define them) and also upon saving the project (with splits if defined).

3.1.2.3 Table of concentrations

With MonolixSuite version 2024, a table of concentrations is now generated after each NCA run. It can either be displayed as a summary table or as a table for individual concentrations.

Summary table of concentrations

This table is displayed by default. The columns contain the concentrations at different time points, which are summarized for different descriptive metrics shown per row.

Individual and summary concentrations

Concentration by nominal time

	0.25	0.5	1	2	3.5	5	7	9	12	24
min	0.85	2.35	5.02	6.32	5.53	4.94	4.02	3.46	2.69	0.86
Q1	1.505	3.52	6.79	6.695	6.23	5.775	4.59	4.25	3.005	0.985
median	2.43	5.425	7.91	7.815	7.295	6.43	5.35	4.735	3.615	1.15
Q3	3.725	7.07	8.455	8.855	8.66	7.96	6.84	6.005	4.47	1.41
max	7.37	9.03	11.4	9.72	10.21	9.18	8.02	7.14	5.94	3.28
mean	2.8692	5.4617	7.9292	7.8875	7.4925	6.7667	5.695	5.0808	3.885	1.4033
SD	1.8779	2.1201	1.7408	1.2392	1.5508	1.3744	1.3196	1.2084	1.0924	0.7247
SE	0.5421	0.612	0.5025	0.3577	0.4477	0.3968	0.3809	0.3488	0.3153	0.2092
CV	65.4508	38.8175	21.955	15.7104	20.6976	20.3114	23.1716	23.783	28.118	51.6403
Nobs	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12

Records per page: 10 / 14
 << Page 1 of 2 >>

If nominal time is available in the dataset, the concentrations are automatically summarized using nominal time points. By deselecting 'Use nominal time' in the right panel, the table can also be displayed based on the actual time contained in the dataset.

The same stratification and filter options are available as for the NCA summary table described above.

The rules set in the NCA task tab for handling censored data are also used in the calculation of the descriptive statistics.

Table of individual concentrations

This table can be displayed in the same tab by enabling the toggle "Display individual profiles" in the right-hand side panel.

project_nominal_time.pkc [demo] * - PKanalix - 2024R1

Project Settings Export Help

Data Tasks **Results** Plots

POINTS FOR λ_z **CONCENTRATIONS** SUMMARY INDIV. ESTIM.

NCA

Individual and summary concentrations

Concentration by nominal time

SUBJECT	0.25	0.5	1	2	3.5	5	7	9	12	24
1	2.84	6.57	10.5	9.66	8.58	8.36	7.47	6.89	5.94	3.28
2	1.72	7.91	8.31	8.33	6.85	6.08	5.4	4.55	3.01	0.9
3	4.4	6.9	8.2	7.8	7.5	6.2	5.3	4.9	3.7	1.05
4	1.89	4.6	8.6	8.38	7.54	6.88	5.78	5.33	4.19	1.15
5	2.02	5.63	11.4	9.33	8.74	7.56	7.09	5.9	4.37	1.57
6	1.29	3.08	6.44	6.32	5.53	4.94	4.02	3.46	2.78	0.92
7	0.85	2.35	5.02	6.58	7.09	6.66	5.25	4.39	3.53	1.15
8	3.05	3.05	7.31	7.56	6.59	5.88	4.73	4.57	3	1.25
9	7.37	9.03	7.14	6.33	5.66	5.67	4.24	4.11	3.16	1.12
10	2.89	5.22	6.41	7.83	10.21	9.18	8.02	7.14	5.68	2.42

Records per page: 10 25 26

DISPLAY

- Paginate
- Use nominal time
- Display individual profiles

STRATIFICATION GROUPS

WEIGHT

SEX

Split Filter

WEIGHT

SEX

Each row in the table corresponds to an individual. The columns correspond to the different time points. There are options for stratification and filtering. Additionally, displaying the columns based on either nominal time or actual time points is possible. Extrapolated points at dosing time are not displayed in the table as well as unused data for NCA, such as data points before last dose or negative values.

If the dataset contains left censored data, these will be displayed in the individual table of concentrations using the “<LLOQ>” tag.

3.1.2.4 Ratios for NCA parameters

With MonolixSuite version 2024, parameter ratios can be calculated. Once this task has been performed, the results are displayed in 2 different tables in the results tab, as a summary table and as a table of individual ratios.

Summary table of ratios

project_occasions1.pkx [demo] * - PKAnalix - 2024R1

Project Settings Export Help

Data Tasks **Results** Plots

POINTS FOR λ_z **RATIOS SUMMARY** RATIOS INDIV. ESTIM. CONCENTRATIONS SUMMARY INDIV. ESTIM.

NCA

Ratio summary

DISPLAY

Paginate

	MIN	Q1	MEDIAN	Q3	MAX	MEAN	SD	SE	
Ratio_AUCINF_2vs1	0.8794	0.9455	1.0034	1.0324	1.1503	0.9942	0.05825	0.01165	5
Ratio_Cmax_2vs1	0.9432	1.1041	1.2195	1.2898	1.7039	1.2115	0.1594	0.03188	13

The calculated parameter ratios are presented using basic descriptive statistics. However, even if the dataset contains additional covariates or occasions, this table cannot be further stratified.

Table of ratios per individual

project_occasions1.pkx [demo] * - PKAnalix - 2024R1

Project Settings Export Help

Data Tasks **Results** Plots

POINTS FOR λ_z RATIOS SUMMARY **RATIOS INDIV. ESTIM.** CONCENTRATIONS SUMMARY INDIV. ESTIM.

NCA

Individual Ratios

DISPLAY

Paginate

id	Ratio_AUCINF_2vs1	Ratio_Cmax_2vs1
1	1.0155	1.3791
2	1.037	1.2698
3	0.9585	1.3626
4	1.0086	1.1448
5	0.8794	1.1013
6	1.0439	1.105
7	1.0498	0.9955
8	1.0309	1.2041
9	1.0102	1.2258
10	1.0042	1.2318

Records per page: 10 25

<< < Page 1 of 3 >>

Showing 1 to 10 of 25 entries

The parameter ratio is calculated per individual. This table shows a list sorted by subject identifier. The number of columns in the table depends on how many ratios have been defined. If a ratio couldn't be calculated for a subject, such as due to missing values, NaN is displayed as the entry for the corresponding ratio parameter.

3.1.2.5 Points for λ_z

In the sub-tab "POINTS FOR λ_z ", there is a table of concentration points used for the terminal slope (λ_z) calculation.

Project Settings Export Help

Data **Tasks** Results Plots

NCA

POINTS FOR λ_z SUMMARY INDIV. ESTIM.

Points included in λ_z calculation

Table of concentration points used for the terminal slope (λ_z) calculation

ID	time	concentration	BLQ	included for λ_z
1	0	0	0	0
1	0.13	2.48	0	0
1	1	14.93	0	0
1	3	19.72	0	0
1	5	17.61	0	1
1	7	14.21	0	1
1	9	13.01	0	1
1	14	9.86	0	1
1	21	5.66	0	1
1	28	4.08	0	1

Records per page: 10 25 50 100 223

<< < Page 1 of 23 > >>

Showing 1 to 10 of 223 entries

This table is displayed only if the number of rows is less than 5000. Above this, the tab appears as usual but with incomplete data. You can find the full table in the result folder: <result folder>/PKanalix/IndividualParameters/nca/pointsIncludedForLambdaZ.txt.

3.1.3 NCA plots

The PLOTS tab shows plots for the individual parameters:

- Correlation between NCA parameters: displays scatter plots for each pair of parameters. You can identify correlations between parameters, which can be used to see the results of your analysis and see the coherence of the parameters for each individual.
- Distribution of the NCA parameters: shows the empirical distribution of the parameters. You can verify the distribution of the parameters over the individuals.
- NCA parameters w.r.t. covariates: displays the individual parameters as a function of the covariates. You can identify correlation effects between the individual parameters and the covariates.
- NCA individual fits: shows the lambdaZ regression line for each individual.

- NCA data: observations are displayed in the same way as in the Observed data plot, taking into account the selected NCA settings in the NCA task tab.

3.1.4 NCA outputs

After running the NCA task, the following files are available in the result folder: <resultFolder>/PKanalix/IndividualParameters/nca

- **Summary.txt** contains the summary of the NCA parameters calculation, in a format easily readable by a human (but not easy to parse programmatically)
- **ncaIndividualParametersSummary.txt** contains the summary of the NCA parameters in a structured format.
 - The first column corresponds to the name of the parameter
 - The second column corresponds to the CDISC name of the parameter
 - The other columns correspond to the several elements describing the summary of the parameters (as explained here)
- **ncaIndividualParameters.txt** contains the NCA parameters for each subject-occasion along with the covariates.
 - The first row corresponds to the name of the parameter
 - The second row corresponds to the CDISC name of the parameter
 - The other rows correspond to the parameter values
- **pointsIncludedForLambdaZ.txt** contains the concentration points used for each individual for the lambda_z calculation.
 - id: individual identifiers
 - occ: occasions (if present). The column header corresponds the data set header of the column(s) tagged as occasion(s).
 - time: time of the measurements
 - concentration: concentration measurements as displayed in the NCA individual fits plot (i.e after taking into account the BLQ rules)
 - BLQ: if the data point is a BLQ (1) or not (0)
 - includedForLambdaZ: if this data point has been used to calculate the lambda_Z (1) or not (0)

The files **ncaIndividualParametersSummary.txt** and **ncaIndividualParameters.txt** can be opened in R using the following command

```
read.table("/path/to/file.txt", sep = ",", header = TRUE)
```

3.1.4.1 Remarks

- To load the individual parameters using PKanalix name as headers, you need to remove the row after the header

```
ncaParameters = read.table("/path/to/file.txt", sep = ",", header = TRUE);  
ncaParameters[-1,] # to remove the CDISC name line
```

- To load the individual parameters using CDISC as headers, you need to skip the first row

```
ncaParameters = read.table("/path/to/file.txt", sep = ",", header = TRUE,  
skip = 1)
```

- In both cases, the 2 subsequent rows specifying the formatted names and units need to be removed and the columns converted to numeric.
- The separator is the one defined in the user preferences. We use “,” in this example as it is the default.

3.2 Check lambda_z

λ_z is the slope of the terminal elimination phase. If estimated, the NCA parameters will be extrapolated to infinity. The “check lambda_z” tab visualizes the linear regression model for each individual and allows selecting the points included in the calculation of the λ_z parameter.

3.2.1 General rule

The “Check lambda_z” tab shows the data for each individual plotted by default in log-scale on the y-axis.

- Points used in the λ_z calculation are in blue.
- Points not used in the λ_z calculation are in grey.
- The λ_z curve is in green.

A main rule to select which points to include in the λ_z calculation applies to all individuals. You can find it on top in the right panel – shown with the red box in the figure above. There are four methods that can be selected in the drop-down menu:

- “R2” chooses the number of points that optimize the correlation coefficient.
- “Adjusted R2” (called “Best Fit” in WinNonlin) optimizes the adjusted correlation coefficient, taking into account the number of points. The “maximum number of points” and “minimum time” allow to further restrict the points selected.
- “Interval” selects all points within a given time interval.
- “Points” corresponds to the number of terminal points taken into account in the calculation.

The calculation of the λ_z is via the linear regression. The selection of the weighting used in the cost function is in the right panel (blue highlight). Three options are available: uniform (default), $1/Y$, and $1/Y^2$.

See the Settings page and the Calculations page for more details. In addition to the main rule, it is possible to define more precisely (manually) which points to include or exclude for each individual.

3.2.2 Manual choice of measurements for the λ_z calculation

Plots in the “check lambda_z” tab are interactive. For each individual, specific points can be selected manually to be included or excluded from the λ_z calculation. There are two methods: define a range (time interval) with a slider or select each point individually.

3.2.2.1 Change of the range

For a given individual, the grey arrow (highlighted in red) below each individual plot defines a range—the time interval in which measured concentrations are used in the lambda-z calculation. New points to include are colored in light blue, and points to remove are colored in dark grey, as shown in the following figure (highlighted in blue):

The button “Apply include/exclude” (in the top-right corner above the plot) applies the manual modifications of the points to the calculation of λ_z . If the modifications concern several individuals, then clicking on the “Apply include/exclude” button updates all of them automatically.

The plots are updated with new points and a new λ_z curve. For modified plots, a “back arrow” appears in the top-left corner (highlighted in red in the figure below). It resets the individual calculation to the general rule. The drop-down menu in the “Apply include/exclude” (blue frame) allows to reset all individuals to the general rule. Clear selection the current selection made before clicking on the “Apply include/exclude” button.

3.2.2.2 Include/exclude single points

It is possible to manually modify each point to include it in the calculation of λ_z or to remove it from the calculation:

- If you click on an unused point (light grey), it will change its color into light blue and will be selected for inclusion (left panel in the figure below).
- If you click on an included point (blue), it will change its color into dark grey and will be selected for exclusion (right panel in the figure below).

Clicking on the “Apply include/exclude” button applies these changes. The “back arrow” in the top-left corner of each individual plot resets the individual selection to the general rule one individual at a time, while the “Reset to general rule” button in the “Apply include/exclude” drop-down menu resets all of individuals at once.

3.2.2.3 Remarks

- If the general rule is modified, only the individuals for which the general rule applies will be updated. Individual for which the points have been manually modified will not be updated.
- If λ_z can not be computed, the background of the plot will be shown in light red as in the following figure.

3.3 Data Processing and Calculation Rules

This page presents the rules applied to pre-process the data set and the calculation rules applied for the NCA analysis.

3.3.1 Data processing

3.3.1.1 Ignored data

All observation points occurring before the last dose recorded for each individual are excluded. Observation points occurring at the same time as the last dose are kept, irrespective of their position in the data set file.

Note that for plasma data, negative or zero concentrations are *not* excluded.

3.3.1.2 Data constraints

For plasma data, mandatory columns are ID, TIME, OBSERVATION, and AMOUNT. For urine data, mandatory columns are ID, TIME, OBSERVATION, AMOUNT and one REGRESSOR (to define the volume).

Two observations at the same time point will generate an error.

For urine data, negative or null volumes and negative observations generate an error.

3.3.1.3 Additional points at dose time

For plasma data, if an individual has no observation at dose time, a value is added:

- **Extravascular and Infusion data:** For single dose data, a concentration of zero. For steady-state, the minimum value observed during the dosing interval.
- **IV Bolus data:** the concentration at dose time (C₀) is extrapolated using a log-linear regression (i.e., log(concentration) versus time) with uniform weight of first two data points. In the following cases, C₀ is taken to be the first observed measurement instead (can be zero or negative):
 - one of the two observations is zero
 - the regression yields a slope ≥ 0

3.3.1.4 BLQ data

Measurements marked as BLQ data with a "1" in the CENSORING column will be replaced by zero, the LOQ value or the LOQ value divided by 2, or considered as missing (i.e., excluded) depending on the setting chosen. They are then handled like any other measurement. The LOQ value is indicated in the OBSERVATION column of the data set.

3.3.1.5 Steady-state

Steady-state is indicated using the STEADY-STATE and INTERDOSE INTERVAL column-types. Equal dosing intervals are assumed. Observation points occurring after the dose time + interdose interval are excluded for Cmin and Cmax, but not for lambda_z. Dedicated parameters are computed such as the AUC in the interdose interval, and a specific formula should be considered for the clearance and the volume, for example. More details can be found here.

3.3.1.6 Urine

Urine data is assumed to be single-dose, irrespective of the presence of a STEADY-STATE column. For the NCA analysis, the data is not used directly. Instead the interval midpoints and the excretion rate for each interval (amount eliminated per unit of time) are calculated and used:

$$\text{midpoint} = \frac{\text{start time} + \text{end time}}{2}$$

$$\text{excretion rate} = \frac{\text{concentration} \times \text{volume}}{\text{end time} - \text{start time}}$$

3.3.2 Calculation rules

3.3.2.1 Lambda_z

PKAnalix tries to estimate the slope of the terminal elimination phase, called λ_z , as well as the intercept called Lambda_z_intercept. λ_z is calculated via a linear regression between $Y=\log(\text{concentrations})$ and $X=\text{time}$. Several weightings are available for the regression: uniform, $1/Y$ and $1/Y^2$.

Zero and negative concentrations are excluded from the regression (but not from the NCA parameter calculations). The number of points included in the linear regression can be chosen via the "Main rule" setting. In addition, the user can define specific points to include or exclude for each individual (see the Check lambda_z page for details). When one of the automatic "main rules" is used, points prior to Cmax, and the point at Cmax for non-bolus models are not included. Those points can, however, be included manually by the user. If λ_z can be estimated, NCA parameters will be extrapolated to infinity.

R2 rule: the regression is done with the last three points, then the last four points, then the last five points, etc. If the R2 for n points is larger than or equal to the R2 for (n-1) points - 0.0001, then the R2 value for n points is used. Additional constrains on the measurements included in the λ_z calculation can be set using the "maximum number of points" and "minimum time" settings. If strictly less than 3 points are available for the regression or if the calculated slope is positive, the λ_z calculation fails.

Adjusted R2 rule: the regression is done with the last three points, then the last four points, then the last five points, etc. For each regression the adjusted R2 is calculated as:

$$\text{Adjusted R2} = 1 - \frac{(1 - R^2) \times (n - 1)}{(n - 2)}$$

with n the number of data points included and R^2 the square of the correlation coefficient.

If the adjusted R2 for n points is larger than or equal to the adjusted R2 for $(n-1)$ points – 0.0001, then the adjusted R2 value for n points is used. Additional constraints on the measurements included in the λz calculation can be set using the “maximum number of points” and “minimum time” settings. If strictly less than 3 points are available for the regression or if the calculated slope is positive, the λz calculation fails.

Interval: strictly positive concentrations within the given time interval are used to calculate λz . Points on the interval bounds are included. Semi-open intervals can be defined using +/- infinity.

Points: the n last points are used to calculate λz . Negative and zero concentrations are excluded *after* the selection of the n last points. As a consequence, some individuals may have less than n points used.

3.3.3 AUC calculation

The following linear and logarithmic rules apply to calculate the AUC and AUMC over an interval $[t_1, t_2]$ where the measured concentrations are C_1 and C_2 . The total AUC is the sum of the AUCs calculated on each interval. If the logarithmic AUC rule fails on an interval because C_1 or C_2 are null or negative, then the linear interpolation rule will be used for that interval.

Linear formula:

$$AUC|_{t_1}^{t_2} = (t_2 - t_1) \times \frac{C_1 + C_2}{2}$$

$$AUMC|_{t_1}^{t_2} = (t_2 - t_1) \times \frac{t_1 \times C_1 + t_2 \times C_2}{2}$$

Logarithmic formula:

$$AUC|_{t_1}^{t_2} = (t_2 - t_1) \times \frac{C_2 - C_1}{\ln\left(\frac{C_2}{C_1}\right)}$$

$$AUMC|_{t_1}^{t_2} = (t_2 - t_1) \times \frac{t_2 \times C_2 - t_1 \times C_1}{\ln\left(\frac{C_2}{C_1}\right)} - (t_2 - t_1)^2 \times \frac{C_2 - C_1}{\ln\left(\frac{C_2}{C_1}\right)^2}$$

3.3.4 Interpolation formula for partial AUC

When a partial AUC is requested at time points not included in the original data set, it is necessary to add an additional measurement point. Those additional time points can be **before** or **after** the last observed data point.

Note that the partial AUC is not computed if a bound of the interval falls before the dosing time.

3.3.4.1 Additional point **before** the last observed data point

Depending on the choice of the “Integral method” setting, this can be done using a linear or log formula to find the added concentration C^* at requested time t^* , given that the previous and following measurements are C_1 at t_1 and C_2 at t_2 .

Linear interpolation formula:

$$C^* = C_1 + \left| \frac{t^* - t_1}{t_2 - t_1} \right| \times (C_2 - C_1)$$

Logarithmic interpolation formula:

$$C^* = \exp\left(\ln(C_1) + \left| \frac{t^* - t_1}{t_2 - t_1} \right| \times (\ln(C_2) - \ln(C_1))\right)$$

If the logarithmic interpolation rule fails in an interval because C_1 or C_2 are null or negative, then the linear interpolation rule is used for that interval.

3.3.4.2 Additional point **after** the last observed data point

If λ_z is not estimable, the partial area will not be calculated. Otherwise, λ_z is used to calculate the additional concentration C^* :

$$C^* = \exp(\text{Lambda}_z\text{intercept} - \lambda_z \times t)$$

3.3.5 Calculating steady-state parameters after each dose

Starting with version **2024R1**, steady state parameters can be calculated for each profile without the dataset requiring the steady state information, meaning that the interdose-interval and SS columns are no longer necessary. To calculate a steady-state parameter (e.g AUC_TAU), the user must check the NCA setting “Interdose interval for single dose profiles” and define a value for the interdose interval tau:

project_Theo_extravasc_SD.plx [demo] * - PKanalix - 2024R1

Project Settings Export Help

Data Tasks Plots

CHECK λ_z RUN

NCA

CA

Non compartmental analysis ▾

NON-COMPARTMENTAL ANALYSIS BIOEQUIVALENCE RUN

Sparse NCA

Settings

Calculations NCA

Administration type

Intravenous Extravascular

Integral method Linear trapezoidal linear

BLQ method before Tmax zero

BLQ method after Tmax Missing

Partial AUC time

Interdose interval for single dose profiles 72

Parameters NCA - BE

Aliases Hide unused

NCA 19 BE 3 log 3

Custom Parameters +

Parameter	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
AUC			
AUC_PerCentExtrap_obs	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
AUC_PerCentExtrap_pred	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
AUC_TAU	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
AUC_TAU_D	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
AUC_TAU_PerCentExtrap	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Single dose parameters are always calculated, irrespective of the presence or absence of an interdose interval column in the dataset or whether the checkbox “Interdose interval for single dose profiles” is checked or not.

Steady-state parameters are calculated for all individuals if the checkbox “Interdose interval for single dose profiles” is checked (and a value of tau is defined). They are also calculated for individuals having a positive interdose interval is defined in the dataset or if the profile (subject or occasion) contains several doses. Depending on the dataset, you may have some profiles with steady-state parameters and some without (appearing as NaN in the results).

Non compartmental analysis results per individual

id	PERIOD	AUC _{0-inf} (h·mg·L ⁻¹)	AUC _{tau} (h·mg·L ⁻¹)	CL _{ss} /F (L·h ⁻¹)	CL/F (L·h ⁻¹)	C _{last} (mg·L ⁻¹)	C _{max} (mg·L ⁻¹)
1	1	255.8943	NaN	NaN	3.1263	4.33	12.55
1	2	284.7535	NaN	NaN	2.8094	3.98	17.14
2	1	387.1152	314.445	2.5442	2.0666	5.88	21
2	2	359.2933	265.385	3.0145	2.2266	6.4	13.52
3	1	271.8842	237.685	3.3658	2.9424	3.74	17.39
3	2	328.0435	242.205	3.303	2.4387	5.86	12.9
4	1	357.2314	291.335	2.746	2.2394	5.35	19.78
4	2	400.0165	319.82	2.5014	1.9999	7.1	17.45
5	1	378.2316	289.02	2.768	2.1151	6.8	16.47
5	2	465.4561	343.55	2.3286	1.7187	7.29	20.91

Records per page: 10 / 24

Some parameters have identical names but are computed using different formulas, contingent upon whether they pertain to a single dose profile (SD) or a multiple dose profile (SS):

Name	Formula/Description – SD	Formula/Description – SS
C ₀	Concentration at dosing time. If profile doesn't contain obs at dosing time: <i>Extravascular or Infusion</i> : C ₀ = 0. For <i>IV bolus</i> : log-linear regression of first two data points to back-extrapolate C ₀ .	Minimum observed during the dose interval.
C _{max}	Maximum observed concentration, occurring at T _{max} . If not unique, then the first maximum is used.	Maximum observed concentration between dose time and dose time + TAU.
C _{max_D}	C _{max} /Dose	C _{max} (based on SS)/Dose
T _{max}	Time of maximum observed concentration; entire curve is considered.	T _{max} corresponds to points collected during a dosing interval.

Name	Formula/Description – SD	Formula/Description – SS
MRTINF_obs	<i>Intravascular:</i> $MRTINF_obs = AUMCINF_obs / AUCINF_obs - TI/2$; $TI = \hat{\text{infusion duration}}$ <i>Extravascular:</i> $MRTINF_obs = AUMCINF_obs / AUCINF_obs \rightarrow AUMCINF_obs$ & $AUCINF_obs$ based on $Clast_obs$.	Mean Residence Time extrapolated to infinity using predicted $Clast$, calculated using AUC_TAU .
MRTINF_pred	Same formulas as above but based on $AUMCINF_pred$ & $AUCINF_pred$ based on $Clast_pred$.	
Vss_obs	$Vss_obs = MRTINF_obs * Cl_obs$ with $MRTINF_obs$ for SD profiles	$Vss_obs = MRTINF_obs * Cl_obs$ with $MRTINF_obs$ for SS profiles
Vss_pred	$Vss_pred = MRTINF_pred * Cl_pred$ with $MRTINF_pred$ for SD profiles	$Vss_pred = MRTINF_pred * Cl_pred$ with $MRTINF_pred$ for SS profiles

These parameters are distinguished by the postfix “_SS” in the list of parameters and in the results table. This extension is also echoed in the aliases by the postfix “, SS”.

Typically, parameters that share the same name are calculated differently based on whether the “Interdose interval for single dose profiles” checkbox is selected. However, there’s one exception: parameter C_0 . In cases where both single dose and multiple dose profiles occur together, the order of profiles influences C_0 ’s calculation. If the first profile is a single dose, followed by either more single dose profiles or multiple dose profiles, and the checkbox is enabled, C_0 for the first occasion follows the single dose formula, while subsequent C_0 ’s follow the steady-state formula.

3.3.6 Ratios for NCA parameters

Starting with PKAnalix version 2024R1 and above, ratios of NCA metrics for each individual along occasions can now be calculated. In the dedicated section “Ratios NCA” in the NCA tasks tab, ratios can be defined by clicking on the plus button. This opens a window, allowing you to specify the ratio.

The ratio is calculated for each individual, using the different occasions (i.e., profiles). When only one occasion corresponds to the modality selected for “ref” and “test”, the ratio is simply the ratio of the two values. If there are subjects who have multiple occasions corresponding to the modality selected for “ref” and “test”, the arithmetic mean of the values for this modality is calculated first, then the ratio is calculated.

If there are subjects without a parameter value for one of the test or comparison modalities, no ratio can be calculated for this parameter. Consequently, the ration is NaN for that subject.

3.4 Parameters

The following page describes all the parameters computed in the non compartmental analysis.

3.4.1 Parameters related to λz

Name	PKPARAMCD CDISC	PKPARAM CDISC	UNITS	DESCRIPTION
Rsq	R2	R Squared	unitless	Goodness of fit statistic for the terminal (log-linear) phase between the linear regression and the data
Rsq_adjusted	R2ADJ	R Squared Adjusted	unitless	Goodness of fit statistic for the terminal elimination phase, adjusted for the number of points used in the estimation of λz
Corr_XY	CORRXY	Correlation Between TimeX and Log ConcY	unitless	Correlation between time (X) and log concentration (Y) for the points used in the estimation of λz
No_points_lambda_z	LAMZNPT	Number of Points for Lambda z	unitless	Number of points considered in the λz regression
Lambda_z	LAMZ	Lambda z	1/time	First order rate constant associated with the terminal (log-linear) portion of the curve. Estimated by linear regression of time vs. log concentration
Lambda_z_lower	LAMZLL	Lambda z Lower Limit	time	Lower limit on time for values to be included in the λz calculation
Lambda_z_upper	LAMZUL	Lambda z Upper Limit	time	Upper limit on time for values to be included in the λz calculation
HL_Lambda_z	LAMZHL	Half-Life Lambda z	time	Terminal half-life = $\ln(2)/\text{Lambda}_z$

Name	PKPARAM CDISC	PKPARAM CDISC	UNITS	DESCRIPTION
Lambda_z_intercept	-	-	unitless	Intercept found during the regression for (λ_z), i.e. value of the regression (in log-scale) at time 0, i.e. the regression writes $\log(\text{Concentration}) = -\lambda_z t + \text{intercept}$
Span	-	-	unitless	Ratio between the sampling interval of the measurements used for the λ_z and the terminal half-life $= (\lambda_{z_upper} - \lambda_{z_lower}) * \lambda_z / \ln(2)$

3.4.2 Parameters related to plasma/blood measurements

Name	PKPARAM CDISC	PKPARAM CDISC	UNITS	DESCRIPTION
Tlag	TLAG	Time Until First Nonzero Conc	time	Tlag is the time prior to the first measurable (non-zero) concentration. Tlag is 0 if the first observation after the last dose is not 0 or LOQ. The value is set to 0 for non extravascular input.
T0			time	Time of the dose
Dose			amount	Amount of the dose
N_Samples	-	-	unitless	Number of samples in the individuals.

Name	PKPARMCD CDISC	PKPARM CDISC	UNITS	DESCRIPTION
C0	C0	Initial Conc	amount/ volume	If a PK profile does not contain an observation at dose time (C0), the following value is added <i>Extravascular and Infusion data.</i> For single dose data, a concentration of zero. For steady-state, the minimum observed during the dose interval. <i>IV Bolus data.</i> Log-linear regression of first two data points to back-extrapolate C0.
Tmax	TMAX	Time of CMAX	time	Time of maximum observed concentration. – For non-steady-state data, the entire curve is considered. – For steady-state data, Tmax corresponds to points collected during a dosing interval. If the maximum observed concentration is not unique, then the first maximum is used.
Cmax	CMAX	Max Conc	amount/ volume	Maximum observed concentration, occurring at Tmax. If not unique, then the first maximum is used.
Cmax_D	CMAXD	Max Conc Norm by Dose	1/volume	Maximum observed concentration divided by dose. $Cmax_D = Cmax/Dose$
Tlast	TLST	Time of Last Nonzero Conc	time	Last time point with measurable concentration
Clast	CLST	Last Nonzero Conc	amount/ volume	Concentration of last time point with measurable concentration
AUClast	AUCLST	AUC to Last Nonzero Conc	time·amount/ volume	Area under the curve from the time of dosing to the last measurable positive concentration. The calculation depends on the Integral method setting.

Name	PKPARAM CDISC	PKPARAM CDISC	UNITS	DESCRIPTION
AUClast_D	AUCLSTD	AUC to Last Nonzero Conc Norm by Dose	time/volume	Area under the curve from the time of dosing to the last measurable concentration divided by the dose. $AUClast_D = AUClast/Dose$
AUMClast	AUMCLST	AUMC to Last Nonzero Conc	time ² -amount/volume	Area under the moment curve (area under a plot of the product of concentration and time versus time) from the time of dosing to the last measurable concentration.
MRTlast	MRTIVLST	MRT Intravasc to Last Nonzero Conc	time	[if intravascular] Mean residence time from the time of dosing to the time of the last measurable concentration, for a substance administered by intravascular dosing. $MRTlast_iv = AUMClast/AUClast - Tl/2$, where <i>Tl</i> represents infusion duration.
MRTlast	MRTEVLST	MRT Extravasc to Last Nonzero Conc	time	[if extravascular] Mean residence time from the time of dosing to the time of the last measurable concentration for a substance administered by extravascular dosing. $MRTlast_ev = AUMClast/AUClast - Tl/2$, where <i>Tl</i> represents infusion duration.
AUCall	AUCALL	AUC All	time-amount/volume	Area under the curve from the time of dosing to the time of the last observation. If the last concentration is positive $AUClast=AUCall$. Otherwise, AUCall will not be equal to AUClast as it includes the additional area from the last measurable concentration down to zero or negative observations.
AUCINF_obs	AUCIFO	AUC Infinity Obs	time-amount/volume	AUC from Dosing_time extrapolated to infinity, based on the last observed concentration. $AUCINF_obs = AUClast + Clast/Lambda_z$

Name	PKPARAM CDISC	PKPARAM CDISC	UNITS	DESCRIPTION
AUCINF_D_obs	AUCIFOD	AUC Infinity Obs Norm by Dose	time/volume	AUCINF_obs divided by dose $AUCINF_D_obs = AUCINF_obs / Dose$
AUC_PerCentExtrap_obs	AUCPEO	AUC %Extrapolation Obs	%	Percentage of AUCINF_obs due to extrapolation from Tlast to infinity. $AUC_ \%Extrap_obs = 100 * (1 - AUClast / AUCINF_obs)$
AUC_PerCentBack_Ext_obs	AUCPBEO	AUC %Back Extrapolation Obs	%	Applies only for intravascular bolus dosing. the percentage of AUCINF_obs that was due to back extrapolation to estimate C(0).
AUMCINF_obs	AUMCIFO	AUMC Infinity Obs	time ² -amount/volume	Area under the first moment curve to infinity using observed Clast $AUMCINF_obs = AUMClast + (Clast / Lambda_z) * (Tlast + 1.0 / Lambda_z)$
AUMC_PerCentExtrap_obs	AUMCPEO	AUMC % Extrapolation Obs	%	Extrapolated (% or total) area under the first moment curve to infinity using observed Clast $AUMC_ \%Extrap_obs = 100 * (1 - AUMClast / AUMCINF_obs)$
MRTINF_obs	MRTIVIFO	MRT Intravasc Infinity Obs	time	[if intravascular] Mean Residence Time extrapolated to infinity for a substance administered by intravascular dosing using observed Clast $MRTINF_obs_iv = AUMCINF_obs / AUCINF_obs - Tl/2$, where <i>Tl</i> represents infusion duration.
MRTINF_obs	MRTEVIFO	MRT Extravasc Infinity Obs	time	[if extravascular] Mean Residence Time extrapolated to infinity for a substance administered by extravascular dosing using observed Clast $MRTINF_obs_ev = AUMCINF_obs / AUCINF_obs$

Name	PKPARMCD CDISC	PKPARM CDISC	UNITS	DESCRIPTION
Vz_F_obs	VZFO	Vz Obs by F	volume	[if extravascular] Volume of distribution associated with the terminal phase divided by F (bioavailability) $Vz_F_obs = Dose/Lambda_z/AUCINF_obs$
Cl_F_obs	CLFO	Total CL Obs by F	volume/time	[if extravascular] Clearance over F (based on observed Clast) $Cl_F_obs = Dose/AUCINF_obs$
Vz_obs	VZO	Vz Obs	volume	[if intravascular] Volume of distribution associated with the terminal phase $Vz_obs = Dose/Lambda_z/AUCINF_obs$
Cl_obs	CLO	Total CL Obs	volume/time	[if intravascular] Clearance (based on observed Clast) $Cl_obs = Dose/AUCINF_obs$
Vss_obs	VSSO	Vol Dist Steady State Obs	volume	[if intravascular] An estimate of the volume of distribution at steady state based last observed concentration. $Vss_obs = MRTINF_obs * Cl_obs$
Clast_pred	-	-	amount/ volume	$Clast_pred = exp(Lambda_z_intercept - Lambda_z * Tlast)$ The values alpha (corresponding to the y-intercept obtained when calculating λz) and lambda_z are those values found during the regression for λz
AUCINF_pred	AUCIFP	AUC Infinity Pred	time·amount/ volume	Area under the curve from the dose time extrapolated to infinity, based on the last predicted concentration, i.e., concentration at the final observation time estimated using the linear regression performed to estimate λz . $AUCINF_pred = AUClast + Clast_pred/Lambda_z$

Name	PKPARAM CDISC	PKPARAM CDISC	UNITS	DESCRIPTION
AUCINF_D_pred	AUCIFPD	AUC Infinity Pred Norm by Dose	time/volume	AUCINF_pred divided by dose = $AUCINF_pred/Dose$
AUC_PerCentExtrap_pred	AUCPEP	AUC %Extrapolation Pred	%	Percentage of AUCINF_pred due to extrapolation from Tlast to infinity $AUC_ \%Extrap_pred = 100*(1 - AUClast / AUCINF_pred)$
AUC_PerCentBack_Ext_pred	AUCPBEP	AUC %Back Extrapolation Pred	%	Applies only for intravascular bolus dosing. The percentage of AUCINF_pred that was due to back extrapolation to estimate C(0).
AUMCINF_pred	AUMCIFP	AUMC Infinity Pred	time ² -amount/volume	Area under the first moment curve to infinity using predicted Clast $AUMCINF_pred = AUMClast + (Clast_pred/Lambda_z)*(Tlast+1/Lambda_z)$
AUMC_PerCentExtrap_pred	AUMCPEP	AUMC % Extrapolation Pred	%	Extrapolated (% or total) area under the first moment curve to infinity using predicted Clast $AUMC_ \%Extrap_pred = 100*(1 - AUMClast / AUMCINF_pred)$
MRTINF_pred	MRTIVIFP	MRT Intravasc Infinity Pred	time	[if intravascular] Mean Residence Time extrapolated to infinity for a substance administered by intravascular dosing using predicted Clast
MRTINF_pred	MRTEVIFP	MRT Extravasc Infinity Pred	time	[if extravascular] Mean Residence Time extrapolated to infinity for a substance administered by extravascular dosing using predicted Clast
Vz_F_pred	VZFP	Vz Pred by F	volume	[if extravascular] Volume of distribution associated with the terminal phase divided by F (bioavailability) $= Dose/Lambda_z/AUCINF_pred$
Cl_F_pred	CLFP	Total CL Pred by F	volume/time	[if extravascular] Clearance over F (using predicted Clast) $Cl_F_pred = Dose/AUCINF_pred$

Name	PKPARAMCD CDISC	PKPARAM CDISC	UNITS	DESCRIPTION
Vz_pred	VZP	Vz Pred	volume	[if intravascular] Volume of distribution associated with the terminal phase $Vz_pred = Dose/Lambda_z/AUCINF_pred$
Cl_pred	CLP	Total CL Pred	volume/time	[if intravascular] Clearance (using predicted Clast) $= Dose/AUCINF_pred$
Vss_pred	VSSP	Vol Dist Steady State Pred	volume	[if intravascular] An estimate of the volume of distribution at steady state based on the last predicted concentration. $Vss_pred = MRTINF_pred*Cl_pred$
AUC_lower_upper	AUCINT	AUC from T1 to T2	time-amount/volume	AUC from T1 to T2 (partial AUC)
AUC_lower_upper_D	AUCINTD	AUC from T1 to T2 Norm by Dose	time/volume	AUC from T1 to T2 (partial AUC) divided by Dose
CAVG_lower_upper	CAVGINT	Average Conc from T1 to T2	amount/volume	Average concentration from T1 to T2

3.4.3 Parameters related to plasma/blood measurements specific to steady state dosing regimen

In the case of repeated doses, dedicated parameters are used to define the steady state parameters and some specific formula should be considered for the clearance and the volume for example. Notice that all the calculation dedicated to the area under the first moment curve (AUMC) are not relevant.

Name	PKPARAMCD CDISC	PKPARAM CDISC	UNITS	DESCRIPTION
Tau	-		time	The (assumed equal) dosing interval for steady-state data.

Name	PKPARAM CDISC	PKPARAM CDISC	UNITS	DESCRIPTION
Ctau	CTAU	Conc Trough	amount/ volume	Concentration at end of dosing interval. <i>If the observed concentration does not exist, the value is interpolated. If it cannot be interpolated, it is extrapolated using lambda_z. If lambda_z has not been computed, it is extrapolated as the last observed value.</i>
Ctrough	CTROUGH	Conc Trough	amount/ volume	Concentration at end of dosing interval. <i>If the observed concentration does not exist, the value is NaN.</i>
AUC_TAU	AUCTAU	AUC Over Dosing Interval	time·amount/ volume	The area under the curve (AUC) for the defined interval between doses (TAU). The calculation depends on the Integral method setting.
AUC_TAU_D	AUCTAUD	AUC Over Dosing Interval Norm by Dose	time/volume	The area under the curve (AUC) for the defined interval between doses (TAU) divided by the dose. $AUC_TAU_D = AUC_TAU/Dose$
AUC_TAU_PerCentExtrap	-	-	%	Percentage of AUC due to extrapolation in steady state. $AUC_TAU_ \%Extrap = 100 * (AUC [Tlast, tau] \text{ if } Tlast \leq \tau) / AUC_TAU;$
AUMC_TAU	AUMCTAU	AUMC Over Dosing Interval	time ² ·amount/ volume	The area under the first moment curve (AUMC) for the defined interval between doses (TAU).
Vz_F	VZFTAU	Vz for Dose Int by F	volume	[if extravascular] The volume of distribution associated with the terminal slope following extravascular administration divided by the fraction of dose absorbed, calculated using AUC_TAU. $Vz_F = Dose/Lambda_z / AUC_TAU$

Name	PKPARAM CDISC	PKPARAM CDISC	UNITS	DESCRIPTION
Vz	VZTAU	Vz for Dose Int	volume	[if intravascular] The volume of distribution associated with the terminal slope following intravascular administration, calculated using AUC_TAU. $Vz = Dose/Lambda_z/AUC_TAU$
CLss_F	CLFTAU	Total CL by F for Dose Int	volume/time	[if extravascular] The total body clearance for extravascular administration divided by the fraction of dose absorbed, calculated using AUC_TAU . $CLss_F = Dose/AUC_TAU$
CLss	CLTAU	Total CL for Dose Int	volume/time	[if intravascular] The total body clearance for intravascular administration, calculated using AUC_TAU. $CLss = Dose/AUC_TAU$
Cavg	CAVG	Average Concentration	amount/ volume	AUCTAU divided by Tau. $Cavg = AUC_TAU /Tau$
FluctuationPercent	FLUCP	Fluctuation%	%	The difference between Cmin and Cmax standardized to Cavg, between dose time and Tau. $Fluctuation\% = 100.0 * (Cmax - Cmin) / Cavg$
FluctuationPercent_Tau	-	-	%	The difference between Ctau and Cmax standardized to Cavg, between dose time and Tau. $Fluctuation\%_Tau = 100.0 * (Cmax - Ctau) / Cavg$
Accumulation_Index	AILAMZ	Accumulation Index using Lambda z	unitless	Theoretical accumulation ratio: Predicted accumulation ratio for area under the curve (AUC) calculated using the Lambda z estimated from single dose data. $Accumulation_Index = 1.0 / (1.0 - exp(-Lambda_z * Tau))$

Name	PKPARAMCD CDISC	PKPARAM CDISC	UNITS	DESCRIPTION
Swing	-	-	unitless	The degree of fluctuation over one dosing interval at steady state $Swing = (C_{max} - C_{min})/C_{min}$
Swing_Tau	-	-	unitless	$Swing_Tau = (C_{max} - C_{tau})/C_{tau}$
Tmin	TMIN	Time of CMIN observation.	time	Time of minimum concentration sampled during a dosing interval.
Cmin	CMIN	Min Conc	amount/ volume	Minimum observed concentration between dose time and dose time + Tau.
Cmax	CMAX	Max Conc	amount/ volume	Maximum observed concentration between dose time and dose time + Tau.
MRTINF_obs	MRTIVIFO or MRTEVIFO	MRT Intravasc Infinity Obs or MRT Extravasc Infinity Obs	time	Mean Residence Time extrapolated to infinity using predicted Clast, calculated using AUC_TAU .

3.4.4 Parameters related to urine measurements

Name	PKPARAMCD CDISC	PKPARAM CDISC	UNITS	DESCRIPTION
T0			time	Time of the last administered dose (assumed to be zero unless otherwise specified).
Dose	-	-	amount	Amount of the dose
N_Samples	-	-	unitless	Number of samples in the individuals.
Tlag	TLAG	Time Until First Nonzero Conc	time	Midpoint prior to the first measurable (non-zero) rate.

Name	PKPARAM CDISC	PKPARAM CDISC	UNITS	DESCRIPTION
Tmax_Rate	ERTMAX	Midpoint of Interval of Maximum ER	time	Midpoint of collection interval associated with the maximum observed excretion rate.
Max_Rate	ERMAX	Max Excretion Rate	amount/time	Maximum observed excretion rate.
Mid_Pt_last	ERTLST	Midpoint of Interval of Last Nonzero ER	time	Midpoint of collection interval associated with Rate_last.
Rate_last	ERLST	Last Meas Excretion Rate	amount/time	Last measurable (positive) rate.
AURC_last	AURCLST	AURC to Last Nonzero Rate	amount	Area under the urinary excretion rate curve from time 0 to the last measurable rate.
AURC_last_D	AURCLSTD	AURC to Last Nonzero Rate Norm by Dose	unitless	The area under the urinary excretion rate curve (AURC) from time zero to the last measurable rate, divided by the dose.
Vol_UR	VOLPK	Sum of Urine Vol	volume	Sum of Urine Volumes
Amount_Recovered			amount	Cumulative amount eliminated.
Percent_Recovered			%	100*Amount_Recovered/Dose
AURC_all	AURCALL	AURC All	amount	Area under the urinary excretion rate curve from time 0 to the last rate. This equals AURC_last if the last rate is measurable.
AURC_INF_obs	AURCIFO	AURC Infinity Obs	amount	Area under the urinary excretion rate curve extrapolated to infinity, based on the last observed excretion rate.
AURC_PerCentExtrap_obs	AURCPEO	AURC % Extrapolation Obs	%	Percent of AURC_INF_obs that is extrapolated

Name	PKPARAM CDISC	PKPARAM CDISC	UNITS	DESCRIPTION
AURC_INF_pred	AURCIFP	AURC Infinity Pred	amount	Area under the urinary excretion rate curve extrapolated to infinity, based on the last predicted excretion rate.
AURC_PerCentExtrap_pred	AURCPEP	AURC % Extrapolation Pred	%	Percent of AURC_INF_pred that is extrapolated
AURC_lower_upper	AURCINT	AURC from T1 to T2 (partial AUC)	amount	The area under the urinary excretion rate curve (AURC) over the interval from T1 to T2.
AURC_lower_upper_D	AURCINTD	AURC from T1 to T2 Norm by Dose	unitless	The area under the urinary excretion rate curve (AURC) over the interval from T1 to T2 divided by Dose
Rate_last_pred	-	-	amount/time	The values alpha and Lambda_z are those values found during the regression for lambda_z

3.4.5 Parameters related to sparse NCA

Name	UNITS	DESCRIPTION
SE_Cmax	amount/volume	Sample standard error of the concentration values at Tmax (standard deviation of the y-values at time Tmax divided by the square root of the number of observations at Tmax)

Name	UNITS	DESCRIPTION
SE_AUClast	time·amount/volume	$SE_{AUClast} = \sqrt{\text{Var}(\hat{AUC})} = \sqrt{\sum_{i=0}^m \frac{w_i^2 s_i^2}{n_i} + 2 \sum_{i < j} \frac{w_i w_j n_{ij} s_{ij}}{n_i n_j}}$ $\text{with } w_i = \begin{cases} \frac{t_1 - t_0}{2}, & \text{if } i=0 \\ \frac{t_{i+1} - t_{i-1}}{2}, & \text{if } i=1, \dots, m \\ \frac{t_m - t_{m-1}}{2}, & \text{if } i=m \end{cases}$ and $s_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^{n_{ij}} \frac{(C_{ik} - \bar{C}_i)(C_{jk} - \bar{C}_j)}{(n_{ij} - 1) + (1 - \frac{n_{ij}}{n_i})(1 - \frac{n_{ij}}{n_j})}$ where: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • m = time of last measurable (positive) mean concentration • n_{ij} = number of individuals sampled at both times i and j • n_i = number of individuals sampled at time i • s_i^2 = sample variance of concentrations at time i • s_{ij} = sample covariance between concentrations C_{ik} and C_{jk} for all individuals k that are sampled at both times i and j
SE_AUCall	time·amount/volume	Same as SE_AUClast with m = last observation time
SE_Max_Rate	amount/time	Same as SE_Cmax with excretion rates
SE_AURC_last	amount	Same as SE_AUClast with excretion rates
SE_AURC_all	amount	Same as SE_AUCall with excretion rates

SE_AUClast, SE_AUCall, SE_AURC_last, SE_AURC_all are available only if the integral method is “linear trapezoidal linear” or “linear trapezoidal linear/log” (because the formula is based on linear calculation of AUC).

3.4.6 Parameter renamings

Starting from the 2023 version of MonolixSuite, default parameter names used in results tables and plots in the graphical user interface and reports do not match the names present in the Name column of the tables above. The names that are used can be customized in the NCA parameters renamings section of Preferences. The section contains two columns:

- **Parameter** – this column contains parameter names from the tables above,

- **Alias** – this column contains parameter names used in the interface and the values in cells can be changed.

NCA parameters renamings

Re-run or reload the project for changes to take effect

Parameter	Alias
AUCINF_D_obs	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 2px; display: flex; align-items: center; gap: 5px;"> ↶ ↷ X₂ X² CF ✖ ✔ </div> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 2px; margin-top: 2px;"> AUC_{0-inf}/Dose</div>
AUCINF_D_pred	AUC _{0-inf, pred} /Dose
AUCINF_obs	AUC _{0-inf}
AUCINF_pred	AUC _{0-inf, pred}
AUC_Int	AUC _{t0-t1}
AUC_Int_D	AUC _{t0-t1} /Dose
AUC_Dose/Body_Weight	% AUC

The Alias column is prefilled with default aliases. By clicking on an alias, PKanalix allows users to input characters. There are several options present, when in the input mode:

- Undo – reverse the last action,
- Redo – redo an undone action,
- Subscript X_2 – formats selected text and subsequently entered characters as subscript,
- Superscript X^2 – formats selected text and subsequently entered characters as superscript,
- CF **CF** – clears formatting of a selected text,
- Cancel – cancels the changes and restores the alias,
- Accept – accepts the changes (changes can be accepted by clicking anywhere in the interface as well).

3.5 Parameters summary

This pages provides the information on the statistics used for the summary of the individual parameters for both NCA tasks and CA tasks. All the statistics are calculated with respect to the NOBS individuals where the parameter has a value. For example, in the NCA task, the parameter λz might not be possible to compute. Thus, the value for these subjects will be missing and not taken into account in the statistics.

- **MIN**: Minimum of the parameter over the NOBS individuals
- **Q1**: First quartile of the parameter over the NOBS individuals
- **MEDIAN**: Median of the parameter over the NOBS individuals
- **Q3**: Third quartile of the parameter over the NOBS individuals
- **MAX**: Maximum of the parameter over the NOBS individuals
- **MEAN**: Arithmetic mean of the parameter over the NOBS individuals
- **SD**: Standard deviation of the parameter over the NOBS individuals
- **SE**: Standard error of the parameter over the NOBS individuals
- **CV**: Coefficient of variation of the parameter over the NOBS individuals
- **NTOT**: Total number of individuals
- **NOBS**: Number of individuals with a valid value
- **NMISS**: Number of individuals with no valid value
- **GEOMEAN**: Geometric mean of the parameter over the NOBS individuals
- **GEOSD**: Geometric standard deviation of the parameter over the NOBS individuals
- **GEOCV**: Geometric coefficient of variation over the NOBS individuals
- **HARMMEAN**: Harmonic mean of the parameter over the NOBS individuals

3.6 Custom parameters

Starting with version 2024R1, it is possible to define custom NCA parameters as formulas of existing parameters and covariates. User-defined NCA parameters can be defined via preferences or for a specific project:

1. Definition via preferences: user-defined NCA parameters defined via “Preferences” can be used in any project with which they are compatible (if parameters that are used in the formula can be calculated in a project and if covariates used in the formula are present in the data set used in a project).
2. Project-specific definition: user-defined NCA parameters defined in a project will be used just in that particular project. However, when or after creating a project-specific NCA parameter, user can send the parameter to preferences.

3.6.1 Parameter definition

To define a parameter in preferences, click Settings > Preferences and define parameters in the section “NCA custom parameters”. To define project-specific parameters, click on the button “+” in the list of parameters in the Tasks tab.

	NCA	BE	log
Custom Parameters	13	0	0
AUC	None		
AUC_PerCentExtrap_obs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
AUC_PerCentExtrap_pred	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

In both cases, a parameter can be defined using the following information:

New custom NCA parameters

Name

Alias

X_y X^y CF

Formula

Units

TIME
AMOUNT
VOLUME
CONC
GRADING

X^2 X^{-1} .

Add to preferences

CANCEL

OK

The fields are the following:

1. **Name:** the name of the parameter used in the list of parameters in the Tasks tab. This field can only start with a letter and cannot contain any special characters except “_”.
2. **Alias:** parameter name used in results tables and plots in the graphical user interface and reports. Can contain special characters and can be formatted with subscripts and superscripts.
3. **Formula:** mathematical expression used to define the parameter. The expression can contain NCA parameters calculated by PKanalix (list) and names of the covariates present in the data set. Operators +, -, *, /, and ^ can be used in the definition, as well as parentheses and functions abs, sqrt, exp, log, log10, logit, invlogit, sin, cos, tan, asin, acos, atan, sinh, cosh, tanh, floor, ceil, factorial, min, max, atan2, rem (definitions of those functions can be found here). Partial AUC parameters can also be used in formulas, with slightly changed names—when the start or end time contains a decimal point, it needs to be replaced by “d” (e.g., AUC_0_0.5 becomes AUC_0_0d5), and if they are in a scientific notation, a minus sign needs to be replaced by “m” (e.g., AUC_0_2e-10 becomes AUC_0_2em10).
When entering parameter names, an autocomplete panel helps users enter the name. If

covariates are present in the project, instead of entering their names directly, users can click on the buttons available above the formula input field.

4. **Units:** contains the unit definition for the parameter. If a unit of a custom parameter depends on a project, generalized strings TIME, AMOUNT, VOLUME, CONC and GRADING can be used for time, amount, volume, concentration and dose normalization units defined in the project (these strings can be entered using buttons above the field). Superscripts can be used with the syntax " x " where x is a positive or a negative number (superscripts 2 and $^{-1}$ are also available via buttons). Different units can be concatenated using the character "." (also available via a button). When defining a project-specific parameter, preview of the unit will be shown (the preview will replace the generalized strings with the units defined in the project). Note that "/" sign cannot be used. To define for instance "mg/L", use "mg.L $^{-1}$ ".

If a definition is project-specific, there is an additional checkbox "Add to preferences", which if checked will save the parameter in preferences, in addition to adding it to the project.

3.6.2 Custom parameter usage

The parameters defined via preferences appear in the dropdown of the parameters section of the Tasks tab if they are compatible with the current project (i.e., if they use parameters that can be calculated for the current project and covariates present in the data set). They can be added to the project by clicking on them in the dropdown.

If selected, they will appear in the parameter list and calculated if the checkbox in the NCA column is checked. Next to the custom parameter names in the parameters section, there are three options available:

1. **Save in preferences:** available when a parameter is available in the project, but is not saved in the preferences (for example, the parameter was created in the project and the “Add to preferences” checkbox was not checked, or the project was shared with a user that does not have the custom parameter in the preferences).
2. **Edit:** edits the name, alias, formula and units of a parameter. If a parameter is saved in the preferences, users will be asked if they want to update the parameter only in the current project, or also in the preferences.
3. **Delete:** removes the parameter from the project (but not from the preferences, if the parameter is saved in preferences).

3.7 Settings

The following page describes all the settings for parameter calculations.

3.7.1 Calculations

▼
Calculations
NCA

Administration type

Intravenous
 Extravascular

Integral method Linear trapezoidal linear ▼

BLQ method before Tmax zero ▼

BLQ method after Tmax Missing ▼

Partial AUC time

min
max

0

72

+

Interdose interval for single dose profiles 72 ▼

These settings correspond to the settings affecting the calculation of NCA parameters.

- **Administration type:** *Intravenous* or *Extravascular*. This defines the drug type of administration. IV bolus and IV infusions should be set as “intravenous.”
- **Integral method:** Method for AUC and AUMC calculation and interpolation. **Trapezoidal** defines the formula to calculate the AUC and **Interpolation** defines the formula to add an additional point in case of partial AUC with a time point not originally present in the data set. See the Calculation rules for details on the formulas.
 - *Linear Trapezoidal Linear* (Linear trapezoidal, linear interpolation): For AUC calculation, linear formula. For interpolation, linear formula.
 - *Linear Log Trapezoidal* (Linear/log trapezoidal, linear/log interpolation): For AUC, linear before C_{max} and log after C_{max}. For interpolation, linear before C_{max} and log after.
 - *Linear Up Log Down* (LinUpLogDown trapezoidal, LinUpLogDown interpolation): For AUC, linear if concentration is going up or is stable, log if going down. For interpolation, linear if concentration is going up or is stable, log if going down.
 - *Linear Trapezoidal linear/log* (Linear trapezoidal, linear/log interpolation): For AUC, linear formula. For interpolation, linear before C_{max}, log after C_{max}. If several C_{max}, the first one is used.

For all methods, if an observation value is less than or equal to zero, the calculation uses the linear trapezoidal or interpolation rule for that point. Similarly, if adjacent observations values are equal to each other, the calculation uses the linear trapezoidal or interpolation rule.

- **Partial AUC time:** Define a partial AUC for a specific time interval. It is possible to define several partial AUC intervals, applicable to all individuals.
- **BLQ before T_{max}:** In case of BLQ measurements, this corresponds to the method by which the BLQ data before T_{max} should be replaced. Possible methods are “missing”, “LOQ”, “LOQ/2” or “0” (default value is 0).
- **BLQ after T_{max}:** In case of BLQ measurements, this corresponds to the method by which the BLQ data after T_{max} should be replaced. Possible methods are “missing”, “LOQ”, “LOQ/2” or “0” (default value is LOQ/2).
- **Interdose interval for single dose profiles:** To compute steady-state parameters for single dose profiles, a value for τ can be manually specified. The input value may be a double, under the condition that it is strictly positive. By default, the last time point of the initial single dose profile is set. This option is available with PKanalix version 2024R1 and above.
- **Obs. ID to use:** When several OBS ID are present in the data, an additional option to choose which Obs ID to use for perform the NCA analysis appears.

Calculations *NCA*

Administration type

Intravenous
 Extravascular

Obs. ID to use
 METABOLITE
 PARENT

Integral method Linear trapezoidal linear ▾

Partial AUC time

Interdose interval for single dose profiles 168 ▴ ▾

3.7.2 Settings affecting the λ_z calculation

These settings affect the calculation of λ_z . See the Check lambda_z page.

- **Main rule** for the λ_z estimation. It corresponds to the rule to define the measurements used for the λ_z calculation. Possible rules are “R2”, “interval”, “points” or “adjustedR2” (called Best Fit in Winonlin) (default value is “adjustedR2”). See the calculation rules for more details.
- In case of “R2” or “adjustedR2” rule, the user can define the *maximum number of points* and/or *minimum time for the λ_z estimation*. This will constrain which points are tested for inclusion.
 - In case of “Interval” rule, the user has the possibility to define the *time interval* to consider.
 - In case of “Points” rule, the user has the possibility to define the *number of points* to consider.
- **Weighting method** used for the regression that estimates λ_z . Possible methods are “Y”, “Y2” or “uniform” (default value is “uniform”).

3.7.3 Selecting NCA parameters to compute

Parameters <i>NCA-BE</i>			
		Aliases	Hide unused
<input type="text"/>		NCA 21 All None	BE 3 log 3
Custom Parameters	<input style="border: none; background-color: #ccc; padding: 2px 5px;" type="button" value="+"/>		
AUC			
AUC_0_72	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
AUC_0_72_D	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
AUC_PerCentExtrap_obs	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
AUC_PerCentExtrap_pred	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
AUC_TAU	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
AUC_TAU_D	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
AUC_TAU_PerCentExtrap	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
AUCall	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

The NCA parameters to compute can be checked in the “NCA” column. The list of NCA parameters is ordered by types of parameters. Custom NCA parameters can be defined using the “+” button.

It is recommended to always compute `Rsq_adjusted`, `No_points_lambda_z`, `Lambda_z` and `Lambda_z_intercept` as these parameters are necessary to display the terminal slope and information box in the NCA fit plot.

The list of parameters computed by default when starting a new PKanalix project can be defined in `Settings > Preferences`.

3.7.4 Acceptance criteria

▼ Acceptance criteria *NCA*

<input type="checkbox"/>	Adjusted R2	0.98	▲ ▼
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	% extrapolated AUC	20	▲ ▼
<input type="checkbox"/>	Span	3	▲ ▼

These settings corresponds to the settings affecting the acceptance criteria. When acceptance criteria are defined, flags indicating if the condition is met or not are added to the output result table. Statistics in the summary table can be calculated using only individuals who satisfy one or several acceptance criteria. The filtering option is available directly in the Summary sub-tab of the NCA results.

- **Adjusted R2:** This corresponds to the threshold of the adjusted R2 for the estimation of λz . If set, it will set the value of Flag_Rsq_adjusted: if $Rsq_adjusted > threshold$, then $Flag_Rsq_adjusted=1$. The default value is .98.
- **% extrapolated AUC:** This corresponds to the threshold of the percentage of the total predicted AUC (or AURC for urine models) due to the extrapolation to infinity after the last measurement. If set, it will set the value of Flag_AUC_%Extrap_pred: if $AUC_ \%Extrap_pred < threshold$, then $Flag_AUC_ \%Extrap_pred=1$. The default value is 20%.
- **Span:** This corresponds to the threshold of the span. The span corresponds to the ratio of the sampling interval length for the λz calculation and the half-life. If set, it will set the value of Flag_Span: if $Span > threshold$, then $Flag_Span=1$. The default value is 3.

3.7.5 Ratios for NCA parameters

Starting with PKanalix version 2024R1 and above, ratios of NCA metrics for each individual across occasions can now be calculated. In the dedicated section "Ratios NCA" in the NCA tasks tab, ratios can be defined by clicking on the plus sign (highlighted in red). This opens a window, allowing you to specify the ratio.

Ratios can only be defined if there are occasions in the dataset.

The screenshot shows the PKanalix software interface with a 'New NCA ratio' dialog box open. The dialog box contains the following fields and options:

- Name:** Ratio_AUCINF_obs_2vs1
- Ratio variable:** OCC
- Reference value:** 1
- Test value:** 2
- Parameter:** AUCINF_obs

The formula preview at the bottom of the dialog box shows: $f(x) = \text{AUCINF_obs}(OCC:2) / \text{AUCINF_obs}(OCC:1)$. The dialog box also includes 'CANCEL' and 'CREATE' buttons.

The definition comprises:

- **Name:** name for the new ratio parameter
- **Ratio variable:** Selection of the stratification variable. Variables tagged in the dataset either as occasion or as categorical variable are available for selection.
- **Reference value:** Selection of the reference modality (specific modality in occasion or covariate variable) to be used as denominator.
- **Test value:** Selection of test modality (specific modality in occasion or covariate variable) to be used as numerator.
- **Parameter:** Selection of the NCA parameter

The formula for the specified ratio is displayed in the blue panel beneath the definition options.

Ratios can only be created using parameters that have been selected in the "NCA" column of the main parameter selection section.

For calculation details, see the Calculations rules page.

The computed parameter ratios are presented in two distinct results tables within the results tab. One table provides an individual listing, while the other offers a summary table with basic descriptive statistical metrics.

3.8 Sparse NCA

Sparse data are data that have few observations per individual or per occasion, and therefore may not be sufficient to reliably estimate individual pharmacokinetic parameters. Sparse data require specific handling in an NCA analysis to get the most informative metrics from the data. PKanalix offers a dedicated mode to perform NCA analysis on sparse data, based on the calculation of mean profiles and standard errors of NCA parameters.

3.8.1 Set up of sparse NCA

To specify a sparse dataset, you need to go to the NCA tab and select the “Sparse NCA” toggle below the NCA task. This will enable the calculation of mean profiles based on the individual data.

Sparse NCA is available for plasma and urine datasets.

3.8.1.1 Stratified sparse data

Calculations

Administration type

Intravenous
 Extravascular

Sparse data stratification DGROUP, STUDY ▼

Select: All | None
 DGROUP
 STUDY

linear ▼

Integral method

Partial AUC time

Interdose interval for single dose profiles 504.53 ▲▼

With “Sparse data stratification” in the NCA calculation settings, you can select one or more stratification covariates to group the data by categories. For example, if you have a categorical covariate indicating the treatment group, you can select it to calculate a mean profile for each treatment group. The stratification covariates must be of type “categorical covariate” or “stratification categorical covariate” in the dataset tagging.

3.8.1.2 BLQ samples

If you have censored data, you can also click on the “BLQ method” button to select a censoring rule to handle the below limit of quantification (BLQ) samples.

The available rules are:

- Single rule: Replace all BLQ samples by [missing/zero/LOQ/(LOQ/2)]

Rule for handling BLQ samples in mean profiles

Single rule ▾

Replace individual BLQ samples by **zero** ▾

- **Two rules based on absolute number of BLQ samples:**

if $N_{BLQ} \geq [\text{number}]$:

- then:
 - either replace BLQ samples by [missing/zero/LOQ/(LOQ/2)]
 - or replace the mean sample by [missing/zero/LOQ/(LOQ/2)]
- else replace BLQ samples by [missing/zero/LOQ/(LOQ/2)]

Rule for handling BLQ samples in mean profiles

Two rules based on absolute number of BLQ samples ▾

If $N_{BLQ} \geq 1$ then replace **Mean sample** ▾ by **Missing** ▾

else replace individual BLQ samples by **zero** ▾

- **Two rules based on fraction of total number of samples:**

if $N_{BLQ} \geq [\text{number}] \% \text{ of } N_{tot}$

- then:
 - either replace BLQ samples by [missing/zero/LOQ/(LOQ/2)]
 - or replace the mean sample by [missing/zero/LOQ/(LOQ/2)]
- else replace BLQ samples by [missing/zero/LOQ/(LOQ/2)]

Rule for handling BLQ samples in mean profiles

Two rules based on fraction of total number of samples ▾

If $N_{BLQ} \geq 33$ % of N_{TOT} then replace Mean sample ▾ by Missing ▾
 else replace individual BLQ samples by zero ▾

In addition, it is possible to check if the mean is below a LOQ value and add special handling in this case:

- Check that mean samples stay above the LOQ:
 If the mean sample is below [number] (LOQ usually), replace the mean sample by [missing/zero/LOQ/(LOQ/2)] before Tmax and [missing/zero/LOQ/(LOQ/2)] after Tmax.

Comparing mean samples to the LOQ

Check that mean samples stay above the LOQ

LOQ 2

If meanSample < LOQ then replace by zero ▾ before Tmax

Missing ▾ after Tmax

Calculation details

- “Replace individual BLQ samples by [missing/zero/LOQ/(LOQ/2)]” = replace each individual censored sample by Missing (i.e., ignore the sample), LOQ (from the dataset for each sample) or LOQ/2.
- “If $N_{BLQ} > 33\%$ of N_{TOT} ”: this condition is checked at each nominal time point and for each stratification group: N_{TOT} is the total number of samples corresponding to that nominal time point and that stratification group, and N_{BLQ} is the number of censored samples among them.

- “Replace mean sample by [missing/zero/LOQ/(LOQ/2)]”: replace the mean sample by missing (i.e., ignore the mean sample in the mean profile), LOQ (largest LOQ found in the dataset among the censored samples involved in this mean sample), or LOQ/2.
- “Check that mean samples stay above the LOQ”: here the LOQ is the global LOQ value entered by the user in these settings.
- “If meanSample < LOQ then replace by LOQ”: here the LOQ in the condition and the replacement is the global LOQ value entered by the user in these settings.

3.8.2 Calculation of mean profiles

When “Sparse NCA” is selected, one or several mean profiles are calculated:

- One mean profile per stratification group is calculated (one group for each combination of modalities from the covariates selected in “Sparse stratification”).
- The mean profile is calculated by taking the mean concentration value across all subject-occasions for each unique time value for plasma data, or the mean rate value for each unique midpoint for urine data.
- If a column of type NOMINAL TIME is selected, the mean profiles are calculated based on nominal time, otherwise they are calculated based on TIME.
- If the individuals used to calculate a mean profile have different dosing regimens (different dosing times or dosing amounts), only the dosing regimen from the first individual is kept for the mean profile.
- For urine data, if the individuals used to calculate a mean profile have different volumes for some interval, only the volumes from the first individual are kept for the mean profile.
- Subject-occasions are handled independently for the calculation of mean profiles.

The mean profiles do not appear in the Observed data plot, but they appear in Check lambda_z and NCA individual fits.

3.8.3 NCA parameters specific to sparse data

All the usual NCA parameters are available in the list of parameters to compute, and in addition the following NCA parameters are available:

- For plasma data: SE_Cmax, SE_AUClast, SE_AUCall
- For urine data: SE_Max_Rate, SE_AURC_last, SE_AURC_all

See the page on NCA parameters for more details.

These parameters are not selected by default. SE_AUClast, SE_AUCall, SE_AURC_last, SE_AURC_all are available only if the integral method is “linear trapezoidal linear” or “linear trapezoidal linear/log” (because the formula is based on linear calculation of AUC).

3.8.4 Sparse NCA results

The results of the NCA analysis on sparse data are displayed in the Results and Plots tabs. The table below summarizes the results available in sparse NCA mode.

Result	Based on
Tables of NCA parameters	mean profiles
Table of concentrations	individual data + mean profiles
NCA data plot	individual data + mean profiles
NCA individual fits	mean profiles
Other NCA plots	disabled

The parameters calculated on the mean profiles appear in the table of individual NCA parameters and the NCA summary table.

Individual estimates

Non compartmental analysis results per individual

id	AUC _{0-inf} /Dose	AUC _{0-inf, pred} /Dose	AUC _{0-inf}	AUC _{0-inf, pred}	AUC _{0-tlast}	CL	C _{last}	C _{max} /Dose	Flag_λ _z _Rule
mean_profile_DGROUP\$0.1_STUDY\$STUDY1	24049.3204	24648.4462	50190.9317	51441.3073	25814.9143	0.00004158	347.1484	308.1668	:
mean_profile_DGROUP\$10_STUDY\$STUDY1	33462.4159	33445.5777	7144225.8024	7140630.8399	6732197.352	0.00002988	2129.3275	240.3415	:
mean_profile_DGROUP\$10_STUDY\$STUDY2	34474.4625	34395.65	7308586.0516	7291877.796	4583798.2061	0.00002901	15990.1	175.938	:
mean_profile_DGROUP\$1_STUDY\$STUDY1	41062.9513	40920.649	754326.4154	751712.3226	574040.6011	0.00002435	1552.6745	309.7016	:
mean_profile_DGROUP\$1_STUDY\$STUDY2	51921.061	50286.0378	1122533.3378	1087184.1365	793409.7	0.00001926	2575.8463	427.605	:

The table of concentrations displays both the individual concentration data, and the mean profiles on the “mean” rows. The table is stratified by the covariates selected for sparse data.

The NCA data plot is a new plot that shows the mean profiles and the individual data points on the same plot, with different colors for the different mean profiles.

The NCA individual fits plot shows the mean profiles and the NCA parameters calculated from them. The other NCA plots are disabled because they are not relevant for sparse data analysis.

4 Bioequivalence

4.1 Overview

After running the “NCA” task to calculate the NCA PK parameters, the “Bioequivalence” task can be launched to compare the calculated PK parameters between two groups, usually one receiving the “test” formulation and the other the “reference” formulation.

4.1.1 Bioequivalence task

The “Bioequivalence” task is available if at least one categorical covariate column has been tagged in the “Data” tab. The “Bioequivalence” task can only be run after running the “NCA” task. It can be run by clicking on the “Bioequivalence” task button (highlighted in pink below) or by selecting it as part of the scenario (checkbox in the upper right corner of the “Bioequivalence” button) and clicking the “Run” button. The parameters to be included in the bioequivalence analysis are selected in the section “Parameters to compute / BE” (highlighted in orange), where the user can also indicate if the parameter should be log-transformed or not. The fixed effects included in the linear model can be chosen in the section “Bioequivalence design” (highlighted in blue).

The screenshot displays the PKanalix software interface for a "Non compartmental analysis". The "Bioequivalence" task button is highlighted in pink. The "Settings" section is expanded, showing the following configuration:

- Calculations:** Administration type: Extravascular; Integral method: Linear up log down; Partial AUC time: ; BLQ method before Tmax: zero; BLQ method after Tmax: Missing.
- Parameters to compute:** Parameters: R_{sq}, Corr_XY, No_points_lambda_z, Lambda_z_lower, Lambda_z_upper, HL_Lambda_z, Span, TO, Tlag, C₀, T_{max}, C_{max_D}, T_{last}, C_{last}; Computed parameters: R_{sq_adjusted}, Lambda_z, Lambda_z_intercept, C_{max}, AUC_{last}, AUC_{INF_obs}, AUC_PerCentExtrap_obs, V_{z_F_obs}, Cl_{F_obs}; BE: ; log-transform: (for R_{sq}, AUC_{last}, AUC_{INF_obs}, V_{z_F_obs}).
- Acceptance criteria:** Adjusted R²: 0.95; % extrapolated AUC: 20; Span: .
- Bioequivalence design:** Study design: parallel; Factors in linear model (fixed effects): formulation (FORM), reference, reference; additional: None available.

4.1.2 Bioequivalence results

The results of the bioequivalence analysis are shown three tables in the “Results” tab, in the “BE” subtab.

4.1.2.1 Confidence intervals

The table of confidence intervals is the key bioequivalence table that determines if the two formulations are equivalent or not. For each parameter selected for bioequivalence analysis, the following information is given:

- the adjusted means (i.e., least square means) for each formulation,
- the number of individuals for each formulation,
- the formulation difference (see calculation rules) and the corresponding confidence interval,
- the formulation ratio (see calculation rules) and the corresponding confidence interval.

If N formulations are present in the dataset, N-1 tables are shown.

project_crossover_bioequivalence.ppx [demo] - PKanalix - 2021R1

Project Settings Export Help

Data Tasks **Results** Plots

ANOVA COEFFICIENTS OF VARIATION **CONFIDENCE INTERVALS**

NCA

BE

Confidence intervals

Least square means, point estimates and confidence intervals for the ratio

test

PARAMETER	TEST		REF		BIOEQUIVALENCE						
	AdjustedMean	N	AdjustedMean	N	Difference	CIRawLower	CIRawUpper	Ratio	CILower	CIUpper	BE
AUCINF_obs (h·mg·L ⁻¹)	138.768	18	146.606	18	-0.0481	-0.09293	-0.008265	95.3041	91.1257	99.6741	✓
AUClast (h·mg·L ⁻¹)	136.892	18	149.918	18	-0.08019	-0.09879	-0.00446	95.1111	90.8654	99.855	✓
Cmax (mg·L ⁻¹)	7.0218	18	8.7637	18	-0.2216	-0.3084	-0.1348	80.1238	78.4602	87.3919	✗

4.1.2.2 Coefficient of variation

For each parameter selected for bioequivalence analysis, this table reports the standard deviation of the residuals and the intra-subject coefficient of variation (CV).

4.1.2.3 ANOVA

This table reports the analysis of variance (ANOVA) for the factors included in the linear model for each parameter selected for the bioequivalence analysis. For each factor, the degrees of freedom (DF), sum of squares (SUMSQ), mean squares (MEANSQ), F-value (FVALUE) and p-value (PR(>F)) are reported. A small p-value indicates a significant effect of the corresponding factor.

For the residuals, only the degrees of freedom, sum of squares, and mean squares are reported.

4.1.3 Bioequivalence plots

In the “Plots” tab, several plots are displayed:

- Sequence by period: This plot shows, for each parameter, the mean and standard deviation for each period, sequence and formulation.
- Subject by formulation: This plot shows, for each parameter, the subject-by-formulation interaction and the inter-subject variability.
- Confidence intervals: This plot shows the confidence intervals of the ratio of each parameter.
- NCA individual fits: This plot shows the individual concentration data with one subplot per individual for all periods.

4.1.4 Bioequivalence outputs

After running the Bioequivalence task, the following files are available in the result folder <result folder>/PKanalix/IndividualParameters/be:

- **anova_XXX.txt**: there is one file for each NCA parameter included in the bioequivalence analysis. It contains the ANOVA table with columns ‘Factor’ (factors included in the linear model), ‘Df’ (degrees of freedom), ‘SumSq’ (sum of squares), ‘MeanSq’ (mean squares), ‘FValue’ (F-value), ‘Pr(>F)’ (p-value). For the residuals (last line), the two last columns are empty.
- **confidenceInterval_XXX.txt**: there is one file per non-reference formulation. It contains the confidence interval table with columns ‘Parameter’ (parameter name), ‘AdjustedMeanTest’ (adjusted mean for the test formulation), ‘NTest’ (number of individuals for the test formulation), ‘AdjustedMeanRef’ (adjusted mean for the reference formulation), ‘NRef’ (number of individuals for the ref formulation), ‘Difference’ (formulation difference – see calculation rules), ‘CIRawLower’ (lower confidence interval bound for the difference), ‘CIRawUpper’ (upper confidence interval bound for the difference), ‘Ratio’ (formulation ratio – see calculation rules), ‘CILower’ (lower confidence interval bound for the ratio), ‘CIUpper’ (upper confidence interval bound for the ratio), ‘Bioequivalence’ (1 if the CI for the ratio falls within the BE limits, 0 otherwise)
- **estimatedCoefficients_XXX.txt**: there is one file for each NCA parameter included in the bioequivalence analysis. It contains the estimated coefficient for each category of each factor included in the linear model, as well as the intercept. This information is only available as an output table and is not displayed in the GUI. The table columns are ‘name’ (factor followed by the category), ‘estimate’ (estimated coefficient), ‘se’ (standard error), ‘tValue’ (estimate divided by the SE), and ‘Pr(>|t|)’ (p-value).
- **variationCoef.txt**: This file contains the standard deviation and coefficient of variation for each NCA parameter. Columns are ‘Parameter’, ‘SD’ and ‘CV(%)’

4.2 Calculation rules

4.2.1 Detection of design

PKAnalix detects the design automatically based on the dataset columns. If no OCCASION column is present, the design is detected as “parallel.” On the other hand, if one or several columns have been tagged as OCCASION, the design is detected as “crossover” (repeated or non-repeated). The detected design is displayed in the bioequivalence settings for the user’s information and cannot be changed. Depending on the detected design, the factors selected by default for the linear model are different (see below).

4.2.2 Linear model

The linear model can only include fixed effects, as recommended by the FDA for parallel and non-repeated crossover design (see *Statistical Approaches to Establishing Bioequivalence*, page 10) and by the EMA for parallel, non-repeated crossover and repeated crossover designs (see *Guideline On The Investigation Of Bioequivalence*, page 15). In addition, “id” is automatically considered as nested in “sequence” and no additional nesting can be defined. Interaction terms and random effects are not supported.

According to the regulatory guidelines, the default models are:

- **parallel design:**

$$\log(\text{NCAparam}) \sim \text{FORM}$$

which can also be written as

$$\log(\text{NCAparam}) = \text{intercept} + \beta_{\text{test}} [\text{if FORM=test}] + \varepsilon$$

in the case of two formulations “ref” and “test” with ε as a normal random variable (i.e., the residual error).

- **crossover design:**

$$\log(\text{NCAparam}) \sim \text{SEQ} + \text{ID} + \text{PERIOD} + \text{FORM}$$

which can also be written as

$$\log(\text{NCAparam}) = \text{intercept} + \beta_{\text{test}} [\text{if FORM=test}] + \beta_{\text{period}2} [\text{if PERIOD=2}] + \beta_{\text{seqTR}} [\text{if SEQ=TR}] + \beta_{\text{id}2} [\text{if ID=id2}] + \beta_{\text{id}3} [\text{if ID=id3}] + \dots + \varepsilon$$

in the case of multiple individuals (id1, id2, etc.), two sequences (“RT” and “TR”), two periods (“1” and “2”) and two formulations (“ref” and “test”).

The model parameters are calculated using QR factorization.

The β parameters are the coefficients. They are saved in the output file **estimatedCoefficients_XXX.txt**. The coefficient of interest representing the formulation effect is β_{test} , which is also called the point estimate.

4.2.3 Difference and ratio

In the Results > Confidence intervals table, the column “Difference” corresponds to the point estimate β_{test} (see above). The column “Ratio” depends on the parameter log-transformation choice:

- without log-transformation: $\text{Ratio} = \text{LSM}_{test} / \text{LSM}_{ref} \times 100$ where LSM is the least square mean (also called adjusted mean, see below)
- with log-transformation: $\text{Ratio} = \exp(\beta_{test}) \times 100$

4.2.4 Confidence intervals

The confidence interval is first calculated for both the difference (CI_{diff}) and the ratio (CI_{ratio}).

$$CI_{diff} = \beta_{test} \pm t(1 - \alpha, df) \times SE$$

with β_{test} the point estimate (“Difference” column, see above), $t(1 - \alpha, df)$ the quantiles of a Student t-distribution at the α level and df degrees of freedom, and SE the standard error of the point estimate.

In case of a parallel design with the **Welch-Satterthwaite correction** (see Bioequivalence settings), the formula is the following:

$$CI_{diff} = \beta_{test} \pm t(1 - \alpha, df) \times \sqrt{\frac{S_R^2}{n_R} + \frac{S_T^2}{n_T}}$$

where S_X is the samples standard deviation of the individuals and n_X is the number of individuals having received formulation X . A correction is also applied to the degrees of freedom, which are calculated as:

$$df = \frac{\left(\frac{S_T^2}{n_T} + \frac{S_R^2}{n_R}\right)^2}{\frac{(S_T^2/n_T)^2}{n_T-1} + \frac{(S_R^2/n_R)^2}{n_R-1}}$$

The confidence interval for the ratio is then calculated using the following formula:

- without log-transformation: $CI_{ratio} = (1 + CI_{diff} / \text{LSM}_{ref}) \times 100$ where LSM_{ref} is the least square mean for the reference formulation (see below)
- with log-transformation: $CI_{ratio} = \exp(CI_{diff}) \times 100$

4.2.5 Adjusted means (least square means)

With the model $NCA_{param} \sim SEQ + ID + PERIOD + FORM$, one can calculate the expected value (mathematical expectation) for any value of SEQ, ID, PERIOD and FORM. The **least square mean (LSM)** for the reference represents the expected value for the reference formulation leaving the value for the other factors undefined. To calculate it, we average the model-predicted values across the levels of ID, PERIOD and SEQ.

The weights assigned to each combination of levels depend if the factors are nested or not. A factor A is said nested in factor B if each level of A appears in only one level of B. By design, in crossover bioequivalence studies, ID is nested in SEQUENCE (i.e., each individual belongs to only one sequence). Thus, in PKAnalix, when ID and SEQUENCE are defined as factors in the linear model, **we assume that ID is nested in SEQUENCE when calculating the least square means**. No further nesting is assumed, nor can be specified. Note that the nesting definition only affects the adjusted means and not the point estimate (ratio) and its confidence interval.

4.2.6 Excluded individuals

In the case of a parallel design, individuals for which the NCA parameter cannot be calculated are excluded.

In case of a crossover design, incomplete individuals are excluded. Incomplete individual are those that do not have a value for each period, either because these were no concentration data for this period (period missing in the data set) or because the computed NCA parameter could not be calculated for this period (e.g., because the data were insufficient to calculate the terminal slope). In the case of a **non-repeated crossover design**, whether the individuals with missing data is excluded or not has no impact on the calculation of the point estimate and confidence interval. In the case of a **repeated crossover design** (i.e., when the individuals receive the same formulation multiple times), excluding the individuals for which the NCA parameter for one or more periods is missing has an impact on the point estimate calculation and confidence interval. The common practice is to exclude incomplete individuals (see also the *EMA Guideline On The Investigation Of Bioequivalence*, page 14).

Which individuals are excluded is calculated for each NCA parameter separately, as some individuals may have values for all periods for C_{max} but not AUC_{INF_obs} for instance.

In the Results > Confidence intervals table, the number of individuals "N" does not count the excluded individuals. Thus, in case of a crossover design, the number of individuals contributing to ref and to test is the same. **In the BE plots, only the individuals included in the bioequivalence analysis are shown.**

4.2.7 ANOVA

The sum of squares presented in the ANOVA table of the Results tab are **type-I sequential sum of squares**. In case of an unbalanced design (i.e., different numbers of individuals receiving RT versus TR), the type-I sum of squares depends on the order of the included factors. In PKAnalix, **the enforced order is SEQUENCE + ID + PERIOD + FORMULATION** (+ ADDITIONAL), following the SAS example code

provided by the FDA (see *Statistical Approaches to Establishing Bioequivalence, 2001, Appendix E*) and EMA (see *Questions & Answers: positions on specific questions addressed to the Pharmacokinetics Working Party, 2015, question 8*).

4.2.8 Coefficient of variation

In the Results > Coefficients of variation table, SD corresponds to the standard deviation of the residuals, i.e., to the standard deviation of the normal random variable ε in the linear model $\log(\text{NCAparam}) = \text{intercept} + \beta_{test} [\text{ if FORM=test}] + \varepsilon$ (for the typical model with a parallel design for instance).

The coefficient of variation is then calculated as:

- without log-transformation: $CV = SD/LSM_{ref}$ (where LSM_{ref} is the least square mean for the reference formulation, see above)
- with log-transformation: $CV = 100 \times \sqrt{\exp(SD^2) - 1}$

4.3 Settings

This page describes the settings of the bioequivalence calculations.

4.3.1 Parameters to compute

In the section “Parameters to compute”, the user can move the parameters from the “**Parameters**” column (list of all available parameters) to the “**Computed parameters**” column to select them for the NCA calculations. Among the parameters selected for the NCA calculations, the user can choose which parameters should be included in the bioequivalence analysis by ticking the box in the “**BE**” column. Regulatory guidelines usually recommend to perform the bioequivalence on the log-transformed NCA parameters. This can be set using the toggles in the “**log-transform**” column.

- **BE**: parameters on which to perform the bioequivalence analysis. *Defaults*: Cmax, AUClast, and AUCINF_obs if plasma single-dose, or AUCtau and Cmax if plasma steady-state, or AURC_last and Max_Rate if urine data.
- **log-transform**: whether the bioequivalence should be computed on the log-transformed NCA parameter (toggle on) or on the NCA parameter directly (toggle off). *Default*: log-transform toggle on, except for Tmax.

The screenshot shows the PKanalix software interface for a crossover bioequivalence study. The main window is titled "project_crossover_bioequivalence.ppk [demo] * - PKanalix - 2021R1". The interface includes a menu bar (Project, Settings, Export, Help) and a task bar (Data, Tasks, Plots). The current task is "CHECK\lambda_z" under "Non compartmental analysis".

The "Settings" panel is divided into four sections:

- Calculations:** Administration type (Intravenous, Extravascular), Integral method (Linear up log down), and Partial AUC time.
- Acceptance criteria:** Adjusted R2, % extrapolated AUC, and Span.
- Parameters to compute:** A table of parameters to be calculated, with checkboxes for "BE" and "log-transform". The parameters listed are:

Parameters	Computed parameters	BE	log-transform
Rsq	Lambda_z	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Rsq_adjusted	Lambda_z_intercept	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Corr_XY			
Ne_points_lambda_z	Cmax	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Lambda_z_lower	AUClast	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Lambda_z_upper	AUCINF_obs	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
HL_Lambda_z			
Span			
- Bioequivalence design:** Study design (parallel, crossover) and Factors in linear model (fixed effects) including id, period, formulation, sequence, and additional.

4.3.2 Bioequivalence design

The study design, parallel or crossover (repeated or not), is detected automatically based on the structure of the ID and OCCASION columns of the data set, see the Calculation rules for more details. The user can then select one or several fixed effect factors to be included in the linear model. By default, for a parallel design, only the formulation is included. For a crossover design, the factors ID, PERIOD, FORMULATION and SEQUENCE are included by default, if present in the data set. When both ID and SEQUENCE are given, ID is considered as nested in SEQUENCE. Additional factors can also be added, to be chosen among the (STRATIFICATION) CATEGORICAL and CONTINUOUS COVARIATES columns of the data set. **All factors are considered as fixed effects and random effects are not available. Nesting of ID in SEQUENCE is considered automatically, but further nesting cannot be specified.** Note that the nesting affects the calculation of the adjusted means but not of the bioequivalence ratio.

- **Study design:** parallel or crossover (repeated or not-repeated). Detected automatically based on the structure of the ID and OCCASION columns of the data set (see Calculation rules). Cannot be changed by the user.
- **Factors in the linear model:**
 - **id [if crossover]:** data set column representing the ID of the individuals. *Default:* the column tagged as ID in the data set. This can be set to "none" if the ID should not be used as a factor in the linear model. When a "sequence" column is defined, "id" is considered as nested in "sequence".

- period [if crossover]:** data set column representing the different periods for each individual. *Default:* the first column tagged as OCCASION in the data set. This setting can be set to “none” if the period should not be used as a factor in the linear model.
- formulation:** data set column representing the different groups for which the bioequivalence is calculated, typically the different formulations of the drug products. *Default:* the column with header ‘trt’, ‘treatment’, ‘form’, or ‘formulation’ (case insensitive) if it exists, otherwise first CATEGORICAL COVARIATE column. It is mandatory to include the formulation in the linear model.
 - reference:** among the categories of the categorical covariate selected as formulation, the one considered as the reference. The bioequivalence will be computed for all categories compared to the reference category. *Default:* ‘r’ or ‘ref’ or ‘reference’ (case insensitive), otherwise the category of the first occasion of the first indiv of the data set.
- sequence [if crossover]:** data set column representing the different sequences. *Default:* the column with header ‘seq’, or ‘sequence’ (case insensitive) if it exist, otherwise “none”. This setting can be set to “none” if the sequence should not be used as a factor in the linear model.
- additional:** data set columns tagged as CATEGORICAL or CONTINUOUS covariates, which have not already been selected above, can be added as additional factors in the linear model.

The screenshot shows the PKanalix software interface for a bioequivalence study. The main window is titled "project_crossover_bioequivalence.ppk (demo) * - PKanalix - 2021R1". The interface is divided into several sections:

- Top Bar:** Includes "Project", "Settings", "Export", and "Help" menus. Below this are tabs for "Data", "Tasks", and "Plots".
- Navigation:** A sidebar on the left contains icons for "NCA" and "CA". The main area has buttons for "CHECK λ_z", "RUN", "NCA", "BIOEQUVALENCE", and "RUN".
- Settings Panel:**
 - Calculations:** Administration type (Intravenous, Extravascular), Integral method (Linear up log down), and Partial AUC time.
 - Acceptance criteria:** Adjusted R2, % extrapolated AUC, and Span.
 - Parameters to compute:** A list of parameters (Rsq, Rsq_adjusted, Corr_XY, No_points_lambda_z, Lambda_z_lower, Lambda_z_upper, HL_Lambda_z, Span) and computed parameters (Lambda_z, Lambda_z_intercept, Cmax, AUClast, AUCINF_obs) with checkboxes for BE and log-transform.
 - Bioequivalence design (highlighted in red):** Study design (parallel, crossover), and factors in the linear model (fixed effects) including id, period, formulation, sequence, and additional.

4.3.3 Confidence interval

Several settings are more specific to the calculation of the confidence interval. They can be changed in the pop-up settings window of the Bioequivalence task.

- **Level:** level of the confidence interval. *Default:* 90% confidence interval. This means that there is a 90% probability that the true ratio is included in the calculated confidence interval.
- **Bioequivalence limits:** limits within which the confidence interval should be in order to conclude for bioequivalence. *Default:* [80,125].
- **Degrees of freedom [if parallel design]:** method to calculate the degrees of freedom involved in the confidence interval calculations, either using the residuals (this assumes equal variance between the groups or using the Welch-Satterthwaite formula (this assumes possibly unequal variances). *Default:* Welch-Satterthwaite

The screenshot displays the PKanalix software interface for a project named 'project_parallel_bioequivalence.plx [demo] - PKanalix - 2021R1'. The main window shows the 'Bioequivalence' task settings, with a 'Confidence interval' pop-up window open. The pop-up window contains the following settings:

- Level (%):** 90
- Bioequivalence limits:** 80 to 125
- Degrees of freedom for parallel design:**
 - Residuals (equal variances)
 - Welch-Satterthwaite (unequal variances)

The background interface shows the 'Settings' section for the 'Bioequivalence' task, including options for BLQ methods, acceptance criteria (Adjusted R2, % extrapolated AUC, Span), and bioequivalence design (parallel/crossover, factors in linear model).

5 Compartmental analysis

5.1 Overview of the workflow

One of the main features of PKanalix is parameter estimation using a compartmental analysis framework. It estimates parameters of a compartmental model representing the PK dynamics for each individual using the Nelder-Mead algorithm. Starting with the 2023 version, PKanalix performs an individual model fit for any model with continuous outputs, either selected from the built-in library or written as a custom model.

5.1.1 CA task

To access the compartmental analysis task in PKanalix, in the “Tasks” tab, select the “CA” on the left-hand side, as shown below.

The screenshot displays the PKanalix software interface for a compartmental analysis task. The window title is 'project_extravasacular.plx [demo] * - PKanalix - 2023R1'. The 'Tasks' tab is active, and the 'CA' (Compartmental Analysis) task is selected in the left-hand navigation menu. The main area shows the 'Compartmental analysis' task with a 'COMPARTMENTAL ANALYSIS' button. Below this, the 'Settings' section is visible, divided into two panels:

- Parameters:** This panel contains a table for parameter settings:

	Initial values	Constraint
ka	0.1	positive
V	1	positive
Cl	1	positive
- Calculations:** This panel shows the 'Cost function' as $(Y_{pred} - Y_{obs})^2 / (Y_{pred} + Y_{obs})$. There is also a 'Pooled fit' option, which is currently turned off. The description for 'Pooled fit' is 'Fit with individual parameters or with the same parameters for all individuals'.

This task contains three sub-tabs, listed horizontally under the “Tasks” tab:

- With the first, **MODEL**, you can select a model, e.g., from the PKanalix model library or a custom model, edit it and fit the model outputs to the observations in a dataset. For a complete guide to model definition, look at the CA model page.
- The second, **CHECK INIT.**, shows model predictions obtained with the initial parameter values for each individual together with the data points. It helps to select initial values for model parameters by changing values manually or using the Auto-init function, as explained in the Initialization page.
- The third, **RUN**, contains a button to run the estimation algorithm and options to change the settings for the model and the estimation. The definition of all the settings and their default values is found on the Estimation page.

5.1.2 CA model

In this section, you specify the model. You can edit the selected model directly in the interface. In the right-hand panel, you match observations from the dataset to model outputs, see here for a complete guide.

The screenshot shows the PKanalix software interface. The top menu bar includes 'Project', 'Settings', 'Export', and 'Help'. Below the menu bar, there are tabs for 'Data', 'Tasks', 'Results', and 'Plots'. The 'Tasks' tab is active, and within it, the 'MODEL' sub-tab is selected. The 'Model file' panel on the left shows a text editor with the following content:

```

1 DESCRIPTION:
2 The administration is extravascular with a first order absorption (rate
3 constant ka).
4
5 [LONGITUDINAL]
6 input = {ka, V, Cl}
7
8 PK:
9 ; PK model definition
10 Cc = pkmodel(ka, V, Cl)
11
12 OUTPUT:
13 output = {Cc}
14
  
```

The 'Mapping' panel on the right shows a visual representation of the model. It has two columns: 'Data (Observation ID)' and 'Model'. A horizontal line connects a blue dot labeled 'Conc' in the 'Data' column to a blue dot labeled 'Cc' in the 'Model' column.

You can use custom models in PKanalix—select BROWSE and load a text file containing the model. There are also built-in libraries (PK, PK double absorption, TMDD, parent–metabolite, etc.), to simplify the modeling process. Note that models can include multiple outputs. Models used in all MonolixSuite

applications are written in the mlxtran language. Note: For PKanalix versions prior to 2023, only classical PK models, from the PK model library, were available.

5.1.3 CA check init.

The “Check init.” tab helps initialize model parameters. It shows the model predictions obtained with the specified initial model parameter values and the individual designs (taking into account doses and regressors). Each sub plot shows model predictions for one individual with overlaid individual data points. You can use auto initialization to find initial values by clicking the Run button in the Auto-init panel on the right, which uses a pooled fit approach. This feature is very useful to find good initial values, as explained here.

5.1.4 CA results

When you run the CA task, Pkanalix automatically shows the results in the “Results” tab, see the CA Results page for a complete guide.

The screenshot shows the PKanalix software interface. The main window displays the 'Individual estimates' section under the 'Results' tab. The interface includes a menu bar (Project, Settings, Export, Help), a sidebar with 'NCA' and 'CA' options, and a main content area with tabs for 'SUMMARY', 'INDIV. ESTIM.', and 'COST'. The 'INDIV. ESTIM.' tab is active, showing a table of compartmental analysis results per individual. The table has columns for 'id', 'Cost', 'ka', 'V', and 'Cl'. Below the table, there are options for 'Records per page' (set to 10) and a pagination control showing 'Page 1 of 2'.

id	Cost	ka	V	Cl
101	0.32	0.098	0.38	0.6
102	0.48	0.091	0.66	0.94
103	0.22	0.076	0.27	0.58
104	0.5	0.095	0.72	0.72
105	0.23	0.1	0.72	1.16
106	0.24	0.12	1.79	1.31
107	0.37	0.065	0.94	0.6
108	0.43	0.092	0.95	0.86
109	0.43	0.086	0.96	1.12
1010	0.23	0.095	0.44	0.65

There are three main sections:

- SUMMARY contains statistics on compartmental analysis results and summary calculation (described here). You can split or filter this table by covariates present in a dataset.
- INDIV. ESTIM contains compartmental analysis results for each individual.
- COST contains cost function information.

All the computed parameters depend on the chosen model. To copy a table and paste in a Word or Excel document, click on the icon on the top-left corner of a table.

5.1.5 CA plots

After running the CA task, several plots associated to the individual parameters are automatically generated and displayed in the "Plots" tab.

- Individual fits: displays model fit for each individual on a separate plot.
- Correlation between CA parameters: displays scatter plots for each pair of parameters to identify correlations between parameters.
- Distribution of the CA parameters: displays the empirical distribution of the parameters to analyze their distribution across individuals.
- CA parameters w.r.t. covariates: displays the individual parameters as a function of the covariates to identify correlations between the individual parameters and the covariates.
- Observations vs predictions displays observations from a dataset versus model predictions computed from the individual parameters to detect misspecifications in the model.

5.1.6 CA outputs

After running the CA task, the following files are automatically generated in the project result folder/IndividualParameters/ca :

- **summary.txt** contains the summary of the CA parameters calculation, in a format easily readable by a human (but not easily machine parsable).
- **cost.txt** contains information about total cost and information criteria for the current model.
- **calIndividualParametersSummary.txt** contains the summary of the CA parameters in a machine-friendly format useful for post-processing:
 - The first column corresponds to the name of the parameters.
 - The other columns correspond to the several elements describing the summary of the parameters (as explained here).
- **calIndividualParameters.txt** contains the CA parameters for each subject-occasion along with the covariates.
 - The first line corresponds to the name of the parameters.
 - The other lines correspond to the value of the parameters.

You can open the files **calIndividualParametersSummary.txt** and **calIndividualParameters.txt** in R using the following command

```
read.table("/path/to/file.txt", sep = ",", header = TRUE)
```

Note: the separator used is the one defined in the user preferences. We use “,” here as it is the default.

5.1.7 CA export to Monolix/Simulx

Using the top menu “Export”, a PKanalix project (dataset information, model, estimated parameters) can be exported to Monolix or Simulx for further analysis, see the Export to Monolix/Simulx page for a complete guide.

The screenshot shows the PKanalix interface with the 'Results' tab selected. A table of individual estimates is displayed, and an 'Export configuration' dialog box is open over it. The dialog box has a 'General' section with the following options:

- Target software:
 - Monolix
 - Simulx
- Generated files next to project

Buttons for 'CLOSE' and 'EXPORT' are at the bottom of the dialog. The background table shows the following data:

id	Cost	ka	V	Cl	WEIGHT	SEX
1	0.82	0.081	0.09	0.44	70.65	F
2	0.68	0.17	0.47	0.5	67.52	F
3	0.37	0.044	0.35	0.91	65.31	M
4	0.32	0.11	0.73	0.97	66.67	M
5	0.22	0.13	1.02	0.61	68.13	F
6	0.53	0.063	0.39	0.36	71.19	F
7	0.64	0.11	1.11	0.54	71.81	F
8	0.25	0.13	2.29	1.75	76.76	M
9	0.27	0.09	0.53	0.36	64.49	F
10	0.29	0.071	0.48	0.32	64.74	F

- Monolix for population modeling and further model development and diagnosis.
- Simulx to use a CA model and estimated individual parameters for simulations of new scenarios, e.g., new dosing regimens.

Note: For PKanalix versions prior to 2023, only export to Monolix is available.

5.2 CA model

The first step to run the compartmental analysis task in PKanalix is selecting a model. Models in PKanalix are .txt files and are selected in the Model sub-tab of the Tasks tab. You can:

- Load a custom model specified in a file by clicking the BROWSE button.
- Load a model from the PKanalix library by clicking the LOAD FROM LIBRARY button.
- Write a new model from scratch in the mlxtran language by clicking the NEW MODEL button.

Note: In PKanalix versions before 2023, only models from the PK library are available.

After loading a model, PKanalix switches automatically from the Model sub-tab to the Check Init. sub-tab to initialize parameters. To view the model file, go back to the Model sub-tab. The left side shows the model file content. With the EDIT MODEL button, you can edit the model, save, and apply it to the current project. For more details, see the custom model documentation page. The right side shows the mapping between the data set observations ids and the model outputs. For more details, see the mapping in Monolix documentation page. This feature is the same in PKanalix and Monolix.

The screenshot shows the PKanalix software interface. The main window is titled "project_customPKPD.pbx [demo] - PKanalix - 2023R1". The interface is divided into several sections:

- Top Menu:** Project, Settings, Export, Help.
- Left Sidebar:** Home, Data, Tasks (selected), Plots. Below this are icons for NCA and CA.
- Model File Section:**
 - Buttons: BROWSE..., LOAD FROM LIBRARY, EDIT MODEL.
 - Model file path: C:/Users/mtwar/txoft/pkanalix/pkanalix2023R1/demos/1_basic_examples/model/sigmoid_absorption_model.txt
 - Code content:


```

7 [LONGITUDINAL]
8 input = {Tk0, ka, V, Cl, R0, kout, Imax, IC50}
9
10 PK:
11 compartment(cmt = 1, amount = Ad)
12 compartment(cmt = 2, volume = V, concentration = Cc)
13 absorption(cmt = 1, Tk0, adm = 1)
14 transfer(from = 1, to = 2, kt = ka)
15 elimination(cmt = 2, k = Cl/V)
16
17 EQUATION:
18 ;===== PD part of the model
19
20 ; Initial values
21 R_0 = R0
22
23 ; Parameter transformation
24 kin = R0 * kout
25
26 ; ODE for the response
27 ddt_R = kin * (1 - Imax * Cc / (Cc + IC50)) - kout * R
28
29 OUTPUT:
30 output = {Cc, R}
          
```
- Mapping Section:**
 - Columns: Data (Observation ID), Model.
 - Mapping: y1 (Data) is connected to Cc (Model). y2 (Data) is connected to R (Model).

5.2.1 Saving model information in the PKanalix project file

In PKanalix, a model file is a text file (.txt) and its name is displayed at the top of the Model sub-tab. If a model is from the PKanalix library, then the file name contains a prefix "lib:". For custom models, the full path to the file is displayed. It is possible to select whether the model file path in the project file uses an absolute or relative path in Settings > Preferences > Options.

Note: when using custom models, be careful if you move a model file. If it was used in a PKanalix project, then you will no longer be able to re-open this project. You will see an error "Missing model file at 'original_path_to_modelFile/model_filename.txt'." To avoid this issue, go to Settings > Project Settings and select "Save the dataset and the model beside the project."

5.2.2 Libraries of models

PKanalix provides libraries of **ready-to-use models** for compartmental analysis. This simplifies the use of the software by decreasing the necessity of coding. You can pick models from the library and use them directly or use them as a starting point for your custom model and edit them. They are accessible in the Model sub-tab of the CA task by clicking the button **“LOAD FROM LIBRARY.”**

The library is organized into several categories:

- **PK model library:** includes standard compartmental pharmacokinetic models. It is possible to select different administration routes (oral, bolus, infusion, first-order absorption, zero-order absorption, with or without a log), different numbers of compartments (1, 2 or 3 compartments), and different types of elimination (linear or Michaelis-Menten). The PK library models can be used with single- or multiple-dose data, and with two different types of administration in the same data set (oral and bolus, for instance).
- **PD model library:** includes pharmacodynamic models with direct response (such as Emax and I_{max} with different baseline options) and turnover response (inhibition or stimulation of production or degradation). These models are PD models only and the drug concentration over time must be defined in the dataset and passed as a regressor.
- **PK/PD model library:** provides all standard combinations of the above pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic models.
- **PK double absorption model library:** includes double absorption models. They take into account all combinations of absorption types and delays for two absorption processes. The absorption processes can be specified as simultaneous or sequential and with a pre-defined or independent order.
- **Parent-Metabolite model library:** includes models describing parent drug and one metabolite, with or without the first pass effect, uni and bidirectional transformation, and up to three compartments for parent and metabolite.
- **Target-mediated drug disposition (TMDD) model library:** includes a large number of TMDD models corresponding to different approximations, different administration routes, different parametrizations, and different outputs.

- **Tumor growth inhibition (TGI) library:** includes a wide range of models for tumour growth (TG) and tumour growth inhibition (TGI) that are available in the literature. Models correspond to different hypotheses for tumor or treatment dynamics.

The screenshot displays the PKAnalix software interface for the TGI library. The top navigation bar includes 'Project', 'Settings', 'Export', and 'Help'. Below this, there are tabs for 'Data', 'Tasks', and 'Plots'. The main interface is divided into a left sidebar and a central panel. The sidebar lists categories: PK, PKPD, PK Double Absorption, Parent Metabolite, TMDD, and TGI. The central panel features a filter bar with tabs for 'Administration', 'Delay', 'Absorption', 'Distribution', 'Elimination', and 'Parametrization'. Below the filter bar, a search bar and a 'CLEAR FILTERS' button are visible. The main area shows a list of model entries, each with a set of parameter icons (e.g., Tlag, ka, V, Cl) and a model name (e.g., oral1_1cpt_TlagkaVCl). A 'CANCEL' button is located at the bottom right of the list.

In each library, available models are displayed in the bottom panel as a list. With the top filtering panel, you can easily selected a model based on its characteristics, such as administration type, number of compartments, or elimination mechanism. To select a model, click on its corresponding line. The model can be previewed by clicking the file icon to the right of the model name. When all filters are used, only one model is shown. After selecting a model, it is loaded and displayed in the Model tab.

The screenshot shows the PKanalix software interface. The top menu bar includes 'Project', 'Settings', 'Export', and 'Help'. Below the menu bar, there are tabs for 'Data', 'Tasks', and 'Plots'. The 'Tasks' tab is active, and within it, the 'MODEL' sub-tab is selected. The main window is divided into two panels. The left panel, titled 'Model file', displays the filename 'lib:orall_lcpt_TlagkavCL.txt' in a text box. Below this are three buttons: 'BROWSE...', 'LOAD FROM LIBRARY', and 'EDIT MODEL'. The main area of the left panel contains a code editor with the following text:

```

1 DESCRIPTION:
2 The administration is extravascular with a first order absorption (rate constant ka)
3 with a lag time (Tlag).
4 The PK model has one compartment (volume V) and a linear elimination (clearance Cl).
5
6 [LONGITUDINAL]
7 input = {Tlag, ka, V, Cl}
8
9 PK:
10 Cc = pkmodel(Tlag, ka, V, Cl)
11
12 OUTPUT:
13 output = {Cc}
14

```

The right panel, titled 'Mapping', shows a diagram with two columns: 'Data (Observation ID)' and 'Model'. A horizontal line connects a blue dot labeled 'DV' in the Data column to a blue dot labeled 'Cc' in the Model column.

The model filename is displayed at the top of the left panel and has a prefix “lib” to distinguish it from custom models. Mapping of model outputs, important when there is more than one observation id, can be done with the right panel.

5.2.3 Custom models

With the compartmental analysis task in PKanalix, you can write your own custom model in the mxtran language. To load an existing model, click on BROWSE in the Model sub-tab, and to write a new model from scratch, click NEW MODEL button.

Custom models are only available with PKanalix versions 2023 and later.

You can also first choose a model from the library and then edit it directly in the Model tab afterwards by clicking on the button **EDIT MODEL**, which opens the interactive editor.

In the editing mode, there are several features that help with model writing in mlxtran. These include syntax coloring, detecting syntax errors, and zooming the editing window. In addition, autocomplete offers function and keyword suggestions for the mlxtran language and variable names.

You can save a new model and automatically apply it to a current project by clicking **SAVE & APPLY**. To save a model with a different name, use **SAVE AS & APPLY** or **SAVE AS**. Note that models from the library cannot be overwritten.

5.2.3.1 Merging two library models

In MonolixSuite application there is a dedicated application to write and edit models: **mlxEditor**. This functionality is integrated directly in the interface, as described above, but you can also use **mlxEditor** independently of PKanalix. The following video shows an example how to merge two models using **mlxEditor**.

5.2.3.2 Writing a model from scratch

The following video describes how to write a custom model. Note that this video uses the old version of **mlxEditor**, but the functionality is the same.

5.2.3.3 Understanding error messages

The error messages generated when syntax errors occur in the model are informative and help to easily correct the model. This video explains the most common error messages.

5.2.4 External model editor

mlxEditor is an application to write, edit and organise models written in the **mlxtran** language. It has **mlxtran** dedicated features, such as syntax coloring, autocompletion and verification, and is integrated with Monolix, Simulx and PKanalix for easier model development.


```

1 DESCRIPTION:
2
3 [LONGITUDINAL]
4 input={alpha_S, RF, RE, epsilon, PSAb, Nmax}
5
6 EQUATION:
7 odeType=stiff
8   stiff
9 p=20
10 delta=0.23
11 g=0.0000001
12
13 alpha_R=RF*alpha_S
14 d=RE*RF*alpha_S
15
16
17 PSA_0=PSAb
18 S_0=delta*PSAb/p
19 R_0=g/max(d-RF*(g+d),1e-9)*delta*PSAb/p
20
21
22 if t>0
23 alpha_S=alpha_S*(1-epsilon)
24 else
25 alpha_S=alpha_S
26 end
  
```

Main functions:

- Writing models in the mlxtran language.
- Editing user custom models and models from the Monolix library, which is integrated with the application.
- Editing models directly in the GUI: Monolix (tab: Structural model), Simulx (Tab: Definition/Model) and PKanalix (tab: Model, CA).
- Managing models in work sessions.

Main features:

- Mlxtran syntax coloring for different model elements, such as block definition, parameters, macros.
- Autocompletion for variables, mlxtran keywords, functions (tab-key accepts a selected item).
- Find and Find&Replace.
- Zoom in/out to increase/decrease the font size.
- Syntax check to verify if the mlxtran code is correct and a model can be loaded in Monolix or Simulx.

In the mlxEditor application:

- Access to the Monolix libraries,

- Monolix and Simulx syntax check,
- Save and export to Simulx,
- Sessions: collections of models that can be reloaded automatically.

In the GUI edit mode:

- Several saving options: Save & apply – saves the model under the same name (overwrites the previous model) and applies it to the current project, Save as & apply – saves the model under a different name and applies it to the current project, Save as – saves the model under a different name without applying to the current project.
- Zoom applied in the edition model remains in the “Tab: Structural model” after closing the edition mode.

5.3 CA task

The following page describes how compartmental analysis estimates individual parameters of a model defined in the MODEL tab. Three elements impact this estimation:

- Initialization of model parameters and the constraints on their values
- Cost function used in the optimization algorithm
- Estimation algorithm

The screenshot shows the PKanalix software interface. The title bar indicates the project is 'project_censoring.plx [demo]' and the version is '2023R1'. The main menu includes 'Project', 'Settings', 'Export', and 'Help'. The left sidebar has 'Data', 'Tasks', 'Results', and 'Plots' tabs, with 'Tasks' selected. Below the sidebar, there are icons for 'NCA' and 'CA'. The main window has three tabs: 'MODEL', 'CHECK INIT.', and 'RUN', with 'RUN' selected. The 'Compartmental analysis' section is active, featuring a large 'COMPARTMENTAL ANALYSIS' button. Below this is the 'Settings' section, which is divided into two panels: 'Parameters' and 'Calculations'.

Parameters

	Initial values	Constraint
ka	1	positive
V	1	positive
Cl	0.5	positive

Calculations

Cost function
 $(Y_{pred} - Y_{obs})^2 / (Y_{pred} + Y_{obs})$

Method for BLQ
 Missing

Pooled fit
 Fit with individual parameters or with the same parameters for all individuals

5.3.1 Initialization of parameters

Parameters of the model you defined in the MODEL tab are listed in the RUN tab under Settings. Each parameter has two attributes: an initial value and a constraint.

Constraints set a range of allowed values for selected parameter during estimation (and as initial values). There are three types of constraints:

- **none**: a parameter is not constraint and its value can be from minus to plus “infinity” (in practice its minus or plus 10e16),
- **positive**: (default option) a parameter is strictly greater then zero,
- **bounded**: a parameter is strictly inside a bounded interval which limits you can specify manually.

You can set an **initial value** of a parameter manually or using the auto-initialization algorithm. Selection of good initial values, those capturing the characteristic features of a selected model (e.g., two different slopes on log scale for a 2-compartment model), is important during the estimation of parameters with the optimization algorithm. It can help to avoid local minima during the optimization process and decrease the runtime of the algorithm.

5.3.1.1 Check initial estimates

In the Tasks tab of the CA section, there is a dedicated sub-tab CHECK INIT. to help with the initialization of parameters. The goal of the CHECK INIT. sub-tab is to:

- Visually check parameter initialization. It displays the model predictions obtained with the initial model parameters values and the individual designs (doses and regressors) for each individual and the data points for comparison.

- Help finding good initial values: update the values manually or use the auto-init function.

The CHECK INIT. tab in PKanalix uses the same auto-init algorithm and has the same features as auto-init in Monolix.

The panel on the right side contains several settings:

- **Auto-init:** You can modify the initial values of the parameters, shown on the bottom of the screen, manually by typing new values or by using the auto-init algorithm—click the button RUN in the Auto-init panel on the right. See more details [below](#).
- **X-axis** and **Y-axis:** Set one or both axes to log-scale. To better compare among individuals, apply the same limits for all individual plots.
- **Grid:** If there are not enough points for the prediction (e.g. there are many doses), change the grid size by increasing the number of points.

Click on the “**SET AS INITIAL VALUES**” button on the top of the plot to save the initial values for the optimization step.

If there are several observation types where the different obs-ids have been mapped to model outputs (for example, a parent and a metabolite, or a PK and a PD observation), then you can switch between them in the “Output” section on the top-right corner, see below:

5.3.1.1 References in the “check initial estimates”

The following video describes how to use the **Reference** option and when it can be helpful (the example is in Monolix, but it works in the same way in PKanalix).

Adding a reference better shows how changing parameter values impacts the prediction. To add a reference, click on the icon to the left “Set as initial values” button. It saves the current parameter values as a reference and adds it to the list at the top of the right panel, see below. If you then further change the parameter values either manually or with auto-int, the solid red curve corresponds to the new current set of parameters (displayed at the bottom), while the dashed one corresponds to the reference. At any time, you can restore the reference as the current parameter values (green arrow next to the reference name), delete the reference (red x) or delete all references (trash icon above the list).

5.3.1.1.2 Auto-init: Automatic initialization of the parameters

PKanalix has an automatic algorithm for initialization. It is in the right panel in the Auto-init section and you can launch it by clicking on the button RUN. The following video describes how it works using an example in Monolix.

After clicking on the button RUN, PKanalix computes initial model parameters that best fit the data points using a pooled-fit approach, starting from the current parameter values displayed at the below the plots. By default, the algorithm uses all individual data from all observations mapped to a model output. You can change the set of individuals in the “Ids” selection panel just below the RUN button.

The algorithm is a custom optimization method on the pooled data. The purpose is not to find a perfect match but rather to have all the parameters in a good range for starting the Nelder-Mead optimization on each individual.

- While auto-init is running, the pop-up shows the evolution of the cost of the optimization algorithm over the iterations. Stop the algorithm at any time, e.g., if you see that the cost has decreased sufficiently and you want to check the parameter values.
- Note that the more individuals you select, the longer the run will take.

- Selecting one or only a few individuals that show clearly model characteristics (e.g., a third compartment, a complex absorption) can help the auto-init algorithm to find set of parameters that is sensitive to specific model features.

After running auto-init, the current parameter values update automatically and are shown in the plots. To use these parameters as initial values for the optimization process, click on the button “SET AS INITIAL VALUES.”

Note that the auto-init procedure uses the current initial values. If it gives poor results, manually change the parameter values before running the auto-init again.

5.3.2 Estimation

The estimation of model parameters is the key function of the compartmental analysis task. It is performed in the framework of generalized least squares estimation. The optimization algorithm consists of minimizing a cost function with an improved version of the Nelder-Mead simplex algorithm, starting from multiple guesses in addition to the initial values provided. To run the algorithm click on the button COMPARTMENTAL ANALYSIS in the RUN tab.

The screenshot displays the PKanalix software interface for compartmental analysis. The main window is titled "project_aPCSK9_SAD.plx [demo] - PKanalix - 2023R1". The interface includes a menu bar (Project, Settings, Export, Help) and a navigation pane (Data, Tasks, Results, Plots). The "Tasks" tab is active, showing the "COMPARTMENTAL ANALYSIS" button highlighted with a red box. Below this, the "Settings" section is visible, divided into "Parameters" and "Calculations".

Parameter	Initial values	Constraint
ka	0.665	positive
V	10.52	positive
Vm	0.481	positive
Km	2.758	positive

The "Calculations" section shows the Cost function as $(Y_{pred} - Y_{obs})^2 / |Y_{pred} * Y_{obs}|$ and the Method for BLQ as Missing. There is also a toggle for "Pooled fit" which is currently turned off.

The goal of the optimization is to find model parameters that give the best model fit to the observed data and thereby minimize the objective (cost) function.

- The **optimization algorithm** performs well in general, but the core algorithm (Nelder-Mead) is local. Therefore **proper initialization of parameters** is crucial.
- The **cost function** is described in this documentation page.
- In case of **censored data**, you can choose a method to treat BLQ data during the optimization: missing, equal to zero, equal to LOQ or equal to LOQ/2.
- By default, the optimization is performed for each individual independently. Switching on the toggle **"Pooled fit"** in the calculation settings will fit the same parameters to all individuals (data from all individuals is analysed together).
- If **occasions** are present and pooled fit is not selected, parameters are all considered occasion-dependent. The optimization for each individual includes $N_{\text{param}} \times N_{\text{occ}}$ parameters (where N_{param} is the number of parameters in the structural model and N_{occ} is the number of occasions for this individual).

5.3.3 Cost, AIC and BIC

5.3.3.1 Cost function

The cost function that is minimized in the optimization performed during CA is described here. The cost is reported in the result tables after running CA, as individual cost in the table of individual parameters, and as total cost in a separate table, together with the likelihood and additional criteria.

Formulas for the cost function used in PKanalix are derived in the framework of generalized least squares described in the publication Banks, H. T., & Joyner, M. L. (2017). AIC under the framework of least squares estimation. Applied Mathematics Letters, 74, 33-45, with an additional scaling to put the same weight on different observation types.

The total cost function, shown in the cost table in the results, is a sum of individual costs per occasion (that is, summed over id-occ):

$$\text{Cost} = \sum_{\text{id-occs}} X_{\text{scaling}} \sum_{\substack{\text{obstypes} \\ \text{with data for} \\ \text{id-occ}}} \frac{1}{N_{\text{obs}}(\text{id\#occ, obstype})} \sum_{j \text{ in time}} (\text{res}_j / w_j)^2$$

Individual cost shown in case of indiv fit and minimized in indiv fit

where in the above formula:

- $N_{\text{obs}}(\text{id\#occ, obstype})$ denotes the number of observations for one individual, one occasion and one observation type (i.e., one model output mapped to data, such as parent and metabolite, or PK and PD, see here).
- $\text{res}_j = Y_{\text{pred}}(t_j) - Y_{\text{obs}}(t_j)$ are residuals at measurement times t_j , where Y_{pred} are the predictions for each time point t_j , and Y_{obs} are the observations from the dataset at that time.

- w_j are weights, selected from the following: 1, Y_{obs} , Y_{pred} , $\sqrt{|Y_{obs}|}$, $\sqrt{|Y_{pred}|}$, $\sqrt{|Y_{obs}| \cdot |Y_{pred}|}$ depending on denominator of the selection in CA task > Settings > Calculations, as explained in this tutorial video.

$X_{scaling}$ is a scaling parameter given by:

$$X_{scaling} = \frac{\sum_{id-occs} n_{obstypes}(id\#occ)}{\sum_{id-occs} \sum_{obstypes} \left(\frac{1}{N_{obs}(id\#occ, obstype)} \right)}$$

where $n_{obstypes}(id\#occ)$ is the number of observation IDs mapped to a model output for one individual and one occasion. Note that if there is only one observation type (corresponding to one observation ID), $X_{scaling} = 1$ and the cost function is a simple sum of squares over all observations, weighted by the weights w_j .

5.3.3.1.1 Likelihood

The likelihood is not directly used in the optimization for CA, but it is possible to derive it based on the optimal cost obtained with the following formula (details in Banks et al.):

$$-2LL = (1 + \ln(2\pi))N_{tot} + 2 \sum_{j \text{ in data}} \ln(w_j) + N_{tot} \ln\left(\frac{Cost}{N_{tot}}\right)$$

where

- $-2LL$ stands for $-2 \times \ln(\text{Likelihood})$,
- N_{tot} is the total number of observations for all individuals, all occasions and all mapped model outputs,
- w_j are the weights as defined above.

5.3.3.2 Additional Criteria

Additional information criteria are the Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) and the Bayesian Information Criteria (BIC). They can be used to compare models. They penalize $-2LL$ by the number of parameters estimated, including the number of model parameters used for the optimization, N_{param} , the total number of observations, N_{tot} , and the number of observations for every subject-occasion, $N_{obs}(id\#occ)$. This penalization enables comparing models with different levels of complexity. Indeed, with more parameters, a model can easily fit better (lower $-2LL$), but with too many parameters, a model loses predictive power and confidence in the parameter estimates. If not only the $-2LL$, but also the AIC and BIC criteria decrease after changing a model, it means that the increased likelihood is worth increasing the model complexity.

Indiv fit

$$AIC = -2LL + 2(N_{param}N_{idocc} + 1)$$

$$BIC = -2LL + \ln(N_{tot}) + N_{param} \sum_{id-occs} \ln(N_{obs}(id\#occ))$$

This formula simplifies if the “pooled fit” option is selected in the calculation settings of the CA task:

Pooled fit

$$AIC = -2LL + 2(N_{param} + 1)$$

$$BIC = -2LL + \ln(N_{tot})(N_{param} + 1)$$

AIC derivation in the case of individual fits

The **total AIC** for all individuals penalizes $-2LL$ with 2 x the number of parameters used in the optimization. For the structural model, we estimate $N_{param} \cdot N_{id\#occ}$ parameters, where N_{param} is the number of parameters in the structural model and $N_{id\#occ}$ is the number of subject-occasions (since there is a set of parameters estimated for each $id\#occ$). For the statistical model, we also implicitly estimate a parameter σ^2 , which is the variance of the residual error model shared by all individuals (it is derived using the sum of squares of residuals as described in Banks et al.). Therefore, AIC penalizes $-2LL$ by $2(N_{param} \cdot N_{id\#occ} + 1)$.

BIC derivation in the case of individual fits

The **total BIC** penalizes $-2LL$ by (number of parameters) x \ln (number of data points). In this case, we should distinguish between the data for each $id\#occ$, which is used to estimate N_{param} parameters, and the data for all individuals, which is used together to estimate the residual variance σ^2 . To penalize each individual's data in the estimation of N_{param} , we add the term $N_{param} \times \ln(N_{obs}(id\#occ))$ for each $id\#occ$. To penalize the estimation of the error model

parameter with all the observations (substitution of σ as described in Banks et al.), we add the term $1 \times \ln(N_{tot})$.

5.4 CA results

PKanalix automatically generates results after running the CA task. This page contains a description of all output tables and files.

5.4.1 Output tables

Compartmental analysis results are displayed in several tables in the “Results” tab, in the CA section at left.

project_covariates.plx [demo] * - PKanalix - 2023R1

Project Settings Export Help

Data Tasks Results Plots

NCA

CA

SUMMARY INDIV. ESTIM. COST

Individual estimates

DISPLAY

Compartmental analysis results per individual

Paginate

id	Cost	ka	V	Cl	WEIGHT	SEX
1	0.82	4.91	5.42	0.44	70.65	F
2	0.68	1.07	3.02	0.5	67.52	F
3	0.37	2.59	20.63	0.91	65.31	M
4	0.32	1.32	9.11	0.97	66.67	M
5	0.22	0.6	4.63	0.61	68.13	F
6	0.53	0.93	5.74	0.36	71.19	F
7	0.64	0.49	5.01	0.54	71.81	F
8	0.25	0.13	2.29	1.75	76.76	M
9	0.27	0.68	3.96	0.36	64.49	F
10	0.29	0.67	4.52	0.32	64.74	F

Records per page: 10 25 50

<< Page 1 of 5 >>

Showing 1 to 10 of 50 entries

5.4.1.1 Individual estimates

This table (shown above) contains results from the compartmental analysis for each individual: model parameter values, cost function values, and covariates (from the dataset). By default, the table shows 10 records (ids) per page. With the settings below the table, you can increase the number of records per page and navigate to subsequent pages.

5.4.1.2 Summary

This table contains summary statistics on compartmental analysis results. The complete description of parameters is here.

The screenshot shows the PKanalix software interface with the 'Results' tab selected. The 'Summary' section displays statistics on compartmental analysis results. A table provides summary statistics for parameters: Cost, ka, V, and Cl. The table includes columns for MIN, Q1, MEDIAN, Q3, MAX, MEAN, SD, SE, CV, GEOMEAN, GEOSD, GEOCV, and HARMMEAN. Below the table, the elapsed time is shown as 0.15 seconds. On the right side, there are controls for 'DISPLAY' (Paginate), 'STRATIFICATION GROUPS' (WEIGHT, SEX), and 'Split/Filter' options (WEIGHT, SEX).

	MIN	Q1	MEDIAN	Q3	MAX	MEAN	SD	SE	CV	GEOMEAN	GEOSD	GEOCV	HARMMEAN
Cost	0.15	0.27	0.37	0.5	1.18	0.41	0.19	0.027	46.93	0.37	1.53	44.51	0.34
ka	0.13	0.56	0.8	1.32	45016.23	2326.96	9462.37	1338.18	406.64	1.58	15.26	4100.49	0.62
V	2.29	4.63	6.79	9.11	20.63	7.27	3.58	0.51	49.22	6.52	1.6	49.92	5.86
Cl	0.25	0.46	0.81	0.97	2.12	0.8	0.41	0.058	51.53	0.7	1.67	55.09	0.62

To better compare among groups, you can split or filter this table using covariates in a dataset. When you select split/filter, PKanalix automatically re-calculates the values according to the stratification settings and displays them. The following *Feature of the week* video explains how this feature works using the NCA individual estimates table as an example.

5.4.1.3 Cost

This table contains model comparison indices calculated for the CA model. It includes: total cost (the sum of individual costs from the INDIV. ESTIM. subtab), -2LL, AIC, and BIC, see here for details about the formulas. Information criteria allow one to statistically compare the fit obtained with different models. For these information criteria, the lower the value of the information criterion, the better the model fits. There is no absolute value of comparison; only the relative difference between two models is important.

5.4.2 Output Files

You can also find the compartmental analysis results in the project results folder in the directory "IndividualParameters > ca". There are four text files:

5.4.2.1 summary.txt

Description: Human readable summary file.

Contents:

- **Header:** project file name, date and time of run, PKanalix version
- **Table:** Summary statistics of the individual cost function and individual model parameters

5.4.2.2 caIndividualParameters.txt

Description: Individual parameter estimates.

Contents:

- **Identifier:** subject name and occasion (if applicable). If one or more occasions are defined in the data, additional column(s) will be present specifying the occasions.
- **Cost:** value of the individual cost function
- **parameterName:** individual model parameter values estimated during the compartmental analysis.
- **Covariates:** continuous and categorical covariates values defined in the dataset.

5.4.2.3 caIndividualParametersSummary.txt

Description: Statistics summary of individual parameter estimates.

Contents:

- **Identifier:** subject name and occasion (if applicable). If one or more occasions are defined in the data, additional column(s) will be present specifying the occasions.
- **Parameter:** cost and model parameters
- **Statistics:** min, Q1, median, Q3, max, mean, SD, SE, CV, geoMean, geoSD, geoCV, harmMean

5.4.2.4 cost.txt

Description: Total cost and information criteria for the model.

Contents:

- **Cost:** Total cost (sum of individual costs)
- **Log-likelihood estimation:** -2LL, AIC, BIC

5.5 Export a PKanalix project

MonolixSuite applications are interconnected and you can import and export a PKanalix project across different applications. This interconnection is facilitated by using the same model syntax (mlxtran language) and the same dataset format. There are two options to export a PKanalix project:

- Export to Monolix for population model development, estimation and diagnosis. See the Monolix documentation.
- Export to Simulx for simulations of new scenarios, e.g., new dosing regimens. It requires specifying a CA model. See the Simulx documentation.

Exporting a PKanalix project to Simulx is available starting with version 2023. In previous versions, you can only export a PKanalix project to Monolix.

To export a PKanalix project to Monolix or Simulx click “Export Project To” in the top menu “Export,” select the target software (Monolix or Simulx), and confirm the process by clicking on the “Export” button at the bottom. By default, associated files, e.g., dataset and model files, are saved next to the target project.

5.5.1 Export to Monolix

Exporting a PKanalix project to Monolix automatically opens a Monolix window and creates a new Monolix project with the following predefined elements:

- Dataset tagging and formatting steps (if present): the same as the PKanalix project.
- Dataset filters (if applied): the same as the PKanalix project.
- Structural model and initial parameter values: the same as those in the CA task in the PKanalix project. If there is no model in the PKanalix project, then Monolix will use a default library model with oral or IV administration (matching the NCA settings), one compartment, and linear elimination.
- Statistical model and tasks: default Monolix settings

Monolix opens at the “Statistical model and tasks” tab, and you can immediately click the “Run” button to estimate parameters and generate diagnostic plots.

5.5.2 Export to Simulx

Exporting a PKanalix project to Simulx creates a new Simulx project and automatically creates all elements useful for simulating the model. This consists of the following elements in the Definition tab:

- Model, individual parameter estimates and output variables – imported from the CA task in PKanalix.

- Occasions, covariates, treatments and regressors – imported from the dataset used in the PKanalix project.

Moreover, Simulx automatically creates exploration and simulation scenarios. The Exploration tab contains one group to explore effects of model parameters and treatments on a typical individual. The Simulation tab contains one group to re-simulate individuals from the PKanalix project. You will find more information about the imported elements and how to create new scenarios in the Simulx documentation webpage.

5.5.3 Share a PKanalix project

The 2024 version of MonolixSuite introduces a convenient method for sharing projects. Simply click on “Share Project” in the export menu, and a zip folder is generated containing all the required files to re-open the project (dataset, model for CA if not from library, ptx file, and result folder). By default, the suggested location for the zipped shared project is next to the project file, but this can be modified to any other location on the computer.

6 Plots

6.1 Overview

The list of plots below corresponds to all the plots that PKanalix can generate. They are partly generated directly after importing the data, partly after running an analysis task.

6.1.1 Data

- Observed data: This plot displays the original data w.r.t. time as a spaghetti plot, along with some additional information.
- Covariate viewer: This plot displays the matrix of all the covariates in one plot.
- Bivariate data viewer: This plot displays data of different observation types (typically PK and PD data) in one.

6.1.2 NCA

6.1.2.1 Model for the observations

- Individual fits: This plot displays the individual fits: individual predictions using the individual parameters and the individual covariates w.r.t. time on a continuous grid, with the observed data overlaid.

6.1.2.2 Diagnosis plots based on individual parameters

- Distribution of the NCA parameters: This plot displays the estimated distributions of the individual parameters.
- Correlation between NCA parameters: This plot displays scatter plots for each pair of individual parameters.
- NCA parameters vs covariates: This plot displays the estimators of the individual parameters w.r.t. the covariates.

6.1.3 CA

6.1.3.1 Model for the observations

- Individual fits: This plot displays the individual fits: individual predictions using the individual parameters and the individual covariates w.r.t. time on a continuous grid, with the observed data overlaid.
- Observations vs predictions: This plot displays observations w.r.t. the predictions computed using the population parameters or the individual parameters.

6.1.3.2 Diagnosis plots based on individual parameters

- Distribution of the CA parameters: This plot displays the estimated distributions of the individual parameters.
- Correlation between CA parameters: This plot displays scatter plots for each pair of individual parameters.
- CA parameters vs covariates: This plot displays the estimators of the individual parameters w.r.t. the covariates.

6.1.4 Bioequivalence

- Sequence by period: This plot displays scatter plots for each pair of individual parameters.
- Subject by formulation: This plot displays for each parameter, the subject-by-formulation interaction and the inter-subject variability.
- Confidence intervals: This plot displays the confidence interval for the ratio for each parameter, as well as the BE limits.
- Individual concentration data: This plot displays the individual concentration data with one individual per subplot and occasions all together

6.1.5 Exporting plots

The user can choose to export each plot as an image with an icon on top of it, or all plots at once with the menu Export. It is also possible to export plots data as table, for example to build new plots with external tools.

project_crossover_foodeffect.pkx [demo] * - PKanalix - 2023R1

Note that:

- the export starts after the display of the plots,
- the plots are exported in the result folder,
- only plot selected in Plots tasks are exported,
- legends and information frames are not exported.

Automatic exporting can be chosen in the project Preferences (in Settings), as well as the exporting format (png or svg):

6.2 Data plots

List of data plots:

6.2.1 Observed data

It is always good to have a look first at the observed data before running the parameter estimation. Indeed, it is very convenient to see if all the data is consistent, or if some outliers appear.

The purpose of this plot, also called a spaghetti plot, is to display the original data w.r.t. time.

In the example below, the concentration of warfarin from the warfarin data set is displayed. A subject is highlighted in yellow by hovering on the line.

One can plot the output in a log-scale to have a better evaluation of the elimination part for example as in the figure below.

The data can be displayed as dots and lines (by default), or only as dots or only as lines, as in the figure below. In addition, a trend line can be overlaid on the plot, based on mean values of the observed data pooled in bins. The user can choose arithmetic or geometric mean, and can add error bars representing either the standard deviations or standard errors. The mean and error values can be displayed as fixed labels next to the bars, or as tooltips when hovering on a bar.

Bin limits can be displayed as vertical lines, and the user can change the number of bins as well as binning criteria.

An interesting feature is the possibility to display the dosing time as on the figure below. The individual dosing time of the individual can be displayed when the user hovers an individual or always visible. Starting in version 2021R1 on, dosing times corresponding to doses with null amounts are not displayed.

The units (only in PKanalix) as well as additional descriptive statistics of the observations (both PKanalix and Monolix) can be displayed. We propose

- The total number of subjects
- The average number of doses per subject
- The total, average, minimum and maximum number of observations per individual.

In addition, if we split the graphic with a covariate, these numbers are recomputed to display the information of the group as in the following plot.

From the version 2023R1 it is now possible to display the mean curves, split by covariate, in a single plot. By switching on the "Merged splits" option, the mean curves of the two wiehgt groups, which appeared in previous versions in separate plots, are merged into a single plot.

6.2.2 Covariate viewer

6.2.2.1 Covariate viewer

It is possible to show the matrix of all the covariates as on the following figure:

It is possible to display one covariate vs another one, selecting in the display panel which covariate to look at.

Here we display the weight versus the height and show the correlation coefficient as an information:

Categorical covariates w.r.t. other categorical covariates are displayed as a histogram (stacked or grouped),

and continuous covariates w.r.t. categorical covariates are displayed as a boxplot as below ("+" are outlier points below $Q1-1.5IQR$ (interquartile range) or above $Q3+1.5IQR$):

6.2.2.2 Covariate statistics

Starting from the 2021 version, it is also possible to get the covariate statistics in a dedicated frame of the interface:

Continuous covariates

Statistics on continuous covariates distribution

	MIN	Q1	MEDIAN	Q3	MAX	SD
AGE	21	22	25	28	39	5
HT	176	179	181	183	191	4.26
WT	65	68	70	77	83	5.27

Categorical covariates

Categorical covariates distribution across modalities

	ref	test	RT	TR
FORM	18	18		
SEQ			18	18

All the covariates (if any) are displayed and a summary of the statistics is proposed. For continuous covariates, minimum, median and maximum values are proposed along with the first and third quartile, and the standard deviation. For categorical covariates, all the modalities are displayed along with the number of each. Note the “Copy table” button that allows to copy the table in Word and Excel. The format and the display of the table will be preserved.

6.2.3 Bivariate data viewer

In case of several continuous outputs, one can plot one type of observation w.r.t. another one as on the following figure for the warfarin data set. The direction of time is indicated by the red arrow. Linear interpolation is used for observations of different types that are not at the same time.

Labels for x and y axes correspond to the observation names in the model for data types that are mapped to an output of the model, or observation ids used in the dataset for data types not captured by the model. It is possible to choose which observation id to display on the X or Y axis in the settings panel on the right.

6.3 NCA plots

List of all NCA plots:

6.3.1 Individual fits NCA

6.3.1.1 Purpose

This plot can be used for two purposes:

- show the terminal slope (lambdaZ) linear regression for each occasion of each individual (default)
- show the individual concentration data with one individual per subplot and all occasions

6.3.1.2 LambdaZ terminal slope

By default, the settings let you see each occasion of each individual on a subplot, in y log-scale with the lambdaZ linear regression.

i In versions prior to 2024R1, the NCA parameters Lambda_z and Lambda_z_intercept need to be selected in the “Computed parameters” of NCA settings in order to display the lambdaZ regression line.

Selecting the “Information” toggle allows you to display information about the rule used to calculate the lambdaZ (“Adjusted R2”, “R2”, “Interval”, “Points” or “custom” – when points have been manually selected), the number of points included in the calculation and the R2 or adjusted R2 criteria.

6.3.1.3 Individual concentration data

The plot can be used to visualize the individual concentration data with one individual per subplot and occasions all together. For a crossover study with two periods and two formulations for instance, one can:

- display the “Lines”
- display the “unused data” as “colored”
- hide the “LambdaZ regression”
- untick the “split occasions”
- set the y axis in linear scale
- color by the Formulation in the stratify tab

6.3.1.3.1 Settings

- *Grid arrange (top left above the plot):* The user can define the number of subplots displayed, as well as the number of rows and the number of columns. This choice is not saved. See below the “Default number of individuals per page” for a setting that is saved.
- *General*
 - Legend: hide/show the legend. The legends adapts automatically to the elements displayed on the plot. The same legend box applies to all subplots and it is possible to drag and drop the legend at the desired place.
 - Grid : hide/show the grid in the background of the plots.
 - Information: hide/show
 - the continuous covariates: continuous covariates values are displayed for each individual
 - the goodness of fit: the rule used to calculate the lambdaZ (“Adjusted R2”, “R2”, “Interval”, “Points” or “custom” – when points have been manually selected), the number of points used to calculate the lambdaZ and the R2 value (if rule=R2) or the adjusted R2 (if rule different from R2).

- Units: hide/show the units next to the NCA parameter names. The color and surrounding characters for the units can be chosen in the plot "Preferences".
- Dosing times: hide/show dosing times as vertical lines for each subject.
- Link zoom between plots: activate the linked zoom for all subplots. The same zooming region can be applied on all individuals only on the x-axis, only on the Y-axis or on both (option "none" in the "zoom constraint").
- *Display*
 - Dots: hide/show the observed data as dots
 - Lines: hide/show the connecting lines between the observed data points
 - Censored data [if censored data present]: hide/show the data marked as [censored \(BLQ\)](#), shown as a red dot according to the "BLQ method before/after Tmax" choice in the NCA settings.
 - Unused data: hide/show the data points not used for the lambdaZ calculation
 - greyed: display the data points not used in the lambdaZ calculation as greyed
 - colored: display the data points not used in the lambdaZ calculation with the default color (set in the plot "Preferences")
 - Split occasions [if occasions present]: Split the individual subplots by occasions or group occasions on a single subplot for each individual.
 - Default number of individuals per page: Set the number of subplots to display. This setting can be saved, whereas the "grid arrange" on the top left corner is not.
 - LambdaZ regression: hide/show the lambdaZ linear regression
- *Sorting*: Sort the subjects by ID, goodness of fit (R2 or adjusted R2 value) or continuous covariate value in ascending or descending order.

6.3.2 Distribution of the individual parameters

6.3.2.1 Purpose

This figure can be used to see the empirical distribution of the NCA parameters. Further analysis such as stratification by covariate can be performed and will be detailed below.

6.3.2.2 PDF and CDF

It is possible to display the theoretical distribution and the histogram of the empirical distribution as proposed below.

The distributions are represented as histograms for the probability density function (PDF). Hovering on the histogram also reveals the density value of each bin as shown on the figure below

Cumulative distribution functions (CDF) is proposed too.

6.3.2.3 Example of stratification

It is possible to stratify the population by some covariate values and obtain the distributions of the individual parameters in each group. This can be useful to check covariate effect, in particular when the distribution of a parameter exhibits two or more peaks for the whole population. On the following

example, the distribution of the parameter k from the same example as above has been split for two groups of individuals according to the value of the sex, allowing to visualize two clearly different distributions.

6.3.2.4 Settings

- *General*: add/remove the legend, and the grid
- *Display*
 - Distribution function: The user can choose to display either the probability density function (PDF) as histogram or the cumulative distribution function (CDF).

6.3.3 Correlation between individual parameters

6.3.3.1 Purpose

This plot displays scatter plots for each pair of parameters. It allows to identify correlations between parameters, which can be used to see the results of your analysis and see the coherence of the parameters for each individuals.

6.3.3.2 Example

In the following example, one can see pairs of parameters estimated for all parameters.

6.3.3.2.1 Visual guidelines

In addition to regression lines, correlation coefficients can be added to see the correlation between random effects, as well as spline interpolations.

6.3.3.2.2 Selection

It is possible to select a subset of parameters, whose pairs of correlations are then displayed, as shown below. In the selection panel, a set of contiguous rows can be selected with a single extended click, or a set of non-contiguous rows can be selected with several clicks while holding the Ctrl key.

6.3.3.2.3 Highlight

Similarly to other plots, hovering on a point provides information on the corresponding subject id, and highlights other points corresponding to the same individual.

6.3.3.2.4 Stratification: coloring and filtering

Stratification can be applied by creating groups of covariate values. As can be seen below, these groups can then be split, colored and/or filtered allowing to check the effect of the covariate on the correlation between two parameters. The correlation coefficient is updated according to the stratifying action. In the following case, We split by the covariate SEX and color bay 2 categories of AGE.

6.3.3.3 Settings

- *General*
 - Legend and grid : add/remove the legend or the grid. There is only one legend for all plots.
 - Information: display/hide the correlation coefficient associated with each scatter plot.
- *Display*
 - *Selection.* The user can select some of the parameters to display only the corresponding scatter plots. A simple click selects one parameter, whereas multiple clicks while holding the Ctrl key selects a set of parameters.
 - *Visual cues.* Add/remove the regression line or the spline interpolation.

6.3.4 Individual parameters vs covariates

6.3.4.1 Purpose

The figure displays the individual parameters as a function of the covariates. It allows to identify correlation effects between the individual parameters and the covariates.

6.3.4.2 Identifying correlation effects

In the example below, we can see the parameters Cl_{obs} and C_{max} with respect to the covariates: the weight WT , the age AGE and the sex category.

6.3.4.2.1 Visual guidelines

In order to help identifying correlations, regression lines, spline interpolations and correlation coefficients can be overlaid on the plots for continuous covariates. Here we can see a strong correlation between the parameter Cl_{obs} and the age and the weight.

6.3.4.2.2 Overlay of values on top of the boxplot

The NCA parameter values used to generate the boxplots for the categorical covariates can be overlaid on top of the boxplots, which enables to better visualize the distribution in case of a small number of individuals.

6.3.4.2.3 Highlight

Hovering on a point reveals the corresponding individual and, if multiple individual parameters have been simulated from the conditional distribution for each individual, highlights all the points points from the same individual. This is useful to identify possible outliers and subsequently check their behavior in the observed data.

6.3.4.2.4 Selection

It is possible to select a subset of covariates or parameters, as shown below. In the selection panel, tick the items you would like to see and click "Accept". This is useful when there are many parameters or covariates.

6.3.4.2.5 Stratification

Stratification can be applied by creating groups of covariate values. As can be seen below, these groups can then be split, colored or filtered, allowing to check the effect of the covariate on the correlation between two parameters. The correlation coefficient is updated according to the split or filtering.

6.3.4.3 Settings

- *General*
 - **Legend:** add/remove the legend. There is only one legend for all plots.
 - **Grid:** add/remove the grid.
 - **Information:** display/hide the correlation coefficient associated with each scatter plot.
 - **Units:** display/hide the units of the NCA parameters on the y axis
- *Display*
 - **Individual parameters:** Selects the NCA parameters to display as subplot on rows. Tick the items you would like to see and click “accept”.
 - **Covariates:** Selects the NCA parameters to display as subplot on columns. Tick the items you would like to see and click “accept”.
 - **Boxplots data:** overlay the NCA parameters as dots on top of the boxplots for categorical covariates, either aligned on a vertical line (“aligned”), spread over the boxplot width (“spread”) or not at all (“none”).

- **Regression line:** Add/remove the linear regression line corresponding to the correlation coefficient.
- **Spline:** Add/remove the spline. Spline settings cannot be changed.

6.3.5 NCA data

6.3.5.1 Purpose

This plot, available with version 2024, enables the interpreted data for NCA to be displayed in the same way as the observed data. The interpreted data in the plot takes into account exclusions, filters and censoring rules.

While executing the NCA task, the NCA plot is automatically generated alongside the standard set of plots.

Compared to the Observed data plot, the following data processing rules have been applied:

- additional points at dose time (if not present in original dataset)
- points before the last dose of each profile (i.e occasion or subject) are removed
- BLQ data is replaced according to the chosen NCA settings (BLQ after Tmax and BLQ before Tmax)

Besides these two mentioned differences from the observed data plot, the NCA data plot offers the same plot settings and stratification properties. Note the option to display the x-axis as nominal time.

6.3.5.2 Sparse data

The NCA plot for sparse data differs in certain points from the one for dense data.

• Stratification

Due to the enforced stratification in the calculation settings, the data also appears according to this stratification in the plots tab. No further stratification settings are possible in the plots tab that deviate from the stratification specified in the calculations panel in the NCA tasks tab.

- *Trend line*

The data is summarized using the arithmetic mean, which is represented by a trend line in the plot. Unlike for dense data in the NCA plot or in the observed data plot, there is no option to select an alternative mean value formula. However, it is possible to display or hide these metrics, arithmetic mean and standard deviation, in the plot using their associated toggles.

- *Censored data*

The rules defined in the NCA task tab for handling censored data are also considered in the calculation and therefore also in the display of the mean curve and the associated error bars in the in plot.

- *Nominal time*

If **nominal time** is present in the dataset, it serves as the time variable in calculations and is consequently enforced as the x-axis in the plot, with no option of changing it.

6.4 CA plots

List of all CA plots:

6.4.1 Individual fits

6.4.1.1 Purpose

The figure displays the observed data for each subject, as well as prediction using the individual parameters.

6.4.1.2 Individual parameters

Information on individual parameters can be used in two ways, as shown below. By clicking on Information (marked in green on the figure) in the General panel, individual parameter values can be displayed on each individual plot. Moreover, the plots can be sorted according to the values for a given

parameter, in ascending or descending order (Sorting panel marked in blue). By default, the individual plots are sorted by subject id, with the same order as in the data set.

6.4.1.2.1 Special zoom

User-defined constraints for the zoom are available. They allow to zoom in according to one axis only instead of both axes. Moreover, a link between plots can be set in order to perform a linked zoom on all individual plots at once. This is shown on the figure below with observations from

6.4.1.2.2 Censored data

When a data is censored, this data is different to a “classical” observation and has thus a different representation. We represent it as a bar from the censored value specified in the data set and the associated limit.

6.4.1.3 Settings

- *Grid arrange*. The user can define the number of subjects that are displayed, as well as the number of rows and the number of columns. Moreover, a slider is present to be able to change the subjects under consideration.
- *General*
 - Legend: hide/show the legend. The legends adapts automatically to the elements displayed on the plot. The same legend box applies to all subplots and it is possible to drag and drop the legend at the desired place.
 - Grid : hide/show the grid in the background of the plots.
 - Information: hide/show the individual parameter values for each subject (conditional mode or conditional mean depending on the “Individual estimates” choice is the setting section “Display”).
 - Dosing times: hide/show dosing times as vertical lines for each subject.
 - Link between plots: activate the linked zoom for all subplots. The same zooming region can be applied on all individuals only on the x-axis, only on the Y-axis or on both (option “none”).
- *Display*
 - Observed data: hide/show the observed data.
 - Censored intervals [if censored data present]: hide/show the data marked as **censored (BLQ)**, shown as a rectangle representing the censoring interval (for instance [0, LOQ]).
 - Split occasions [if IOV present]: Split the individual subplots by occasions in case of IOV.
 - Number of points of the calculation for the prediction
- *Sorting*: Sort the subjects by ID or individual parameter values in ascending or descending order.

By default, only the observed data and the individual fits are displayed.

6.4.2 Observations vs predictions

The observations vs predictions plot displays observations (y_{ij}) versus the corresponding predictions (\hat{y}_{ij}) estimated by the CA task. It is a useful tool to detect misspecifications in the structural model. The points shall scatter as close as possible along the $y = x$ line (black solid line). If a large amount of points are not scattered close to the identity line, then this might be due to the chosen structural model not capturing certain kinetics. Moreover, the distribution of the dots should be symmetrical around the $y=x$ line, meaning that the model prediction is sometimes above and sometimes below the observed data.

This plot is generated automatically when you run the compartmental analysis task. You can access it from the CA section in the plots list.

6.4.2.1 Visual Guides

In addition to the observed data, in the DISPLAY settings panel you can add: the identity line $y = x$ and spline interpolation.

6.4.2.2 Highlight

Hovering on any point of observed data shows:

- the subject id and time corresponding to this point
- highlights all the points corresponding to this subject
- segments linking all points corresponding to the same individual to visualize the time chronology.

Highlighting works across plots. An individual data highlighted in this plot, will be highlighted in every other plot to help you in the model diagnosis.

6.4.2.3 Log scale

A log scale allows to focus on low observation values. You can set it in the AXIS section of the settings panel for each axis separately or for both together.

The example below displays the predicted concentrations of [remifentanyl](#), modeled via a two-compartment model with a linear elimination. In this case, the log-log scale reveals a misspecification of the model: the small observations are under-predicted. These observations correspond to late time points, meaning that the last phase of elimination is not properly captured by the two-compartment model. A three-compartment model might give better results.

6.4.2.4 Settings

- *General*
 - Legend and grid : add/remove the legend or the grid.
- *Display*
 - BLQ data : show and put in a different color the data that are BLQ (Below the Limit of Quantification)
 - Visual cues: add/remove visual guidelines such as the line $y = x$ or a spline interpolation.
- *Axis*
 - Use log scale
 - Set automatic or manual (user – defined step) tick values
 - Edit axis labels

6.4.2.5 Stratification

You can split, color or filter the plot as described for the observed data.

6.4.3 Distribution of individuals parameters

6.4.3.1 Purpose

This figure can be used to see the empirical distribution of the CA parameters. Further analysis such as stratification by covariate can be performed and will be detailed below.

6.4.3.2 PDF and CDF

It is possible to display the theoretical distribution and the histogram of the empirical distribution as proposed below.

The distributions are represented as histograms for the probability density function (PDF). Hovering on the histogram also reveals the density value of each bin as shown on the figure below.

Cumulative distribution functions (CDF) is proposed too.

6.4.3.3 Example of stratification

It is possible to stratify the population by some covariate values and obtain the distributions of the individual parameters in each group. This can be useful to check covariate effect, in particular when the distribution of a parameter exhibits two or more peaks for the whole population. On the following example, the distribution of the parameter k from the same example as above has been split for two groups of individuals according to the value of the SEX, allowing to visualize two clearly different distributions.

6.4.3.4 Settings

- *General*: add/remove the legend, and the grid
- *Display*
 - Distribution function: The user can choose to display either the probability density function (PDF) as histogram or the cumulative distribution function (CDF).

6.4.4 Correlation between individual parameters

6.4.4.1 Purpose

This plot displays scatter plots for each pair of parameters. It allows to identify correlations between parameters, which can be used to see the results of your analysis and see the coherence of the parameters for each individuals.

6.4.4.2 Example

In the following example, one can see pairs of parameters estimated for all parameters.

6.4.4.2.1 Visual guidelines

In addition to regression lines, correlation coefficients can be added to see the correlation between random effects, as well as spline interpolations.

6.4.4.2.2 Selection

It is possible to select a subset of parameters, whose pairs of correlations are then displayed, as shown below. In the selection panel, a set of contiguous rows can be selected with a single extended click, or a set of non-contiguous rows can be selected with several clicks while holding the Ctrl key.

6.4.4.2.3 Highlight

Similarly to other plots, hovering on a point provides information on the corresponding subject id, and highlights other points corresponding to the same individual.

6.4.4.2.4 Stratification: coloring and filtering

Stratification can be applied by creating groups of covariate values. As can be seen below, these groups can then be split, colored and/or filtered allowing to check the effect of the covariate on the correlation between two parameters. The correlation coefficient is updated according to the stratifying action. In the following case, We split by the covariate SEX and color bay 2 categories of AGE.

6.4.4.3 Settings

- *General*
 - Legend and grid : add/remove the legend or the grid. There is only one legend for all plots.
 - Information: display/hide the correlation coefficient associated with each scatter plot.
- *Display*
 - *Selection.* The user can select some of the parameters to display only the corresponding scatter plots. A simple click selects one parameter, whereas multiple clicks while holding the Ctrl key selects a set of parameters.
 - *Visual cues.* Add/remove the regression line or the spline interpolation.

6.4.5 Individual parameters vs covariates

6.4.5.1 Purpose

The figure displays the individual parameters as a function of the covariates. It allows to identify correlation effects between the individual parameters and the covariates.

6.4.5.2 Identifying correlation effects

In the example below, we can see the parameters Cl and $V1$ with respect to the covariates: the weight WT , the age AGE and the sex category.

6.4.5.2.1 Visual guidelines

In order to help identifying correlations, regression lines, spline interpolations and correlation coefficients can be overlaid on the plots for continuous covariates. Here we can see a strong correlation between the parameter Cl and the age and the weight. This is the same with $V1$.

6.4.5.2.2 Highlight

Hovering on a point reveals the corresponding individual and, if multiple individual parameters have been simulated from the conditional distribution for each individual, highlights all the points from the same individual. This is useful to identify possible outliers and subsequently check their behavior in the observed data.

6.4.5.2.3 Selection

It is possible to select a subset of covariates or parameters, as shown below. In the selection panel, a set of contiguous rows can be selected with a single extended click, or a set of non-contiguous rows can be selected with several clicks while holding the Ctrl key. This is useful when there are many parameters or covariates.

6.4.5.2.4 Stratification

Stratification can be applied by creating groups of covariate values. As can be seen below, these groups can then be split, colored or filtered, allowing to check the effect of the covariate on the correlation between two parameters. The correlation coefficient is updated according to the split or filtering.

6.4.5.3 Settings

- *General*
 - Legend and grid : add/remove the legend or the grid. There is only one legend for all plots.
 - Information: display/hide the correlation coefficient associated with each scatter plot.
- *Display*
 - *Selection*. The user can select some of the parameters or covariates to display only the corresponding plots. A simple click selects one parameter (or covariate), whereas multiple clicks while holding the Ctrl key selects a set of parameters.
 - *Visual cues*. Add/remove a regression line or a spline interpolation.

6.5 Bioequivalence plots

List of all bioequivalence plots:

6.5.1 Sequence-by-period

6.5.1.1 Purpose

The sequence-by-period plot allows to visualize, for each parameter, the mean and standard deviation for each period, sequence and formulation.

6.5.1.2 Description

For each formulation, period and sequence (as defined in the Bioequivalence settings), the mean and standard deviation is displayed. The dots are colored according to the formulation, and dots belonging to the same sequence connected by lines. Dots are placed on the x-axis according to the occasion value.

If the parameter has a log-transform (see Bioequivalence settings), the dots represents the geometric mean and the error bars $\ast/$ the geometric standard deviation. If the parameter is not log-transformed, the dots represent the arithmetic mean and the error bars \pm the standard deviation. NCA parameter values being NaN are excluded and a warning message is displayed.

The example below shows a repeated crossover with sequences TRTR and TRTR. Three NCA parameters are displayed.

6.5.1.3 Troubleshooting

- **The connecting lines do not appear:**

If the plot setting “Lines” is selected and the connecting lines do not appear, it is because no categorical covariate column has been defined as “Sequence” in the Bioequivalence settings.

- **There are vertical connecting lines:**

This means that the column defined as “Sequence” in the Bioequivalence settings is not consistent with the sequence of formulation according to the Occasion column. In the tab “Data”, you can define an “additional covariate” and select the “covariate sequence (XXX)” with XXX being the column representing the formulation. Then use this column as “Sequence” when defining the factors in the model.

- **There are several periods on the x-axis although no column was indicated as “period” in the Bioequivalence settings:**

When no column is indicated as “period”, we use the column tagged as “occasion” in the data set.

If no column has been tagged as “occasion” (parallel design), the occasion is considered to be 1 for all individuals.

6.5.1.4 Settings

- *General*
 - Legend: hide/show the legend. The legends adapts automatically to the elements displayed on the plot. The same legend box applies to all subplots and it is possible to drag and drop the legend at the desired place.
 - Grid : hide/show the grid in the background of the plots.
 - Units: hide/show the units of the NCA parameters. Note that the color and surrounding character can be chosen in the plot “Preferences”.
- *Display*
 - Dots: hide/show the dots representing the means
 - Lines: hide/show the lines connecting the dots belonging to the same sequence
 - Error bars: hide/show the error bars representing the standard deviation
 - Individual parameters: select which individual parameters to show on the plot

6.5.1.5 Stratify

This plot can be split and filtered by the covariates but not colored. The categorical covariate indicated of Formulation in the Bioequivalence settings is automatically used to color the dots. **The colors can be changed in the plot “Preferences > Formulations”:**

6.5.2 Subject-by-formulation

6.5.2.1 Purpose

This plot allows to visualize, for each parameter, the subject-by-formulation interaction and the inter-subject variability.

6.5.2.2 Description

Each subplot corresponds to one NCA parameter and one non-reference (test) formulation. The individual parameter values for the test and reference formulations are displayed side by side. Values corresponding to the same individual are connected by a line. When an individual has received several times the same formulation (repeated crossover), the average for each formulation is calculated and plotted.

6.5.2.3 Settings

- *General*
 - Legend: hide/show the legend. The legends adapts automatically to the elements displayed on the plot. The same legend box applies to all subplots and it is possible to drag and drop the legend at the desired place.
 - Grid : hide/show the grid in the background of the plots.
 - Units: hide/show the units of the NCA parameters. Note that the color and surrounding character can be chosen in the plot "Preferences".
- *Display*
 - Dots: hide/show the dots representing the individual parameter values

- Lines: hide/show the lines connecting the dots belonging to the same individual
- Individual parameters: select which individual parameters to show on the plot

6.5.2.4 Stratify

The plot can split and filtered but not (yet) colored.

6.5.3 Confidence intervals

6.5.3.1 Purpose

This plot allows to visualize the confidence interval for the ratio for each parameter, as well as the BE limits. Confidence intervals within the BE limits are shown in green while the others are shown in red.

6.5.3.2 Settings

- *General*
 - Legend: hide/show the legend. The legends adapts automatically to the elements displayed on the plot. The same legend box applies to all subplots and it is possible to drag and drop the legend at the desired place.
 - Grid : hide/show the grid in the background of the plots.
 - Units: hide/show the units of the NCA parameters. Note that the color and surrounding character can be chosen in the plot "Preferences".
- *Display*

- Median: hide/show the line at ratio=100%.
- Bioequivalence limits: hide/show the horizontal lines at the BE limits, which can be set in the BE settings
- Individual parameters: select which individual parameters to show on the plot

6.5.3.3 Stratify

This plot cannot be stratified by covariates.

6.5.4 Individual concentrations

It is possible to visualize individual concentrations using the NCA Individual fits plot.

The plot can be used to visualize the individual concentration data with one individual per subplot and occasions all together. For a crossover study with two periods and two formulations for instance, one can:

- display the “Lines”
- display the “unused data” as “colored”
- hide the “LambdaZ regression”
- untick the “split occasions”
- set the y axis in linear scale
- color by the Formulation in the stratify tab

6.5.4.1 Settings

- *Grid arrange (top left above the plot):* The user can define the number of subplots displayed, as well as the number of rows and the number of columns. This choice is not saved. See below the “Default number of individuals per page” for a setting that is saved.
- *General*
 - Legend: hide/show the legend. The legends adapts automatically to the elements displayed on the plot. The same legend box applies to all subplots and it is possible to drag and drop the legend at the desired place.
 - Grid : hide/show the grid in the background of the plots.
 - Information: hide/show
 - the continuous covariates: continuous covariates values are displayed for each individual
 - the goodness of fit: the rule used to calculate the lambdaZ (“Adjusted R2”, “R2”, “Interval”, “Points” or “custom” – when points have been manually selected), the number of points used to calculate the lambdaZ and the R2 value (if rule=R2) or the adjusted R2 (if rule different from R2).
 - Units: hide/show the units next to the NCA parameter names. The color and surrounding characters for the units can be chosen in the plot “Preferences”.
 - Dosing times: hide/show dosing times as vertical lines for each subject.
 - Link zoom between plots: activate the linked zoom for all subplots. The same zooming region can be applied on all individuals only on the x-axis, only on the Y-axis or on both (option “none” in the “zoom constraint”).
- *Display*
 - Dots: hide/show the observed data as dots
 - Lines: hide/show the connecting lines between the observed data points
 - Censored data [if censored data present]: hide/show the data marked as [censored \(BLQ\)](#), shown as a red dot according to the “BLQ method before/after Tmax” choice in the NCA settings.
 - Unused data: hide/show the data points not used for the lambdaZ calculation
 - greyed: display the data points not used in the lambdaZ calculation as greyed
 - colored: display the data points not used in the lambdaZ calculation with the default color (set in the plot “Preferences”)
 - Split occasions [if occasions present]: Split the individual subplots by occasions or group occasions on a single subplot for each individual.
 - Default number of individuals per page: Set the number of subplots to display. This setting can be saved, whereas the “grid arrange” on the top left corner is not.
 - LambdaZ regression: hide/show the lambdaZ linear regression
- *Sorting:* Sort the subjects by ID, goodness of fit (R2 or adjusted R2 value) or continuous covariate value in ascending or descending order.

6.6 Transferring plot formatting

i The features described on this page are not available in MonolixSuite versions prior to 2024R1.

MonolixSuite offers the ability to transfer plot formatting from one plot to another within the same project or across projects. This can save you time and effort when you want to apply the same formatting options, such as stratification, preferences, or settings, to multiple plots, or when you want to use the same plot formatting for different analyses or datasets.

6.6.1 Transferring plot formatting within one project

To transfer plot formatting within one project, you need to use the “Apply...” button on the bottom left of the Plots tab and select “From plot” in the window that opens:

6.6.1.1 Selecting the source and target plots

The window allows you to select the source plot, which is the plot that has the formatting you want to transfer, and the target plots, which are the plots that you want to apply the formatting to. You can select all plots by clicking on the Select all button, or select all plots specific to some observation id with the “Fast selection”.

6.6.1.2 Choosing the sections to transfer

You can also choose which sections of the configuration you want to transfer: Stratify, Settings, or Preferences.

Plot formatting: STRATIFY SETTINGS PREFERENCES

By default, Stratify and Preferences are selected.

- The Stratify section includes the options to stratify the plots by covariates or occasions.
- The Settings section includes the options to customize the content of the plots: elements displayed or not on the plots, such as the legend, the grid, the observed data points, etc, and calculation settings such as the axes, bins etc.
- The Preferences section includes the options to change the colors, fonts, sizes, etc.

Once you have selected the source plot, the target plots, and the sections to transfer, you can click on the Apply button to transfer the plot configurations.

6.6.2 Transferring plot formatting across projects with plot presets

To transfer plot formatting across different projects, you need to use the **plot presets** feature, which allows you to define and apply presets for plot configurations.

6.6.2.1 Defining a plot preset

To define a plot preset, you need to first set up your plot configuration as you would like by choosing the stratification, preferences, and settings options for each plot (you can use the transfer or plot formatting between plots within the same project, described in the first section, to help you). Then, you can save this configuration as a preset by clicking on the Save icon in the Apply from the Plot Formatting panel:

You will be asked to give a name and a description to your preset, and to select which sections of the formatting you want to include in the preset among Stratify, Settings and Preferences. If the project has several types of observations, only the plots corresponding to one of them can be used to define the preset so it is necessary to select the observation id. You can also choose to set this preset as your default, which means that when you click on Reset, the plot formatting from this preset will be applied instead of the system default.

New custom preset from current plots

Name: From Obs ID: 1_Cp ▾

1_Cp
2_Cm

STRATIFY
 SETTINGS
 PREFERENCES

Description:
Add description

Use this preset as default to generate plots in all MonolixSuite apps

CANCEL
CREATE

6.6.2.2 Applying a plot preset

After saving your preset, it will be available in the list of presets that you can choose from when you click on "From preset" in the window that opens with "Apply..." in the Plot Formatting panel.

Apply formatting...

From plot Observed data | Obs ID: 1_Cp ▾

From preset MyPlotPreset ▾

Plot formatting: ▾ PREFER

- Greyscale_Preferences
- Typical_Reporting_Settings
- CompanySettings
- GreyScaleMargins_Monolix
- GreyScaleMargins_PKanalix
- MyPlotPreset

...to the following

Observed data

Observed data

You can apply your preset to a list of plots in another project, by opening this project, clicking on “Apply...” and “From preset” and by selecting the preset and the target plots, and finally clicking on Apply. This will transfer the plot configurations from the preset to the target plots.

The target plots must be the same type of plots that were used to define the preset: for example if no CA plot had been generated in the project used to define the preset, then the plot preset cannot be applied to a CA plot in a new project, as there is no CA formatting option to apply.

Note that axis limits values and bins settings are not saved as part of the preset because they are considered too project-specific.

Note this major difference between “Apply formatting from plot” and “Apply formatting from preset”:

- “Apply formatting from plot”: applies **selected options from the source plot only** to **all selected target plots**.
 - Example: if you select:
 - the NCA data plot stratified by STUDY as source plot
 - and the Observed data plot as target plot,
 - and “Stratify” section in plot formatting to be transferred,
 - after applying the formatting, you will obtain the Observed data plot stratified by STUDY.
- “Apply formatting from preset”: applies **selected options from each plot** saved in the preset **to the corresponding plot only** in your project.
 - Example: if you saved a preset:
 - from a project where the NCA data plot is stratified by STUDY but not the Observed data plot,
 - including the “Stratify” section,
 - after applying that preset to another project, you will obtain the NCA data plot stratified by STUDY, but not the Observed data plot.

6.6.2.3 Managing plot presets

You can also manage your presets by going to Settings > Manage presets > Plot formatting.

This will open a window where you can see all presets, modify, update or remove your custom presets, and export or import them as separate files with a lixpst extension. That way you can easily share your presets with your colleagues or collaborators to standardize your plot formatting.

6.6.3 Applying predefined plot formatting

In addition to your custom presets, MonolixSuite also provides two predefined presets that you can use to apply plot formatting. These presets are:

- **Greyscale_Preferences:** This preset affects only the Preferences section of the plot configurations, and produces publication-ready greyscale plots with optimized size and spacing of the texts to improve readability of the plots (example shown below for the NCA Individual fits).

- **Typical_Reporting_Settings:** This preset affects only the Settings section of the plot configuration, and corresponds to plot settings typically chosen to report the analysis results. It has additional settings for Monolix plots, but in PKanalix it only removes the grid in the background for all plots:

You can apply these presets to any plot in your project by selecting them from the list of presets and clicking on Apply. You can also combine these presets with your own presets or with the Apply from plot feature, to create the plot configuration that suits your needs.

6.6.4 Restoring default plot configuration

6.6.4.1 Using the Reset button

If you want to restore the default plot configuration, you can click on the Reset icon in the Apply from plot panel. This will reset all plots to the system default, or to your custom default if you have defined one.

Note that resetting the plot configuration will not affect the plot presets that you have defined or imported. You can still apply them to any plot after resetting.

6.6.4.2 Defining a custom default

To define a custom default, you need to create a preset and select the option “Use this preset as default” when saving it. This will make this preset the default configuration for all plots. You can also unset a preset as default by going to Settings > Manage presets > Plot formatting, and unchecking the option “Use this preset as default” for the preset.

7 Reporting

7.1 Overview

Starting from the 2023R1 version of the MonolixSuite, PKanalix includes a feature of automated report generation. This feature is available in PKanalix through Export > Generate report. After defining settings in the window that pops up and clicking on the Generate report button, a report in the form of a Microsoft Word (docx) document will be generated in the specified directory. Note that reports generated using command line and lixoftConnectors will contain tables but no plots. Reporting module is not available on CentOS 7.

To see examples of a full workflow of report generation in PKanalix, you can visit [this page](#).

7.1.1 Report generation strategies

When selecting Export > Generate report..., there are two different strategies available for report generation:

1. **Using a default template file** – choosing this option will generate the report containing tables of NCA settings, individual NCA metrics, summary of NCA metrics, BE settings and results, CA settings, individual CA parameters, summary of CA parameters and CA cost, as well as all plots available in the interface using their current settings. This option allow to obtain a basic report with all results in one click.
2. **Using a custom template file** – if users choose this option, they will be required to provide a path to the template word file which contains placeholders that will be replaced by tables, plots and keywords when generating the report.

Several other options are available in the pop-up window after the Generate report option is clicked on:

1. **Document watermark** – users can specify a custom text that will appear as a watermark in the report. Font family, font size, color, layout and transparency can be specified, if text is entered into the Text input widget.
2. **Generated report file** – users can choose if the generated report will be saved next to the project file (in that case only the name of the generated report file needs to be given to PKanalix) or in a custom directory (absolute path that includes the generated report file name needs to be given).
3. **Table styles** (only when the custom template file option is selected) – users can choose a style for tables from the list of styles available by default in Microsoft Word. This setting can be

overridden by specifying the style directly in the table placeholder. This way custom user-created or company-specific styles can be used.

7.1.2 Default template file

Selecting the option to use the default template file to generate a report gives users a possibility to quickly generate a document containing results of an analysis.

Such a report will consist of:

1. name of the PKanalix project
2. data set file name,
3. a date of report generation,
4. a table containing settings used in NCA analysis (if NCA was run),
5. a table of individual NCA parameters with mean and CV% (if NCA was run),
6. a table with a summary of NCA parameters (if NCA was run),
7. a table with BE settings (if BE was run),
8. a table with results of BE analysis (if BE was run),
9. a table of compartmental analysis (CA) calculation settings (if CA was run),
10. a table of individual CA parameters and costs with mean and CV% (if CA was run),
11. a table with a summary of CA parameters (if CA was run),
12. a table with total cost, -2LL, AIC and BIC (if CA was run),
13. all plots displayed in the GUI with settings currently defined in the interface.

By clicking on View default template, a Word document containing placeholders for all the elements that will be present in the generated report can be downloaded. This document can then be used as a basis for the creation of a custom template file.

7.1.3 Custom template file

The option to use the custom template file can be selected if a user has previously created a Word document (a template) that typically contains placeholders to be replaced by project-specific information, such as tables of results, plots or settings used in a project. Placeholders are strings with a specific syntax that define the settings and layout with which tables and plots will be generated during the report generation process.

For example, in the picture below, a template file on the right contains a placeholder for the observed data plot. So, after report generation, the report file on the right contains a plot for the observed data instead of this placeholder.

7.1.3.1 Using placeholders

There are three types of placeholders that can be used:

1. placeholders for project settings,
2. placeholders for plots,
3. placeholders for tables.

Placeholders for project settings are of format `%keyword%` and, during the report generation step, they will be replaced by project or global PKanalix settings. For example, if a custom template file contains the placeholder `%NCA_integralMethod%`, this placeholder will be replaced by the integral method (e.g. "linear up log down") used by a PKanalix project for which the report is being generated. The list of all project settings placeholders can be found [here](#).

Placeholders for plots are of format `<lixoftPLH>settings</lixoftPLH>` and, during the report generation step, they will be replaced by plots that are available in the PKanalix user interface. Placeholders for plots contain settings that describe how the generated plots should look like. All settings that are available for plots in the interface are available in reporting as well, with addition of several others that describe plot dimensions and display of captions. The list of the main plot settings placeholders can be found [here](#).

Placeholders for tables are also of format `<lixoftPLH>settings</lixoftPLH>`. Placeholders for tables contain settings that describe how the generated table should look like and they allow more flexibility in the layout compared to the display of tables in the GUI. Indeed, table placeholders can

contain settings that result in generated tables being different from the ones available in the Results tab of the PKanalix interface, such as an option to choose which rows or columns to include in the table, or to split tables in a different direction than the one present in interface. Here is the list of all settings that can be used for table placeholders.

Placeholders do not need to be written by the users. They can be generated through the interface, using the Copy reporting placeholder button which can be found next to every plot and results table. Clicking on this button will display the corresponding placeholder in a pop-up window. The displayed placeholder can then be copied to a template file and will be replaced by the table or plot, exactly as they are shown in the interface, with all stratification options and display settings applied.

Let's take a look at how "Copy reporting placeholder" buttons work on a specific example. If we load the demo project_censoring.pkx, go to the Observed data plot and click on the Copy reporting placeholder button above the plot, a pop-up window will appear containing the placeholder for the plot, which can then be used in a report template to generate the plot that looks exactly like the plot currently shown in the interface. As you can see on the screenshot below, the placeholder contains information about plot type, plot size, caption and axes labels.

If we now close the pop-up, enable legend and open the pop-up again, the placeholder will contain the enabled legend setting and, if we put the placeholder in a report template, the generated plot will have a legend present in its corner, as shown in the screenshot on the right.

Figure 1: Concentration-time profiles

If we would like our report to have the Observed data plot stratified by a categorical covariate, *STUDY*, we can stratify the plot in the interface and click on the Copy reporting placeholder button again to generate a placeholder for this plot, as shown on the images below. You can notice that the generated placeholder now contains settings stratification and layout, which control stratification and plot layout.

Figure 1: Concentration-time profiles

There are several options present inside the “Placeholder for Report Template” pop-up:

1. **indent** – determines number of spaces used for indentation of settings in the placeholder,
2. **flow level** – determines the compactness of placeholders, i.e how often we start a new line (lower the number, more compact the placeholder will be),
3. **dimensions units** – gives the ability to choose if width and height will be in cm or inches,
4. **lock aspect ratio** – if on, changing width or height will change the other dimension to keep the aspect ratio present on the screen.

It is possible to edit placeholders directly inside the pop-up. Clicking on the **Preview** button will generate and open a Word document containing a plot or a table described with the placeholder. This option is especially useful when a user manually modifies placeholders, to check if the syntax and the behavior are correct.

Copy to clipboard button will copy the placeholder with the <lixoftPLH> tag, ready to be pasted to the custom Word template.

7.1.3.2 Using areTaskResultsAvailable

Besides placeholders, templates can include the `areTaskResultsAvailable` tag, which can be used to display part of the template conditionally in the report.

For example, if a template contains the text:

```
<? areTaskResultsAvailable(nca) ?>  
Show this if NCA has been run  
</?>
```

The text “Show this if NCA has been run” will be present in the generated report, only if NCA results are available, otherwise the tags and the text will not be present in the generated report. Besides text, it is possible to include placeholders inside the `areTaskResultsAvailable` tag. Keywords that can be used inside the parentheses are “nca” for non-compartmental analysis, “be” for bioequivalence and “ca” for compartmental analysis.

7.1.4 Renamings

In the PKanalix Preferences, there is an option to replace default names of NCA parameters by custom names (see screenshot below). Changing these options will change the names in the interface (after restarting the program) and in generated reports.

A section Reporting placeholder entry renamings in Preferences can be used to change words and phrases that will appear in generated reports by default. For example, if we give alias “LeastSquareMean” to a placeholder entry “AdjustedMean”, the word “AdjustedMean” in the BE table generated by the reporting feature will be replaced by the word “LeastSquareMean”.

NCA parameters renamings	
Re-run or reload the project for changes to take effect	
Parameter	Alias
AUCINF_D_obs	AUC _{0-inf} /Dose
AUCINF_D_pred	AUC _{0-inf, pred} /Dose
AUCINF_obs	AUC _{0-inf}
AUCINF_pred	AUC _{0-inf, pred}
AUC_Int	AUC _{t0-t1}
AUC_Int_D	AUC _{t0-t1} /Dose
AUC_PerCentBack_Ext_obs	% AUC backextrapolated
AUC_PerCentBack_Ext_pred	% AUC backextrapolated _{pred}
AUC_PerCentExtrap_obs	% extrapolated AUC

Reporting placeholder entry renamings	
Use the <code>__void__</code> alias to get an empty table cell	
Placeholder entry	Alias
-2LL	
AIC	
AdjustedMean	LeastSquareMean
BE	
BIC	
BLQ	
Bioequivalence	
CILower	
CIRawLower	

In addition, it is possible to rename words found in generated tables, by specifying an argument `renamings` inside the placeholder. This allows users to change words present in the data set as well. For example, if an imported data set contains a column "Formulation" with values T (for the test drug) and R (for the reference drug), specifying the following inside a placeholder will replace all occurrences of word "T" inside the table with "test" and "R" with "reference":

```
renamings:
  T: test
  R: reference
```

For categorical covariates, it is possible to specify both the covariate name and the covariate modality to be replaced, in order to avoid ambiguities if category "0" appears in several covariates. In addition, quotes can be used if spaces are needed within the strings:

```
renamings:
  SEX#0: Male
  SEX#1: Female
  RACE#0: Caucasian
  RACE#1: "African american"
  RACE#2: Hispanic
```


Respecting the indentation before the modalities to replace and the space after the ":" is crucial to have the placeholder properly recognized.

7.1.5 Generating reports from the command line

It is possible to generate a report directly through the command line, without using the PKanalix interface. This can be useful when running PKanalix on a server.

 Note that reports generated via command line will not contain plots. This is a known limitation of the current implementation of the reporting feature. If generating reports with plots from R or from the command line is important for you, please let us know so that we take it into account for future versions.

To generate a report via command line, the executable `reportGenerator` can be called from the `lib` folder (typically `$HOME/Lixoft/MonolixSuite2024R1/lib/`):

```
reportGenerator -p pkanalix_project_path
```

Multiple options can be provided to `reportGenerator`:

<code>-?, -h, -help</code>	Displays the help.
<code>-p, -project <path></code>	Project file to load
<code>-tpl, -template <path></code>	Template .docx file used as reporting base (if not provided a default report file is generated)
<code>-onxt, -output-next-project <[true], false></code>	Generate report next to project
<code>-op, -output-path <path></code>	Generated report file name (if <code>output-next-project</code> is true) or complete path (if <code>output-next-project</code> is false)
<code>-tab, -tables-style <style></code>	Table style sheet applied on generated tables
<code>-wt, -watermark-text <text></code>	Watermark text
<code>-wff, -watermark-font-family <[Arial], ...></code>	Watermark font family
<code>-wfs, -watermark-font-size <integer></code>	Watermark font size
<code>-wc, -watermark-color <[255:0:0]></code>	Watermark color (RGB)
<code>-wl, -watermark-layout <[horizontal], diagonal></code>	Watermark layout

```
-wst, -watermark-semi-transparent <[true],
false>
```

Watermark semi-transparent

7.2 Reporting examples

7.2.1 NCA summary table split by a covariate horizontally

- example: demo **project_Theo_extravasc_SS.pkx**

```
<lixoftPLH>
data:
  task: nca
  metrics: [Nobs, mean, CV, min,
median, max]
  parameters: [Cmax, AUClast,
CLss_F, Vz_F, HL_Lambda_z]
display:
  units: true
  inlineUnits: true
  metricsDirection: horizontal
  significantDigits: 4
  fitToContent: true
stratification:
  state: {split: [FORM]}
  splitDirection: [h]
</lixoftPLH>
```

FORM	Metrics	ref						test					
		N	mean	CV(%)	min	median	max	N	mean	CV(%)	min	median	max
	C _{max} (mg·L ⁻¹)	12	17.82	24.05	11.74	17.27	27.23	12	13.39	21.24	10.08	12.95	18.88
	AUC _{0-∞} (h·mg·L ⁻¹)	12	258.35	35.86	138.39	238.73	469.12	12	234.49	25.33	150.55	230	335.41
	CL _{ss} F (L·h ⁻¹)	12	3.47	35.63	1.71	3.35	5.78	12	3.62	25.32	2.39	3.49	5.31
	V _d F (L)	12	34.16	30	19.47	32.63	62.1	12	41.77	20.99	28.25	41.75	61.96
	T _{1/2} (h)	12	7.26	29.4	4.27	7.81	11.59	12	8.51	39.16	5.49	7.36	18.01

7.2.2 NCA summary table split by a covariate vertically

- example: demo **project_aPSCCK9_SAD.pkx**

In this example, the parameters are listed vertically, the summary metrics horizontally and the table is split by dose group vertically. The renamings are used to replace the summary metrics names.

```

<lixoftPLH>
data:
  task: nca
  metrics: [Nobs, mean, CV, min,
median, max]
  parameters: [AUCINF_D_obs,
AUClast_D, CL_F_obs, Cmax_D,
HL_Lambda_z, Tmax, Vz_F_obs]
display:
  units: true
  inlineUnits: true
  metricsDirection: horizontal
  significantDigits: 2
  fitToContent: true
stratification:
  state: {split: [DOSE_mg]}
  splitDirection: [v]
renamings:
  mean: MEAN
  Dose_mg: "Dose group"
  Metrics: "Parameter"
  min: MIN
  median: MEDIAN
  max: MAX
</lixoftPLH>

```

Dose group	Parameter	N	MEAN	CV(%)	MIN	MEDIAN	MAX
150mg	AUC _{0-inf} /Dose (d·L ⁻¹)	5	1.23	29.18	0.91	1.16	1.8
	AUC _{0-last} /Dose (d·L ⁻¹)	6	1.38	37.89	0.89	1.22	2.22
	CL/F (L·d ⁻¹)	5	0.86	25.5	0.55	0.86	1.1
	C _{max} /Dose (L ⁻¹)	6	0.076	38.99	0.054	0.066	0.13
	T _{1/2} (d)	5	5.78	10.66	4.75	5.92	6.4
	T _{max} (d)	6	6	40.82	3	7	9
300mg	V _d /F (L)	5	7.33	33.66	3.8	7.34	10.16
	AUC _{0-inf} /Dose (d·L ⁻¹)	6	2.13	28.97	0.95	2.27	2.7
	AUC _{0-last} /Dose (d·L ⁻¹)	6	2.11	29.06	0.95	2.26	2.7
	CL/F (L·d ⁻¹)	6	0.53	48.54	0.37	0.44	1.05
	C _{max} /Dose (L ⁻¹)	6	0.091	23.37	0.051	0.095	0.11
	T _{1/2} (d)	6	7.4	11.51	6.37	7.42	8.52
800mg	T _{max} (d)	6	6.67	22.58	5	7	9
	V _d /F (L)	6	5.57	41.38	3.73	5.22	10.02
	AUC _{0-inf} /Dose (d·L ⁻¹)	6	2.19	19.55	1.53	2.27	2.73
	AUC _{0-last} /Dose (d·L ⁻¹)	6	2.15	20.98	1.44	2.25	2.68
	CL/F (L·d ⁻¹)	6	0.47	21.98	0.37	0.44	0.65
	C _{max} /Dose (L ⁻¹)	6	0.095	27.15	0.074	0.089	0.14
	T _{1/2} (d)	6	11	15.21	9.43	10.69	13.59
	T _{max} (d)	6	6	45.95	3	6	9
	V _d /F (L)	6	7.37	14.81	6.17	7.23	9.36

7.2.3 Individual NCA parameters and summary metrics in a single table

- example: demo **project_aPSCCK9_SAD.pkx**

By default when copying the tables from the GUI, individual NCA parameters and summary metrics are in two different tables but it is possible to merge them together by listing both ID and the summary metrics in the `metrics` argument. In this example, the table is also split by dose group and renamings are used.

```

<lixoftPLH>
data:
  task: nca
  metrics: [ID, mean, CV]
  parameters: [AUCINF_D_obs,
Cl_F_obs, Cmax_D, HL_Lambda_z, Tmax]
display:
  units: true
  inlineUnits: false
  metricsDirection: vertical
  significantDigits: 2
  fitToContent: true
stratification:
  state: {split: [DOSE_mg]}
  splitDirection: [v]
renamings:
  mean: MEAN
  Dose_mg: "Dose group"
</lixoftPLH>

```

Dose group	ID	AUC _{0-inf} /Dose (d·L ⁻¹)	CL/F (L·d ⁻¹)	C _{max} /Dose (L ⁻¹)	T _{1/2} (d)	T _{max} (d)
150mg	1			0.13		3
	2	1.8	0.55	0.083	4.75	7
	3	1.32	0.76	0.074	5.78	7
	4	0.91	1.1	0.054	6.4	7
	5	0.96	1.04	0.056	6.03	3
	6	1.16	0.86	0.058	5.92	9
	MEAN	1.23	0.86	0.076	5.78	6
CV(%)	29.18	25.5	38.99	10.66	40.82	
300mg	7	0.95	1.05	0.051	6.6	9
	8	2.1	0.48	0.089	7.73	7
	9	2.7	0.37	0.1	7.1	7
	10	2.39	0.42	0.11	8.52	5
	11	2.15	0.47	0.1	8.1	5
	12	2.46	0.41	0.09	6.37	7
	MEAN	2.13	0.53	0.091	7.4	6.67
CV(%)	28.97	48.54	23.37	11.51	22.58	
800mg	13	1.53	0.65	0.074	9.94	9
	14	1.87	0.53	0.082	9.43	9
	15	2.22	0.45	0.079	9.49	5
	16	2.48	0.4	0.097	11.44	7
	17	2.73	0.37	0.14	13.59	3
	18	2.32	0.43	0.097	12.12	3
	MEAN	2.19	0.47	0.095	11	6
CV(%)	19.55	21.98	27.15	15.21	45.95	

7.2.4 BE table for absolute bioavailability

- example: demo **project_parallel_absBioavailability.pkx**

The default column name can be renamed using the `renamings` section to state “relative bioavailability” instead of “bioequivalence”.

```

<lixoftPLH>
data:
  task: be
  table: confidenceIntervals
  metrics: [Ratio, CILower, CIUpper]
  parameters: [AUCINF_obs, AUClast]
display:
  units: true
  inlineUnits: true
  significantDigits: 4
  fitToContent: true
renamings:
  bioequivalence: "Relative
bioavailability (%) based on:"
  CILower: "Lower 90% CI"
  CIUpper: "Upper 90% CI"
</lixoftPLH>

```

ORAL

Parameter	Relative bioavailability (%) based on:		
	Ratio	Lower 90% CI	Upper 90% CI
AUC _{0-inf} (h·ug·L ⁻¹)	87.9105	81.0865	95.3089
AUC _{0-last} (h·ug·L ⁻¹)	87.856	81.2746	94.9703

7.2.5 Table of NCA settings

- example: demo **project_censoring.pkx**

Data type	%data_type%
Dose type	%NCA_administration Type%
Weighting for λz slope calculation	%NCA_lambdaWeighting%
Point selection method for λz slope calculation	%NCA_lambdaRule%
AUC calculation method	%NCA_integralMethod%
BLQ before Tmax treated as	%NCA_blqMethodBeforeTmax%
BLQ after Tmax treated as	%NCA_blqMethodAfterTmax%

Data type	plasma
Dose type	extravascular
Weighting for λz slope calculation	uniform
Point selection method for λz slope calculation	adjusted R2
AUC calculation method	linear trapezoidal linear
BLQ before Tmax treated as	zero
BLQ after Tmax treated as	LOQ/2

7.2.6 Individual NCA parameters for a group

- example: demo **DoseAndLOQ_byCategory.pkx**

```

<lixoftPLH>
data:
  task: nca
  metrics: [ID]
  parameters: [AUCINF_D_obs,
AUCINF_obs, AUClast, AUClast_D, Cmax,
Cmax_D, Tmax]
display:
  units: true
  inlineUnits: true
  metricsDirection: vertical
  significantDigits: 2
  fitToContent: true
stratification:
  state: {split: [STUDY], filter:
[[STUDY, [1]]]}

```

STUDY	ID	AUC _{0-inf} /Dose	AUC _{0-inf}	AUC _{0-last}	AUC _{0-last} /Dose	C _{max}	C _{max} /Dose	T _{max}
SD_400mg	1	0.19	77.18	76.69	0.19	3.63	0.0091	14
	2	0.26	103.32	103.16	0.26	5.91	0.015	14
	3	0.15	60.29	60.23	0.15	6.1	0.015	8
	4	0.28	111.57	111.07	0.28	5.24	0.013	16
	5	0.23	92.78	92.54	0.23	4.83	0.012	8
	6	0.22	88.78	88.51	0.22	4.55	0.011	12
	7	0.22	89.74	89.56	0.22	7.18	0.018	12
	8	0.55	218.6	209.84	0.52	8.35	0.021	8
	9	0.34	134.01	132.98	0.33	5.77	0.014	16
	10	0.22	89.08	88.98	0.22	6.19	0.015	16
	11	0.19	74.35	74.05	0.19	6.28	0.016	10
	12	0.25	100.25	100.13	0.25	6.15	0.015	10

```
splitDirection: [v]
</lixoftPLH>
```

7.2.7 NCA summary table with summary metrics filtered by group

- example: demo **DoseAndLOQ_byCategory.pkx**

```
<lixoftPLH>
data:
  task: nca
  metrics: [Nobs, mean, SE, CV, min,
median, max, geoMean, harmMean]
  parameters: [AUCINF_D_obs,
AUCINF_obs, AUClast, AUClast_D, Cmax,
Cmax_D, Tmax]
display:
  units: true
  inlineUnits: true
  metricsDirection: vertical
  significantDigits: 2
  fitToContent: true
stratification:
  state: {split: [STUDY], filter:
[[STUDY, [1]]]}
  splitDirection: [v]
</lixoftPLH>
```

STUDY		AUC _{0-inf} /Dose	AUC _{0-_{last}}	AUC _{0-_{last}}	AUC _{0-_{last}} /Dose	C _{max}	C _{max} /Dose	T _{max}
SD_400mg	N	12	12	12	12	12	12	12
	mean	0.26	103.33	102.31	0.26	5.83	0.015	12
	SE	0.03	11.8	11.16	0.028	0.36	0.0009	0.92
	CV(%)	39.57	39.57	37.78	37.78	21.33	21.33	26.59
	min	0.15	60.29	60.23	0.15	3.63	0.0091	8
	median	0.23	91.26	91.05	0.23	6.01	0.015	12
	max	0.55	218.6	209.84	0.52	8.35	0.021	16
	GeoMean	0.24	97.86	97.24	0.24	5.71	0.014	11.6
	HarmMean	0.23	93.71	93.29	0.23	5.58	0.014	11.19

7.2.8 Individual covariate table

- example: demo **project_M2000_bolus_SD.pkx**

By using `excludedParameters: all`, it is possible to hide all parameters and keep only covariates.

```
<lixoftPLH>
data:
  task: nca
  metrics: [ID]
  excludedParameters: all
  covariates: all
  covariatesAfterParameters: true
display:
  units: true
  inlineUnits: true
  metricsDirection: vertical
  significantDigits: 4
```

```
fitToContent: true
</lixoftPLH>
```

ID	AGE	HT	WT	GENDER
271	69	157	63.7	F
272	66.8	165	66.5	M
273	67.7	163	57.1	F
274	73.7	167	81.3	M
275	68	149	61.4	F
276	73.6	189	88.6	M
277	67.8	169	82.6	M
278	73.2	165	66	F
279	66.5	178	80.4	M
280	65.6	173.5	80	M
281	66.8	170	57.9	M
282	73.5	174	78.8	M

7.2.9 Included in LambdaZ table

- example: demo **project_censoring.pqx**

```
<lixoftPLH>
data:
  task: nca
  table: pointsIncludedForLambdaZ
  metrics: [ID, time, concentration,
BLQ, includedForLambdaZ]
display:
  significantDigits: 2
  fitToContent: true
</lixoftPLH>
```

ID	time	concentration	BLQ	included for λ_z
1	0	0	0	0
1	0.5	3.05	0	0
1	2	5.92	0	0
1	4	4.7	0	1
1	6	4.14	0	1
1	8	4.65	0	1
1	12	2.64	0	1
1	18	2	0	1
1	24	0.9	1	1
1	30	0.9	1	1
2	0	0	0	0
2	0.5	6.24	0	0
2	2	7.08	0	0
2	4	5.82	0	1

7.2.10 Individual NCA parameters for ref and test

- example: demo **project_Theo_extravasc_SD.pqx**

The occasion column is shown by default but can be hidden with `nbOccDisplayed: 0`.

```

<lixoftPLH>
data:
  task: nca
  metrics: [ID]
  parameters: [AUCINF_obs, AUClast,
Cmax]
  covariates: FORM
  covariatesAfterParameters: false
  nbOccDisplayed: 0
display:
  units: true
  inlineUnits: true
  metricsDirection: vertical
  significantDigits: 3
  fitToContent: true
</lixoftPLH>

```

ID	FORM	AUCINF_obs (h·mg·L ⁻¹)	AUClast (h·mg·L ⁻¹)	Cmax (mg·L ⁻¹)
1	ref	181.075	178.315	9.05
1	test	210.284	207.4	10.2
2	ref	114.434	114.04	7.94
2	test	98.695	97.56	4.72
3	test	225.896	224.12	9.82
3	ref	241.111	238.275	11.49
4	ref	176.715	173.665	10.51
4	test	182.391	179.885	8.99
5	test	146.483	144.02	7.64
5	ref	139.567	139.035	11.17
6	test	97.156	96.435	5.93
6	ref	123.944	122.715	7.73
7	ref	146.768	145.005	10.83
7	test	137.645	136.265	6.23

7.2.11 Replacing missing values by "NC"

- example: demo **project_aPSCk9_SAD.pkx** with modified point selection for lambdaZ for id 1

By default, NCA parameters which could not be calculated are displayed as empty cell. In order to replace the empty cell by a string, it is possible to display a NaN using `displayNaNs: true` and then using the `renamings` section to replace the NaN by another string, such as NC for instance.

```

<lixoftPLH>
data:
  task: nca
  metrics: [ID]
  parameters: [AUCINF_D_obs,
AUClast_D, Cl_F_obs, Cmax_D]
  covariates: none
  covariatesAfterParameters: true
display:
  units: true
  inlineUnits: true
  metricsDirection: vertical
  significantDigits: 2
  fitToContent: true
  displayNaNs: true
</lixoftPLH>

```

ID	AUC _{0-inf} /Dose (d·L ⁻¹)	AUC _{0-last} /Dose (d·L ⁻¹)	Cl/F (L·d ⁻¹)	C _{max} /Dose (L ⁻¹)
1	NC	2.22	NC	0.13
2	1.8	1.8	0.55	0.083
3	1.32	1.3	0.76	0.074
4	0.91	0.89	1.1	0.054
5	0.96	0.95	1.04	0.056
6	1.16	1.14	0.86	0.058
7	0.95	0.95	1.05	0.051
8	2.1	2.07	0.48	0.089
9	2.7	2.7	0.37	0.1
10	2.39	2.39	0.42	0.11
11	2.15	2.14	0.47	0.1
12	2.46	2.43	0.41	0.09

7.3 List of reporting keywords

7.3.1 List of all reporting keywords

This page provides a list of placeholders for project settings that can be used in report templates for PKanalix projects.

Keyword	Description	Possible values
%NCA_administrationType%	Administration type for NCA parameter calculation.	"intravenous" or "extravascular" if one adm id, otherwise "1: intravenous, 2: extravascular" with 1/2 corresponding to the administration id
%NCA_ObsIdUsed%	Observation id used for the NCA calculations.	string of the observation id, e.g "PK" or "1"
%data_type%	Type of data defined on the Data page.	"plasma" or "urine" if one observation id, otherwise "PK: plasma, PD: plasma" with PK/PD corresponding to the observation ids
%NCA_integralMethod%	Method for AUC and AUMC calculation and interpolation.	as in the associated dropdown menu (linear trapezoidal linear, linear log trapezoidal, linear up log down, linear trapezoidal linear/log)
%NCA_blqMethodBeforeTmax%	Method by which the BLQ data before Tmax should be replaced.	as in the associated dropdown menu (missing, zero, LOQ, LOQ/2)
%NCA_blqMethodAfterTmax%	Method by which the BLQ data after Tmax should be replaced.	as in the associated dropdown menu (missing, zero, LOQ, LOQ/2)
%NCA_ajdr2AcceptanceCriteria%	Value of the adjusted R2 acceptance criteria for the estimation of lambda_Z.	a number
%NCA_extrapAucAcceptanceCriteria%	Value of the AUC extrapolation acceptance criteria for the estimation of lambda_Z.	a number
%NCA_spanAcceptanceCriteria%	Span acceptance criteria for the estimation of lambda_Z.	a number

%NCA_lambdaRule%	General rule for the lambda_Z estimation. Includes information about the main rule, together with settings defined in the “rules” tab.	Examples: “R2 with maximum 500 points, minimum time 20” “Time interval between 10 and 50” “Fixed number of points (3 points)”
%NCA_lambdaWeighting%	Weighting used for the lambda_Z estimation.	as in the associated dropdown menu (uniform, 1/Y, 1/Y ²)
%CA_cost%	Cost function used for CA.	as in the associated dropdown menu ((Ypred – Yobs) ² , (Ypred – Yobs) ² / Yobs, (Ypred – Yobs) ² / Ypred, (Ypred – Yobs) ² / Yobs ² , (Ypred – Yobs) ² / Ypred ² , (Ypred – Yobs) ² / Ypred * Yobs)
%CA_method%	Fit with individual parameters or with the same parameters for all individuals.	pooled fit, individual fit
%CA_blqMethod%	BLQ method for CA.	as in the associated dropdown menu (missing, zero, LOQ, LOQ/2)
%BE_level%	Level of the confidence interval for bioequivalence	a number
%BE_limits%	Limits in which the confidence interval must be to conclude the bioequivalence is true	Two numbers separated by a comma. Example: 0.8, 1.25
%BE_linearModelFactors%	Factors tested in the linear model for bioequivalence.	Data set column names. Example: ID, PERIOD, FORM, SEQ
%BE_design%	Design of a bioequivalence study.	parallel, crossover
%BE_reference%	Categorical covariate modality selected as a reference	One of the modalities present in the data set. Example: REF or IV
%TotalNbSubjects%	Total number of subjects in the data set (all observation ids together).	a number
%TotalNbSubjectsOcc%	Total number of subjects-occasions in the dataset (all observation ids together).	a number
%AvgNbDosesPerSubject%	Average number of doses per subject (any administration id, any occasion, all observation ids).	a number
%TotalNbObservations%	Total number of observations in the data set.	if one obs id, number, if several obs id, PK: xx, PD: xx

%AvgNbObservationsPerID%	Average number of observations per id (all occasions together).	if one obs id, number, if several obs id, PK: xx, PD: xx
%MinNbObservationsPerID%	Minimum number of observations per id (all occasions together).	if one obs id, number, if several obs id, PK: xx, PD: xx
%MaxNbObservationsPerID%	Maximum number of observations per id (all occasions together).	if one obs id, number, if several obs id, PK: xx, PD: xx
%PercentCensoredObservations%	Percentage of censored observations.	if one obs id, number, if several obs id, PK: xx, PD: xx
%StructModelCode%	Mlxtran code for the structural model.	whole structural model file content, as shown in the CA model tab
%reportGenerationDateTime(yy-MM-dd HH:mm:ss)%	Report generation date and time. For date format syntax, see below.	yyyy-MM-dd HH:mm:ss
%system%	Operating system on which report was generated.	Linux, macOS, Windows
%version%	Version of PKanalix with which report was generated.	2023R1
%project_fileName%	File name of the project (without path).	Example: NCA_run.pkx
%project_filePath%	File path of the project.	Example: C:/Users/user/lixoft/monolix/monolix2024R1/demos/1.creating_and_using_models/1.1.libraries_of_models/theophylline_project.mlxtran
%data_fileName%	File name of the data set (without path).	Example: data.csv

7.3.2 Report generation date and time format

These expressions may be used in *reportGenerationDateTime* for date formatting:

Expression	Output
d	The day as a number without a leading zero (1 to 31)
dd	The day as a number with a leading zero (01 to 31)

Expression	Output
ddd	The abbreviated day name ('Mon' to 'Sun').
dddd	The long day name ('Monday' to 'Sunday').
M	The month as a number without a leading zero (1 to 12)
MM	The month as a number with a leading zero (01 to 12)
MMM	The abbreviated month name ('Jan' to 'Dec').
MMMM	The long month name ('January' to 'December').
yy	The year as a two digit number (00 to 99)
yyyy	The year as a four digit number. If the year is negative, a minus sign is prepended, making five characters.

Example date format strings (assuming that the date is the 20 July 1969):

Format	Result
dd.MM.yyyy	20.07.1969
ddd MMMM d yy	Sun July 20 69
dddd	Sunday

These expressions may be used in *reportGenerationDateTime* for time formatting:

Expression	Output
h	The hour without a leading zero (0 to 23 or 1 to 12 if AM/PM display)
hh	The hour with a leading zero (00 to 23 or 01 to 12 if AM/PM display)
H	The hour without a leading zero (0 to 23, even with AM/PM display)
HH	The hour with a leading zero (00 to 23, even with AM/PM display)
m	The minute without a leading zero (0 to 59)
mm	The minute with a leading zero (00 to 59)

Expression	Output
s	The whole second, without any leading zero (0 to 59)
ss	The whole second, with a leading zero where applicable (00 to 59)
z or zz	The fractional part of the second, to go after a decimal point, without trailing zeroes. Thus "s.z" reports the seconds to full available (millisecond) precision without trailing zeroes (0 to 999). For example, "s.z" would produce "0.25" for a time a quarter second into a minute.
zzz	The fractional part of the second, to millisecond precision, including trailing zeroes where applicable (000 to 999). For example, "ss.zzz" would produce "00.250" for a time a quarter second into a minute.
AP or A	Use AM/PM display. A/AP will be replaced by 'AM' or 'PM'.
ap or a	Use am/pm display. a/ap will be replaced by 'am' or 'pm'.
aP or Ap	Use AM/PM display (since 6.3). aP/Ap will be replaced by 'AM' or 'PM'.
t	The timezone abbreviation (for example "CEST"). Note that time zone abbreviations are not unique.
tt	The timezone's offset from UTC with no colon between the hours and minutes (for example "+0200").
ttt	The timezone's offset from UTC with a colon between the hours and minutes (for example "+02:00").
tttt	The timezone name (for example "Europe/Berlin"). Note that this gives no indication of whether the datetime was in daylight-saving time or standard time, which may lead to ambiguity if the datetime falls in an hour repeated by a transition between the two.

Example time format strings (assuming that the time is 14:13:09.042):

Format	Result
hh:mm:ss.zzz	14:13:09.042
h:m:s ap	2:13:9 pm
H:m:s a	14:13:9 pm

7.4 List of table settings

The following page describes all the settings that can be used in table placeholders in reporting templates. Placeholders for tables can include four different groups of settings. These are:

- “**data**” (required) – containing settings about table content, such as type of the table, and rows and columns that the table will contain,
- “**display**” (optional) – containing information about table display (e.g., number of significant digits to which the values in the table should be rounded, table direction, style, ...)
- “**stratification**” (optional) – containing information about table splitting and/or filtering,
- “**renamings**” (optional) – containing various words present in the data set or PKanalix that should be reworded in the table.

Settings inside these groups of settings need to be indented or put inside curly brackets. It is crucial to respect the indentation rules and the space after the “:” for the placeholder to be properly interpreted.

7.4.1 Data

Data settings define the type of the table that will be generated, as well as rows and columns that the table will contain. Here is the list of all settings of the data group of settings, along with their descriptions:

Setting	Table	Required	Possible values	Description
task	All	yes	be, ca, nca	Task of which the table represents the results.
table	Points included for lambdaZ (NCA) Anova table (BE) Table of CVs (BE) Table of confidence intervals (BE) Cost table (CA)	yes	pointsIncludedForLambdaZ, anova, coefficientsOfVariation, confidenceIntervals, cost	Table type. If empty, CA or NCA parameters table will be generated (depending on the task argument).
formulation	Table of confidence intervals (BE)	no (default: all)	name of one of the test formulations present in the data set, or “all”	In case of confidenceIntervals table and multiple test formulations, setting can be used to select one of the non-reference formulations.

metrics	Table of parameters (CA or NCA)	no	"all" or one or several of: ID, min, Q1, median, Q3, max, mean, SD, SE, CV, Ntot, Nobs, Nmiss, geoMean, geoSD, geoCV, harmMean	If equal to "all", all available rows or columns will be present in the table. If specific metrics are given, only those rows/columns will be available in the table.
metrics	Points included for lambdaZ (NCA)	no	"all" or one or several of: ID, time, concentration, BLQ, includedForLambdaZ	If equal to "all", all available rows or columns will be present in the table. If specific metrics are given, only those rows/columns will be available in the table.
metrics	Table of confidence intervals (BE)	no	"all" or one or several of: AdjustedMean, N, Difference, CIRawLower, CIRawUpper, Ratio, CILower, CIUpper, BE	If equal to "all", all available rows or columns will be present in the table. If specific metrics are given, only those rows/columns will be available in the table.
metrics	Coefficient of variation (BE)	no	"all" or one or several of: SD, CV	If equal to "all", all available rows or columns will be present in the table. If specific metrics are given, only those rows/columns will be available in the table.
metrics	Anova table (BE)	no	"all" or one or several of: DF, SUMSQ, MEANSQ, FVALUE, PR(>F)	If equal to "all", all available rows or columns will be present in the table. If specific metrics are given, only those rows/columns will be available in the table.
metrics	Cost table (CA)	no	"all" or one or several of: Cost, -2LL, AIC, BIC	If equal to "all", all available rows or columns will be present in the table. If specific metrics are given, only those rows/columns will be available in the table.
excludedMetrics	All	no (default: none)	Same arguments as for metrics, excluding "all".	Metrics that will be excluded from the table. Handy when a user wants to keep most of them.

parameters	Table of parameters (CA/NCA)	no (default: all)	One or more of parameters calculated in NCA or CA, including Cost if CA, or "all".	Parameters that will be included in the table. Used when table setting isn't specified.
excludedParameters	Table of parameters (CA/NCA)	no (default: none)	Same arguments as for parameters, excluding "all".	Parameters that will be excluded from the table. Handy when a user wants to keep most of them.
factors	Anova table (BE)	no (default: all)	One or more of the headers of columns used in the BE linear model, including Residuals, or "all".	Factors included in the linear model.
excludedFactors	Anova table (BE)	no (default: none)	Same arguments as for factors, excluding "all".	Factors included in the linear model.
ids	Table of parameters (CA/NCA) Points included for lambdaZ (NCA)	no (default: all)	One or several of IDs present in the dataset, or "all".	IDs of subjects whose parameters should be shown in the table. The summary statistics will be calculated on all individuals, not just ones shown in the table. If not present, default is "all".
excludedIds	Table of parameters (CA/NCA) Points included for lambdaZ (NCA)	no (default: none)	Same arguments as for ids, excluding "all".	IDs of subjects whose parameters should be excluded from the table. The summary statistics will be calculated on all individuals, not just ones shown in the table.
covariates	Table of parameters (CA/NCA)	no (default: all)	One or more of covariates present in the data set, or "all".	Which covariates to include in the table.
covariatesAfterParameters	Table of parameters (CA/NCA)	no (default: true)	true, false	If covariates should be shown after parameters in the table.
nbOccDisplayed	Table of parameters (CA/NCA) Points included for lambdaZ (NCA)	no (default: -1 meaning all)	-1 or an integer	-1 means all occasion levels are displayed. 0 mean none of the occasion levels are displayed. 1 means only the first occasion level is displayed, etc.

7.4.2 Display

Display group of settings defines how the information in the tables will be displayed. Here is the list of all settings for the display group of settings:

Setting	Table	Required	Possible values	Description	Example(s)
units	Table of parameters (CA/NCA) Anova table (BE) Table of CVs (BE) Table of confidence intervals (BE) Cost table (CA)	no (default: true)	true, false	If true, units will be output next to parameters.	units: true
CDISCNames	Table of parameters (CA/NCA) Anova table (BE) Table of CVs (BE) Table of confidence intervals (BE) Cost table (CA)	no (default: false)	true, false	If true, CDISC names of parameters will be shown in the table.	CDISCNames: true
style	All	no (default: selected in Generate report pop-up)	Name of table styles present in the template document.	Microsoft Word document template style to apply to the table. This setting overrides the setting in the Generate report pop-up.	style: "Medium Grid 1 – Accent 1"
metricsDirection	All	no (default: vertical)	vertical, horizontal	Direction of metrics.	metricsDirection: horizontal
significantDigits	All	no (default: taken from Preferences)	positive integers	Number of significant digits values in the table will be rounded to.	significantDigits: 3
trailingZeros	All	no (default: taken from Preferences)	true, false	If trailing zeros should be shown in the tables.	trailingZeros: true

inlineUnits	Table of parameters (CA/NCA) Anova table (BE) Table of CVs (BE) Table of confidence intervals (BE) Cost table (CA)	no (default: true)	true, false	If units should be inline with parameters. If false, there will be a new line between a parameter name and a unit.	inlineUnits: false
fitToContent	All	no (default: true)	true, false	If true, width of the table will be equal to the width of content, otherwise width of the table will be equal to the width of the page.	fitToContent: false
caption	All	no (default: no caption)	a phrase inside quotation marks	Caption that will appear next to the table.	caption: "Individual NCA parameters"
captionAbove	All	no (default: false)	true, false	If true, caption will be positioned above the table. If false, caption will be positioned below the table.	captionAbove: true
fontSize	All	no (default: 12)	a number	Font size of the table content (will not be applied to the caption).	fontSize: 10
displayNaNs	All	no (default: false)	true or false	Display NCA parameters which could not be calculated as NaN instead of empty cell	displayNaNs: true

7.4.3 Stratification

Stratification group of settings defines how the table will be split. List of stratification settings:

Setting	Table	Required	Possible values	Description	Example(s)
---------	-------	----------	-----------------	-------------	------------

state	Table of parameters (CA/NCA)	no	Two possible subsettings: – split – can contain header names of covariates and/or occasions – filter – can contain header names of covariates and/or occasions and number(s) that describe alphabetical order of modalities	Contains information of how to split the table.	state: {split: [FORM]} state: {split: [FORM, OCC]} state: {filter: [[FORM, [1]]]} state: {filter: [[SEQ, [1, 2]]]} state: {filter: [[FORM, [1]], [OCC, [1]]]} state: {split: [FORM, OCC], filter: [[OCC, [1]], [SEQ, [1]]]}
splitDirection	Table of parameters (CA/NCA)	no	One or more of v, h	In which direction the table should be split. Number of arguments corresponds to number of covariates by which the table was split.	splitDirection: [v] splitDirection: [v, v] splitDirection: [v, h]

Let's take a look at the demo project `project_crossover_bioequivalence.pbx`. It contains data from a 2x2 crossover bioequivalence study of two controlled release formulations of theophylline. We would like to generate a placeholder for the summary table of NCA parameters and split it across sequences and formulations. If we select that we only want to compute C_{max} and AUC_{last}, here is how a default placeholder looks like when we click on the placeholder button next to the NCA summary table and which table it produces:

```
<lixoftPLH>
data:
  task: nca
  metrics: [min, Q1, median, Q3, max, mean, SD, SE, CV, Ntot, Nobs, Nmiss, geoMean,
geoSD, geoCV, harmMean]
  parameters: [AUClast, Cmax]
display:
  units: true
  inlineUnits: true
  metricsDirection: horizontal
  significantDigits: 4
  fitToContent: true
</lixoftPLH>
```

	min	Q1	median	Q3	max	mean	SD	SE	CV(%)	Ntot	N	Nmiss	GeoMean	GeoSD	GeoCV	HarmMean
AUC _{0-tlast} (h·mg·L ⁻¹)	45.6709	116.8202	142.4099	179.027	236.6814	148.5547	46.7732	7.7955	31.4855	36	36	0	140.3561	1.4369	37.4696	130.4717
C _{max} (mg·L ⁻¹)	3.56	6.12	8.76	9.94	11.53	8.1806	2.2192	0.3699	27.1282	36	36	0	7.8445	1.3597	31.4694	7.4633

If we want to split the table by the period and the formulation, we can select the appropriate checkboxes on the right and the default placeholder will change automatically. However, doing this always splits the table vertically. We can also remove some of the statistics that we want to exclude from the table by modifying the metrics argument.

```

<lixoftPLH>
data:
  task: nca
  metrics: [min, median, max, mean, CV, Nobs, geoMean, geoCV]
  parameters: [AUClast, Cmax]
display:
  units: true
  inlineUnits: true
  metricsDirection: horizontal
  significantDigits: 4
  fitToContent: true
stratification:
  state: {split: [FORM, Period]}
  splitDirection: [v, v]
</lixoftPLH>
  
```

FORM	Period	Metrics	N	mean	CV(%)	GeoMean	GeoCV
ref	1	AUC _{0-tlast} (h·mg·L ⁻¹)	9	154.8982	26.3033	150.3623	26.1424
		C _{max} (mg·L ⁻¹)	9	9.82	11.8862	9.7571	12.1369
	2	AUC _{0-tlast} (h·mg·L ⁻¹)	9	147.6183	36.178	137.7505	43.7537
		C _{max} (mg·L ⁻¹)	9	8.3244	32.019	7.8713	39.0231
test	1	AUC _{0-tlast} (h·mg·L ⁻¹)	9	133.3989	39.8426	122.3564	49.8543
		C _{max} (mg·L ⁻¹)	9	6.4689	28.8987	6.2384	29.1102
	2	AUC _{0-tlast} (h·mg·L ⁻¹)	9	158.3035	26.9691	153.1323	28.1126
		C _{max} (mg·L ⁻¹)	9	8.1089	22.1858	7.9035	25.4489

If we want to change the direction of splitting, for example, make a split by Period horizontal, instead of vertical, we can modify the splitDirection argument.

```

<lixoftPLH>
data:
  task: nca
  metrics: [Nobs, mean, CV, geoMean, geoCV]
  parameters: [AUClast, Cmax]
display:
  
```

```

units: true
inlineUnits: true
metricsDirection: horizontal
significantDigits: 4
fitToContent: true
stratification:
  state: {split: [FORM, Period]}
  splitDirection: [v, h]
</lixoftPLH>

```

Period		1					2				
FORM	Metrics	N	mean	CV(%)	GeoMean	GeoCV	N	mean	CV(%)	GeoMean	GeoCV
ref	AUC _{0-tlast} (h·mg·L ⁻¹)	9	154.8982	26.3033	150.3623	26.1424	9	147.6183	36.178	137.7505	43.7537
	C _{max} (mg·L ⁻¹)	9	9.82	11.8862	9.7571	12.1369	9	8.3244	32.019	7.8713	39.0231
test	AUC _{0-tlast} (h·mg·L ⁻¹)	9	133.3989	39.8426	122.3564	49.8543	9	158.3035	26.9691	153.1323	28.1126
	C _{max} (mg·L ⁻¹)	9	6.4689	28.8987	6.2384	29.1102	9	8.1089	22.1858	7.9035	25.4489

7.4.4 Renamings

Renamings setting can be provided to the placeholder to replace certain words or expressions that will appear in the table with a user-defined word or expression. We will explain the usage of renamings setting on a concrete example.

Let's take a look at the demo project `project_parallel_absBioavailability.pqx`. The project contains data from 18 subjects, of which 9 received an IV formulation of a certain drug and other 9 received an oral formulation. Let's say we want to use the Bioequivalence feature of PKanalix to calculate bioavailability of the oral formulation and generate a report. It would be suitable to put a bioequivalence confidence intervals table in the report, with certain renamings.

A generated placeholder for a BE confidence intervals table, with its default settings, is shown below, including the table it generates.

```

<lixoftPLH>
data:
  task: be
  table: confidenceIntervals
  metrics: [AdjustedMean, N, Difference, CIRawLower, CIRawUpper, Ratio, CILower, CIUpper, BE]

```

```

parameters: [AUCINF_obs]
display:
  units: true
  inlineUnits: true
  significantDigits: 4
  fitToContent: true
</lixoftPLH>

```

ORAL

Parameter	ORAL		IV		Bioequivalence						
	AdjustedMean	N	AdjustedMean	N	Difference	CIRawLower	CIRawUpper	Ratio	CILower	CIUpper	BE
AUC _{0-inf} (h·ug·L ⁻¹)	223.9609	9	254.76	9	-0.1289	-0.2097	-0.04805	87.9105	81.0865	95.3089	yes

Let's say we would like to hide some of the columns and rename some of the expressions in the table. For example, it would be convenient to rename "Bioequivalence" to "Absolute bioavailability", "IV" to "intravenous", "ORAL" to "oral formulation", and "CI Lower" to "90% CI (lower)". We can then modify the placeholder to look like the one on the left and it will generate the table on the right.

```

<lixoftPLH>
data:
  task: be
  table: confidenceIntervals
  metrics: [AdjustedMean, N, Ratio, CI Lower, CI Upper]
  parameters: [AUCINF_obs]
renamings:
  IV: "intravenous"
  ORAL: "oral formulation"
  Bioequivalence: "Absolute bioavailability"
  CI Lower: "90% CI (lower)"
  CI Upper: "90% CI (upper)"
  AdjustedMean: "Adjusted mean"
</lixoftPLH>

```

Oral capsule

Parameter	Oral capsule		IV solution		Absolute bioavailability		
	Adjusted mean	N	Adjusted mean	N	Ratio	90% CI (lower)	90% CI (upper)
AUC _{0-inf}	223.9609	9	254.76	9	87.9105	81.0865	95.3089

7.5 List of plot settings

This page describes all the settings that can be used in plot placeholders and are not editable by changing settings in the interface. All of them are optional (default values are described in the Default column).

Setting	Group	Default	Possible values	Description	Example
widthCm	-	16	positive numbers	Width of the plot in the report document in centimetres.	widthCm: 16
widthInches	-	6.3	positive numbers	Width of the plot in the report document in inches.	widthInches: 6.3
heightCm	-	11.1	positive numbers	Height of the plot in the report document in centimetres.	heightCm: 11.09
heightInches	-	4.37	positive numbers	Height of the plot in the report document in inches.	heightInches: 4.37
zoom	-	100	positive numbers	Larger values will increase the label font sizes and margins.	zoom: 80
caption	-	no caption	a phrase	Caption that will appear next to the plot.	caption: Individual fits
captionAbove	-	false	true, false	If true, caption will be positioned above the plot. If false, caption will be positioned below the plot.	captionAbove: true
legendPosition	settings	ne	n, ne, e, se, s, sw, w, nw	Position of the legend, based on abbreviations of compass points.	legendPosition: sw

For all other settings, select the settings of your plot in the GUI and then click the “copy placeholder” button to see the corresponding placeholder.

8 FAQ

8.1 Frequently asked questions

We list here the questions regarding the use of PKanalix when everything runs fine. If you have an issue with download, installation, run and display, please check Frequent installation issues.

If you think there is a bug in one of the MonolixSuite apps, please check if it is already in our List of known bugs, and otherwise write us at support@lixoft.com.

8.1.1 Regulatory

- **Are NCA and CA analyses done with PKanalix accepted by the regulatory agencies like the FDA and EMA?** Yes.
- **How to cite PKanalix?** Please reference each application as here (adjusting to the version you used):

```
Monolix 2024R1, Simulations Plus, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11401936  
Simulx 2024R1, Simulations Plus, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11402004  
PKanalix 2024R1, Simulations Plus, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11401684
```

8.1.2 Running PKanalix

- **On what operating systems does PKanalix run?** PKanalix runs on Windows, Linux and MacOS platform. The requirements for each platform can be found on our download page.
- **Is it possible to run PKanalix in command line?** It is possible to run PKanalix from the R command line. This complete R API provides the full flexibility on running and modifying PKanalix projects with R functions.

8.1.3 Input data

- **Does PKanalix support sparse data?** Yes. Starting from the version 2024R1, PKanalix has a Sparse data NCA feature.
- **Does PKanalix support drug-effect or PD models?** It is possible to use custom models in CA, and PD models are available via built-in model libraries. However, a time column is required in the dataset.

- **What type of data can PKanalix handle?** Extravascular, intravenous infusion, intravenous bolus for single-dose or steady-state plasma concentration and single-dose urine data can be used. See here.
- **Can I give the concentration data and dosing data as separate files?** Yes, this is possible with the data formatting module.
- **Can I give the dosing information directly via the interface?** Yes, this is possible with the data formatting module.
- **Can I have BLQ data?** Yes, see here.
- **Can I define units?** Yes, see here.
- **Can I define variables such as “Sort” and “Carry”?** Yes, check here.
- **It is possible to define several dosing routes within a single data set?** Yes, check the [ADMINISTRATION ID](#) column.
- **Can I use dose normalization to scale the dose by a factor?** Yes. In PKanalix 2023R1, the amount can now be specified in mass of the administered dose per body mass or body surface area.

8.1.4 Settings (options)

- **How do I indicate the type of model/data?** Extravascular versus intravenous is set in the Settings window. Single versus steady-state and infusion versus bolus are imputed based on the data set column-types.
- **Can I exclude data with insufficient data?** The “Acceptance criteria” settings allow the user to define acceptance thresholds. The result tables can then be filtered in the interface according to these acceptance criteria.
- **Can I set the data as being sparse?** No, sparse data calculations are not supported. If supporting sparse data is important for you, please let us know so that we take it into account for future versions.
- **Which options are available for the lambda_z calculation?** Points to be included in the lambda_z calculation can be defined using the adjusted R2 criteria (called best fit in Winonlin), the R2 criteria, a time range or a number of points. In addition, the a specific range per individual can be defined, as well as points to include or exclude. Check the lambda_z options here and here.
- **Can I define several partial areas?** Yes.
- **Can I save settings as template for future projects?** Not as such. However, the user can set the data set headers that should be recognized automatically in “Settings > Preferences”. Moreover, browsing a new dataset in a given project keeps the calculation settings that are compatible with the new dataset.
- **Do you have a “slope selector”?** Yes, check here for information on the “Check lambda_z”.
- **Can I define a therapeutic response range?** No.
- **Can I set a user-defined weighting for the lambda_z?** No. But most common options are available as a setting.
- **Can I disable the calculation of lambda_z (curve stripping in WinNonlin)?** Yes, Lambda_z can be removed from the list of parameters to compute.

8.1.5 Settings (output results)

- **Can I change the name of the parameters?** Yes, in the preferences of PKanalix (since 2023R1 version), you can rename NCA parameters as you wish. The output files will contain both your custom names and CDISC names.
- **Can I export the result table?** The result tables are automatically saved as text files in the result folder. In addition, result tables can be copy-pasted to Excel or Word using the copy button on the top right of the tables.
- **Can I choose which parameters to show in the result table and to export to the result folder file?** Yes, see here.
- **Are the calculation rules the same as in Winonlin?** Yes.
- **Can I define myself the result folder?** By default, the result folder corresponds to the project name. However, you can define it by yourself. See here to see how to define it on the user interface.

8.1.6 Results

- **What result files are generated by PKanalix?** When running a task like NCA, CA or BE, results are automatically generated (one output file per table) in a result folder, and displayed in the RESULTS tab. Plots are also automatically generated and displayed in the PLOTS tab.
- **Can I replot the plots using another plotting software?** Yes, if you go to the menu Export and click on "Export charts data", all the data needed to reproduce the plots are stored in text files.
- **When I open a project, my results are not loaded (message "Results have not been loaded due to an old inconsistent project"). Why?** When loading a project, PKanalix checks that the project (i.e all the information saved in the .pkx file) being loaded and the project that has been used to generate the results are the same. If not, the error message is shown. In that case the results will not be loaded because they are inconsistent with the loaded project.

8.1.7 Reporting

- **Can I generate a report?** Yes, starting from PKanalix 2023R1, automated report generation is possible.
- **How can I include plots and table from different PKanalix projects into the same Word document?** It is currently not possible to include plots and tables coming from different PKanalix runs into the same Word document in one step. You can add placeholders to an already generated report and use it as a template for another project, however we are aware that this is not a very convenient solution. If generating a single report for several projects is important for you, please let us know so that we take it into account for future versions.
- **The report I generated via command line or via R do not contain plots.** This is a known limitation of the current implementation of the reporting feature. If generating reports with plots from R or from the command line is important for you, please let us know so that we take it into account for future versions.

8.2 Submission of PKanalix runs to regulatory agencies

PKanalix is used for **regulatory submissions (including the FDA and the EMA)** of NCA, BE and CA analyses. The FDA and the EMA do have access to PKanalix and the experts to understand, review and run PKanalix. In addition, regulators are also taking part in publishing research articles with PKanalix.

8.2.1 Files to include for submissions

Regulatory guidelines provide only little information on the required electronic files for submission. Based on exchanges with regulatory agencies and confirmed through past regulatory submissions using PKanalix, the following listed files in Table 1 and 2 are required for a PKanalix analysis submission package.

Table 1 lists all files needed to run PKanalix and reproduce the results and diagnostic plots. Attention must be paid to use relative file path definitions (Settings > Preferences > Use relative path) to facilitate the project transfer from one computer system to another. It is also possible to create a .zip containing all requires input files, as well as all results with Export > Share project. **Table 2** lists the files containing the key results.

Note that all files are in a human readable format. Thus, the information contained in these files can also be included into the appendices of the report creating one single document that contains everything to reproduce the results.

All MonolixSuite file types are accepted by the FDA and are listed in the "Specifications for File Format Types Using eCTD Specifications".

Table 1 Pkanalix files required for reproducibility of results

File	When to include	Content	File extension
Dataset file	Always	Input dataset	.txt, .csv, .xls, .xlsx, .sas2bdat or .xpt
Additional columns file	If "additional columns" in data formatting module was used	Additional columns appended to the dataset	.txt, .csv, .xls, .xlsx, .sas2bdat or .xpt
PKanalix project file (.pkx)	Always	Path to dataset, dataset settings (column tagging, filters, etc), NCA/BE/CA settings	.pkx
Compartmental model file	If using CA and not using a model from the libraries	Compartmental model in mlxtran syntax	.txt

Plot properties (.pkxproperties)	Always (except if file not present because only default settings)	Plot stratify, settings and preferences	.pkxproperties
-------------------------------------	---	---	----------------

Table 2 PKanalix files containing the key results

File	When to include	Content	File extension
nca/ ncaIndividualParameters .txt	If NCA has been run	Individual NCA parameters and exclusion flags	.txt
nca/ pointsIncludedForLambdaZ.txt	If NCA has been run	Individual concentrations and points included in terminal slope (lambdaZ) regression	.txt
be/ confidenceInterval_XXX.txt	If BE has been run	Confidence intervals for NCA parameters include din the BE analysis	.txt
ca/ caIndividualParameters.txt	If CA has been run	Individual CA parameters	.txt
ca/ cost.txt	If CA has been run	Cost function and likelihood of CA model	.txt

The **other output files** (nca/concentrations.txt, nca/ncaIndividualParametersSummary.txt, be/anova.txt, be/estimatedCoefficients.txt, be/variationCoef.txt, ca/caIndividualParametersSummary.txt) can also be included if needed.

8.2.2 Examples of submissions

This section lists examples of Clinical pharmacology reviews (FDA) and Assessment reports (EMA) explicitly mentioning the use of MonolixSuite.

8.2.2.1 Submissions to the FDA using MonolixSuite

- ZALTRAP (Aflibercept) - Sanofi - Clinical pharmacology review ([link](#))
- CORLANOR (Ivabradine) - Amgen - Clinical pharmacology review ([link](#))
- JEVTANA (Cabazitaxel) - Sanofi - Clinical pharmacology review ([link](#))
- PONVORY (Ponesimod) - Janssen - Clinical pharmacology review ([link](#))
- RYZNEUTA (Efbemalenograstim) - Evive Biotechnology Singapore - Integrated review ([link](#))
- EXBLIFEP (Cefepime and enmetazobactam) - Allecra Therapeutics - Integrated review ([link](#))

8.2.2.2 Submission to the EMA using MonolixSuite

- OSELTAMIVIR (Tamiflu) - Roche - Assessment report (link)
(Procedure No. EMEA/H/C/000402/II/0110/G – EMA/CHMP/186699/2015)
- BOSENTAN (Tracleer) - Actelion - Assessment report (link)
(Procedure No. EMEA/H/C/000401/II/0066 – EMA/168487/2015)
- ISATUXIMAB (Sarclisa) - Sanofi - Assessment report (link) and Statistical analysis plan (link)
(Procedure No. EMEA/H/C/004977/II/0003 – EMA/CHMP/186236/2021)

8.3 Specific applications

This page covers analyses and use cases that go beyond the typical PKanalix workflow, offering guidance for specific and non-standard applications.

8.3.1 Average absolute bioavailability

8.3.1.1 Introduction

Average bioavailability is a **key metric** for understanding **how a drug is absorbed across a population**. It offers insights into drug exposure under different administration routes, such as intravenous (IV) and oral (PO), and is calculated using non-compartmental analysis (NCA).

This metric is essential for assessing systemic exposure and comparing formulations. Unlike individual bioavailability, which highlights inter-individual variability, average bioavailability provides a population-level view, smoothing out individual differences.

Average bioavailability calculations can be used instead of individual calculations in these key scenarios:

- Parallel study designs where each group receives one administration route (e.g., IV or oral).
- Sparse sampling where subjects have incomplete measurements across different administration routes.
- When aiming for a population-level comparison of drug absorption between routes.

For scenarios involving individual bioavailability, the [parameter ratio tool](#) can be used.

8.3.1.2 Workflow

The bioequivalence module in PKanalix enables average absolute bioavailability calculations. Specific preliminary steps are essential for proper setup of the module

1. **Dataset setup**

- For **parallel designs**, include a column distinguishing administration routes (e.g., "IV" and "PO") and tag it as a categorical covariate. An administration ID column still has to be provided to link dosing with exposure data for NCA calculations.
- For **crossover designs**, in addition to the administration route and administration ID columns, an occasion column has to be included to differentiate the profiles for each subject across occasions.

NCA.plx - PKanalix - 2024R1

Project Settings Export Help

Data Tasks Plots

Data formatting

Data file: C:/Users/skollmann/Desktop/Projects_2024/Projec...
 BROWSE... FORMAT

Data information: Urine Plasma

Units: Units

TIME column x 1 = hour
 CONC column x 1 = milligram / liter
 AMT column x 1 = milligram

Add. covariates: NONE

LINE NUMBER	ID	CATEGORICAL COVARIATE	ADMINISTRATION ID	AMOUNT	INFUSION DURATION	OCCASION	TIME	OBSERVATION	CENSORING
	ID	ROUTE	ADM	AMOUNT	TINF	OCC	TIME	DV	CENS
1	1#1	IV							
2	1	IV	1	1000	0.166667	1	0		
3	1	IV				1	0.0833333	28.4	notCensored
4	1	IV				1	0.5	32.8	notCensored
5	1	IV				1	1	20.7	notCensored
6	1	IV				1	2	11.2	notCensored
7	1	IV				1	3	7.5	notCensored
8	1	IV				1	4	4.3	notCensored
9	1	IV				1	5	3.2	notCensored

Records per page: 10 25 50 100 403
 << Page 1 of 9 >>
 Showing 1 to 50 of 403 entries - 15 Individuals

2. BE module configuration

The bioequivalence module in PKanalix should be used, with the administration route assigned as a factor in the general linear model. "IV" is typically set as the reference formulation to enable group comparisons.

▼ Bioequivalence design *BE*

Study design
 parallel crossover

Factors in linear model (fixed effects)

id	ID	
period	OCC	
formulation	ROUTE	reference IV
sequence	none	
additional	None available	

8.3.1.3 Methodology

The calculation employs a **general linear model** to determine the ratio of the geometric means of the NCA parameter e.g. AUC/dose for the different administration routes:

$$F_{\text{average}} = \frac{\text{Geometric Mean}(AUC_{PO}/Dose_{PO})}{\text{Geometric Mean}(AUC_{IV}/Dose_{IV})}$$

The **GLM aggregates data for each administration route**, calculating e.g. the geometric mean of the dose-normalized area under the curve (AUC/dose). This step accounts for **variability between individuals** and ensures a population-level comparison.

The model uses the specified factor (administration route) to partition the data into groups. Each group represents a different administration route. The GLM then fits a linear equation to the log-transformed parameter values to calculate the mean ratio between the groups.

8.3.1.4 Interpretation

The resulting average bioavailability values provide a population-level perspective:

PO vs. IV

PARAMETER	PO		IV		BIOEQUIVALENCE						
	AdjustedMean	N	AdjustedMean	N	Difference	CIRawLower	CIRawUpper	Ratio	CILower	CIUpper	BE
AUC _{0-inf} /Dose (h·L ⁻¹)	0.03892	14	0.0924	14	-0.8644	-1.0265	-0.7024	42.1289	35.8268	49.5395	0
AUC _{0-tlast} /Dose (h·L ⁻¹)	0.03448	15	0.08083	15	-0.8518	-1.0414	-0.6622	42.6641	35.2946	51.5724	0

- **Higher values** suggest the oral route has greater absorption efficiency compared to the intravenous (IV) route. It could be considered "high" if the value approaches or exceeds 1 (100%), as oral bioavailability typically does not surpass IV bioavailability due to factors like first-pass metabolism (where the drug being partially broken down by the liver when taken orally before reaching general circulation).
- **Lower values** indicate reduced absorption via the oral route. These are considered "low" when they are close to 0, indicating very poor oral bioavailability.

8.3.2 Incorporating interaction terms in the linear model

8.3.2.1 Introduction

Interaction terms in general linear models capture the combined effect of two variables on an outcome, reflecting how the relationship between one factor and the outcome changes depending on the modality of the other factor. For instance, a treatment-by-period interaction term reveals whether the treatment effect varies across different study periods. These terms are particularly useful in identifying dependencies or inconsistencies in study designs.

8.3.2.2 Workflow

Currently, PKanalix does not natively support interaction terms in the BE module, but a workaround can be applied by creating a new "combined" covariate. The example below demonstrates this process using Period and Treatment of the demo project *project_repeated_4periods.plx* as interaction variables, but the same approach applies to other variables requiring interaction analysis.

1. Identify the Variables for Interaction

Determine the two variables to be combined, such as `PER` and `TRT`. Ensure these variables are properly formatted in the dataset.

The screenshot shows the PKanalix software interface for a project named 'project_repeated_4periods.plx [demo] - PKanalix - 2024R1'. The interface includes a menu bar (Project, Settings, Export, Help) and a sidebar with options like Data, Tasks, and Plots. The main area displays data formatting options, including a data file path, data information (Urine/Plasma), units, and a table of data. The table has columns: LINE NUMBER, SUBJ, PER, TIME, DV, AMOUNT, TRT, and SEQ. The 'PER' and 'TRT' columns are highlighted with red boxes. The 'TRT' column values are 'R' for all rows. The 'PER' column values are '1' for all rows. The 'SEQ' column values are 'RTRT' for all rows.

LINE NUMBER	SUBJ	PER	TIME	DV	AMOUNT	TRT	SEQ
1	1#1	1				R	RTRT
2	1	1	0		300	R	RTRT
3	1	1	0.5	4.69028		R	RTRT
4	1	1	1	8.08695		R	RTRT
5	1	1	2	13.0787		R	RTRT
6	1	1	3	18.5727		R	RTRT
7	1	1	4	19.6631		R	RTRT

2. Create the combined covariate

Use a tool like Excel, R, or SAS to concatenate the modalities of the chosen variables into a new categorical variable. For example:

```
# Define the path to the Monolix Suite installation
path.software <- paste0("C:/Program Files/Lixoft/MonolixSuite2024R1")

# Uncomment the line below to install the Lixoft connectors package if not already
# installed
# install.packages(paste0(path.software, "/connectors/lixoftConnectors.tar.gz"), repos
# = NULL, type="source", INSTALL_opts = "--no-multiarch")
```

```

suppressWarnings(library(lixoftConnectors))

# Initialize the Lixoft connectors for PKanalix
initializeLixoftConnectors(software = "pkanalix", path = path.software)

# Load the demo dataset
data <- read.csv(paste0(getDemoPath(),"/3.bioequivalence/data/
repeated_4periods_data.csv"),header = TRUE, sep = ",")

# Create a new column for the interaction term (e.g., Period and Treatment)
data$Interaction_Term <- paste0(data$PER, "-", data$TRT)

# Save the updated dataset to a new file
write.csv(data,"repeated_4periods_interactionterm.csv", row.names = F, quote = F)

```

This step creates a new column (e.g., `Interaction_Term`) representing the interaction term.

3. Update the dataset in PKanalix

Load the updated dataset into PKanalix, ensuring the new interaction covariate is included:

LINE NUMBER	SUBJ	PER	TIME	DV	AMOUNT	TRT	SEQ	Interaction_Term
1	1	1	0		300	R	RTRT	1-R
2	1	1	0.5	4.69028		R	RTRT	1-R
3	1	1	1	8.08695		R	RTRT	1-R
4	1	1	2	13.0787		R	RTRT	1-R
5	1	1	3	18.5727		R	RTRT	1-R
6	1	1	4	19.6631		R	RTRT	1-R
7	1	1	6	22.741		R	RTRT	1-R
8	1	1	8	21.7997		R	RTRT	1-R

4. Incorporate the combined covariate in the model

Configure the general linear model to include the new "combined" covariate as a factor for interaction analysis:

PARAMETER ~ SEQ:SUBJ + PER + TRT + SEQ + Interaction_Term

▼ Bioequivalence design BE

Study design
 parallel crossover

Factors in linear model (fixed effects)

id	SUBJ	▼	<i>(nested in sequence)</i>
period	PER	▼	
formulation	TRT	▼	reference R ▼
sequence	SEQ	▼	
additional	Interaction_Term	▼	

After running the model, the ANOVA table provides the breakdown of variance across factors, including the interaction term.

C_{max}

FACTOR	DF	SUMSQ	MEANSQ	FVALUE	PR(>F)
SEQ	1	0.03631	0.03631	8.3063	4.5979e-3
SUBJ	45	3.0252	0.06723	15.3797	0e+0
PER	3	0.02065	0.006883	1.5746	1.9845e-1
TRT	1	0.000005354	0.000005354	0.001225	9.7213e-1
Interaction_Term	2	0.001055	0.0005276	0.1207	8.8639e-1
Residuals	135	0.5901	0.004371		

The interaction term has a p-value of 0.88639, indicating no significant interaction effect between the factors PER and TRT. This means the combined effect of these variables does not significantly impact the response, here C_{max} .

8.3.2.3 Conclusion

Interaction terms offer valuable insights for detecting patterns and inconsistencies in complex datasets, especially in scenarios with heightened regulatory scrutiny. With a straightforward workaround, they can be effectively conducted in PKAnalix to address specific analytical needs.